

UNIVERSIDADE DE LISBOA
INSTITUTO SUPERIOR TÉCNICO

**MicroPathID: Development of an In-Field Microfluidic System
for Detection of Pathogens**

Catarina Raquel Fernandes Caneira

Supervisor: Doctor João Pedro Estrela Rodrigues Conde

Co-supervisor: Doctor Elisabete Ramos Fernandes

**Thesis approved in public session to obtain the PhD Degree in
Biomedical Engineering**

Jury final classification: Pass with Distinction

2023

UNIVERSIDADE DE LISBOA
INSTITUTO SUPERIOR TÉCNICO

**MicroPathID: Development of an In-Field Microfluidic System
for Detection of Pathogens**

Catarina Raquel Fernandes Caneira

Supervisor: Doctor João Pedro Estrela Rodrigues Conde
Co-supervisor: Doctor Elisabete Ramos Fernandes

**Thesis approved in public session to obtain the PhD Degree in
Biomedical Engineering**

Jury final classification: Pass with Distinction

Jury

Chairperson: Doctor Duarte Miguel de França Teixeira dos Prazeres, Instituto Superior Técnico da Universidade de Lisboa

Members of the Committee:

Doctor Pedro Miguel Ribeiro Viana Baptista, Faculdade de Ciências e Tecnologia Universidade Nova de Lisboa;

Doctor João Pedro Estrela Rodrigues Conde, Instituto Superior Técnico Universidade de Lisboa;
Doctor Duarte Miguel de França Teixeira dos Prazeres, Instituto Superior Técnico Universidade de Lisboa;

Doctor Domenico Caputo, Dipartimento di Ingegneria dell'Informazione, Elettronica e Telecomunicazioni, Sapienza Università di Roma, Italy;

Doctor Frederico Castelo Alves Ferreira, Instituto Superior técnico Universidade de Lisboa.

Funding Institution

Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia (FCT) – PhD Grant PD/BD/135274/2017

2023

Abstract

The detection of pathogens in primary care settings is increasingly critical, particularly in the fight against antimicrobial resistance, and has applications in areas such as food and feed safety, environmental monitoring and control, biodefense, to animal and human health. Currently, the methods used for detection are time-consuming or expensive and require specialized personnel, an elevated amount of hands-on time, and laboratory infrastructures. The increased burden of antimicrobial resistance and the predictions of future impact on human health motivate an increasing demand for a fast, simple, portable, cost-effective, sensitive, and specific device for the early detection of antibiotic-resistant bacteria, with application in the early detection in hospital environments.

This thesis reports the development of several miniaturized modules that included (1) cell lysis and (2) nucleic acid extraction, (3) amplification, and (4) optical target detection using miniaturized photosensors for optical transduction and signal acquisition to perform bacterial detection based on molecular assays. The use of nanoporous microbeads on the microfluidic device allowed for device simplification and an increase in sensitivity. Fluidic control and sensor integration can also be employed in the device to achieve a sample-to-answer system. We were able to achieve a lysis module capable of lysing bacterial and virus-like particles, and successfully extracting DNA/RNA in under 20 min. The development of an isothermal amplification module allowed the detection of sub-femtomolar concentrations of DNA on a chip in less than 2 hours targeting a specific gene that allows the identification of the presence of *Staphylococcus aureus*.

These developments contribute significantly to the state-of-the-art and pave the way toward the development of a fully integrated molecular-based device, to be used at the point-of-care to allow rapid detection and screening of patients that present antibiotic-resistant bacteria.

Keywords

Nucleic acid detection, antibiotic resistance, microfluidics, nanoporous microbeads, integration

Resumo

A detecção de patógenos em ambientes de cuidados primários de saúde é cada vez mais crítica, particularmente no combate à resistência antimicrobiana mas tem aplicações em áreas tão vastas como segurança de alimentos e rações, monitoramento e controle ambiental, biodefesa e saúde animal e humana. Atualmente, os métodos utilizados para a detecção são demorados ou caros, requerem utilizadores especializados, uma quantidade elevada de tempo de trabalho e infraestruturas laboratoriais. O aumento da carga de resistência antimicrobiana e as previsões de impacto na saúde humana num futuro próximo, motivaram uma procura crescente por um dispositivo rápido, simples, portátil, econômico, sensível e específico para a detecção precoce de bactérias resistentes a antibióticos, em particular, com importante aplicação na detecção antecipada e rápida destas bactérias em ambiente hospitalar.

Esta tese descreve o desenvolvimento de vários módulos miniaturizados que incluíram (1) lise celular e (2) extração de ácidos nucleicos, (3) amplificação de material genético e (4) detecção ótica da molécula de interesse usando fotodetectores miniaturizados para transdução ótica e aquisição de sinal. O uso de microesferas nanoporosas no dispositivo microfluídico permitiu a simplificação do dispositivo e aumento da sensibilidade. Sistemas de controle fluídico e sensores também podem ser integrados ao dispositivo para obter um sistema verdadeiramente da amostra para resposta. Conseguimos obter um módulo de lise capaz de lisar bactérias e partículas semelhantes a vírus e efetuar extração e DNA/RNA em menos de 20 min com sucesso. O desenvolvimento de um módulo de amplificação isotérmica permitiu a detecção no chip levando à confirmação da presença de *Staphylococcus aureus* através de um gene específico.

Estes desenvolvimentos contribuíram significativamente para o estado da arte e abrem caminho para o desenvolvimento de um dispositivo, totalmente integrado, baseado em testes moleculares, para ser usado no local de atendimento o que permitirá uma rápida detecção e triagem de doentes com a presença de bactérias resistentes a antibióticos.

Palavras-Chave

Detecção de ácidos nucleicos, resistência a antibióticos, microfluídica, microesferas nanoporosas, integração

Acknowledgements

I express my most sincere thanks to all who made this journey possible.

To my supervisor, Professor João Pedro Conde, I am deeply grateful for the opportunities given to me to explore my academic career, from the master's thesis to the moment of this doctoral thesis. Thank you for the scientific guidance, for believing in my abilities along the way, and for the patience and understanding I always felt I received in good and bad times. It will forever be a reference for me of what it means to be an excellent Teacher, Advisor, and Human Being. I would also like to thank Dr. Virgínia Chu for her availability to always discuss my project, for her precious help and suggestions for the dissemination of the scientific work that was being carried out, and for having also been an example and inspiration for me how it is possible to manage a research group. I want to thank both of them for welcoming me into what I consider to be more than the BioMEMS research group at INESC MN, but my scientific family. A family that helped me grow as a researcher and as a person.

To my co-supervisor at INL, Doctor Elisabete Fernandes, I thank her for her sympathy, availability to talk, and good heart. Of all our encounters, she was always available to help in any way he could. Thank you so much for this.

In addition to my formal supervisors, I could not fail to mention Dr. Silvia Monteiro and Dr. Ricardo from LAIST for having welcomed me and sharing countless discussions about my project, science, life, and so many other topics with me. Thank you for your scientific guidance, company, and friendship.

To my former colleagues and friends at INESC MN. In particular, my deepest thanks to Dr. Ruben Soares for having been a mentor, a scientist I greatly admire and who inspires me, and a good friend. Professionalism, focus and determination, scientific acumen, rectitude, and good heart are characteristics that define him and that I know have led him to fly high. And, of course, I would like to thank my friend and companion during the afternoons of experience at Biolabo, Dr. Inês Pinto. It was a pleasure and a privilege to meet Inês and work alongside her. A scientist and person that I will always look up to and that I know will have a bright future. To Doctor Eduardo Brás, thank you for the company, friendship, and philosophical and nerd conversations. I would also like to thank Dr. Narayanan Madaboosi Srinivasan for being a reference to what it meant to be an excellent researcher when I started working at INESC MN. To all the other people who have been in the group over the years and who have contributed to making it a family, Dr. Denis Santos, Dr. Rui Pinto, Dr. Ricardo Fradique, Cristiana

Rodrigues, Pedro Monteiro, Tiago Pestana, Débora Albuquerque, Andreia Jardim, Roberta Epifania, Yasmin Geiger, Filipa Flora, Sofia Relvas, Rui Meirinho and all those who passed INESC MN.

To Rafaela Rosa, thank you for embarking on the challenge of doing a master's thesis on the topic of amplification and for the dedication you showed. Thank you for also being a good company, both to complain about less good results and to celebrate the positive ones! I believe in your abilities, and I am sure you will be a very successful Ph.D. student.

To my exquisite group of friends that Técnico brought together, and since then, we were never apart. Thank you for understanding the numerous time I said I could not go to dinner, trip, or event and ear about my complaints. Raquel Porteira, Ana Bastos, Constança Roquette, Teresa Cordeiro, João Santos, Sandro Nunes, e Vasco Conceição, thank you for letting me fall asleep after 11 p.m. during the parties on the days I was tired and only waked me up in the end. A big thank you to Raquel, more than a friend, a sister to me, and for being there for me all these years, I'm glad Técnico brought us together.

To my family, in particular, to my Father and Mother, who always supported me in everything they could and encouraged me to follow my dreams. Without him, this would not have been possible. A deep thank you. I hope you are proud of my journey as a scientist and person.

To my grandparents who are gone. Especially to my grandmother Maria, who always asked me how school was going and if it had finished, and who left a few months before I could say yes. "Já está terminado, Querida Avó."

This Ph.D. was not just a scientific Ph.D. It was also a process of self-discovery and reflection. I discovered and learned a lot about the exact sciences, like microfluidics, molecular biology, materials science, etc., but I learned a lot about myself and those around me. I came to question the path, I questioned myself, and realized that it is in science that I find refuge. I learn because I enjoy learning, and the more I learn, the more I realize that there's a lot I don't know. However, the basis of learning gives us the freedom to be free of thought, and to imagine new possibilities and ideas, which fascinates me most about science. I learned that science is made up of people, relationships, and collaborations and that without people, there would be no scientific advancement. I feel thankful for the journey I took, and I take a little bit of all these people who have marked me on this trip. I hope our paths cross again, whether in science or life.

Agradecimentos

O meu mais sincero obrigada a todos aqueles que tornaram esta jornada possível.

Ao meu orientador, o Professor João Pedro Conde, agradeço profundamente as oportunidades que me foram dadas de explorar a minha carreira académica, desde a tese do mestrado até ao momento desta tese de doutoramento. Obrigada pelas orientações científicas, o acreditar nas minhas capacidades ao longo do percurso e pela paciência e compreensão que sempre senti receber ao longo do percurso, nas alturas boas e menos boas. Será, para sempre, uma referência para mim do que é ser um excelente Professor, Orientador e Ser Humano. À Doutora Virginia Chu, agradeço também a disponibilidade para discutir sempre o meu projeto, as preciosas ajudas e sugestões para a divulgação do trabalho científico que ia sendo realizado e por ter sido também um exemplo e inspiração, para mim, de como é possível gerir um grupo de investigação. Aos dois agradeço por terem-me acolhido, no que considero ser mais que o grupo de investigação BioMEMS do INESC MN, na minha família científica. Uma família que me ajudou a crescer enquanto investigadora e pessoa.

À minha co-orientadora do INL, Doutora Elisabete Fernandes, agradeço a simpatia, a disponibilidade para conversar e o bom coração. De todos os encontros que tivemos foi sempre notória a boa vontade e disponível para ajudar em tudo o que podia. Muito obrigada por isso.

Além dos meus orientadores formais, não podia deixar de mencionar a Doutora Sílvia Monteiro e o Doutor Ricardo Santos do LAIST, por me terem acolhido e partilhado comigo inúmeras discussões sobre o meu projeto, a ciência, a vida e tantos outros temas. Obrigada pela orientação científica, pela companhia e pela amizade.

Aos meus antigos colegas e amigos do INESC MN. Em particular, ao Doutor Rúben Soares, por ter sido um mentor, um cientista que muito admiro e que me inspira e um bom amigo, o meu profundo obrigado. O profissionalismo, o foco, a determinação, a perspicácia científica, a retidão e o bom coração são características que o definem e que sei que o levaram a voar bem alto. E claro, agradeço à minha amiga e companheira das tardes de experiência no Biolabo, a Doutora Inês Pinto. Foi um prazer e um privilégio conhecer a Inês e trabalhar ao lado dela. Uma cientista e pessoa que também irei sempre admirar e que sei que terá um futuro brilhante. Ao Doutor Eduardo Brás um obrigado pela companhia e amizade, pelas conversas filosóficas e nerds. Agradeço também ao Doutor Narayanan Madaboosi Srinivasan por ter sido uma referência do que era ser um excelente investigador quando comecei a

trabalhar no INESC MN. A todas as outras pessoas que foram passando no grupo ao longo dos anos e que contribuíram para que este fosse uma família, Doutor Denis Santos, Doutor Rui Pinto, Doutor Ricardo Fradique, Cristiana Rodrigues, Pedro Monteiro, Tiago Pestana, Débora Albuquerque, Andreia Jardim, Roberta Epifania, Yasmin Geiger, Filipa Flora, Sofia Relvas, Rui Meirinho e todos os que passaram no INESC MN, obrigada. À Rafaela Rosa, obrigada por teres embarcado no desafio de fazer a tese de mestrado no tópico da amplificação e pela dedicação que mostraste. Obrigada por teres sido também uma boa companhia tanto para reclamar de resultados menos bons como para festejar os positivos! Acredito nas tuas capacidades e tenho a certeza de que vais ser uma aluna de doutoramento com muito sucesso.

Ao meu primoroso grupo de amigos que o Técnico juntou e desde então nunca mais nos separámos. Obrigado por compreender as inúmeras vezes que eu disse que não poderia ir a um jantar, viagem ou evento e em que ouviram as minhas reclamações. Raquel Porteira, Ana Bastos, Constança Roquette, Teresa Cordeiro, João Santos, Sandro Nunes e Vasco Conceição, obrigado por me deixarem adormecer durante as festas depois das 23h nos dias em que eu estava muito cansada e só me acordarem no final. Um muito obrigado à Raquel, mais do que uma amiga, uma irmã, obrigada por estar ao meu lado todos estes anos, fico feliz que o Técnico nos tenha juntado.

À minha família, em particular, ao meu Pai e à minha Mãe que sempre me apoiaram em tudo o que puderam e me incentivaram a seguir os meus sonhos. Sem eles, nada teria sido possível. Um profundo obrigado. Espero que fiquem orgulhos do meu percurso enquanto cientista e enquanto pessoa. Aos meus avós que já partiram. Em particular, à minha avó Maria, que me perguntava sempre como ia a escola e se já tinha terminado, e que partiu uns meses antes de eu lhe conseguir responder que sim. “Já está terminado, Querida Avó.”

Este doutoramento não foi só um doutoramento científico. Foi também um processo de autodescoberta e de reflexão. Descobri e aprendi muito sobre as ciências exatas como microfluídica, biologia molecular, ciência dos materiais, etc., mas aprendi muito sobre mim e sobre quem me rodeia. Cheguei a questionar o percurso, questionei-me a mim e percebi que é na ciência que encontro refúgio. Aprendo pelo simples facto de gostar de aprender, e quanto mais aprendo, mais percebo que há muito que não sei. No entanto, a base da aprendizagem dá-nos a capacidade de sermos livres de pensamento, de imaginar novas possibilidades e ideias e é isso que me mais me fascina na ciência. Aprendi que a ciência é feita de pessoas, de relações e colaborações e que sem as pessoas não existiria um avançar científico.

Agradeço por isso o percurso que fiz e levo um bocadinho de todas estas pessoas que me marcam nesta viagem. Espero que os nossos caminhos se voltem a cruzar, seja na ciência ou na vida.

Table of contents

<i>Abstract</i>	<i>iv</i>
<i>Keywords</i>	<i>iv</i>
<i>Resumo</i>	<i>vi</i>
<i>Palavras-Chave</i>	<i>vi</i>
<i>Acknowledgements</i>	<i>viii</i>
<i>Agradecimentos</i>	<i>x</i>
<i>Table of contents</i>	<i>xiv</i>
<i>List of Figures</i>	<i>xviii</i>
<i>List of Tables</i>	<i>xxi</i>
<i>List of acronyms and abbreviations</i>	<i>xxii</i>
1. Ph.D. project contextualization	1
1.1. Overview	1
1.2. Aim.....	2
1.3. Objectives and Milestones	3
1.4. Research Project Timeline	5
1.5. Research Project Structure.....	6
1.6. Structure of this thesis	6
2. Introduction	9
2.1. The technology, the problem, and the proposed solution – A brief description	9
2.2. Microfluidic devices for the detection of pathogens.....	13
2.3. State of the art μ TAS device	28
2.4. Pathogens of interest.....	37

2.5.	Fundamentals of microfluidics	40
2.6.	Assay requirements to develop a fit for purpose biosensor	44
3.	<i>General fabrication and experimental methods</i>	49
3.1.	Overview of a microfluidic device fabrication process	49
3.2.	Fabrication of a-Si:H <i>p-i-n</i> photodiodes	56
3.3.	Microfluidic structure general handling.....	57
3.4.	Optical signal transduction.....	58
4.	<i>Development of a rapid bead-based microfluidic platform for DNA hybridization using single- and multi-mode interactions for probe immobilization</i>	59
4.1.	Introduction.....	59
4.2.	Materials and experimental methods	61
4.3.	Results and Discussion	68
4.4.	Chapter conclusions	80
5.	<i>Regenerable Bead-based Microfluidic Device with Integrated Thin-film Photodiodes for Real-time Monitoring of DNA Detection</i>	83
5.1.	Introduction.....	84
5.2.	Materials and experimental methods	86
5.3.	Results and Discussion	92
5.4.	Chapter Conclusions	99
6.	<i>Silica bead-based microfluidic device with integrated photodiodes for the rapid capture and detection of rolling circle amplification products in the femtomolar range</i>	103
6.1.	Introduction.....	104
6.2.	Materials and experimental methods	105
6.3.	Results and Discussion	111
6.4.	Chapter Conclusions	116

7. Chemical lysis and nucleic acid capture of Gram-positive, Gram-negative, and virus-like particles using a bead-based microfluidic chip	119
7.1. Introduction.....	120
7.2. Materials and experimental methods	122
7.3. Results and discussion	129
7.4. Chapter Conclusions	142
8. Systematic implementation of padlock probing-based rolling circle amplification in an integrated microfluidic device for quantitative biomolecular analyses	145
8.1. Introduction.....	146
8.2. Materials and experimental methods	148
8.3. Results and discussion	160
8.4. Chapter Conclusions	176
9. Conclusion and Future developments.....	177
9.1. Novelty and main improvements to the state-of-the-art.....	177
9.2. Future developments toward a fully integrated microfluidic system for the detection of pathogens.....	178
Bibliography	181

List of Figures

Figure 1.1 - Research project timeline.	5
Figure 1.2 - Doctorate structure.....	6
Figure 2.1 - Schematics and comparison of pathogen detection using conventional laboratory detection methods - A - and PoC methods - B.....	13
Figure 2.2 – Schematics of an ideal μ TAS device for nucleic acid detection.	14
Figure 2.3 – Sample types and possible interferences of each sample type that may interfere with downstream processes which make sample preparation crucial for the success of assay development.	17
Figure 2.4 – Types of cell lysis that includes mechanical methods	18
Figure 2.5 – Optical and non-optical detection methods used in μ TAS device.	28
Figure 2.6 - Representative illustration of the cell wall components of gram-negative, gram-positive bacteria and non-enveloped and enveloped viruses.....	40
Figure 2.7 - Biosensor characterization.....	45
Figure 3.1 – Schematics of the microfabrication process to obtain the PDMS microfluidic devices.	51
Figure 3.2 - Schematics of the thin-film a-Si:H photodiodes.	57
Figure 4.1 - General overview of the microfluidic setup and the DNA detection strategies using nanoporous microbeads.	62
Figure 4.2 – Schematics of the assays for blocking optimization using Q Sepharose beads.	65
Figure 4.3 - Summary of the hybridization assays performed for the three different optical detection labels used, fluorescence using ATTO 430LS coupled with Q Sepharose™ and Capto™ Adhere beads, Qdots™ 605 coupled with Capto™ Adhere beads and chemiluminescence using horseradish peroxidase (HRP) coupled with Q Sepharose™ beads.....	66
Figure 4.4 - Schematics of the mass balance method used to calculate the mass of probe DNA immobilized on the beads and captured target DNA.	68
Figure 4.5 - Quantification of the target DNA non-specifically bound to the PDMS walls for (A) cDNA and (B) ncDNA.....	68
Figure 4.6 - BSA-FITC adsorption isotherms and effect of conductivity on molecular adsorption.....	70
Figure 4.7 - Optimization of probe DNA-FITC immobilization on a positively charged surface, silanized with (3-Aminopropyl)triethoxysilane (APTES).....	71
Figure 4.8 - Optimization of the blocking time.....	72
Figure 4.9 - Effect of different blocking agents on blocking efficacy and hybridization selectivity on QS beads.	73
Figure 4.10 - Comparison of fluorescence intensity of probe DNA immobilized on QS beads and CA beads before and after the blocking step.	74
Figure 4.11 - (A,B) Calibration curves for known concentrations of DNA, used to determine <i>mDNAOUT</i> . 75	75

Figure 4.12 - Biosensing of DNA in QS or CA beads using three different optical detection labels: (A) fluorescence using Atto 430LS in QS or QA bead-based assays, (B) Qdots labels and CA beads or (C) chemiluminescence using HRP and QA beads.....	77
Figure 4.13 - Comparison of background fluorescence for QS beads and CA beads before and after the blocking step.....	78
Figure 4.14 - Comparison of the chemiluminescence signal profile when using CA beads or QS beads. ..	79
Figure 5.1 - Bead-based microfluidic assays.....	88
Figure 5.2 - Integrated optical transduction after target capture in regeneration assays.	91
Figure 5.3 - Optimization of microcolumn regeneration conditions.	94
Figure 5.4 - Measurements of the hybridization assay cycles, including detection of specific complementary target DNA, column regeneration, non-complementary target DNA control, and column regeneration.	97
Figure 5.5 - Fluorescence A and B and chemiluminescence C and D monitoring using photosensors.	98
Figure 6.1 - Schematics of the off-chip target detection and amplification, followed by on-chip RCA product (RCP) capture and fluorescence signal transduction.....	110
Figure 6.2 A - Bright field (top) and fluorescence (bottom) microscopy imaging of the silica bead microcolumn and captured RCPs and B - flow-rate optimization.....	112
Figure 6.3 - Monitoring of RCP capture on the microfluidic device using the integrated photodiode	114
Figure 6.4 - Calibration curve for increasing target RNA concentrations and correlation with a commercial RCP counter (Q-linea Aquila 400)..	115
Figure 6.5 - Detection of Ebola vRNA using RCA and the miniaturized read-out device.....	116
Figure 7.1 - Schematics of the microfluidic device for pathogens lysis and genetic material detection..	124
Figure 7.2 - Schematics of the protocol to obtain the total copies of genetic material captured by the beads packed in the microfluidic chamber.	128
Figure 7.3 - Confirmation of results using TSA plates. (A) and (B) BPER lysis of Gram-positive and negative bacteria. (C) and (D) Combination of Genolyse and BPER solutions to perform chemical lysis.	131
Figure 7.4 - SEM micrographs.....	132
Figure 7.5 - Fluorescence results of the controls for the EvaGreen® detection.....	133
Figure 7.6 - Calibration curve of the lysis device for Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria using a chemical lysis strategy (Mixture of GenoLyse® (GL) and B-PPER™ (BPER) solutions).	134
Figure 7.7 - Summary of the lysis results obtained using a mass balance approach for quantification...	139
Figure 8.1 - (A) Schematics of the microfluidic device used for rolling circle amplification (RCA) on-chip.	149
Figure 8.2 - Half-normal plot for the various effects and interactions.	161
Figure 8.3 - Calibration curve for the detection of biotinylated S. aureus target DNA using a solid-phase capture and rolling circle amplification on-chip.	163
Figure 8.4 - Flow rate optimization for the capture of ssDNA.....	164

Figure 8.5 - Target single-strand DNA capture studies.....	165
Figure 8.6 - Capture capacity for the first column of Q Sepharose beads and a second column.....	166
Figure 8.7 - Detection of rolling circle amplification products for strategy A and strategy B.	171
Figure 8.8 - Comparison of PLP-RCA performed on a well plate and on-chip for both strategies A and B.....	174
Figure 8.9 - Fluorescence signal obtained by microscopy and image analysis for the different strategies used to detect <i>S. aureus</i> gDNA.....	175

List of Tables

Table 1.1- Structure of this report.....	6
Table 2.1– PoC devices in the market for pathogen detection using nucleic acid amplification.	33
Table 2.2 – The leading pathogens of that cause hospital acquired infections and relevant characteristics.	38
Table 3.1 - Materials and equipment required for device fabrication and operation.	53
Table 3.2 - General timeline of the sequence of steps required to perform the fabrication of the microfluidic device.	55
Table 4.1 - Description of the oligonucleotide sequences used in this work with respective modifications.....	62
Table 4.2 - Description of on-chip steps performed in the microfluidic device with the respective flow rates and assay times for fluorescence and chemiluminescence assays. Steps that were not applied in a given assay are identified as not applicable (n.a.). Off-chip steps are described in the text.....	63
Table 5.1 - Description of the oligonucleotide sequences used in this work and respective modifications.....	87
Table 5.2 - Critical comparison of similar methodologies in the literature.	100
Table 7.1 - Real-time RT-qPCR primers and fluorogenic probes sequences	126
Table 7.2 - Summary of the quantitative results obtained for the different lysis treatments.	137
Table 8.1 - DNA oligonucleotide sequences used throughout this work to perform RCA.	151
Table 8.2 - Description of on-chip steps performed in the microfluidic device with the respective flow rates and assay times to detect ssDNA with model strategy.	153
Table 8.3 - Description of on-chip steps performed in the microfluidic device with the respective flow rates and assay times for the different strategies tested to detect ssDNA.	154
Table 8.4 - Concentration of reagents used in each step of the PLP-RCA assay, and flow conditions.	156
Table 8.5 - Description of on-chip steps performed in the microfluidic device with the respective flow rates and assay times for the different strategies tested to detect gDNA.	156
Table 8.6 - Description of on-well RCA for gDNA, solutions prepared for each step, and incubation times on well.	158
Table 8.7 - Fractional factorial design.	160

List of acronyms and abbreviations

μTAS	Micro total analysis systems
a-Si:H	Hydrogenated amorphous silicon
a-SiC:H	Hydrogenated amorphous silicon carbide
<i>A. baumannii</i>	<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i>
AC	Alternating current
ACK	Ammonium-Chloride-Potassium
ACV	Alternating current voltammetry
Al	Aluminum
AMF	Alternate current magnetic field
AMR	Antimicrobial resistance
ARB	Antibiotic-resistant bacteria
ASMD	Amplified single-molecule detection
ASSURED	Affordable, Sensitive, Specific, User-friendly, Rapid and robust, Equipment-free, and Deliverable
ATP	Adenosine triphosphate
AU	Arbitrary units
<i>B. cereus</i>	<i>Bacillus cereus</i>
BHQ	Black Hole Quencher
BP	Band pass
BPER	Bacterial protein extraction reagent
BSA	Bovine serum albumin
C2CA	Circle to circle amplification
CA	Capto Adhere
CCD	Charged-coupled device
cDNA	Complementary deoxyribonucleic acid

CFU	Colony forming units
COVID-19	Coronavirus disease
CPA	Cross-priming amplification
CRE	Carbapenem-resistant <i>Enterobacteriaceae</i>
Ct	Cycle threshold
CV	Coefficient of variation
DC	Direct current
DI	Deionized
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic acid
dNTPs	Deoxynucleotide triphosphates
DO	Detection oligo
DoE	Design of experiment
dsDNA	Double-stranded deoxyribonucleic acid
DWL	Direct write lithography
<i>E. coli</i>	<i>Escherichia coli</i>
EDTA	Ethylenediamine tetraacetic acid
EG	EvaGreen dye
ESKAPE-E	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i> , <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> , <i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i> , <i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i> , <i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> and <i>Enterobacter spp</i> and <i>Escherichia coli</i>
EXPAR	Exponential amplification reaction
FAM	6-Carboxyfluorescein
FITC	Fluorescein isothiocyanate
GAS	Group A streptococcus
GC	Genome copies
gDNA	Genomic deoxyribonucleic acid
GL	GenoLyse

GPIB	General purpose interface bus
GUI	Graphical user interface
HIV	Human immunodeficiency virus
HRP	Horseradish peroxidase
IAV/IBV	Influenza virus A/B
IPA	Isopropyl Alcohol
ITO	Indium tin oxide
ITP	Isotachophoresis
JOE	4-5-Dichloro carboxy fluorescein
LAMP	Loop-mediated isothermal amplification
LED	Light-emitting diode
LFA	Lateral flow assay
LLE	Liquid-liquid extraction
LNA	Locked nucleic acid
LoB	Limit of blank
LoC	Lab-on-a-chip
LoD	Limit of detection
LoQ	Limit of quantification
LP	Long pass
LS	Lysis solution
MDRTB	Multi-drug resistant tuberculosis
MERS-CoV	Middle east respiratory syndrome coronavirus
MRSA	methicillin-resistant <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>
MTB	<i>Mycobacterium tuberculosis</i>
NA	Nucleic acids
NAAT	Nucleic acid amplification test

ncDNA	Non-complimentary deoxyribonucleic acid
ND	Neutral density
NEAR	Nicking enzyme amplification reaction
NHS	N-hydroxysuccinimide-activated
OD	Optical density
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>
PA	Sodium polyacrylate
PBS	Phosphate buffered saline
PBST	Phosphate buffer saline tween
PCB	Printed circuit board
PCR	Polymerase chain reaction
PDMS	Polydimethylsiloxane
PEG	Polyethylene glycol
PFU	Plaque-forming units
PGMEA	Propylene glycol monomethyl ether acetate
PK	Proteinase K
PLP	Padlock
PNA	Peptide nucleic acid
PoC	Point-of-care
PoN	Point-of-need
QCM	Quartz Cristal Mass
QDots	Quantum-dots
qPCR	Real-time polymerase chain reaction
QS	Q Sepharose Fast Flow
R&D	Research and development
RCA	Rolling circle amplification

RCP	Rolling circle amplification product
rf-PECVD	Radio frequency plasma-enhanced chemical vapor deposition
RIE	Reactive ion etching
RNA	Ribonucleic acid
ROI	Region of interest
ROX	Carboxy-X-rhodamine
RPA	Recombinase polymerase amplification
RSD	Relative standard deviation
RSV	Respiratory syncytial virus
rt	Room temperature
RT-dPCR	Reverse transcription digital polymerase chain reaction
RT-LAMP	Reverse transcription loop-mediated isothermal amplification
RT-PCR	Reverse transcription polymerase chain reaction
RT-qPCR	Reverse transcription real-time polymerase chain reaction
<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>
<i>S. enterica</i>	<i>Salmonella enterica</i>
<i>S. hominis</i>	<i>Staphylococcus hominis</i>
<i>S. Typhimurium</i>	<i>Salmonella Typhimurium</i>
saDNA	Salmon sperm deoxyribonucleic acid
SAF	Super critical angle fluorescence
SARS-CoV-1	Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 1
SARS-CoV-2	Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2
SDS	Sodium dodecyl sulfate
SP	Solid phase
SP-PCR	Solid-phase polymerase chain reaction

SPE	Solid-phase extraction
SPR	Surface plasmon resonance
SSC	Saline sodium citrate
ssDNA	Single-stranded deoxyribonucleic acid
ssRNA	Single-stranded ribonucleic acid
TMP	Transmembrane potential
TSA	Tryptic soy agar
Tth	<i>Thermus thermophilus</i>
UV	Ultraviolet
UVO	Ultraviolet ozone
vRNA	Viral ribonucleic acid
WHO	World Health Organization

Chapter 1

Ph.D. project contextualization

1. Ph.D. project contextualization

This chapter gives a brief overview and contextualization of the work. The scope and motivation of the Ph.D. project are defined as well as the main objectives and milestones. The research timeline and the research project structure are presented. At the end of the chapter, the structure of the thesis is provided.

1.1. Overview

Detecting pathogens such as bacteria, fungi, and viruses is vital for food and feed safety, environmental monitoring and control, biodefense, and to animal and human health. Currently, the methods used for detection are time-consuming or expensive and require specialized personnel, an elevated amount of hands-on time, and laboratory infrastructures. In recent years, the world has dealt with a viral pandemic that has killed from 2019 to 2022 more than 6 million people around the world. The early detection, and in particular the use of point-of-care devices, proved to be a significant weapon in this war, stopping the spread of the virus, decreasing the spread rate, and unburdening the healthcare facilities, which in turn helped to save lives. History can repeat itself, and history should be a place to look for answers. When we started this Ph.D. project, the field application was to target antibiotic-resistant bacteria. In 2017, the world health organization had already considered antimicrobial resistance (AMR) one of the more serious public health concerns. As the world continues to respond to the coronavirus pandemic, there is still a hidden threat of AMR lurking and threatening the effective prevention and treatment of an ever-increasing range of infections caused by bacteria, fungi, and viruses. With high levels of hospitalizations from coronavirus disease (COVID-19), there is a risk that the burden of AMR has already accelerated due to the increased use of antibiotics. A recent study estimated that drug-resistant infections contribute directly to 1.27 million deaths per year [1]. Up to 5 million people who died in 2019 suffered from at least one

drug-resistant infection [1]. Immediate actions are required, at a multisectoral level, to mitigate the impact of AMR on lives, livelihoods, and societies. These combined actions could prevent common diseases, such as urinary tract infections, from becoming untreatable and prevent modern life-saving procedures from becoming riskier. Not to mention that an uncontrolled AMR would result in a similar effect as the COVID-19 pandemic, dramatically increasing health expenditure and damage to food systems and livelihoods, leading to an increased disparity of inequality and poverty. The World Health Organization (WHO) defined three priorities in the "World Health Organization strategic priorities on antimicrobial resistance" report published in 2021 [2]. While the first two are more directed to coordinated responses in actions in the world and each country by creating awareness, guidance, and AMR monitoring, the third priority focus on the research and development for better access to quality AMR prevention and care. In this sense, a point-of-use device that is fast, inexpensive, easy to use, and internet-connected can potentially disrupt the way health, food, and environmental safety parameters are monitored for AMR. Although our first field of application, and the one used to develop the Ph.D. project, is the detection of antibiotic-resistant bacteria, the approach defined and developed would allow the device to detect not only antibiotic-resistant bacteria but other bacteria, fungi, and viruses. This Ph.D. project has wider applications, and its development can be helpful and advance the development of a device that could help in a future pandemic, by performing an early detection and control of the desired pathogens.

1.2. Aim

This doctorate aimed to develop a microfluidic-based system that could identify in a raw biological sample the presence of specific bacteria. In 2017, the WHO published a list of high-priority pathogens of antibiotic-resistant bacteria from which R&D should be working to respond to urgent public health needs and avoid future pandemics [3]. Following the list indication, this Ph.D. project selected the carbapenem-resistant *Enterobacteriaceae* (CRE) (classified as priority 1: **CRITICAL**) group and methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) (classified as priority 2: **HIGH**) as target bacteria to be detected by the microfluidic-based system. This selection allowed us to work towards a detection system that could identify both gram-negative and gram-positive bacteria without significant changes on the device or reagents. Both pathogens pose a considerable threat in hospitals, nursing homes, and patients requiring ventilators, blood, and urinary catheters. They are relevant in the contamination/infection control of hospital-acquired (nosocomial) infections. The device must be compatible with use in hospitals, nursing homes, and healthcare

facilities to comply with the field application. Four specifications must be followed to facilitate the uptake of the developed microfluidic system. **FAST** – the turnover time from sample to answer should be fast enough to allow a decision to be taken during triage; **INEXPENSIVE** – must be significantly cheaper than a polymerase chain reaction (PCR)-based analysis; **SIMPLE** – minimal user intervention and minimal steps. Simplicity should also translate into device portability; **PERFORMANCE** – sensitivity, selectivity, and repeatability comparable to standard laboratory methods.

Our approach rested on integrating all steps of cell capture/lysis and deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) extraction, amplification, and detection in a single location in the device, to dramatically simplify the analysis process, minimize user intervention, decrease analysis time, and significantly increase the robustness of the assay. Fluidic control and sensor can also be integrated into the device to achieve a sample-to-answer system. We hypothesized that the novel integration of nanoporous microbeads on the microfluidic device that captures the DNA would allow performing all the steps in the same device location. Furthermore, the large surface area, dense packing, and robust functionalization of the nanoporous microbeads offer an ideal substrate for high-yield DNA capture, amplification, and efficient coupling to integrated optical detection. In addition, integrating nanoporous microbeads is expected to contribute to increased sensitivity and promote a faster analysis.

1.3. Objectives and Milestones

The doctorate project presented here was structured into three main tasks. **Task 1** comprised developing the individual modules for sample analysis in model conditions. **Task 2** requires the sequential integration of the modules from the end (detection) up to the start of the assay (cell lysis). This means that the integration flowline will increase complexity until a complete analysis system is obtained. Finally, **Task 3** focuses on optimizing the integrated system using test samples and evaluation in the clinical environment. Below, the objectives for each Task and Milestones to be reached in each step are defined.

1.3.1. Task 1

1.3.1.1. Objectives

1. To develop the individual modules required for the sample analysis in model conditions.
 - 1.1. Development of a lysis module.
 - 1.2. Development of an acid nucleic extraction module.

- 1.3. Development of an amplification module.
- 1.4. Development of optical detection module.
- 1.5. To perform pre-validation against the gold standard techniques in central laboratories for each module.

1.3.1.2. Milestones

- M1.1. Sensitivity curve for fluorescence using integrated photodiodes.
- M1.2. Demonstration of the capture of the DNA in microbeads trapped in the microfluidic channel.
- M1.3. Demonstration of bacterial lysis in a microfluidic system.
- M1.4. Demonstration of rolling circle amplification (RCA) in a microfluidic system.

1.3.2. Task 2

1.3.2.1. Objectives

2. To integrate the individual modules successfully towards a complete analysis platform still using model solutions and conditions. To test and evaluate the device requirements.
 - 2.1. Development of an integrated module for DNA amplification and detection. Photodiodes should be included to perform optical signal transduction.
 - 2.2. Coupling of DNA extraction to the device obtained in 2.1.
 - 2.3. Addition of the module of cell lysis and pre-concentration to the previous devices.
 - 2.4. To test the integrated system for sensitivity, specificity, and time of analysis, using a model solution with a different titer of the bacteria of interest and an other bacterium.
 - 2.5. To perform the pre-validation of the integrated system against the gold standard molecular biology methods.

1.3.2.2. Milestones

- M2.1. Demonstration of integrated detection of DNA amplification.
- M2.2. Demonstration of amplification from on-chip captured DNA.
- M2.3. Demonstration of DNA detection from bacterial cell culture.

1.3.3. Task 3

1.3.3.1. Objectives

3. Perform a test of the device in a clinical environment.
 - 3.1. To optimize the integrated system, namely for sensitivity and time of analysis.
 - 3.2. Detection of positive spiked samples (swab sample) with a different titter.
 - 3.3. Test in clinical environment done by trained hospital laboratory technical staff.

1.3.3.2. Milestones

M.3.1 Demonstration of DNA detection from positive clinical samples and assay verification with negative control samples.

The milestones are identified in the timeline presented in the following subsection. The milestone's original delivery time is first represented in solid blue color. When the expected deliverable time was not accomplished, the effective delivery time is represented in front in a lighter blue (**Figure 1.1**).

1.4. Research Project Timeline

This section presents a Gantt chart with the project timeline.

Figure 1.1 - Research project timeline.

1.5. Research Project Structure

This section schematizes the project development and how each of the chapters fit in the modules required for the device. The research doctorate structure is illustrated below in **Figure 1.2**.

Figure 1.2 - Doctorate structure.

1.6. Structure of this thesis

In this section, the structure of the thesis is presented in **Table 1.1**.

Table 1.1- Structure of this report.

Chapter	Description
1 Ph.D. project contextualization	Introduces the challenges of detecting pathogens at the point of care and presents the aims, objectives, and structure of the project to develop a novel integrated microfluidic device.
2 Introduction	Presents a more detailed review on the problem, state of the art and theoretical concepts required to develop the project.
3 General fabrication and experimental methods	Presents the general fabrication, such as standard fabrication techniques, and experimental method used throughout the project.
4 Bead-based microfluidic platform for DNA hybridization	Presents the rationale for the use of the specific methodologies for the development of a bead-based module to detect DNA via hybridization, and the results obtained. [Article published]

5 Regenerable bead-based microfluidic platform for DNA detection	Presents the development of a microfluidic device able to detect DNA and perform regeneration. Integration of photosensors was also achieved. [Article published]
6 Bead-based microfluidic device for the capture and detection of DNA amplification products	Presents the results of a bead-based device developed to capture product of an isothermal amplification technique. Integration of photosensors was also achieved. [Article published]
7 Bead-based microfluidic chip for chemical lysis and nucleic acid detection of bacteria and virus-like particles	Presents the results of the development of the lysis module. Extraction of nucleic acids was also achieved in this chapter. [Article submitted to publication]
8 Rolling circle amplification in an integrated microfluidic device for quantitative biomolecular analyses	Presents the results from the development of the amplification module using an isothermal technique on-chip (RCA). [Article submitted to publication]
9 Conclusion and Future developments	Discusses the research impact of the work, concludes with remarks around the essential findings and contributions of this work and future developments.

Chapter 2

Introduction

2. Introduction

This introductory chapter describes and discusses micro total analysis systems (μ TAS) and the several modules required to identify pathogens via nucleic acid detection. We present a comprehensive analysis of the several modules required and enhanced relevant works in the literature demonstrating these modules. We also review commercially available μ TAS highlighting the most critical features and gaps that can be filled with new detection devices. Furthermore, we highlighted the pathogens more prominent in nosocomial infections and pathogens characteristics that can influence the detection performance of μ TAS. Finally, we lay the theoretical background that allows us to study microfluidics and characterize biosensors.

2.1. The technology, the problem, and the proposed solution – A brief description

Micro total analysis systems (μ TAS), also called lab-on-a-chip (LoC), are defined as systems that include all the steps required to perform biochemical analysis of a sample. This includes all the steps usually performed in a standard laboratory (e.g., sample preparation, purification, preconcentration, chemical reaction or biological event, and detection) in an automated, miniaturized, single device [4]. The first μ TAS was reported in 1979 by Terry *et al.* and consisted of a miniaturized gas chromatographic analyzer fabricated on silicon [5]. However, with the novel work of Manz *et al.*, published in 1990, the scientific community got interested in the technology. Manz described a miniaturized high-pressure liquid chromatography system fabricated on a silicon wafer and simultaneously proposed the concept of μ TAS [6], [7]. By that time, the main argument for pursuing miniaturization of the chemical analytical systems was enhancing the analytical performance.

Nonetheless, it was also acknowledged that miniaturization would lower reagent consumption and possibly monitor several components using a single device. Such devices soon saw their field of applications broadening from analytical chemistry to biomedical [8]–[10], food and environmental control [11]–[14], or biosafety [15]. Over the years, LoC devices have demonstrated the potential to be used *in loco*,

responding to a pressing need to decentralize the sample analysis in the fields of applications mentioned. Furthermore, improving the analytical turnaround time was a significant advance for these devices compared to standard laboratory techniques. This led to the concepts of point-of-care and point-of-need. A point-of-care (PoC) test is usually defined as a diagnostic test performed near or at the actual patient site, producing a rapid and reliable result (turnaround time of up to 1 hour) used in urgent patient care decisions. For instance, short turnaround times are crucial for patient triage in healthcare settings.

Similarly, point-of-need (PoN) testing is commonly used when the application and sample is not a patient but an environmental, food, or biosafety sample and on-site (e.g., municipal sewage and water supply, farms, crop fields, etc.). In this case, rapid analysis response is vital to contain pathogen dissemination in animals, crops, or even through the air. LoC devices used for PoC testing and PoN testing should follow the ASSURED criteria implemented by the WHO in 2003 [16], [17]. The requirements establish a general guideline for benchmarking a diagnostic test for a given application. This can be useful when selecting a PoC/PoN testing device already available in the market and when developing a new device by trying to fulfill the ASSURED requirements. The ASSURED criteria stand for Affordable, Sensitive, Specific, User-friendly, Rapid and robust, Equipment-free, and Deliverable to end-users. It should be affordable to those that require the test, sensitive enough to display few or no false negatives, and specific to avoid false positives. It should deliver a fast result to enable an immediate medical decision on triage or treatment to perform and be robust enough to withstand the changes in the environment, such as temperature altering the assay result.

Moreover, it should be easy enough to perform, requiring minimal training, equipment-free, or minimal equipment that can be portable, and demanding no plug into an electric outlet. The acronym REASSURED was proposed to accompany the technology's evolution [18]. Real-time connectivity should be embedded in the device, and the device should be connected to a display showing real-time test results, or a cell phone can be used to receive and analyze the data. Finally, the Ease of specimen collection should be considered, and if possible, the collection should be non-invasive or minimally invasive. Another concern coupled with the requirement of Equipment free or simple is that ideally, the tests should be Environment friendly and fabricated from recycled material. After completion, they should be easy to dispose of.

In this spirit, microfluidics technology enables LoC devices for PoC/PoN testing. Microfluidic technology is fluid manipulation in channel design with at least one channel's dimensions within tens of micrometers [19]. And while at the macroscale, inertial forces such as gravity dominate the fluid mechanics, at the microscale, it is the viscosity that most influences the fluid regime. Microfluidics physics is governed by different forces than those that govern fluids at the macroscale mainly because as the systems go down in size, we see an increased dominance of surface effect over volumetric effects. This is a crucial feature of microfluidics devices, a high surface-to-volume ratio typically in 10^6 m. Thus, the fluid mechanics at this scale is controlled by viscous forces, surface tension, and electrostatic/electrodynamics forces [20].

Usually, when working with human clinical samples, analyte concentration varies between 10^{14} to 10^{21} copies/mL. For immunoassays is between 10^8 to 10^{18} copies/mL, and detection of DNA for genomic assays, bacteria, or virus detection ranges between 10^2 to 10^7 copies/mL [21]. Depending on the analyte concentration, we can decrease the sample volume from femtoliter (with higher analyte concentration) to milliliters range (for lower analyte concentration). Therefore, when working with nucleic acid detection in microfluidics, steps of preconcentration and amplification are required. Nevertheless, microfluidic devices offer several advantages for detecting bacterial pathogens. These systems allow the reduction of sample volume and reagents consumption (10^{-6} to 10^{-18} liters), increased speed of reactions, increased sensitivity, a decrease in cost, and simplification of the detection process by developing autonomous systems that allow for pathogen isolation, lysis and nucleic acid extraction, nucleic acid amplification and amplicon detection in one single chip [22], [23].

Pathogens can be defined as a microorganism or an agent of infection that causes infectious disease, also referred to as communicable disease. The most common pathogens include parasites, fungi, bacteria, and viruses. Overall, the spread of these pathogens increases due to global traveling and the growing population, increasing the risk of an infectious outbreak. Many specialists predicted that a major pandemic was sure to happen before COVID-19, caused by SARS-CoV-2 (severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2), and now we are experiencing the effects of not having prepared for such a scenario. In the last report from WHO, lower respiratory infections remained the world's most deadly communicable disease (the 4th leading cause of death globally). And according to the report, infectious diseases are more likely to lead to death in low-income countries, primarily due to poor hygiene and health conditions and barriers to health care services [24], [25]. However, there is also

a threat of these pathogens in high-income countries, and it is particularly important, for instance, in nosocomial infections (hospital-acquired infections).

Antibiotic-resistant organisms, such as MRSA and multi-drug Resistant Tuberculosis (MDRTB), are significant threats to global health due to years of misuse of antibiotics. Then there is also the concern of emerging pandemic viral infections, recently with the ongoing pandemic SARS-CoV-2, but previously with SARS-CoV-1, MERS-CoV (Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus), Ebola, Zika, Influenza, and Chikungunya infections. And if, in the case of bacteria, the misuse of antibiotics is a problem for viral infections, not having antiviral drugs to treat these emerging viral infections is a major concern. There is also a significant fear revolving around foodborne and waterborne pathogens. Some of the most common foodborne pathogens include *Salmonella*, *Shiga bacillus*, *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*) O157:H7, *Bacillus cereus* (*B. cereus*), *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S. aureus*), and *Listeria monocytogenes*.

Hence, detecting pathogens is essential to help decrease antimicrobial resistance, the spread of pandemics, and foodborne contaminations and spreads. Some approaches can be implemented to fight this emergent threat for infectious disease control. The first one is vaccines, antibiotics, curative treatments, which already exist, and the continued search for new ones that can help eradicate when possible. Another measure of the highest importance is a rapid and differential diagnosis. Current detection methods rely on cell culture methods, enzyme immunoassay, and PCR; the test result will often take half a day to 3 days or more to be obtained. These tests are usually centralized in laboratories traditionally located in large cities (**Figure 2.1 - A**). Because of the long time to result, the spread of the infection can occur, creating a chain of infection in the community. With the PoN/PoC devices, we can remove the necessity of performing sample transportation to the laboratory, and the assay simplicity helps improve the turnaround time to a window frame between 15 min to 3 hours (**Figure 2.1 - B**). As a consequence, the possible infection chain in the community is contained.

There is clearly an interest in developing point-of-need devices to perform the detection. Adopting the rapid and easy-to-use test for malaria detection shows the success of adopting this strategy. The development of quick point-of-care tests is one of our significant assets in this war against infectious diseases [26]. Micro total analysis systems (μ TAS) can be the answer to achieving such tests. In the following subchapters, we review the several modules and strategies in microfluidic device

technology developed in the last years that allow pathogen identification in a sample-to-answer type of assay.

Figure 2.1 - Schematics and comparison of pathogen detection using conventional laboratory detection methods - A - and PoC methods - B. Transportation into a central laboratory is required for conventional methods, and the laboratory assay steps are labor and time intensive. In contrast, for point-of-care devices, the analysis can be performed next to or near the patient. The point-of-care devices allow assay automation, decreasing user intervention and turnaround time.

2.2. Microfluidic devices for the detection of pathogens

The detection of a pathogen can be done by searching for different biomarkers. Two of the most common biomarkers used to detect pathogens are antibodies (immunological tests) and specific nucleic acid sequences (molecular tests) [27], [28]. It is also worth mentioning that besides antibodies, aptamers have also been used to detect these pathogens [29], [30]. The binding properties of aptamers can be easily tunable since they are synthesized in the lab without resorting to animals for production, and they are more chemically stable than antibodies. There is also a new trend of using bacteriophage-based techniques since phage replication only occurs in living cells, thus identifying viable pathogens [31]–[33]. Overall, in all the microfluidic devices developed, we can find some closer to μ TAS devices or simple modules of a

more complex system. In the following subsections, we review the state-of-the-art microfluidics devices to execute a part of the process that can include sample preparation and pre-concentration, lysis, amplification, and detection, and in the end, devices that combine all the steps required from sample-to-answer (**Figure 2.2**). This review focused on the devices that perform the detection via nucleic acid-based methods.

Figure 2.2 – Schematics of an ideal μ TAS device for nucleic acid detection. After sample collection, the sample is inserted inside the μ TAS device. The ideal μ TAS device should include inside the device several steps that include pathogen isolation and enrichment, cell lysis, nucleic acid purification and enrichment, nucleic acid amplification, and final signal detection and transduction to report an answer to the user. To increase the assay automation, the device should also include reagent storage, sample injection, mixing, liquid control, temperature control, and others.

Sample preparation I

Sample preparation is the processing of samples that helps to reduce the complexity and interference from the solution after specimen collection [34]. The complexity of the sample preparation procedure will depend on the sample type, the type of downstream analysis being done, and the type of analyte to be detected. It is also important to highlight that after having the liquid sample, an essential step of the sample preparation, a concentration step, or enrichment can be performed before (pathogen concentration) or after lysis (nucleic acid concentration) while removing possible downstream process inhibitors. In this regard, we distinguished a sample preparation (I) corresponding to pathogen capture and enrichment and sample preparation (II) corresponding to nucleic acid extraction and concentration.

Regarding sample type and focusing on clinical samples, the specimen collection can englobe liquid samples (e.g., blood, serum, sputum, aspirates, nasopharyngeal, buccal, or rectal swabs) and solid samples (e.g., stools). Stool samples are quite a complex matrix, presenting an amalgam of constituents normal in the intestinal flora, including bacteria, cells, viruses, and other accessible biomarkers. Furthermore, stool samples can display a wide range of solidity degrees varying from a turbid liquid to a consistent mass. Pre-treatment is required to homogenize the physical aspect of the sample, and purification is also necessary since stool samples contain several organic inhibitors for the downstream molecular diagnostic analysis. Standard methods of stool process include homogenization by applying vortex mixing, purification via filtration or centrifugation, and retrieving the top phase of the solution. In traditional methods, sample preparation usually involves a step where the sample is eluted to a lysis stool solution/extraction buffer before lysis and pathogens can be concentrated in a solution. Blood samples, being less complex than stools, are also challenging to prepare since molecular diagnostics analysis requires the elimination of possible sample interference, such as hemoglobin or heparin [35]. Moreover, sample collection is invasive and requires a healthcare worker to collect. Nasal samples are easy to assemble and can present relatively high concentrations of pathogens for certain respiratory infectious diseases, as in the case of MRSA. A sample with a high viral/bacterial load that the user can easily collect is considered the perfect sample for the μ TAS PoN device.

Sample preparation is a pivotal step that can impact downstream analysis. However, it is challenging to implement sample preparation in μ TAS, and even in commercially available devices, the sample preparation is performed off-chip or simply bypassed, and the analysis is performed directly from a swab sample (e.g., Abbott ID NOW) [36].

The standard methods for sample enrichment use plate culture, which takes at least one day to achieve and up to 5 days for a positive response [37]. A step of pathogens enrichment is usually required since the presence of pathogens in a clinical sample, such as blood, can have concentrations as low as 1-10 colony forming units (CFU)/mL or in severe cases of infection, above 1000 CFU/mL [38], [39]. Pathogen enrichment can be performed using the physical/chemical properties of the pathogens, including size, affinity, and dielectric properties.

In microfluidic devices, several strategies have been employed to concentrate the pathogens in a sample using solid-liquid phase extraction [40]–[42], inertial focusing

[43]–[45], dielectrophoresis [38], [46], acoustophoresis [32], isotachophoresis [47] and immunoaffinity-based methods [29], [48]–[51].

Filters and membranes are usually used on macroscale to perform enrichments of pathogens, especially when large volumes of samples need to be processed. In microfluidic devices, filters and membranes are also integrated on-chip to capture pathogens from the sample matrix. Krafft *et al.* used a nanoporous polycarbonate membrane with a 200 nm pore size stacked between two microfluidic channels [42]. One of the channels contained the sample, and by potential-driven forces, the pathogens in the sample will try to move to the second channel, getting trapped in the membrane. The enrichment step lasted 2 minutes and worked with both *E. coli* DH5 α and *Pseudomonas taiwanensis* VLB120. The membrane, in this case, also acts as a detection device since it is coated with silver nanoparticles, and the bacteria detection is done by Surface-Enhanced Raman Spectrometry (SERS) [42]. Inertial focusing is also used to separate bacteria from the sample matrix. Fuchs *et al.* developed an inertial fungal focuser to separate *Candida spp* from blood using inertial forces applied inside a microfluidic device and achieve a 2.6-fold analyte concentration above the original sample. After separation, an enrichment step was done by growing the fungal cells on-chip and performing direct detection [43].

Immunomagnetic separation is one of the most common methods to enrich and capture pathogens from a complex matrix (combining magnetic particles functionalized with immunoaffinity capture molecules). Vinayaka *et al.* used specific antibody-coupled magnetic beads to concentrate *Salmonella Typhimurium* (*S. Typhimurium*) from spiked blood samples leading to a significant improvement in assay sensitivity achieving a limit of detection (LoD) as low as 14 CFU/mL in blood samples with a total analysis time of fewer than two hours, including sample preparation [49].

In general, the sample preparation step before lysis is done for applications where the sample matrix has much interference, as is the case of whole blood. In some cases, the purification of bacteria and enrichment is enough to detect bacteria directly without needing molecular diagnostic-based tests. However, for samples with a low concentration of pathogens or samples where culture is not feasible, performing pathogen lysis, DNA extraction, and amplifications increases the sensitivity and specificity of the detection. **Figure 2.3** summarizes the sample types from where pathogens can be isolated.

Figure 2.3 – Sample types and possible interferents of each sample type that may interfere with downstream processes making sample preparation crucial for assay development's success. The pathogens' isolation and concentration can contribute to increased assay sensitivity and selectivity. Vortex mixing, centrifugation, and solid-liquid phase extraction are sample preparation techniques that can be integrated into μ TAS devices.

2.2.1. Lysis

After isolating pathogens and previous amplification, it is necessary to lyse and extract the template DNA from the cells. Cell disruption can be divided into two main groups. Briefly, the first group is defined as mechanical methods. Shear stress forces physically break the cell membrane. This can be accomplished by high-pressure homogenizer methods, where the cells are forced through an orifice at high pressure and are compressed, and the high shear force breaks the cell membrane. Another method called impingement submits the cell to a high velocity and pressure so that it hit a stationary phase or a second stream of cells. The contact between the cells disrupts the cell membrane. The bead beating method consists in mixing in the cell suspension microbeads of glass, steel, or ceramic and mixing everything at high speeds. When the beads collide with cells, the shear force produced by the impact leads to cell membrane disruption. The second group refers to non-mechanical methods, which can be divided into physical, chemical, and enzymatic processes. In the first case, physical disruption of the cell membrane is accomplished by non-contact methods that utilize external forces such as heat, pressure, electric fields, and sound energy. For instance, thermal lysis includes repeated freezing and thawing

cycles or heating at high temperatures. In the case of high temperatures, the cell membrane proteins are denatured, releasing intracellular components. In osmotic shock, the different salt concentrations inside and outside the cell make the water molecules go inside the cell, which then swell and burst. In cavitation, the formation and rupture of cavities or bubbles lead to cell lysis. These cavities are formed due to a decrease in pressure, and the bubble's collapse and release of a large amount of mechanical energy in the form of a shockwave disrupt the cell membrane.

Chemical and enzymatic methods use lysis buffers to disrupt the cell membranes, for instance, alkalies buffers. The main constituents of these buffers are sodium hydroxide and sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS). The OH ions will break the fatty acid glycerol ester bonds, and the SDS solubilizes the membrane leading to cell disruption. One downside of this method is that the process is usually prolonged (6 -12 h). Detergents can also disrupt lipid-lipid, lipid-protein, and protein-protein interactions to affect the cell membrane. Finally, enzymes such as lysozyme and protease can be used to lyse specific cells. Lysozyme is usually used to lyse gram-positive bacteria by attacking the peptidoglycan layer and breaking down the glycosidic bond. Commercial lysis kits are also available and can be chosen according to the type of cell to be lysed. Usually, commercial kits use a combination of standard lysis methods. For instance, GenoLyse®, used to extract DNA from bacteria, uses a variety of alkaline lysis buffers and thermal heating. In **Figure 2.4** a summary of the mentioned lysis mentioned is presented.

Figure 2.4 – Types of cell lysis include mechanical methods, such as bead milling, and non-mechanical methods, including physical, chemical, and enzymatic methods. There are also commercial kits available that can combine the previous methods mentioned. All of the cell lysis methods have the potential to be integrated into μ TAS.

There were several attempts to miniaturize the lysis techniques on-chip. Mechanical lysing of pathogens often requires complex electronic instrumentation to actuate the device or include beads that will move inside the chip and collide with pathogens. Designing obstacles inside the microchannels, such as pillars, is also frequently used, although increasing the complexity of device designs. The obstacles squeeze the cells, and their membranes are destroyed. One advantage of this method is that the risk of inhibition of downstream processes is low by not adding chemical solutions. Flanders *et al.* used a grinding lysis step to detect *Bacillus subtilis* and *Bacillus glibbigi*, reaching a minimum spore concentration detected of 5 spores/mL [40]. The device comprised two main fluidic parts: an inlet chamber separated from the outlet chamber by a filter. The floor of the inlet chamber had an abrasive surface, and the ceiling of the outlet chamber was a flexible membrane that, by actuation, allowed for grinding lysis. The lysis was completed in 30 sec. Yan *et al.* used a different mechanical lysis technique resorting to magnetic beads to break down the bacteria cell wall [52]. Rotating magnets actuated the beads and 98% of the bacteria were lysed. Loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LAMP) was performed on-chip, and an LoD of 1×10^4 CFU/mL was reached. Perebikovskiy *et al.* developed a point-of-care diagnostic tool to detect ribosomal DNA from bacteria [53]. The device consisted of a centrifugal disc, and silica zirconia beads were used inside the lysis chamber. Using an array of permanent magnets, the beads were actuated to collide with the bacteria in the sample. In this case, chemical lysis (1 M NaOH) was also used to enhance lysis efficiency. The hybrid lysis detection method lasted 6 min and displayed efficiencies between 80% and 100% for gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria.

Acoustic lysis is also used to lyse pathogens on-chip. Recently, Lu *et al.* developed a device that used a traveling surface acoustic wave for *E. coli* lysis [54]. When using higher power and exposing the cells to the acoustic waves, 90% were lysed, and about 20% of the intracellular material (nucleic acids and proteins) was successfully recovered. However, the device's life was shortened and led to substrate cracking. When applying a lower power, they found a 33% lysis efficiency while allowing for prolonged device operation. Although promising, improvements in device longevity are still required.

Electrical lysis is also widely integrated into microfluidic devices. Electroporation, as the name suggests, creates pores in the cell membrane. By exposing cells to an external electric field, electroporation is accomplished through the creation of a potential across the cell membrane, known as the transmembrane potential (TMP). Pores are made once the potential exceeds a certain threshold, and the intracellular

components are released. Lo *et al.* reported a rectangular microchannel with a planar electrode built on its bottom wall and actuated by alternating current (AC) voltages between neighboring electrodes [55]. Human whole blood was pumped through the device; the cells were lysed entirely (lysis efficiency 100%) within 7 s after the application of a 20 V. While electrical lysis methods usually present the fastest times of the lysis methods, with reasonable efficiencies, they require electrode integration and power consumption, increasing the complexity of the devices.

Thermal lysis usually requires the integration of a heater and a temperature sensor on chip, increasing the complexity of the device. Since the heaters require a power source, the tendency is to use low-power heating, such as ohmic heating, to make system integration easier. Nevertheless, this lysis strategy cannot be applied if the microfluidic device material is permeable to gases (like polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS)), leading to sample evaporation and creating air bubbles inside the device. On the other hand, thermal lysis also eliminates the need for chemical buffers that can compromise downstream processing. Geissler *et al.* developed a lab-on-chip device that integrates thermal lysis and PCR amplification [56]. The chip is made of a thermoplastic material, allowing the sample solution to heat to 95 °C for 5 min. The disk is rotated at high speed during this step (800 rpm) to handle condensation and air bubbles. The lysis efficiency of *E. coli* cells for all the concentrations tested was above 99%. Burklund *et al.* reported a system with a magnetic polymer substrate (Mag-Polymer microchip) that allows for highly controlled, on-chip heating of biological targets when an alternate current magnetic field (AMF) is applied [57]. After being concentrated using magnetic beads coated with a selective antibody from 1 mL to 5 µL, the bacteria were lysed by applying an AMF for 60 sec. The temperature on-chip ranged from 100 °C - 105 °C. This strategy proved to have the efficiency to lyse *S. aureus* from 87% to 100% for a bacteria concentration between 10⁵ CFU/mL and 10³ CFU/mL, respectively. Liu *et al.* developed a single-cell lysis protocol for both gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria, combining thermal, chemical, and enzymatic lysis [58]. The device was made of PDMS, but since a combination of lysis methods was used, the temperature required was 65 °C. In fact, the strategy used was a cycle of - 20 °C / 65 °C heat shock treatment to alter the fluidity of the cell membrane, creating pores due to thermal shock. Interestingly, an ice / 65 °C heat shock slightly increased the single-cell amplification rate compared to no heat-shock treatment. A more aggressive heat shock was tested (ice/90 °C), but no DNA was amplified. The authors postulate that over-denaturation of DNA may have occurred rather than DNA degradation. DNA degradation is associated with temperatures

above 100 °C. Using -20 °C for 2 min and 65 °C for 2 min led to a 90% rate of single-cell amplification with 6.81 ng of the DNA detection limit.

Due to the simplicity of integration in microfluidic channels, there are many reports of chemical cell lysis integrated on-chip. The reagents are commercially available and well-established, and implementing this strategy requires minimal modification of the chip design. The device has a separate inlet for the sample and the chemical lysis reagents for chemical lysis implementation. The channel length is also an important feature to allow enough residence time for lysis. Mixers should also be considered to improve the mixing of the samples and, consequently, the efficacy of the lysis. Recently, Fradique *et al.* developed a microfluidic device to lyse *E. coli* using a commercial bacterial protein extraction reagent (BPER) solution and an enzymatic solution of lysozyme [59]. The retail solution BPER showed efficiencies in the range of 100%. Kaba *et al.* overcame microfluidic devices' low mixing capacity and enhanced chemical lysis by applying cavitation-microstreaming [60]. The device used commercially available lysis buffer and proteinase K (PK) to lyse CHO K1 mammalian cells and perform DNA extraction in under 25 min, with a 77% efficiency. Such a method could also be considered to be applied to bacteria and viruses. Shamloo *et al.* described the process of chemical lysing of cells within a droplet-based microfluidic chip by modeling the assay in a computational fluid dynamics program. The lysis simulation was defined to happen inside a droplet. They conclude that increasing the volume fraction of the lysis reagent (the ratio of the volume initially filled with the lysis reagent to the total volume of the droplet) to 97% achieved a complete cell solution lysis within 0.25 s in a 2 mm long microchannel [61]. Ma *et al.* developed an integrated self-driven device capable of virus isolation, virus lysis, and isothermal nucleic acid amplification. The lysis was achieved by adding the lysis buffer and incubating it with Influenza A virus for 5 min. The detection was performed on-chip by reverse transcription LAMP, achieving an LoD of 87 copies of the H1N1 virus per reaction [62]. In this case, a 2-fold dilution with phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) was performed after lysis to decrease amplification inhibition. Berger *et al.* developed a portable pathogen diagnostic cartridge that detects *E. coli* from whole blood by lysing and amplifying, via LAMP, the extracted DNA. The effect of saponin, Ammonium-Chloride-Potassium (ACK), SDS, and Triton X-100 lysis buffer was studied, and the saponin formulas demonstrated a faster amplification threshold time of around 25 min. Triton X and SDS had threshold times ~30 min, while all samples were amplified by 45 min. The saponin lysis buffer showed an LoD of 10 CFU/ μ L after 50 min of

amplification in buffer, and when tested directly from whole blood, the sensitivity dropped to 50 CFU/ μ L [63].

To conclude, several key lysis aspects must be considered when integrating a lysis strategy on the chip. If we are developing a device to detect low concentrations of pathogens, a method with high efficiencies, such as chemical or electrical, should be preferred. If the goal is to have a portable device, the ease of integration should be increased, which is the case with chemical lysis. Electrical methods are a good choice considering the time for the result and if the application requires a fast assay. The lysis method selected should also be compatible with downstream processing, such as nucleic acid purification and amplification.

2.2.2. Sample preparation II - Nucleic acid isolation and purification

After lysis, nucleic acid extraction and purification are crucial steps that can enhance the sensitivity and specificity of the detection. Standard methods usually follow liquid-liquid extraction (LLE) or solid-phase extraction (SPE) techniques.

Liquid-liquid extraction uses two liquids, where one of them will be preferred by the target analyte. Zhang *et al.* developed a microfluidic platform for nucleic acid purification of gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria (*Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (*P. aeruginosa*) and *S. aureus*) using a phase partitioning technique [64]. The aqueous-phase bacterial lysate was isolated in an array of microwells, and the immiscible organic phase was then introduced into a headspace channel connecting the microwell array. At the optimum flow rate of the organic phase, DNA or (ribonucleic acid) RNA from as few as five bacteria could be selectively recovered in the aqueous phase. Although LLE presented better results than the conventional Qiagen solid-phase nucleic acid purification technique, the use of hazardous organic solvents, which require safe handling and disposal, can be a disadvantage when integrating this extraction method on-chip, particularly when a point-of-care and resource-limited application is required.

On the other hand, SPE is faster and less complex, holding higher nucleic acid yield and purity. On common material used in SPE to extract nucleic acids is silica, either membranes or beads. In commercial kits, such as QIAmp nucleic acid purification kits from Qiagen, a spin column of silica particles is used to purify nucleic acids before nucleic acid amplification. In microfluidics, SPE methods using membranes [65] and bead-based particles (magnetic [41] and non-magnetic) are commonly employed.

Silica membranes can be integrated into microfluidic devices to perform nucleic acid extraction. Loo *et al.* reported a microfluidic disk to complete sample-to-answer detection of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (MTB) and *Acinetobacter baumannii* (*A. baumannii*). A silica membrane, made by adding silica gel on a polycarbonate track etch membrane, allowing for 90% nucleic acid extraction of the pathogens and an LoD of 10^2 CFU/mL *A. baumannii* in blood within two hours after sample loading [66]. Lee *et al.* reported a silica membrane-based DNA extraction-based device [67]. A 3 mm-diameter membrane was selected to process 1 mL plasma with a recovery DNA rate of 78%.

Magnetic silica particles are also a frequent SPE support for microfluidic nuclei acid extraction. Li *et al.* reported a fully integrated cassette that uses magnetic silica beads to extract DNA from *E. coli*, *Proteus mirabilis*, *S. typhimurium*, and *S. aureus*. This device achieved LoDs in the order of 1 to 10 CFU/ μ L in urine samples. The complete process of DNA extraction, including the washing step, lasted 18 min. There was no difference between nucleic acid extraction performed on the microfluidic device and benchtop extraction for the four bacteria tested [68]. Similarly, Wang *et al.* used a continuous flow extraction device to extract DNA from large samples (10 mL) [69]. The channel comprises a magnetic DNA extractor with two concentric half-ring magnets to generate a homogeneous magnetic field. It leads to the formation of magnetic silica beads chains in a serpentine channel of the PDMS flexible chip. This device extracted more than 90% of the DNA of *S. typhimurium* in less than an hour with an LoD of as low as 10^2 CFU/mL.

Paper nucleic acid extraction in microfluidic devices is also reported and commonly used for simple and low-resource applications [70]. Recently, Sullivan *et al.* reported a paper-based device for purifying nucleic acids from whole blood using isotachopheresis (ITP) [71]. The paper-based ITP purifies and concentrates target nucleic acids that are fractionated and filtered via an integrated plasma separation membrane, achieving 88% plasma extraction efficiency. After the extraction, nucleic acids are added directly to recombinase polymerase amplification (RPA) reactions. The device detected as low as 3×10^3 copies of nucleic acid per mL input blood, with extraction and purification taking only 30 min. Although paper extraction is more straightforward and cheaper, for low-concentration detection of nucleic acid, it is essential to select a method with a high yield of extraction efficiency. Silica has proven stable with high extraction yields, regardless of application types, such as membrane or microbead. After nucleic acid extraction and purification of possible downstream inhibitors, the sample is ready to go under an amplification technique.

2.2.3. Nucleic acid amplification

When the analyte concentration in the sample is very low, amplification is indispensable for nucleic acid detection. Implementing nucleic acid amplification test (NAAT) on-chip is of great interest since it increases the test's sensitivity. PCR is the most common DNA amplification technique in centralized labs and has also become popular for implementation in microfluidic devices [72]–[74]. However, the several heating-cooling cycles that allow DNA denaturation, primer annealing, and strand extension require a precise temperature cycler and controller integrated within the microfluidic device. This integration leads to the increased complexity of the device. Isothermal amplification strategies have also been integrated on-chip since they do not require a complex temperature profile to amplify, thus simplifying chip design [75]–[77].

2.2.3.1. PCR

In conventional PCR, the target sequence is amplified using two oligonucleotide primers (reverse and forward primers) that hybridize in opposite strands and flank the region of interest in the target DNA and DNA polymerase (e.g., Taq polymerase). The PCR product (amplicon) is visualized by gel electrophoresis using DNA intercalating fluorescence dyes (e.g., ethidium bromide). In the case of real-time PCR (qPCR), the reaction solution contains a fluorescently labeled probe and a passive reference dye (e.g., carboxy-X-rhodamine (ROX)). The quantification of the amplicon is performed at each cycle, which allows the monitoring of the exponential amplification phase to obtain the quantity of initial template DNA. On the other hand, in conventional PCR, the detection and quantification are only performed at the end of the amplification process and require extra analysis steps. A typical qPCR consists of an initial denaturation step and amplification cycle that includes three major phases (1) denaturation, (2) annealing, and (3) extension, and can be repeated up to 40 times. The initial denaturation is performed at a high temperature, usually 95 °C, and the solution is incubated for a few minutes to ensure that the double-stranded DNA molecules are separated into single-stranded DNA to allow amplification. In the second step of the process occurs the annealing of the primers, facilitated by the change in the temperature to approximately the melting temperature of the primer. Finally, the last step of the cycle occurs extension at 70-72 °C, where the activity of DNA polymerase is optimal [78].

Several groups integrated PCR on-chip in microfluidics as a standalone device or in conjunction with other modules [79]. We can divide the microfluidic devices used for

PCR into stationary/reactor type and flow type devices [80], [81]. The amplification occurs in the static/reactor type by thermocycling to the reagent inside the chamber [64], [82]. For the flow-type device, the sample goes through several channel zones with the distinctive temperatures required in the PCR cycle, or the solution can be pumped between reactors at different temperatures [83]. Recently, Huang *et al.* developed a microfluidic chip-based PCR-array system to detect 21 pathogens within 1.5 h with an LoD of 10^3 copies/mL [84]. Hung *et al.* adopted a strategy of performing PCR in a solid phase coupled with a supercritical angle fluorescence (SAF) microlens array embedded in a microchip for signal detection [85]. The found limit of detection of the LoC system was 0.8 fluorophores/ μm^2 with a sensitivity of the solid phase (SP)-PCR as low as 1.6 copies/ μL for the *Salmonella Enteritidis* DNA template. In recent years droplet, digital PCR has also been applied to microfluidics [86]. This amplification method results in higher sensitivity. However, for all PCR-based methods, the requirement of several temperatures that include high temperatures (95 °C) makes the integration more challenging than for isothermal techniques.

2.2.3.2. Isothermal

To overcome some of the limitations displayed by PCR, isothermal nucleic acid amplification has gained much interest, particularly for point-of-care applications.

Rolling circle amplification (RCA) amplifies the nucleic acids at a temperature of 37 °C, and it is based on the rolling circle replication mechanism present in bacteria and viruses. RCA requires a circular DNA template termed padlock (PLP), a short DNA or RNA primer/target, and a DNA polymerase to start the reaction. The amplification generates a long single-stranded molecule containing thousands of repeated copies of the circular template tethered to the original circular DNA. PLPs are linear oligonucleotides composed of two end-sequences and a linker sequence. The two end-sequences complement a target DNA, such as the DNA of a pathogen. Upon hybridization with the target, the PLP becomes circularized with a nick between the two linker sequences that a DNA ligase can seal, usually T4 DNA ligase of *Thermus thermophilus* (Tth) DNA ligase. DNA ligases demand a perfect hybridization to efficiently join the 5'-phosphorylated end of the DNA strand to the 3'-end of another strand. Phi29 is a replicative polymerase from *Bacillus subtilis* phage phi29 with a 3' - 5' proofreading exonuclease activity. An advantage of padlock probing-based rolling circle amplification (PLP-RCA) is that it can also detect RNA directly, simplifying the process by eliminating the need for reverse transcription when detecting a virus. Although this linear amplification process already provides high sensitivity, it can be

further enhanced by performing another variation of RCA that allows for exponential amplification, such as hyperbranched RCA, multiprimed RCA, or circle-to-circle (C2C) RCA [87]. Sato *et al.* reported the integration of PLP and RCA in microfluidic, used beads as solid support to capture the target DNA of *Salmonella enterica* (*S. enterica*), and performed the amplification [77]. The amplification on-chip took 3.5 h, and 88 ng of *Salmonella* genomic DNA (30 amol) could be successfully detected. RCA has also been combined with aptamers and CRISPR-Cas12a technology to detect pathogens [88], [89].

One of the most widely studied isothermal techniques is LAMP, performed at a constant temperature of 60 °C to 65 °C. LAMP requires 4 to 6 primers, complementary to six specific regions on the target gene, and a *Bst* polymerase enzyme with high displacement activity but lacks a 3' to 5' exonuclease proofreading capability. There are at least two primers present in the reaction, the inner and outer primers [90]. LAMP can also amplify RNA simply by using a reverse transcriptase without requiring additional time for the reaction. However, the method also carries several disadvantages: false positives are still an issue, the complicated design of the four specific primers, and the amplified products cannot be used for downstream experiments. In microfluidics, LAMP has been frequently reported to perform multiplex detection [91]–[93]. Meng *et al.* developed a LAMP-based microfluidic system that can identify *S. aureus*, *Staphylococcus epidermidis* (*S. epidermidis*), *Staphylococcus haemolyticus* (*S. haemolyticus*), and *Staphylococcus hominis* (*S. hominis*) within 70 min, including the hands-on time. LoDs of 20 CFU/reaction for *S. aureus*, *S. epidermidis*, *S. hominis*, and MRSA or 200 CFU/reaction for *S. haemolyticus* were achieved [94]. Compared with other well-known techniques, on-chip LAMP assay provides low sample and reagent consumption, ease-of-use, accelerated analysis, multiple bacteria on-site detection, and high reproducibility. However, the temperature required is superior to the one needed by RCA, which can still be a hurdle to implement on-chip.

Recombinase polymerase amplification (RPA) [95]–[103] and isothermal cross-priming amplification (CPA) [104] are also found in microfluidic devices. RPA is widely implemented since the amplification temperature is 25 °C - 40 °C with a comparable LoD to PCR and can amplify the target in less than 30 min. But the main disadvantage is that it can lead to false-positive results. CPA is a novel isothermal DNA amplification technology developed by Ustar Biotechnologies Co., Ltd. It can be carried out by a strand displacement DNA polymerase at the assay temperature of 63 °C and does not require a nicking enzyme or an initial denaturation step [105]–[108].

After the amplification is performed, transducing the amplicon signal is an essential step and miniaturizing the components required to do so defines the portability of the devices. In the next section, the detection of the amplification product is discussed.

2.2.4. Detection

2.2.4.1. Optical detection

Fluorescence is the most common optical method for molecular sensing in microfluidic systems due to the well-established, highly sensitive, and highly selective fluorescent labeling techniques from the conventional genomic and proteomic analysis [109], [110]. Boissinot *et al.* described a bead-based DNA microfluidic device to capture and detect amplicons via DNA hybridization and fluorescence optical detection. The device had an LoD of 5.6 to 5.8×10^{-5} M [109]. Fluorescence is also the most common detection method commercially available for μ TAS devices for pathogen detection. Colorimetry is another attractive option for optical detection in which analyte binding causes photochemical emission, either directly or with the help of an enzyme label [111]–[114]. One of the advantages of using enzymes as a biological recognition element in biosensor technology is that they are highly selective to a specific substrate or a class of substrates. The second advantage is that enzymes can produce ions, protons, heat, photons, and/or electrons during catalytic turnover, which are all measurable parameters in colorimetric detection. Surface plasmon resonance (SPR) is a common optical detection technique applied in microfluidic devices. Yuan *et al.* reported a precise and replicable DNA sensing platform for specific target DNA oligo detection with a detection limit down to 3.21 fM [115].

2.2.4.2. Others

An electrochemical signal read-out has been proposed for highly sensitive detection of nucleic acids by portable and miniaturized POCT devices. Integrating electrochemical sensors on a microfluidic chip provides continuous measurement and collection of electrical signals from nucleic acids. Ichzan *et al.* developed a DNA detection method using a combination of solid-phase RPA and electrochemical detection [99]. To obtain a high electrochemical signal-to-background ratio, electrochemical-enzymatic redox cycling employing 1,4-naphthoquinone was used. The detection limit for synthetic template DNA was measured using microfabricated indium tin oxide (ITO) electrodes was approximately 0.1 fM. Mass-based sensing devices can also be used to detect pathogens on-chip [116]. For instance, Hong *et al.*

developed a Quartz Cristal Mass (QCM) sensor with a LoD detection limit of 1.6×10^{-9} M [117]. Magnetic detection is also a growing detection mode on-chip [118].

Figure 2.5 – Optical e non-optical detection methods used in μ TAS device.

Overall, all the detection methods featured and presented in **Figure 2.5** have the potential for integration into μ TAS devices. While some will require more instrumentation of the device or even a stand-alone system to perform the detection, such as the case of fluorescence, others could be implemented easily without the need to resource complex instrumentation, e.g., colorimetric detection. However, the sensitivity can also be affected by choice of method. Usually, electrochemical detection methods can achieve higher sensitivities. When selecting the appropriate detection method, a balance between these characteristics should be considered. When all the assay modules are developed (sample extraction, lysis, nucleic acid extraction, amplification, and detection), a μ TAS can be achieved. The following section presents a review of commercially available μ TAS for pathogen detection.

2.3. State of the art μ TAS device

The main goal when developing a device for pathogen detection is to integrate all the steps involved in a molecular diagnostic test in a single sample-in/answer-out device. Ideally, the user would only be required to collect a sample, insert it in the device, and push a bottom. Recent advances in microfluidic molecular diagnostics tests and electric components integration (smaller and cheaper instruments), how these instruments connect to laboratory information systems, providers, and patients, combined with the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic and the pressing need to decentralize the detection of pathogens, had led to an increase in the development, approval by public health agencies, and commercialization of μ TAS devices. Most of these devices have as their primary application the detection of SARS-CoV-2, but not only. The adaptability of these devices (changing the target gene to be detected) allows

translating the technology, with few modifications, to other pathogens and infectious diseases and antibiotic resistance testing, for instance. In this subsection, recent devices approved in the market are presented, discussed, and compared.

Products available and characteristics such as turnaround time, LoD, cost, techniques employed, and sample throughput can be found in **Table 2.1**. A standard key feature of these devices is that they are composed of one (or more) cartridges with all the reagents already sealed inside and adapted for the pathogen to be detected and usually a separated analyzer instrument. Each cartridge is single-use, and after the assay, it is discarded, and no μ TAS device presented here can be fully reutilized. Apart from Lucira's Covid test, PortNAT and EasyNAT from Ustar, and Visby Medical from Click Diagnostics Inc., all the devices required a separate analyzer instrument. This analyzer allows for mechanical actuation in the cartridge, controlled thermocycling, and signal readout, usually in the form of a fluorescence signal. In that sense, we cannot affirm that they are truly portable. Still, they satisfy the requisites to be considered point-of-need devices and allow for decentralization in the diagnostics workflow.

As highlighted in **Table 2.1**, some devices require steps off-chip regarding automation. The EasyNAT, RTIsochipTM-A by Capitalbio, and the Novodiag developed by Mobidiag are examples that require ex-situ sample preparation. The EasyNAT requires nucleic acid extraction using magnetic beads outside the device. Similarly, the RTIsochipTM-A doesn't have a lysis on-chip, and lysis is achieved using commercial kits off-chip, requiring several steps with pipetting and handling. Novodiag device requires sample inactivation with a step of vortexing, chemical lysis, and nucleic acid extraction, all performed off-chip. Most products still rely on skilled operators and central laboratories due to their multiple operation steps with bulky analyzers. Abbot ID NOW tried to simplify the device's complexity by bypassing a sample preparation step and allowing the assay to occur directly in the swab sample. Also, Simplexa by DiaSorin, Visby Medical, and the all-in-one test kit® for COVID-19 diagnosis delivered by Lucira Health requires the collection of the sample, followed by lysis, where the reagents can be lyophilized in the sample vial or the cartridge. The user only needs to insert the sample into the device to obtain a result. Although this simplification can be an advantage to simplify the apparatus, for samples with complex matrixes, the sensitivity, specificity the ability to detect the pathogens can be compromised. Regarding fluidic flow actuation, RTIsochipTM-A uses centrifugal forces, enabling efficient miniaturization, parallelization, and integration of assays. Pressure valves (Visby Medical) and rotating valves (GeneXpert®) are used in other devices.

In general, the devices presented have all functions of (1) lysis and nucleic acid extraction, (2) amplification, and (3) finally detection. The lysis implemented on these devices is mostly chemical. GeneXpert® uses silica beads inside the device to lyse the pathogens when applying sonication. Biofire FilmArray® uses a combination of mechanical and chemical lysis, in which silica-coated magnetic beads are used to break the pathogen wall, and for nucleic acid extraction. The nucleic acid extraction is usually based on SPE, as in the case of Biofire FilmArray®. Silica membranes or magnetic beads are the preferred choices to perform SPE on-chip. We can also conclude that most devices use PCR as the standard gold technique to amplify the nucleic acids of interest. For example, iCubate® uses a traditional quantitative PCR strategy to amplify the target sequence. Cobas® Liat® PCR system displays three different temperature zones to replace traditional Peltier-based thermal cycling, shortening the amplification time (within 20 min). Only the Visby Medical device by Click Diagnostics Inc. presents a continuous PCR on-chip instead of a steady state amplification from all devices using standard PCR. It is common due to their simplicity in temperature regulation, energy consumption, simplicity of the device, portability, and faster turnaround time in isothermal amplification techniques, such as LAMP. The all-in-one test kit for COVID-19 diagnosis by Lucira Health amplifies the nucleic acids by LAMP. Isothermal nicking enzyme amplification reaction (NEAR)/ exponential amplification reaction (EXPAR) is used by Abbot in the ID NOW device. And isothermal CPA is used in the Ustar devices portNAT and easyNAT.

The signal detection of the amplification product is mainly done via fluorescence signal acquisition. Still, in some cases, a colorimetric signal is preferred due to the simplicity of the instrumentation compared to fluorescence acquisition. Visby medical, through an enzymatic reaction (using horseradish peroxidase) and a lateral flow assay (LFA) type of device, gives an optical result. After PCR, the biotinylated product is moved to the detection module, which contains covalently bound capture probes immobilized in the shape of two distinct rectangular spots along a flow channel. The target-specific PCR product is detected using an enzyme-linked colorimetric assay using streptavidin-bound horseradish peroxidase (HRP) and a colorimetric substrate that forms a purple precipitate. The operator observes a color change at the specific locations, indicating an amplified target. Similarly, Lucira Health uses a simple colorimetric readout with a pH-sensing molecule. Ustar Biotech is not clear about the detection strategy of both portNAT and easyNAT devices. However, a proprietary LFA-based detection is mentioned where a flow dipstick can be used to detect biotin- and FAM-labelled analytes. Electrochemical detection is also used by ePlex, which

allows one of the best performances in coupling LoD/Time of analysis. In the ePlex device, nucleic acid extraction from biological samples occurs within the cartridge via cell lysis, nucleic acid capture onto magnetic beads, and release for amplification. The nucleic acid extraction is processed through microfluidic liquid handling. Once the nucleic acid targets are captured, and inhibitors are washed away, the magnetic particles are delivered to the electrowetting environment on the printed circuit board (PCB). The targets are eluted from the particles and amplified. During hybridization, the single-stranded target DNA binds to a complementary, single-stranded capture probe immobilized on the gold electrode surface. Single-stranded signal probes (labeled with electrochemically active ferrocenes) bind to a specific target sequence/region adjacent to the capture probe. Simultaneous target hybridization to signal probes and capture probe is detected by alternating current voltammetry (ACV). Each working electrode on the array contains specific capture probes, and sequential analysis of each electrode allows the detection of multiple analyte targets. This device can detect as few as 190 copies/mL in less than 1h30min. Abbott developed a 'sample-to-answer' system, ID NOW COVID-19, based on their existing technologies with LAMP. With three disposable cartridge modules, the ID NOW system is the fastest device presented, with results in 13 min (5 min for a high positive test), sensitivities of 94.7%, specificities of 98.6%, and an LoD of 511 copies/mL. GeneXpert system can perform pathogen detection in 45 min (30 min for a positive test) with a sensitivity of 98% and specificity of 100% and a LoD of 610 CFU/mL. Cobas Liat from Roche is the device that reported the lowest LoD (<10 copies/mL), and in experimental assays reported in the literature LoDs of 250 copies/mL were achieved. So far, most reported commercial integrated NAT products can detect multiple samples simultaneously, where high throughput detection is usually realized by introducing multiple cartridges simultaneously. GeneXpert® system mainly focuses on infectious diseases, such as MRSA, group A streptococcus (GAS), influenza virus A/B (IAV and IBV), respiratory syncytial virus (RSV) and MTB. Novodiag® delivered by Mobidiag and GeneXpert® system can perform penicillin and myxomycetin and rifampicin resistance tests to carry out personalized medical treatment. In addition, another application area is genetic testing, such as cancer early screening, obstetrics, and gynecology examination. For instance, Idylla®, developed by Biocartis, contains an analyzer and 1 – 8 cartridges, which can detect epidermal growth factor receptor mutations within 90 – 150 min. These single-use consumables need to be modified with new reagents for different application scenarios. Cost-wise, Simplexa DiaSorin presents the lowest cost per test (\$9.56/test) but requires a

benchtop size instrument that costs \$35000. For instrument-free devices, both Lucia kit and Visby medical device cost \$50/test.

Table 2.1– PoC devices in the market for pathogen detection using nucleic acid amplification.

System	Company	Targets/ Diseases	Time (min)	LoD	Type of system	Sample Preparation	Lysis	Amplificat ion technique	Signal Readout	Effective sample volume tested (μ L)	Throughput	Cost	Ref.
GeneXpert	Cepheid	Influenza/ SARS-CoV-2/ respiratory syncytial virus/ Enteroviral meningitis/ Mycobacterium tuberculosis and resistance to rifampicin/ MRSA	20	610 CFU/mL or 58 CFU/swab	Sample-to- answer	Organism in sample captured in SPE filter	Mechanical lysis (sonication)	Stationary Real-Time PCR	Fluorescence signal	300	1 to 16	\$42.7/test; €56000 for instrument	[119]
Biofire Filmarray	bioMérieux	Respiratory tract/ Blood Infection/ SARS-Cov-2	60	330 genomic copies/mL	Sample-to- answer	Off-chip: Sample is first mixed by vortex or inversion On-chip: Nucleic acid extraction using magnetic beads	Chemical and mechanical lysis (sonication)	Stationary Nested Real-Time PCR	Fluorescence signal (Melt curve analysis)	300	1	\$125/test; \$49000 for analyzer	[120], [121]
Cobas Liat	Roche	Influenza A and B/ respiratory syncytial virus/ MRSA	20	< 10 copies/mL; 250 copies/mL	Sample-to- answer	Nucleic acid extraction using magnetic beads	Chemical lysis (Chaotropic agent)	Stationary Real-Time PCR	Fluorescence signal	400	1	\$30- \$75/test; €20000 for analyzer	[36], [122], [123]
ID NOW	Abbot	Influenza A and B/ SARS-Cov-2	13	511 copies/mL	Sample-to- answer	Elution after lysis; Purification n.a.	Chemical lysis (Chaotropic agent) @ 56°C	Stationary NEAR/EXP AR	Fluorescence signal	100 (target), 100 (internal control)	1	\$100/test	[36]

System	Company	Targets/ Diseases	Time (min)	LoD	Type of system	Sample Preparation	Lysis	Amplificat ion technique	Signal Readout	Effective sample volume tested (μ L)	Throughput	Cost	Ref.
COVID-19 all-in-one test kit	Lucira Health	Influenza A and B/ SARS-Cov-2	30	900 copies/mL or 2700 copies/swab	Sample-to- answer	Organism in sample captured in SPE filter; Extraction of nuclei acids using SPE filter	Off-Chip: Lyophilized lysing reagent (on sample vial)	Stationary Real-Time LAMP	Absorbance of colorimetric signal (halochromic agent)	n.d.	1	\$50/test	[124]–[126]
Portable NA analytical system (PortNAT)	Ustar	SARS-CoV-2	n.d.	3000 copies/mL	Sample-to- answer	n.d.	n.d.	Isothermal Cross- priming Amplificatio n	n.d.	80	1 to 2	n.d.	[127]–[129]
Automated NA analytical system (EasyNAT)	Ustar	Respiratory tract diseases/ Reproductive tract diseases/ Malaria	55	200 copies/mL	Manual sample preparation	Off-chip: Nucleic acid extraction using magnetic beads	Off-Chip: Thermal Lysis + chemical lysis	Isothermal Cross- priming Amplificatio n	Fluorescence signal using integrated lateral flow strip	1000	1 to 2	\$15/test; ¥200000 for analytical system	[127], [130]– [132]
RTisochip- A	Capitalbio	Food-born microbe/ Respiratory tract pathogen	50	500 copies/reaction	Manual sample preparation	Off-chip: Different commercial kits can be used On-chip: Nuclei acid purification using centrifugal flex purification system	Off-chip: Commercial kits or thermal lysis	LAMP	Fluorescence signal	100	1 to 24	¥100000- 420000 for analyzer	[133], [134]

System	Company	Targets/ Diseases	Time (min)	LoD	Type of system	Sample Preparation	Lysis	Amplificat ion technique	Signal Readout	Effective sample volume tested (μ L)	Throughput	Cost	Ref.
Novodiag	Mobidiag	CarbaR+/ SARS-CoV-2/ C. difficile	80	313 copies/mL	Manual sample preparation	Off-Chip: Sample inactivation and vortexing) On-chip: Nucleic acid extraction	Off-Chip: Chemical Lysis	Multiple RT- PCR and microarray detection	Fluorescence signal (RT- PCR) and total internal reflection fluorescence [TIRF]-based detection (microarray)	250	1 to 4	€45/test; €45000 for analyzer	[135]–[137]
Idylla	Biocartis	Cancer- associated mutations	90- 150	500 copies/mL	Sample-to- answer	Extraction of nucleic acids using SPE (silica membrane)	Chemical Lysis (3 M guanidinium- based lysis buffer), enzymes, heat and high-intensity focused ultrasound	Real-Time PCR	Fluorescence signal	1000	1 to 8	£115- 395/test	[138]–[140]
ePlex	GenMark Dx	Respiratory/ Blood/ Central nervous system infections	90	190 copies/mL	Sample-to- answer	Nucleic acid extraction using magnetic beads	Off-Chip: Chemical lysis (adding a solution to sample)	PCR	Electrochemical signal	200	1 to 24	\$90/test	[36], [141]
MDx platform iC-GPC Assay™	iCubate	Nontuberculo s mycobacteria	300	106 CFU/ml	Sample-to- answer	n.d.	n.d.	Arm-PCR	Fluorescence signal	n.d.	1 to 4	¥700000 for terminal instrument	[142], [143]
BD MAX system	BD	MRSA/ Influenza / SARS-CoV-2	120- 180	273 to 645 CFU/swab	Sample-to- answer	Combination of lytic and extraction reagents designed to perform cell lysis and total nucleic acid extraction	Chemical lysis	Real-Time PCR	Fluorescence signal	50	1 to 24	\$38/test	[144], [145]

System	Company	Targets/ Diseases	Time (min)	LoD	Type of system	Sample Preparation	Lysis	Amplificat ion technique	Signal Readout	Effective sample volume tested (μ L)	Throughput	Cost	Ref.
Simplexa	DiaSorin	SARS-CoV-2/ Influenza/ respiratory syncytial virus/ C. difficile	60	167 copies/mL	Sample-to- answer	n.a.	Chemical lysis "reaction mixture"	Real-Time PCR	Fluorescence signal	50	1 to 8	\$9.56/test; \$35000 for instrument	[146]
Visby Medical	Click Diagnostics Inc	SARS-CoV-2	30	500 copies/mL	Sample-to- answer	n.d.	Heat and chemical lysis	Continuous- flow PCR	Colorimetric (LFA)	*initial sample volume 500-1000	1	\$50/test	[147]–[150]

Recent advancements in sample preparation have improved the recovery of pure NAs while reducing the time required for sample preparation. Lysis methods have also evolved to simplify the chip requirements. A move towards automation has also occurred by integrating sample preparation steps in microfluidic devices supported by the advancement and miniaturization of electronic components. COVID-19 also propelled the approval and commercialization of more μ TAS devices. But, although a certain number of integrated μ TAS products exist on the market, there is still plenty of room for improvement. Firstly, the detection cost on these products is still relatively high, taking tens to hundreds of dollars, due to the high cost of reagents and consumables. Secondly, most commercial products suffer from an insufficient capacity for quantitative signal readout, especially those relying on isothermal amplification technologies. Thirdly, the high throughput detection on such products is based on introducing multiple parallel consumables with preloaded reagents, which will increase additional consumables' cost and operation complexity. Fourthly, most products still rely on skilled operators and central laboratories due to their multiple operation steps with bulky analyzers, with some exceptions. Since sample preparations are usually performed off-chip, a fully integrated device is required with sample preparation on-chip and can achieve detection limits in the order of 1 - 10 CFU/mL. And finally, expanding the panel of pathogens these devices can detect is also urgent to fight viral infections and antibiotic-resistant bacteria. The development of a microfluidic-based system that, starting from the raw biological sample (namely a buccal swab), will identify the presence of specific pathogens, such as viruses or bacteria, by performing steps of sample preparation exploiting SPE methods (bead-based), universal chemical cell lysis for bacteria and viruses, isothermal amplification (RCA) and integrated optical detection using photosensors will help to satisfy a present need in the market that was still not fulfilled.

2.4. Pathogens of interest

Bacterial pathogens of interest to human health and with clinical relevance are presented in this subsection. As mentioned, in 2017, the WHO created a priority list of antibiotic-resistant bacteria that pose the most significant risk to human health to guide research and development of new detection systems and antibiotics [2], [151]. The WHO has also included in the priority list of antibiotic-resistant bacteria to guide research, discovery, and development of new antibiotics for the ESKAPE pathogens. The ESKAPE pathogens can 'escape' the biocidal action of antibiotics and collectively represent new paradigms in pathogenesis, transmission, and resistance [152]. And recently, the ESKAPE-E was adopted to define the leading pathogens that cause

hospital-acquired infections [153]. The ESKAPE-E includes *Enterococcus faecium*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Acinetobacter baumannii*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Enterobacter spp* and *Escherichia coli* and main characteristics of these pathogens are presented in **Table 2.2**.

Table 2.2 – The leading pathogens causing hospital-acquired infections and relevant characteristics.

Bacterial pathogen	Class and Family	Relevant diseases	Gram stain test	Nucleic acids	WHO Priority
<i>Enterococcus faecium</i> (vancomycin-resistant)	Bacilli, Enterococcaceae	nosocomial bacteremia, infective endocarditis, and intraabdominal and urinary tract infections	Gram-positive	Circular Chromosome	2 (HIGH)
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> (methicillin-resistant, vancomycin-intermediate and resistant)	Bacilli, Staphylococcaceae	pneumonia, nosocomial bacteremia, and infections of the bone and wounds. Toxic shock syndrome	Gram-positive	Circular Chromosome	2 (HIGH)
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i> (carbapenem-resistant, ESBL-producing)	Gammaproteobacteria, Enterobacteriaceae	pneumonia, bloodstream infections, wound or surgical site infections, and meningitis	Gram-negative	Circular Chromosome	1 (CRITICAL)
<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i> , <i>carbapenem-resistant</i>	Gammaproteobacteria, Moraxellaceae	pneumonia, bloodstream infections, brain infections, urinary tract and wound infections	Gram-negative	Circular Chromosome and circular plasmid	1 (CRITICAL)
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> (carbapenem-resistant)	Gammaproteobacteria, Pseudomonadaceae	urinary tract infections, respiratory system infections, dermatitis, soft tissue infections, bacteremia, bone and joint infections, gastrointestinal infections	Gram-negative	Circular Chromosome	1 (CRITICAL)
<i>Enterobacter spp</i> , (carbapenem-resistant, ESBL-producing)	Gammaproteobacteria, Enterobacteriaceae	cerebral abscess, pneumonia, meningitis, septicemia, and wound, urinary tract and abdominal cavity/intestinal infections	Gram-negative	Circular Chromosome	1 (CRITICAL)
<i>Escherichia coli</i> (carbapenem-resistant, ESBL-producing)	Gammaproteobacteria, Enterobacteriaceae	traveler's diarrhea and dysentery, pneumonia, bacteremia, and abdominal infections such as spontaneous bacterial peritonitis	Gram-negative	Circular Chromosome	1 (CRITICAL)

In the context of developing a new device for early detection, we can direct the device to be as universal as possible, enabling the detection of the pathogens of interest

independently of the differences between them. In this sense, two essential characteristics should be considered when developing a biosensor to detect pathogens, especially when using a nucleic acid amplification test-based biosensor. The first aspect should consider the easiness of sample preparation and nucleic acid extraction, which is affected by the cell wall. The second aspect is related to the efficient capture of the nucleic acid of interest, which is usually more complex when the pathogen's genome is double-stranded.

Regarding the first aspect, the gram stain provides an important classification that correlates with the bacteria's cell wall structure. The ESKAPE-E list includes both pathogens classified as gram-positive and pathogens classified as gram-negative. The gram-positive bacteria have a thicker cell wall (20-80 nm) [154]. Briefly, they are composed of two main components the inner membrane and peptidoglycan. They can also present an optional S-layer external to the peptidoglycan layer (**Figure 2.6**). The inner membrane surrounds and encloses the cell cytoplasm and acts as a semi-permeable barrier. Then the peptidoglycan layer is a single, highly interconnected macromolecule outside the inner membrane that gives rigidity to the cell. Peptidoglycan is composed of repeating units of N-acetylglucosamine-N-acetylmuramic acid disaccharides, also called glycan strands. The degree of chains crosslinked varies from the organism and can go up to almost 90% of available peptide stems in *S. aureus* to 16% in *Bacillus anthracis*. It also presents amino acids attached to the glycan strand, and two or more side chains can be crosslinked to one another by a covalent bond. The peptidoglycan layer also contains glycopolymers such as teichoic acids. Teichoic acid is a negative molecule that can work as a protective cloak against antimicrobial compounds. For instance, for *S. aureus*, teichoic acids protect the bacteria against the antibacterial effects of fatty acids [155]. In contrast, Gram-negative bacteria have a relatively thin (<10 nm) layer of a cell wall made of peptidoglycan. Still, they harbor an additional lipid-protein bilayer encompassing the outer membrane with several pores and appendices. The outer membrane is constituted of different phospholipids in the inner face and lipopolysaccharide in the outer face. Proteins are a significant component of the outer membrane and contribute to the integrity and stability of the gram-negative cell wall. Gram-negative bacteria can also present an S-layer after the outer membrane (**Figure 2.6**). An array of paracrystalline proteins constitutes the S-layer and usually contributes to making the bacterial surface more hydrophobic [155]. Depending on the lysis method, gram-positive bacteria may be more challenging to lyse than gram-negative or the opposite. For instance, ethylenediamine tetraacetic acid (EDTA) or

CaCl_2 are outer membrane disrupting agents that promotes electrostatic repulsion, which destabilizes the cell wall structure.

Figure 2.6 - Representative illustration of the cell wall components of gram-negative, gram-positive bacteria, and non-enveloped and enveloped viruses.

Besides bacterial detection, detecting viruses responsible for infectious diseases such as Dengue, Zika, Chikungunya, Ebola, human immunodeficiency virus (HIV), or Influenza through a PoC device would also have a positive impact on the control of emerging infectious diseases worldwide [156]. In this case, detecting enveloped and non-enveloped viruses may affect the lysis efficiency. In the case of non-enveloped viruses, only present a capsid that protects the virus's genetic material (**Figure 2.6**). The capsid is formed by proteins called capsomere. However, in enveloped viruses, besides the capsid, an outer lipid membrane composes the viral envelope (**Figure 2.6**).

Regarding nucleic acid extraction and capture, we can have pathogens that present double-stranded DNA genomes (both for bacteria and some viruses). In this case, there is a need to extract and, previous to amplification, denature the double-strand DNA to allow the start of the amplification. For RNA-based genomes, a reverse transcription step is usually required to synthesise a cDNA that will work as a template for amplification. This increases the complexity of implementing the detection in a PoC device.

2.5. Fundamentals of microfluidics

This subsection summarizes the fundamentals of microfluidics technology, the main physical characteristics of these systems, and the advantages and disadvantages of using these systems for analytical assays. Microfluidic is the technology of fluid manipulation in channels, designed with at least one of the channel's dimensions within tens of micrometers [19]. While at the macroscale, inertial forces such as gravity dominates the fluid mechanics, at the microscale it is the viscosity that most influence

the fluid regime. Microfluidics physics is governed by different forces than the ones that govern fluids at the macroscale mainly because as the systems go down in size, we see an increased dominance of surface effect over volumetric effects. This is a key feature of microfluidics devices with a high surface-to-volume ratio typically in the order of 10^6 m. Thus, the fluid mechanics at this scale is controlled by viscous forces, surface tension, and electrostatic/electrodynamics forces [20]. The characterization of the fluid flow regime in microsystems uses the Reynolds number (Re) (**Equation 2.1**). This adimensional parameter is a ratio between kinetic energy (ρv^2) and viscous energy ($\eta v/D$). It uses the hydraulic diameter of the channel (d), the average velocity of the liquid (v), the mass density of the liquid (ρ), and the viscosity of the fluid (η), giving:

$$Re = \frac{\rho v d}{\eta}$$

Equation 2.1

For non-circular systems, such as rectangular cross-section microchannels, the hydraulic diameter is given by **Equation 2.2**:

$$d = \frac{4A}{P}$$

Equation 2.2

Where $A = WH$, is the area of a microchannel cross-section with a width W and height H , and P is the total perimeter of the walls that are in contact with the liquid [157]. The Reynolds number can be used to evaluate the type of flow regime inside a microfluidic channel. For $Re > 4000$, it is expected a turbulent flow, $4000 > Re > 2300$, we are in the range of transitional flow, and for $Re < 2300$, we are in the laminar flow regime. Usually, in microchannels, $Re \approx 1$, meaning that we are inside the laminar flow regime with predictable fluid dynamics. Due to this, there is no convective mixing inside the microchannels, and the transport of molecules is done solely by diffusion. It is essential to understand if the species under analysis can diffuse across the channel to get to a sensor area, for instance, or if it will be drawn downstream by the fluid flow. The Péclet number (Pe), which is the ratio between the advective and diffusive transport, in **Equation 2.3** assesses the molecular diffusion:

$$Pe = \frac{lv}{D}$$

Equation 2.3

Where l and v are the characteristics length and characteristic velocity, respectively, and D is the diffusion coefficient of the species under analysis. When the $Pe > 1000$ the diffusion of the species can be neglected, and the advection is the main process. If the $Pe < 10$, then the diffusion process dominates, and the advection can be neglected [158]. Microfluidic devices tend to present high Peclet and low Reynolds numbers with simple and steady boundary conditions. As such, the laminar flow does not shorten the diffusion length scales [159]. The laminar flow regime and the short diffusion lengths make mixing solutions challenging, particularly along the microfluidic channel's width. This can be verified for each channel by calculating the characteristic diffusion time along the width (τ_{DW}). Starting with the Stokes-Einstein, **Equation 2.4**, we can estimate the D or the diffusion coefficient:

$$D = \frac{K_B T}{6\pi\eta r}$$

Equation 2.4

Where K_B is Boltzmann's constant, T is the absolute temperature, η is the dynamic viscosity, and r is the particle radius. For a bacterial cell, such as *E. coli*, the diffusion can be modeled by a 2 μm spherical particle. The diffusion time (τ_D) is defined as the time that it takes one molecule to travel the distance l (length of the mixing path) by diffusion as expressed in **Equation 2.5**:

$$\tau_D = \frac{l^2}{D}$$

Equation 2.5

The movement of a single molecule in a fluid is characterized by the Einstein-Smoluchowski relation of **Equation 2.6**:

$$x = \sqrt{2D\tau}$$

Equation 2.6

Where x is the root-mean-square distance transverse by a particle during the time interval τ for a given diffusion coefficient D . For instance, in the case of adjacent

streams, one can assume that along the width, the diffusion distance corresponds to half of the channel width. With **Equation 2.6** it is possible to estimate the amount of time required for each particle of interest to achieve complete diffusion in the microchannel [160]. When the mixing of the solutions is dependent on molecular diffusion, the time for diffusion is proportional to the square of the diffusion distance that limits the mixing. The time for diffusion can be incompatible high with the assay application. In this case, mixing enhancement of the solutions is required, and strategies for mixing should be considered. In some devices, there is an advantage in designing pillars, using hydrogel mesh or even microporous beads inside the channel to shorten the molecules' diffusion length, leading to a faster assay reaction [161].

Moreover, another important parameter is the thermal Péclet number (Pe_{th}) being, in this case, a ratio between heat transport due to advective transport (heat transfer by bulk fluid flow) and diffusive transport (heat conduction), given by **Equation 2.7**:

$$Pe_{th} = \frac{dvpC_p}{k}$$

Equation 2.7

Using the diameter of the channel (d), the average velocity of the liquid (v), mass density of the liquid (ρ), the specific heat capacity (C_p) and the thermal conductivity (k). In the case of chemical reactions that require heat, and we apply heat onto the channel walls to increase the temperature inside the device, this ratio allows us to understand how hastily the heat is displaced by the moving fluid relative to how fast it is transferred from the channel wall to the center of the fluid flow where the reaction can be occurring [23]. When $Pe_{th} \ll 1$, the heat transfer occurs due to conduction (equivalent to diffusion for mass transfer), while for $Pe_{th} \gg 1$, heat transfer occurs due to convection. Usually, microfluidic devices display a low Pe_{th} and the thermal convection is neglected. Since we have a high surface-to-volume ratio in microfluidic channels, the heat/cooling time is usually considered faster than at the macroscale. Nevertheless, the heat transfer could be enhanced by creating a turbulent flow inside the microfluidic channel which can be required when performing assays that require fast temperature cycles, such as PCR for DNA amplification.

On the other hand, there is also a question of the maximum sensitivity a sensor can have. This is limited by the amount of analyte that is present in a sample volume (V) and can be expressed as **Equation 2.8**:

$$V = \frac{1}{\eta_s N_A A_i}$$

Equation 2.8

Using as a parameter the sensor efficiency ($0 < \eta_s < 1$) Avogadro's number (N_A) and the concentration of analyte (A_i). Usually, when working with human clinical samples, analyte concentration varies between 10^{14} to 10^{21} copies/mL. For immunoassays is between 10^8 to 10^{18} copies/mL, and for genomic assays to detect bacteria or viruses the range is between 10^2 to 10^7 copies/mL [21]. Depending on the analyte concentration, we can decrease the sample volume from femtoliter (with higher analyte concentration) to milliliters range (for lower analyte concentration). Therefore, when working with nucleic acid detection in microfluidics, steps of preconcentration and amplification are required.

With all things considered microfluidic devices offer several advantages for the detection of bacterial pathogens. These systems allow the reduction of sample volume and reagents consumption (10^{-6} to 10^{-18} liters), increase speed of reactions, increase sensitivity, a decrease of cost, and simplification of the detection process by developing autonomous systems that allow for pathogen isolation, lysis and nucleic acid extraction, nucleic acid amplification and amplicon detection in one single chip [22][23].

2.6. Assay requirements to develop a fit for purpose biosensor

This section briefly summarizes the fundamentals of standard procedures in analytical chemistry to evaluate if an assay is fit-for-purpose for a specific DNA detection threshold. This is particularly important to discuss the trade-offs between performance and other considerations, such as simplicity of use and cost when developing a point-of-need analytical device.

The microfluidic system should be studied for performance. The relevant parameters to consider when looking at biosensor performance are sensitivity, the limit of detection (LoD), specificity, reproducibility, and dynamic range [162]. To understand the adequacy of the biosensor and to optimize the detection capability of the biosensor for a specific application, cut-off values should be known. The sample matrix could also be an important parameter affecting the biosensor detection capacity. **Figure 2.7** summarizes in a schematic fashion the parameters for biosensor characterization.

Figure 2.7 - Biosensor characterization. A - Schematics of the main flow on the Biosensor analysis and signal output. B - Representation of the signal output for biomolecular recognition. C - Definition of the limit of blank (LoB), the limit of detection (LoD), and the limit of quantification (LoQ).

Specificity is distinguishing a particular substance from others (selective) and capturing a particular target (specific). Therefore, the biosensing system should be configured to detect a particular target by binding with the specific biorecognition element through strong and selective affinity. To evaluate the specificity performance, the measurement of the non-complementary samples should be compared to the specific target. A functional biosensor should be able to distinguish these different samples producing significantly different response signals. Ideally, the non-specific target's resulting signal level is similar to the zero-concentration measurement of the biosensor. One solution to improve the assay's specificity is developing a blocking strategy for the non-specific signal.

Sensitivity can be defined as the slope of the analytical calibration function in the linear region, which can be seen as the response per unit concentration. We can assume that the higher the signal reaction for a given target concentration, the higher the sensitivity [163]. There is also the **dynamic range** which helps characterize the interval between the minimum and maximum concentration that is detected by the system. In other words, it can be seen as the interval between the detection limit and the saturation level of the signal [162], [164]. To be noted that in the lower concentrations and higher concentrations, the signal is not linearly proportional to the target concentration. However, one can define the **dynamic linear range** that only considers the linear region of a fitting curve. The dynamic linear range and the sensitivity influence each other. When sensitivity is high, the saturation level will be

reached at lower target concentrations reducing the detection range. If an application requires to span the dynamic linear range, the sensitivity will be affected and decrease. Both sensitivity and dynamic range can be increased by increasing the surface-to-volume ratio of the sensing part. On the other hand, labeling can also help to improve sensitivity.

For instance, chemiluminescence-based methods proved more sensitive than fluorescence, increasing the sensitivity by two orders of magnitude for fluorescence [165]. **The limit of detection (LoD)** is the smallest concentration that can be detected with a reasonable certainty confidence level [166]. The LoD can be obtained through the **limit of blank (LoB)**. The limit of blank is the apparent analyte concentration expected to be found when no analyte is present in the sample [167]. The LoB is estimated by measuring replicates of a blank sample and calculating the 95% confidence interval value for the results obtained, assuming a gaussian distribution for the raw signals, using **Equation 2.9**:

$$LoB = \mu_{blank} + 1.645(\sigma_{blank})$$

Equation 2.9

Where μ represents the mean value of the blank replicates and σ represents the standard deviation of the blank replicates.

The LoD is the lowest analyte concentration likely to be reliably distinguished from the LoB, and the detection is achievable with a 95% confidence interval value [167]. Several approaches can be used to determine the LoD [168]. The LoD can be calculated according to **Equation 2.10**:

$$LoD = LoB + 1.645(\sigma_{low\ concentration\ sample})$$

Equation 2.10

The samples considered for the standard deviation should be natural such as native serum, plasma, and urine. Artificial or spiked samples may lead to varying results. In this sense, when optimizing the assays in the buffer, the LoD is calculated based on the measurement of the magnitude of the analytical background response, and the standard deviation of the blank is used [168]. **Equation 2.10** can be rewritten as **Equation 2.11**:

$$LoD = \mu_{blank} + 3.29(\sigma_{blank})$$

Equation 2.11

The **limit of quantification** (LoQ) is the lowest analyte concentration that can be quantitatively detected with a stated accuracy, precision, and uncertainty. Usually, these values can be defined as 20% accuracy and 80 - 120% precision. The LoQ can be calculated using several approaches, such as the LoD [168]. Based on the standard deviation of the blank, we can have an estimation of LoQ using **Equation 2.12**:

$$LoQ = \mu_{blank} + 10(\sigma_{blank})$$

Equation 2.12

Accuracy or trueness can be defined as the agreement between the result of a measurement at a given concentration and the true value of the measured concentration. Usually, it should be assessed using nine determinations over three concentration levels that cover the concentration range of interest [168]. Accuracy is influenced by bias and imprecision, reflecting the total error. **Precision** can be defined as the closeness of agreement between independent results of measurements obtained under specific conditions and can be calculated as the standard deviation or as the coefficient of variation (CV), which is the ratio between the standard deviation and the mean values obtained for the measurement of a specific condition [169]. **Bias** can be defined as the consistency deviation from the true value. To quantify the assay bias, one must test the same samples with a gold standard assay and plot the results obtained in the assay developed with the gold standard assay [169].

Reproducibility is also an essential feature of an assay and is characterized by the accuracy and precision of the system measurement by different users using identical samples and assay conditions. Ideally, when developing a biosensor for analytical purposes, the effect of other users should be minimal or nonexistent [162], [169].

The clinical cut-off value is also essential when developing a diagnostic tool. The clinical cut-off ideally gives a value for the analyte that allows distinguishing between clinical conditions and healthy patients. The healthy patient's definition of this value also allows for determining false negatives and positives [162], [169].

Chapter 3

General fabrication and experimental methods

3. General fabrication and experimental methods

This chapter describes the fabrication protocols of the microfluidic devices, starting from the hard-mask fabrication, SU-8 mold fabrication, PDMS microfluidic structure fabrication, and sealing. Microfluidic handling description and signal acquisition using a microscope or thin-film a-Si:H photodiodes are also described. A brief depiction of the process for a-Si:H photodiodes is also provided. The methods are adapted from a publication co-authored and produced during the Ph.D. project [165], [170]–[172]. In the main Methods publication [170], I fabricated the microfluidic devices, designed, performed, and analyzed the results from the experiments related to nucleic acid detection. I also co-write the publication.

3.1. Overview of a microfluidic device fabrication process

The schematization of the process of PDMS microfluidic device fabrication, starting with the hard mask fabrication, then the SU-8 mold, and finally the PDMS replica molding obtaining a PDMS structure that can be then sealed against glass or a PDMS membrane is presented in **Figure 3.1**. In general, the microfluidics devices used in this work presented two heights and to fabrication process required the fabrication of two hard masks (one for each height) and two SU-8 spin-coats and exposure. In **Table 3.1**, all the materials and reagents used are listed, and **Table 3.2** presents the protocol conditions for each microfabrication step.

3.1.1. PDMS mold-replication and sealing

The SU-8 mold is first placed at the bottom of a Petri dish, with the patterned surface facing up, and taped on each corner of its silicon substrate. To prepare the PDMS elastomer, a 10:1 weight ratio of PDMS to curing agent is mixed, degassed for 30 min, and poured into the Petri dish containing the mold up to 0.5-1 cm height. The Petri dish is then left to cure at 70 °C for 90 min. The cured PDMS is then cut using a

scalpel and peeled off from the mold using tweezers. Access holes are punched with blunt 20 and 18 Gauge needles for the outlets and inlets, respectively (see Table 3.2). A PDMS slab (500 μm thick) is prepared by spin coating the PDMS mixture on top of a silicon wafer at 250 rpm for 25 s with an acceleration of 100 rpm/s. This membrane is baked as described above and then cut into pieces at least the size of, or a little larger than, the PDMS piece with patterned structures. The PDMS structures are sealed against the PDMS slabs by first oxidizing both sides using an oxygen plasma cleaner at the medium power setting (11 W applied to the radiofrequency coil) for 60 s. The membrane is placed in contact with the PDMS structure within a few min of the plasma treatment. After the sealing step, the PDMS becomes relatively hydrophilic for a few hours due to the plasma treatment. To allow hydrophobic recovery and stabilization by diffusion of the unreacted siloxane oligomers to the surface, the PDMS structures are stored for at least 24 h before being used.

3.1.2. Hard-mask fabrication

The aluminum masks are designed using AutoCAD software (Autodesk Inc., Mill Valley, CA/USA). Since the design required two different mask levels, all the following steps are performed in duplicate. After cleaning a glass (Corning) substrate by sequentially rinsing with acetone, deionized (DI) water, immersion in Alconox solution for 15 min at 65 °C, and thoroughly rinsing with DI water followed by drying with compressed air, a 200 nm Aluminum (Al) layer is subsequently deposited using a Nordiko 7000 magnetron sputtering system. A positive photoresist (PFR 7790G) layer of 1.5 μm is spin-coated onto the deposited Al layer.

The AutoCAD file is then converted and transferred to a DWLii laser direct write lithography system (diode laser: 405 nm). The DWLii system is then used to photolithographically transfer the pattern to the photoresist. The resist is then developed, exposing parts of the Al layer, which is later removed by wet etching with a standard aluminum etchant. Finally, the remaining photoresist is stripped away, resulting in a patterned Al mask on the glass substrate. The previous microfabrication steps are all performed under class 100 clean-room conditions, except for the photolithography step performed in class 10 conditions.

Figure 3.1 – Schematics of the microfabrication process to obtain the PDMS microfluidic devices. A - Schematics of the Hard mask fabrication process step by step. B - Schematics of SU-8 mold fabrication process step by step. C - Photos of two different PDMS microfluidic devices used in this doctorate.

3.1.3. SU-8 cast fabrication

The master mold is fabricated using SU-8, a negative photoresist. Firstly, a silicon substrate is cleaned by sequential rinsing with acetone, isopropanol (IPA), and DI water to remove any residues of photoresist (used during the cutting process) or other organic contaminants on the surface. Then, the wafer is immersed in a heated Alconox™ detergent bath (65°C) for 15 min (see **Table 3.2**), followed by thorough rinsing in DI water and drying with compressed air. The substrate is then placed in a UVO cleaner for 15 min to degrade any remaining organic contaminants. To fabricate the mold, SU-8 2015 is spin-coated onto the cleaned silicon substrate for 10 s at 500 rpm with an acceleration of 100 rpm/s, followed by 34 s at 1700 rpm with an acceleration of 300 rpm/s, resulting in a 20 μm thick layer. After a 4 min pre-exposure bake at 95 °C using a hot plate, the substrate is allowed to cool down for 1 min, and the hard mask with the design for the 20 μm channels is placed over the SU-8 layer

with the aluminum surface facing down, to prevent a loss in resolution due to scattering effects. The stack is exposed to a 400 W UV light with an energy per unit area of 178 mJ/cm^2 , baked for 5 min at $95 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, and cooled down to room temperature (rt) for 2 min. The development of the non-exposed photoresist is achieved by immersion of the SU-8 in a propylene glycol monomethyl ether acetate (PGMEA) solution for 2 min with manual orbital agitation. After the development, the substrate is rinsed with IPA and dried with compressed air. The second layer with $100 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ height is defined by spin-coating a SU-8 50 film on top of the previous layer at 10 s at 500 rpm with an acceleration of 100 rpm/s, followed by 30 s at 1000 rpm with an acceleration of 300 rpm/s. A pre-exposure bake process is then performed, which involves baking at $65 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 10 min, followed by a gradual ramping-up of the temperature to $95 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, where it is baked for 30 min and then allowed to cool for 1 min. Then, the second hard mask for the $100 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ features is manually aligned to the previous layer using a stereomicroscope and placed on the SU-8, again with the aluminum surface facing down and exposed again to the UV light with an energy per unit area of 416 mJ/cm^2 . The second photoresist layer is developed after a post-exposure bake at $65 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 1 min, followed by 10 min at $95 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and 2 min of cooling down. The mold is developed in PGMEA for 10 min with manual orbital agitation (see **Table 3.2**), rinsed with IPA, and dried. Finally, the mold is hard baked for 15 min at $150 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and left to slowly cool down on top of the hot plate until the temperature drops below $50 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

Table 3.1 - Materials and equipment required for device fabrication and operation.

Reagents/Materials	Equipment /Facilities
Substrate Cleaning	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Glass / Silicon substrate - Alconox solution, Alconox Inc. (White Plains, NY/USA) - Acetone (99.6%), LabChem Inc. (Zelienople, PA/USA) - Isopropyl Alcohol (IPA, 99.9%), LabChem Inc. (Zelienople, PA/USA) - DI water - Petri dish - Tweezers - Crystallizing dish 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Kerry Ultrasonic Cleaning Bath, Guyson (Skipton, North Yorkshire, UK) - Automatic Dicing Saw DAD-321, Disco Corporation, (Tokyo, JP)
Hard Mask Fabrication	
<i>Aluminum Deposition</i>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Clean glass substrate, Corning Inc. (Corning, NY/USA) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Class 10/ 100 clean room - Nordiko 7000 magnetron sputtering system, Nordiko Technical Services Ltd (Havant, Hampshire, UK)
Lithography	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Photoresist PFR 7790G, JSR (Sunnyvale, CA/USA) - Photoresist developer TMA238WA, JSR (Sunnyvale, CA/USA) - Silicon wafer (150 mm diameter), University Wafer (South Boston, MA/USA) - Adhesive tape - TechniEtch Al80 Aluminum etchant, Microchemicals (Ulm, DE) - Crystallizing dish 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Class 10/100 clean room - SVG Resist coater and developer track, Silicon Valley Group Inc. (San Jose, CA/USA) - Heidelberg DWLi direct write laser lithograph, Heidelberg Instruments (Heidelberg, DE)
Mold Fabrication	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Clean silicon substrate, University Wafer (South Boston, MA/USA) - SU-8 50 photoresist, Microchem Corp. (Newton, MA/USA) - SU-8 2015 photoresist, Microchem Corp. (Newton, MA/USA) - Propylene glycol monomethyl ether acetate (PGMEA, 99.5%), Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO/USA) - Isopropyl Alcohol (IPA, 99.9%), LabChem Inc. (Zelienople, PA/USA) - Styrofoam box - 2 crystallizing dishes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Vertical laminar airflow cabinet, FASTER-BSC-EN (Cornaredo, IT) - UVO Cleaner 1444AX-220, Jelight Company, Inc. (Irvine, CA/USA) - Spin coater, Laurell Technologies Corp. (North Wales, PA/USA) - Digital hotplate, Stuart (Staffordshire, UK) - UV Light (254 nm, 400 W), UV Light Technology Limited (Birmingham, UK)

- Tweezers	- Stereo microscope, AmScope (Irvine, CA/USA)
- Aluminum foil	
PDMS Casting and Sealing	
- Plastic cup	- Analytical Balance, Scientech (Bradford, MA/USA)
- Sylgard 184 poly(dimethyl)siloxane, Dow Corning (Midland, MI/USA)	- Vacuum desiccator, Bel-Art Products (South Wayne, NJ/USA)
- Spatula	- Oven loading model 100-800 (70°C), Memmert (Schwabach, DE)
- Petri dish	- Expanded oxygen plasma cleaner PDC-002-CE (200 W), Harrick Plasma (Ithaca, NY/USA)
- Scalpel	
- Blunt syringes tips (18 and 20 Gauge), Instech Laboratories, Inc. (Plymouth Meeting, PA/USA)	
Microfluidic Handling	
- Insulin syringe 1 mL U-100 Luer-Lock, Codan (Lensahn, DE)	- Syringe pump NE- 1002X, New Era Pump Systems, Inc. (Farmingdale, NY/USA)
- Luer stub adapter (20 Ga), Instech Laboratories, Inc. (Plymouth Meeting, PA/USA)	- Inverted Fluorescence Microscope CKX41, Olympus (Shinjuku, Tokyo, JP)
- Polyethylene tubing (BTPE-90), Instech Laboratories, Inc. (Plymouth Meeting, PA/USA)	- CCD color camera XC30, Olympus (Shinjuku, Tokyo, JP)
- Tubing couplers (SC20/15), Instech Laboratories, Inc. (Plymouth Meeting, PA/USA)	- Leica DMLM Microscope, Leica Microsystems (Wetzlar, DE)
- Syringe filter (0.2 µm), Whatman GE healthcare Life Sciences (Piscataway, NJ/USA)	- Digital color camera DFC300FX, Leica Microsystems (Wetzlar, DE)

3.1.4. PDMS mold-replication and sealing

The SU-8 mold is first placed at the bottom of a Petri dish, with the patterned surface facing up, and taped on each corner of its silicon substrate. To prepare the PDMS elastomer, a 10:1 weight ratio of PDMS to curing agent is mixed, degassed for 30 min, and poured into the Petri dish containing the mold up to 0.5-1 cm height. The Petri dish is then left to cure at 70 °C for 90 min. The cured PDMS is then cut using a scalpel and peeled off from the mold using tweezers. Access holes are punched with blunt 20 and 18 Gauge needles for the outlets and inlets, respectively (see **Table 3.2**). A PDMS slab (500 µm thick) is prepared by spin coating the PDMS mixture on top of a silicon wafer at 250 rpm for 25 s with an acceleration of 100 rpm/s. This membrane is baked as described above and then cut into pieces at least the size of, or a little larger than, the PDMS piece with patterned structures. The PDMS structures are sealed against the PDMS slabs by first oxidizing both sides using an oxygen plasma

cleaner at the medium power setting (11 W applied to the radiofrequency coil) for 60 s. The membrane is placed in contact with the PDMS structure within a few min of the plasma treatment. After the sealing step, the PDMS becomes relatively hydrophilic for a few hours due to the plasma treatment. To allow hydrophobic recovery and stabilization by diffusion of the unreacted siloxane oligomers to the surface, the PDMS structures are stored for at least 24 h before being used.

Table 3.2 - Timeline of the sequence of steps required to fabricate the microfluidic device.

Step	Time Frame
Designing the mask using AutoCAD software	As needed
Cleaning of glass and silicon substrates	30 min
Hard mask fabrication (two hard masks)	3 h 10 min (Total time)
Aluminum deposition	15 min
Photoresist spin-coating	5 min
DWL exposure	2 x 60 min
Development of exposed photoresist	5 min
Aluminum etching	10 min
Photoresist removal	5 min
Mold fabrication	Approximately 2 h 15 min (Total time)
Photoresist spin-coating 1	44 s
Pre-exposure bake	4 min
Mask 1 alignment	As needed
UV exposure (5,94 mW/cm ²)	30 s
Post-exposure bake	7 min
Photoresist development	2 min
Hard bake	15 min
Photoresist spin-coating 2	40 s
Pre-exposure bake	40 min
Mask 2 alignment (manual)	As needed
UV exposure (5,94 mW/cm ²)	1 min 10 s
Post- exposure bake	11 min
Photoresist development	10 min
Final hard bake	15 min
PDMS casting and sealing	3 h 30 min (Total time)
Preparation of PDMS	10 min

Degassing PDMS mixture	40 min
Baking PDMS	90 min
Peeling off PDMS and punching holes	60 min
PDMS sealing to glass/PDMS	10 min
Device stabilization	24 hours (recommended)

3.2. Fabrication of a-Si:H *p-i-n* photodiodes

Unless stated otherwise, the a-Si:H *p-i-n* photodiodes were fabricated following the procedure next described. The *p-i-n* a-Si:H photodiodes with (**Figure 3. 2 – A – I**) and without (**Figure 3. 2 – A – II**) an amorphous silicon carbide (a-SiC:H) absorption filter were used for fluorescence and chemiluminescence assays, respectively. In summary, the fabrication of the photodiodes started with the deposition of a bottom Al contact layer (200nm) by DC magnetron sputtering and patterned using DWL. Then a sequence of thin films was deposited, first an n-type a-Si:H (100 nm), then an intrinsic a-Si:H (500 nm), and finally a p-type a-Si:H (100 nm). This deposition was done on top of a bottom Al contact by radio frequency plasma enhanced chemical vapor deposition (rf-PECVD) by decomposition of silane for the intrinsic layer and a gas mixture of silane and phosphine or diborane for n- or p-type doping, respectively. Using direct-write optical lithography (Heidelberg Instruments DWLii), mesa junctions (200 × 200 μm) were patterned and defined by reactive ion etching (RIE). After this, a passivation layer of SiNx (100 nm) was deposited by rf-PECVD and patterned through a lift-off process to open a via through which electric contact could be made between the p-type a-Si:H layer and the indium tin oxide (ITO) transparent conductive top contact. The 50 nm ITO layer top contact was deposited by DC magnetron sputtering and circumscribed by lift-off. After depositing and patterning Al lines to address the top contact, the device was again passivated with 200 nm SiNx. A 1.8 μm-thick a-SiC:H filter was deposited by rf-PECVD and patterned by lift-off for the fluorescence assays. The a-SiC:H layer acts as an absorption filter to block the excitation light ($\lambda_{ex} = 405$ nm) while being almost transparent to the emission light of the Atto 430 LS fluorophore ($\lambda_{em} = 540$ nm). The photodiode chips were then diced and wire-bonded to printed circuit boards (PCBs). Data regarding the performance and spectral properties of the filter is depicted in detail and can be found elsewhere [22].

Figure 3. 2 - Schematics of the thin-film a-Si:H photodiodes. A – I thin-film a-Si:H photodiode with integrated a-SiC:H filter used for fluorescence assays. A – II a-SiC:H filter photodiode used for chemiluminescence and colorimetric assays. This device were fabricated at INESC MN by former Ph.D. student Denis Santos.

3.3. Microfluidic structure general handling

Commercially available beads are typically provided as a slurry in a storage buffer (ethanol 20%), so the first step is to homogenize the bead stock using a pipette, ensuring thorough mixing. Then, a specific volume of stock solution is added to a polyethylene glycol (PEG) 8000 30% (w/w) solution to obtain a final solution with 1-2% bead volume. A viscous solution allows the beads to remain suspended and homogeneously dispersed without significant settling, thus avoiding clogging problems when flowing the beads inside the micro-columns (see **Table 3.2**). The flow is driven by applying negative pressure at the outlet via a syringe pre-filled with water up to about half the total capacity, adapted to a syringe pump, and connected to the microfluidic structure via capillary tubing and a metal coupler. It is essential that the syringe and capillary tubing always remain free of air gaps that may hinder the rapid decrease in pressure; therefore, the syringe should be appropriately purged until the liquid reaches the tip of the metal coupler before inserting the coupler about 2/3 of the way (see **Table 3.2**) into the 20 Gauge access holes. The pipette tip (2-200 μL) containing the bead suspension should be inserted roughly halfway (see **Table 3.2**) into the inlet access holes punched using the 18 Gauge blunt syringe, and the syringe pump subsequently turned on with the appropriate flow rate. Within approximately 40 s, the beads accumulate at the interface region of the microchannels and fill the entire field of view of the microscope. After the first liquid flowing step, it is critical that the metal adapter connected to the syringe pump be removed before removing the pipette tip. Otherwise, any accumulated negative pressure can quickly trap air bubbles at the interface between the liquid column in the inlet hole and the subsequent solution. Subsequently, the PEG solution is washed from the micro-columns using an appropriate buffer solution (e.g., PBS).

3.4. Optical signal transduction

3.4.1. Microscopy detection

Fluorescence or chemiluminescence measurements are performed using an inverted fluorescence microscope (Olympus CKX41) coupled to a charged couple device (CCD) color camera (Olympus XC30) and 50 W short arc mercury lamp, or a fluorescence microscope (Leica DMLM) coupled to a digital camera (DFC300FX) and a 100 W short arc mercury lamp. For each microscope, three different filters were available. Olympus microscope presented a U filter (λ_{ex} Band Pass (BP): 360 – 370 nm; λ_{em} Long Pass (LP): 420 nm), B filter (λ_{ex} BP: 460 – 490 nm; λ_{em} LP: 520 nm), and G filter (λ_{ex} BP: 480 – 550 nm; λ_{em} LP: 590 nm). Leica microscope presented a D filter (λ_{ex} BP: 355 – 425 nm; λ_{em} LP: 470 nm), I3 filter (λ_{ex} BP: 450 – 490 nm; λ_{em} LP: 515 nm), and TX2 filter (λ_{ex} BP: 560/40 nm; λ_{em} BP: 645/75 nm). Details of the acquisition of images are also presented throughout the results chapters, as they are specific to each assay. Images are analyzed using ImageJ software, and, in each case, the average grayscale quantification is obtained by considering the entire end-section of the micro-columns.

3.4.2. Photodiodes detection

To measure the optical signal using the photodiodes, an optical table was used to set the setup. The photodiodes were bonded to an oriented circuit board (PCB), and the photodiode pads were wire bonded to the PCB pads. The photocurrent (measured at 0V) was recorded using a picoammeter (Model 237; Kiethley Instruments, Inc.) connected to the photodiode PCB via coaxial and triaxial connections was used. This connection allowed noise mitigation. The measurements from the picoammeter are acquired using a general interface bus (GPIB) by a computer graphical user interface (GUI) programmed in Python and PyQt4, which is used to read, process, store and plot the raw data. Former Ph.D. student Denis Santos developed the interface. The microfluidic devices, particularly the areas with the packed beads, were manually aligned directly on top of the photodiode. A laser with the appropriate excitation wavelength was shone on top of the microfluidic device with the packed beads for fluorescence measurements. Details of the acquisition of images are also presented throughout the results chapters, as they are specific to each assay.

Chapter 4

Bead-based microfluidic platform for DNA hybridization

4. Development of a rapid bead-based microfluidic platform for DNA hybridization using single- and multi-mode interactions for probe immobilization

This chapter reports the development of rapid and simple bead-based microfluidic platform to detect a specific short DNA strand (22-mer DNA sequence) via hybridization using single- and multi-mode interactions for probe immobilization. The microfluidic device uses commercial nanoporous chromatography beads as solid support for probe DNA immobilization, using either a single-mode electrostatic interaction or multi-mode interactions (electrostatic and hydrophobic). Using a mass balance approach, a probe density of $2.4 \times 10^{13} \pm 18$ (\pm RSD%) molecules/cm² was quantified in optimized conditions, which was found to provide hybridization efficiencies above 95% and a hybridization dissociation constant below 1 nM. Comparing targets with different optical labels, namely Atto 430LS, quantum dots, and horseradish peroxidase, the lowest limit of detection of 9.5 ± 1.1 pM was achieved with an assay time of 10 min using a quantum dot label coupled with a multi-mode immobilization. These results highlight the system's potential to be applied as a simple and highly sensitive DNA hybridization platform, achieving low pM sensitivities without needing a DNA amplification procedure. The contents of this chapter are summarized and reproduced from one original research article [171], based on experimental results obtained during my MSc project [173] and the beginning of the Ph.D. project. I fabricated the microfluidic devices. Co-conceived, designed, performed, and analyzed the experimental results. I was the main writer of the publication.

4.1. Introduction

Integrated DNA hybridization-based miniaturized biosensors are currently of great interest to allow decentralized DNA testing that provides high specificity and sensitivity while being faster, simpler, and cheaper than conventional lab-based methods typically comprising PCR, performed in real-time or followed by gel-

electrophoresis. Furthermore, these biosensors have been used in a wide range of applications not only in health monitoring and diagnostics [174]–[176] but as well in food analysis [177], [178], environmental monitoring [179] and bioterrorism [180]. Despite the potential of those biosensors, only a few have reached the market [181], [182]. One of the reasons for this is that the direct detection of DNA without pre-amplification is very challenging since target concentrations in a real sample are typically in the fM to pM range [183]. Thus, the development of portable DNA biosensors providing low LoD in a simple and fast manner without needing a pre-amplification step is in great demand for integration in LoC devices. Several recent reports in the literature have described the coupling of microbeads with microfluidic systems to improve further the sensitivity of the detection assays [184]–[189]. Much of this research has focused on using magnetic beads since they are biocompatible, can be easily functionalized, have a large surface area, and can be controlled by a magnetic field. For example, a microfluidic device for the separation of target DNA from a complex mixture was developed by Wang *et al.* using streptavidin-coated magnetic beads to immobilize probe DNA, used to capture the target DNA within 15 min [184]. In another work, a microfluidic system with integrated loop-mediated isothermal amplification was developed, incorporating specific probe-conjugated magnetic beads to recognize target DNA from MRSA in a lysate solution [185]. The system presented a LoD $\sim 6 \times 10^{-18}$ M after a total analysis time of 60 min. More recently, a microfluidic system to detect RNA from the Ebola virus was developed using 4-formyl benzamide functionalized magnetic beads with covalently immobilized probe DNA [186]. This system achieved a detection limit below the value required for pre-symptomatic detection of the infection (0.04 plaque-forming units (PFU)/mL) for clinical samples and a detection time of roughly 60 min. Other groups have focused on the use of non-magnetic beads using physical entrapment to confine the beads to specific regions, such as filters [190], chambers [191], membranes [192] or two-level microchannels [193]. Many reported bead-based microfluidic systems for DNA detection use biotin-streptavidin interactions for probe immobilization. For instance, Kim *et al.* successfully used SuperAvidin-coated beads to immobilize probe DNA (biotin-streptavidin bond), allowing an enhanced detection of target DNA within 14 min with an LoD of 10^{-10} M [187]. A different study by Sochol *et al.* presented a microfluidic system that used streptavidin-coated polystyrene beads to immobilize a molecular beacon probe DNA [188]. This system could parallelly detect three different target DNA (3×10^{-5} M). In another work, polystyrene and Sepharose beads were used for primer immobilization and rolling circle amplification [189]. This microfluidic system detected viral pathogens within

15 min with an LoD of 10^{-13} M. Other groups have focused on using nanoporous beads, offering increased surface-to-volume ratios and potentially further improving the sensitivity of the system [194]. These have been employed in microfluidics to study protein breakthrough curve analysis [195], [196], toxin screening [193], and detection of protein cancer biomarkers [197]. However, few have focused on using nanoporous beads for DNA detection, and in all these cases, an amplification step was included in the assay [189], [198]. Furthermore, electrostatic, or multi-mode commercial chromatography beads explored for probe DNA immobilization in microfluidics systems potentially allow a rapid, cost-effective, and single-step analysis using a highly stable solid support, which can be highly advantageous compared to other strategies requiring expensive biomolecules (such as thiol-modified probes) and lengthy covalent functionalization procedures, long incubation times and several washing steps [186], [197].

This chapter reports the development of a bead-based microfluidic optical biosensor for detecting DNA using commercial electrostatic or multi-modal chromatography beads, tested without pre-amplification, to specifically detect a model 22-mer DNA strand. Two different types of microbeads were used as an immobilization platform providing (i) single-mode (electrostatic) or (ii) multi-mode (electrostatic, hydrogen bonding, and hydrophobic) interactions with probe DNA. To improve the non-specific signal, a blocking step using sodium polyacrylate (PA) molecules was employed and optimized. Moreover, different optical detection modes were tested and compared using (i) an organic fluorophore, (ii) a quantum-dot, and (iii) an enzyme label. Finally, the probe DNA density, hybridization efficiency, and equilibrium dissociation constant (K_d) were quantified to characterize this system.

4.2. Materials and experimental methods

4.2.1. DNA oligonucleotides and beads

Synthetic oligonucleotide sequences (**Table 4.1**) were purchased from StabVida Genomics Lab. The stock solution was prepared by resuspension of the lyophilized DNA in 1x TE buffer (10 mM Tris, 1 mM EDTA, pH 8.0.) (Sigma-Aldrich) to a final concentration of 100 μ M and stored at -20°C . The streptavidin (Sigma-Aldrich) stock solution was diluted to a 1 mg/mL working solution in PBS and held at -20°C . Q Sepharose Fast Flow (QS) beads and Capto Adhere (CA) beads were purchased from GE Healthcare as a slurry in 20% ethanol (**Figure 4.1**).

Table 4.1 - Description of the oligonucleotide sequences used in this work with respective modifications.

Oligonucleotide	Sequence	5' Mod	3' Mod
Atto 430LS - probe DNA - biotin	5'-CAGGTCAAAGGGTCCTTAGGGA-3'	Atto 430LS	Biotin
probe DNA - biotin	5'-CAGGTCAAAGGGTCCTTAGGGA-3'	None	Biotin
cDNA – Atto 430LS	5'-TCCCTAAGGACCCTTTTGACCTG -3'	None	Atto 430LS
ncDNA – Atto 430LS	5'-CGTGTTCGTTACATCTGTCCGT -3'	None	Atto 430LS
cDNA – biotin	5'-TCCCTAAGGACCCTTTTGACCTG -3'	None	Biotin
ncDNA – biotin	5'-CGTGTTCGTTACATCTGTCCGT -3'	None	Biotin

Figure 4.1 - General overview of the microfluidic setup and the DNA detection strategies using nanoporous microbeads. A - Microchannel design of the two-height microfluidic structure. Fluid flow was imposed by applying a negative pressure at the outlet. B - Schematics of the nanoporous microbeads used in this work (B - I) Q Sepharose (QS) bead with strong ion exchange for ionic interactions and (B - II) Capto-Adhere (CA), a multi-modal bead with ionic, hydrophobic and hydrogen bonding interactions. C - Schematics of the detection assay architecture for the three types of labels used: (C - I) organic fluorophore Atto 430LS, (C - II) quantum-dot 605, and (C - III) enzyme HRP; with the respective wavelengths of excitation and emission.

4.2.2. Microfluidic experimental method

The liquids were driven inside the microchannel using a syringe pump exerting a negative pressure at the outlet (NE-1002X, New Era Pump System Inc., USA) (**Figure 4.1 - A**). The beads (**Figure 4.1 – B**) were first suspended in a solution of polyethylene glycol 8000 (PEG) (Sigma-Aldrich) and packed inside the channel, followed by a washing step with PBS. Two experiments using cDNA or ncDNA were performed simultaneously in two independent microchannels for the hybridization assays. The flow rates and the duration of the steps used for each experimental step are detailed in **Table 4.2**. A short washing with PBS was performed between immobilization, blocking, and molecular recognition steps.

Table 4.2 - Description of on-chip steps performed in the microfluidic device with the respective flow rates and assay times for fluorescence and chemiluminescence assays. Steps not applied in a given assay are identified as not applicable (n.a.). Off-chip steps are described in the text.

Step		Fluorescence measurements		Chemiluminescence measurements	
		Flow rate ($\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$)	Time (min)	Flow rate ($\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$)	Time (min)
General steps	Packing of beads	5	1	5	1
	Short washing with PBS	5	1	5	1
	Long washing with PBS	5	4	n.a	n.a
	Hybridization buffer	5	5	n.a	n.a
	Luminol	n.a	n.a	20	3
Blocking steps	Blocking of beads	5	2	n.a	n.a
	BSA 4% (Blocking of channel walls)	1	5	n.a	n.a
	Casein (Blocking of channel and beads)	n.a	n.a	5	5
Immobilization steps	(Atto 430LS - biotinylated probe DNA - streptavidin)	1	10	n.a	n.a
	(biotinylated probe DNA - streptavidin)	1	10	n.a	n.a
	BSA-FITC	1	5	n.a	n.a

Molecular recognition steps	target DNA – Atto 430LS (Blocking optimization assays)	1	10	n.a	n.a
	target DNA – Atto 430LS (Hybridization assays)	7	5	n.a	n.a
	target DNA – biotinylated	7	5	7	5
	Qdots™ 605 - streptavidin	5	3	n.a	n.a

4.2.3. Fluorescence-based assays

Preliminary studies on the effect of buffer conductivity on the immobilization step assays were performed using bovine serum albumin (BSA)-FITC (1.25 mg/mL), purchased from Sigma Aldrich and diluted to concentrations of 10, 50, 100, and 200 µg/mL in PBS. To optimize the BSA-FITC concentration to be immobilized onto the beads, the channel walls were first blocked by flowing 4% BSA inside the channel to avoid nonspecific adsorption of the BSA-FITC. Images were acquired using a light exposure time of 50 ms and a gain of 2.5 dB. Water from a Milli-Q purification system (Millipore, USA), PBS, and 20x concentrate saline sodium citrate (SSC) buffer purchased to Sigma Aldrich, concentrated, and diluted in Milli-Q water to a 4% SSC were used as hybridization buffers.

Blocking optimization assays were performed using an Olympus CKX41 inverted fluorescence microscope coupled to a CCD color camera (Olympus XC30), with a 50 W mercury arc lamp and equipped with a filter cube with a band-pass excitation of 460-490 nm and a long-pass emission of 520 nm. Images were acquired with a 100× total magnification. BSA (Sigma Aldrich) was prepared from a stock solution at a concentration of 1 mg/mL and diluted in PBS to a 4% (w/v) solution. Sodium Polyacrylate (PA) 45% (w/w) (8000 average molecular weight) and PA 35% (15000 average molecular weight) (all from Sigma Aldrich) were diluted in PBS to 5%, 1% and 0.1% (w/w) working solutions. Salmon sperm DNA (saDNA) at a concentration of 200 µg/mL was diluted to 10 µg/mL in PBS. PBS was used as a control for blocking agents. The duration of the blocking step was optimized to ensure that the blocking agent did not remove more than 50% of the complex biotinylated probe DNA - streptavidin immobilized onto the QS beads (**Figure 4.2 - A**). For the blocking efficacy tests, fluorescence signal from the probe DNA - Atto 430LS labeled strands was acquired using an exposure time of 50 ms and gain of 2.5 dB (**Figure 4.2 - B**). For the hybridization step in the blocking assay optimization, the fluorescence signal of the target DNA – Atto 430 LS labeled was obtained with an exposure time of 5 s and

gain of 5 dB (**Figure 4.2 - C**).

Figure 4.2 – Schematics of the assays for blocking optimization using Q Sepharose beads. A short PBS washing step at 5 μ L/min for 1 minute was performed between assay steps. **A** - Blocking time optimization assay. **B** - Blocking efficiency assay. **C** - Blocking optimization assay monitored by hybridization of target DNA.

The hybridization experiments and quantitative analysis were performed in a Leica DMLM microscope equipped with a DFC300FX CCD camera and a 100 W mercury arc lamp coupled to a blue light excitation filter with a band-pass excitation of 450-490 nm and a long-pass emission of 515 nm, for measurements performed with Atto 430LS, or with a UV/violet filter with a band-pass excitation of 355-425 nm and a long-pass emission of 470 nm excitation, in the case of Qdots™ 605 (QDots). Images were acquired with a 160 \times magnification. Biotinylated probe DNA (9.4 μ M) was first incubated with streptavidin (2.35 μ M) in PBS for 10 min. CA beads or QS beads were added to the previous solution to obtain a final solution with 0.12% bead volume. They were incubated for an additional 10 min with orbital agitation at 3000 rpm. After this, PA 8000 was added to the previous solution, obtaining a final solution with PA 8000 5% volume, which was incubated for 2 min with QS beads or 5 min with CA beads. The solution with the beads was then packed inside the channel, and detection using an organic fluorophore (**Figure 4.1 – C I**), a synthetic fluorophore (**Figure 4.1 – C II**), and an enzyme (**Figure 4.1 – C III**) was performed as described below. For the organic fluorophore the signal was acquired with an exposure time of 1 s and 1 \times gain and 320 \times magnification. When the synthetic fluorophore was used as the label, a solution of Qdots– streptavidin (Thermo Fisher Scientific) at a concentration of 10 nM was prepared in a mixture containing 0.5% PBST (Sigma Aldrich) and 1% Triton X-

100 (Sigma Aldrich). Images were acquired using an exposure time of 1 s and 1× gain, and 320× magnification (**Figure 4.3**).

All the images were analyzed with ImageJ software (National Institute of Health, USA) in terms of grayscale intensity [170].

Figure 4.3 - Summary of the hybridization assays performed for the three different optical detection labels, fluorescence using ATTO 430LS coupled with QS and CA beads, Qdots associated with CA beads, and chemiluminescence using HRP coupled with QS beads. The yellow background represents steps performed off-chip, while the blue background represents steps performed on-chip.

4.2.4. Chemiluminescence-based assays

For the chemiluminescence experiments, streptavidin horseradish peroxidase conjugate (HRP - streptavidin) was purchased from Invitrogen and was diluted from the stock solution to 1 mg/mL in PBS and stored at -20°C. Luminol SuperSignal® West Femto Chemiluminescent Substrate kit (Thermo Scientific) was used as substrate. The immobilization of the complex streptavidin-biotinylated probe DNA to QS beads, and the blocking and packing of the beads are described in the previous section. After packing the beads, a flow of target DNA is initiated inside the channel after blocking the channel and the beads with 1% casein in PBS. Then, HRP - streptavidin was diluted to 500 nM in PBS and introduced into the channel. Luminol was introduced into the channel by applying positive pressure, and the emitted chemiluminescence light was acquired under dark conditions using an exposure time of 10 s, 10× gain, and 160× magnification (**Figure 4.3**).

4.2.5. Quantitative analysis of DNA immobilization and hybridization

The quantitative analysis of DNA immobilization and hybridization was made using a mass balance methodology (**Figure 4.4**). A calibration curve was obtained for a range of probe DNA and target DNA concentrations to allow the correlation of captured molecules to the measured signal intensity for both immobilization and hybridization. The intensity of the signal was proportional to the total mass of probe DNA or target DNA $m(DNA)_{Total}$ captured inside the microchannel, and this mass accounts for DNA specifically bound to the beads, and DNA non-specifically bound to the PDMS walls $m(DNA)_{PDMS}$ according to **Equation 4.1**:

$$m(DNA)_{Total} = m(DNA)_{Beads} + m(DNA)_{PDMS}$$

Equation 4.1

The non-specific DNA bound to the walls, $m(DNA)_{PDMS}$, was measured and determined to be negligible (**Figure 4.5**), for all tested conditions (p-values > 0.05), and **Equation 4.1** simplifies to:

$$m(DNA)_{Beads} = m(DNA)_{IN} - m(DNA)_{OUT,p}$$

Equation 4.2

The term $m(DNA)_{IN}$ from **Equation 4.2** is known a priori since each solution is prepared from a stock solution of known volume and concentration. The term $m(DNA)_{OUT,p}$, is calculated by measuring the signal intensity of the solution after the exit of the bead-packed channel and correlating this signal level with the DNA concentration using the previously obtained calibration curves. The calibration curve and the quantification of signal intensity of the outlet solutions were performed using a quantification flow rate (Q_{qt}) of 3 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ for probe DNA and 1 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ for target DNA. The measurements were acquired with an exposure time of 25 ms, 1 \times gain, and 10 \times magnification for probe DNA experiments and an exposure time of 50 ms, 1 \times gain, and 10 \times magnification for target DNA experiments. The experimental flow rate (Q_{ex}) is presented in **Table 4.2** for each case. Since probe DNA was already immobilized onto the beads, the Q_{ex} corresponds to the flow rate used to pack the beads inside the channel (5 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$), while for target DNA, the flow rate Q_{ex} was 7 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$.

Figure 4.4 - Schematics of the mass balance method used to calculate the mass of probe DNA immobilized on the beads and captured target DNA. (A) Measurement of calibration curves. A fixed volume (V_i) of a known concentration (C_i) of the probe or target DNA flowed through a channel with packed beads at a flow rate (Q_{qt}) of 3 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ for probe DNA and 1 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ for target DNA. This calibration curve is then used to measure the $m(DNA)_{OUT}$ by correlating fluorescence intensity with concentration. (B) Measurement of DNA non-specifically bound to the PDMS walls ($m(DNA)_{PDMS}$). In this case, a fixed volume (V_i) of known concentration (C_i) of the probe or target DNA flowed through a bare channel at an experimental flow rate (Q_{ex}) of 5 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ for probe DNA and 7 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ for target DNA. (C) Determination of the total mass of DNA ($m(DNA)_{Total}$) immobilized on the beads and adsorbed to the PDMS walls. A fixed volume (V_i) of a known concentration (C_i) of the probe or target DNA flowed through a channel with packed beads at an experimental flow rate (Q_{ex}) of 5 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$. The solution was collected at the outlet and quantified according to the schematics in Figure 4.2 - A.

Figure 4.5 - Quantification of the target DNA non-specifically bound to the PDMS walls for (A) cDNA and (B) ncDNA. The error bars in all plots correspond to the standard deviation of three individual measurements. For both cDNA and ncDNA, the amount of DNA non-specifically bound to the PDMS walls was considered non-significant (ns) ($p\text{-value} > 0.05$). Therefore, ($m(DNA)_{PDMS}$) was not included in the mass balance equations.

4.3. Results and Discussion

4.3.1. Electrostatic immobilization of probe DNA and optimization of the blocking step

Immobilization of probe DNA on the beads was achieved via (1) electrostatic interaction only using QS beads or (2) a combination of electrostatic and hydrophobic

interactions, using CA beads. QS beads (**Figure 4.1 - B I**) are functionalized with quaternary ammonium (Q), which are strong anion exchange groups, resulting in a positively charged surface that allows an electrostatic immobilization of the complex streptavidin-probe DNA. CA beads (**Figure 4.1 - B II**), which have a strong anion exchanger with a primary amine group and a phenyl group, allow multi-modal electrostatic and hydrophobic interactions during the immobilization of the complex streptavidin-probe DNA. Typically, the multi-modal interactions confer a higher salt tolerance, which can expand the range of stringency conditions tolerated by the immobilized probe. In our tests, however, the electrostatic and multi-mode ligands' binding capacities were comparable when using BSA labeled with FITC as a model molecule since it is negatively charged at pH 7 (**Figure 4.6**). From **Figure 4.6 - A**, it is possible to see that the amount of BSA-FITC immobilized on the two types of beads is comparable in the tested range of concentrations and that saturation is achieved when using 200 µg/mL of BSA-FITC. This concentration was fixed and used for the subsequent experiments. To evaluate the effect of buffer conductivity, the fluorescence of BSA-FITC was measured after flowing solutions with 0 M, 0.137 M, 0.660 M, and 3.300 M of NaCl. The concentration of 0.137 M corresponds to PBS buffer, 0.660 M corresponds to the NaCl in 4x SSC buffer, commonly used as hybridization buffer, 3.300 M of sodium ion concentration corresponds to the SSC stock solution. Finally, 0 M of sodium ion concentration corresponds to MilliQ water, considered the most stringent condition. **Figure 4.6 - B** shows that higher concentrations of sodium ions in solution will significantly decrease BSA-FITC adsorbed onto the QS beads, resulting in complete desorption at 3.300 M. On the other hand, BSA-FITC is effectively captured on the CA beads independently of the sodium ion concentration. At the same time, a peak of adsorption was obtained using a NaCl concentration of 0.660 M. Overall, both QS and CA beads may be used when higher stringency levels (lower buffer conductivity) are required. However, lower stringency conditions are only achievable using CA beads.

Figure 4.6 - BSA-FITC adsorption isotherms and effect of conductivity on molecular adsorption. A - Optimization of BSA-FITC concentration adsorbed on QS and CA beads. The error bars represent the standard deviation of two independent assays. B - Measurement of the fluorescence intensity of BSA-FITC adsorbed on QS and CA beads after flowing solutions of increasing sodium ion concentrations. The error bars represent the standard deviation of two independent measurements. For the two solutions with higher concentrations of sodium ion, the adsorbed BSA onto the QS or CA beads was statistically different with a confidence level of 95% (p -value < 0.05 and highlighted with *).

This work used a complex streptavidin-biotinylated probe DNA (hereafter mentioned as complex streptavidin-probe DNA) in a molar ratio of 1 : 4 for DNA immobilization. This molar ratio proved optimal in probe surface density and 3-fold superior for immobilizing only probe DNA (**Figure 4.7**). Therefore, streptavidin contributes to a favorable conformation of the probe DNA to facilitate hybridization by promoting a more upright orientation instead of a horizontal immobilization on the bead surface via the phosphate groups.

Figure 4.7 - Optimization of probe DNA-FITC immobilization on a positively charged surface, silanized with (3-Aminopropyl)triethoxysilane (APTES). (1) Electrostatic immobilization of probe DNA to a PDMS surface functionalized with APTES. (2) APTES functionalization of the PDMS channel followed by streptavidin immobilization and sequential flow of probe DNA. (3.1-4) APTES functionalization of the PDMS channel followed by a flow of a pre-mixed solution of the complex streptavidin : probe DNA in a molar ratio of 1:1, 1:2, 1:3, and 1:4 (illustrated in (3.1), (3.2), (3.3), (3.4), respectively). The error bars correspond to the standard deviation of two individual measurements, and the experiments were performed using an exposure time of 1 s and a 1x gain. These results highlight a statistical difference between the immobilization strategy (1) and (3.3) with a confidence level of 95% (p -value < 0.05) and between immobilization strategy (1) and (3.1), (3.2) and (3.4) with a confidence level of 99% (p -value < 0.01). Furthermore, we found a statistical difference between immobilization strategy (3.1) and (3.2), (3.1) and (3.4), and (3.2) and (3.4) with a confidence level of 95% (p -value < 0.05). Although no statistical difference was found between the immobilization strategy (3.3) and (3.4), the last condition was chosen as the immobilization strategy since it presented a smaller variability and was used throughout this work. Using a streptavidin : probe DNA complex in a molar ratio of 1:4 to perform the immobilization, the fluorescence intensity is increased by ~3-fold when compared to electrostatic immobilization of free probe DNA.

A critical step in biosensor development is guaranteeing that the blocking agent effectively minimizes non-specific interactions with the free electrostatic or multi-mode ligands on the surface. The rationale behind the choice of blocking agents was to use molecules resembling the DNA probes in length and charge. Therefore, several polyacrylate (PA) molecules with different molecular weights were tested, as well as standard procedures, including saDNA and BSA (4%). It was observed that all blocking agents induced a time-dependent release of the previously immobilized probe. Therefore, a total blocking time of 2 min was selected to minimize probe loss (Figure 4.8).

Figure 4.8 - Optimization of the blocking time. This experiment was performed to assess whether the blocking agents removed the DNA probe from the surface of the beads over time. Each blocking agent was flowed at 5 μ L/min for 10 min after immobilizing probe DNA using the procedure described in section 2.4. This allowed the selection of an optimal time for the blocking step. The images were acquired with an exposure time of 50 ms and 2.5 dB gain. The two-minute time point was chosen since, for the majority of the blocking agents, at least 50% of the initial DNA probes remained bound to the beads.

The efficacy of the blocking was then tested by first blocking the beads with each blocking agent and then flowing probe DNA (**Figure 4.9 – A and B**). From **Figure 4.9 – A** it was possible to conclude that the most effective blocking agents were PA 15000 (5%), PA 15000 (1%), PA 8000 (5%), and PA 8000 (1%) with blocking efficiencies of 85.6%, 91.7%, 77.1% and, 74.6%, respectively, calculated as the percentage of the signal after washing relative to the control signal obtained using PBS only (**Figure 4.9 – B**). Three combinations were chosen from the previous blocking agent candidates and concentrations to be evaluated when performing a hybridization assay (**Figure 4.9 – C and D**). According to **Figure 4.9 – C**, the blocking agent that allowed a higher fluorescence ratio (5.9-fold difference) between cDNA and ncDNA was PA 8000 (5%), which was selected as the blocking agent for further experiments.

4.3.1. Quantitative analysis of DNA immobilization and hybridization

The quantitative analysis of DNA immobilization and hybridization was performed for the more versatile CA beads since these beads displayed higher binding capacity towards the streptavidin–probe DNA complex after the blocking step (**Figure 4.10**). Before the blocking steps, we can see that the binding capacity for streptavidin–probe DNA is similar for CA and QS beads by the results obtained with BSA-FITC (**Figure 4.6 – A**). The accurate quantification of immobilized DNA probes is critical in biosensor development since it is known that there is an optimal probe density for hybridization kinetics and capture efficiency that peaks before decreasing for higher probe density values due to stereochemical effects [199].

Figure 4.9 - Effect of different blocking agents on blocking efficacy and hybridization selectivity on QS beads. PBS was used as a control. A - Blocking efficiency – fluorescence from immobilized DNA for different blocking agents during immobilization and washing; B - Absolute fluorescence values at the end of each immobilization and washing step. C - Hybridization selectivity – fluorescence intensity ratio of cDNA hybridization to ncDNA measured during hybridization and washing for different blocking agents. D - Comparison of the fluorescence ratio at the end of the hybridization and washing steps for the different blocking agents.

Figure 4.10 - Comparison of fluorescence intensity of probe DNA immobilized on QS and CA beads before and after the blocking step. Probe DNA labeled with Atto 430LS was used to monitor the probe DNA immobilized onto the beads. The images were acquired using a fluorescence microscope and an exposure time of 50 ms, 1x gain, and 160x total magnification. Before the blocking step, the probe density immobilized onto the beads was similar for both QS (A) and CA beads (C). However, for QS beads before (A) and after (B) the blocking steps, there was a loss of approximately 50% of probe density immobilized onto the beads, while for CA beads before (C) and after (D) the blocking step there was a loss of approximately 25%. This difference in probe density loss leads to a higher probe density in the CA beads compared to the QS beads in the step before target DNA detection.

To quantify the mass of probe and target DNA, a mass balance approach was used to correlate the fluorescence signal intensity with the mass of molecules immobilized on the beads. First, calibration curves, one for the probe DNA immobilization onto the beads (**Figure 4.11 - A**) and two for target DNA (complementary DNA (cDNA) and non-complementary (ncDNA)) were obtained (**Figure 4.11 - B**). For the probe DNA calibration curve, concentrations ranging from 0 to 9.4 μM were tested, and the amount of probe DNA immobilized onto the beads was calculated as $(70.4 \pm 2.0) \times 10^{-12} \text{ mol}$ for a probe DNA concentration of 9.4 μM . The microbeads used in this work were 4% crosslinked agarose beads with an estimated total surface area of 5 m^2/mL , allowing to estimate a probe surface density of $(40.4 \pm 7.5) \times 10^{-12} \text{ mol}/\text{cm}^2$. Comparing the probe density found in the microbeads with other 3D immobilization platforms, such as paramagnetic beads, the value found here is 23-fold higher. One possible explanation for this difference is the extra surface in porous beads where the probes can also be immobilized. In fact, from the total estimated surface area of the

agarose beads (5 m²/mL), only 2% corresponds to the outer surface of a solid sphere with an average diameter of ~90 μm.

Figure 4.11 - (A,B) Calibration curves for known concentrations of DNA, used to determine $m(DNA)_{OUT}$. (A) Standard curve obtained for streptavidin - probe DNA complex as a function of probe concentration. The vertical dotted line represents the probe concentration used in subsequent assays. (B) Calibration curves for cDNA and ncDNA as a function of increasing concentrations of the target concentration. The fluorescence intensity is derived from propidium iodide as a specific intercalator of double-stranded DNA. Higher concentrations of cDNA were statically different from the blank with a confidence level of 95% (p-value < 0.05 and highlighted with *) or a confidence level of 99% (p-value < 0.01 and highlighted with **). Concentrations of ncDNA were not statically different from the blank assay. (C) Fluorescence intensity as a function of hybridized target DNA labeled with Atto 430LS. The vertical dotted line corresponds to probe DNA immobilized on the beads, and the orange band represents the standard error. (D) Target DNA molecules bound (left Y-axis) as a function of target concentration in solution introduced in the microfluidic channel, which was used to calculate the hybridization efficiency (right Y-axis). Error bars represent the standard deviation of two (A) or three independent experiments (B, C, and D).

For the target DNA calibration curves, concentrations ranging from 0.3 to 100 nM were used. From **Figure 4.11 – B**, it is possible to conclude that, for the range of concentrations tested, the signal from the ncDNA was not significantly above the blank assay, thus in conditions where the mass measured at the outlet was not significantly different from the inlet, the hybridized mass was considered zero. For the cDNA target, it was possible to calculate the number of molecules hybridized to the probe DNA for the entire range of concentrations tested, from $3.4 \times 10^{-14} \pm 5.0 \times 10^{-15}$ mol to $1.3 \times 10^{-12} \pm 1.8 \times 10^{-14}$ mol (**Figure 4.11 – C**). For target concentrations above 3 nM, the average hybridization efficiencies varied between $(95.3 \pm 4.0)\%$ to $(97.3 \pm 4.1)\%$ (**Figure 4.11 – D**). This result demonstrates that the

probe density is in a regime that allows all probes to be available to bind the target DNA in solution without significant steric hindrance. In contrast, for 1 nM of target concentration, the hybridization efficiency is only $(75.6 \pm 11.4) \%$, since we are approaching the equilibrium dissociation constant (K_D) of the assay. Therefore, the expected K_D for this system is lower than 1.0×10^{-9} M (Experimental temperature: 20 °C; GC content: 52%). This estimated value of K_D is below a previously reported value of $([2.9 \pm 0.9] \times 10^{-9}$ M) using a 22-mer target with a 40.9% GC content. This difference could be due to the difference in the GC content, since a higher GC content for short strands results in a higher K_D value. Moreover, in another study focusing on detecting a 16-mer target (50% GC content) with electrostatically adsorbed probe DNA at a density of 2.5×10^{13} cm⁻², the K_D value obtained 0.2×10^{-6} M was above of the K_D estimated in this work. Another reported system reports an average K_D of $(434.5 \pm 18.8) \times 10^{-12}$ M for a 20-mer target with a 50% GC content. In this case, the probe DNA was covalently immobilized to the biosensor, and the authors estimated a probe density of (1.1×10^{11}) cm⁻². One possible explanation for this low K_D could be the probe conformation and structural difference of the hybridization strand due to different immobilization strategies used, covalent versus electrostatic. Due to the covalent immobilization strategy, the probes can be more accessible to the target. In addition, it is possible that the energy necessary to form the double DNA strand differs when the probe is immobilized electrostatically to a positively charged surface or to a covalently bound probe.

4.3.2. DNA detection in model buffer solutions

After optimizing the assay architecture, calibration curves for increasing concentrations of target DNA were measured using three different labels for optical detection: Atto 430LS, Qdots, and HRP. The results are shown in **Figure 4.12 – A, B, and C**, respectively. **Figure 4.12 – A** shows the absolute fluorescence intensity for the hybridization of target DNA (cDNA and ncDNA) in both QS and CA beads. It can be observed that the CA beads provide lower minimum detectable limits for cDNA, above the 3σ threshold (three times the standard deviation (σ) of a blank assay), despite the relatively higher nonspecific signal than QS beads. Furthermore, it can be noted that the CA bead assay provides a significantly higher background signal associated with the higher intrinsic fluorescence of the CA beads relative to the QS beads and due to the PA molecules used in the blocking step, which causes an increase in the baseline fluorescence of the assay (**Figure 4.13**).

Figure 4.12 - Biosensing of DNA in QS or CA beads using three different optical detection labels: (A) fluorescence using Atto 430LS in QS or QA bead-based assays, (B) Qdots labels and CA beads or (C) chemiluminescence using HRP and QA beads. The shaded regions represent the 3σ thresholds. The 3σ thresholds are calculated as the average of three blank assays, and the error bars represent the standard deviation of three independent measurements. (D) The signal intensity ratio between target cDNA and target ncDNA for each optical label. The horizontal dashed lines represent the 3σ thresholds. (E-G) Microscopy images for each detection method for target cDNA (top images) and target ncDNA (bottom images). (E) Fluorescence image of the Atto 430LS label, (F) fluorescence image of the Qdots label, and (G) optical microscopy image of the HRP label. All images were contrast-enhanced for visualization purposes.

Figure 4.13 - Comparison of background fluorescence for QS and CA beads before and after the blocking step. The images were acquired using an exposure time of 1s, 1x gain, and 160x total magnification. Before the blocking step, QS beads (A) displayed a lower background fluorescence than CA beads (C). After the blocking step the baseline for the background fluorescence increased in both cases. However the increase was higher for CA beads (D) than for QS beads (B), contributing to the higher fluorescence baseline associated with the CA beads.

Defining the LoD as the concentration of cDNA providing a signal equal to 3σ , values of (42.7 ± 0.8) pM and (675.5 ± 0.8) pM were obtained for the CA and QS beads, respectively. The LoD for the CA beads was observed to be one order of magnitude below that reported for a similar system where probe DNA was immobilized to the beads via biotin-streptavidin interaction coupled to an optical detection using an organic fluorophore (LoD ~ 100 pM). It is also important to highlight that in both the CA and QS bead assays, the signal provided by the ncDNA is below the 3σ threshold. Nevertheless, it is clear that in both bead systems, the achievable LoDs are limited by the intrinsic background (baseline fluorescence) of the assay. To further decrease the LoD, another detection method using Qdots as labels and CA beads to immobilize the probe DNA was tested (**Figure 4.12 – B**). CA beads were selected since they were previously observed to provide the lowest LoD. In this case, a LoD of (9.5 ± 1.1) pM was achieved, limited by a significant background from Qdot aggregation and physical trapping on the beads during the experiment. Despite the high background, the achieved LoD is comparable to a previously reported Qdot-based hybridization

assay for the detection of a 44-mer DNA target (LoD ~ 4 pM). **Figure 4.12 – C** shows the results for the DNA detection using an enzyme-based detection by labeling the target DNA with HRP. In this case, CA beads could not be used since they hindered the signal intensity of the reaction by accumulating a yellow-colored product (3-aminophthalate) from the luminol oxidation, resulting in a pronounced decrease in chemiluminescence signal over time (**Figure 4.14**). An LoD of (10.6 ± 0.6) pM was achieved using the QS beads, and again the sensitivity of the assay was limited by a nonspecific signal. Recently, a similar microfluidic system to detect 25-mer viral DNA using a covalently immobilized probe DNA and a chemiluminescence assay were reported, providing an LoD of 80 pM. Our device offers a ~ 7.6 -fold enhanced sensitivity compared to this system, which can be explained by the higher density of probes achieved using nanoporous beads as the physical support.

Figure 4.14 - Comparison of the chemiluminescence signal profile when using CA or QS beads. Although the target concentration is different for both photos presented, one can see that the chemiluminescence signal for the CA beads is not homogenous through the beads like in the case of QS beads. In fact, for CA beads, we observed in the center of the beads a 0 gray value, while for QS beads in the center of the beads, we still have a grey value of 40. This difference in intensity profiles was systematically observed between beads. One possible justification for the CA beads profile is the adsorption of a colored product (3-aminophthalate) from the luminol oxidation resulting in a pronounced decrease in the chemiluminescence signal over time. For this reason, the chemiluminescence assay was performed using QS beads.

From these three detection strategies, the Qdots and enzyme detection methods provide the lowest LoDs. It was expected that the Qdots would give an enhancement over standard organic fluorophore labels due to their optical properties, such as high fluorescence quantum yields, low photobleaching and flexibility in excitation wavelengths due to broad absorption spectra. In this work, using Qdot-labelled DNA with the CA beads assay resulted in an enhancement of ~ 5-fold in sensitivity compared to the assay using CA beads and Atto 430LS as a label. An enhancement of 64-fold in sensitivity was obtained when using QS bead assays and HRP labels compared to Atto 430LS labels. In previous work from our group, HRP-based detection was also found to be more sensitive (80-fold) than detection with standard organic fluorophores. Comparing detection times between the three assays, the Atto 430LS-based detection was the fastest by allowing DNA detection in a single step within 7 min. The Qdot-based detection took 10 min since this method required an extra step of flowing the streptavidin – Qdot conjugate. On the other hand, it is reasonable to assume that the biotinylated target and detection conjugate could be incubated off-channel to improve microfluidic assay times. Finally, the HRP-based detection was the most time-consuming, taking up to 18 min due to an extra blocking step and the flow of the luminol substrate. It is important to highlight that the detection times do not account for probe DNA immobilization, representing solely the time necessary for signal acquisition when flowing target DNA through the channel. In **Figure 4.12 – D**, the signal intensity ratio between target cDNA and target ncDNA is summarized for the previous experiments. Comparing a range of concentrations between 10 pM -100 pM, it is possible to conclude that the Qdot-based detection method provides the lowest LoD and is the most selective method of the three. Nevertheless, coupling QS beads with Atto 430LS labels presents itself as a superior method when working with relatively high target DNA concentrations (above 1 nM).

4.4. Chapter conclusions

In this study, we successfully developed a microfluidic method for fast DNA detection by a simple and reversible probe DNA immobilization to commercial chromatography beads. In particular, single-mode (quaternary amine group) and multi-mode (primary amine group and a phenyl group) beads were successfully used to develop a probe DNA immobilization strategy. This simple strategy does not require the modification of probe DNAs allowing a rapid (10 min), cost-effective, and single-step immobilization. By selecting an appropriate ligand on the beads, the system can be adapted to assay stringency requirements while maintaining detection performance and minor probe release. By quantifying the density of probes immobilized using this

system ($2.4 \times 10^{13} \pm 4.5 \times 10^{12}$ molecules/cm²) and compared with values from the literature, it was possible to conclude that the typical values considered as excessive density values ($\sim 1.1 \times 10^{13}$ molecules/cm²), *i.e.*, capable of inducing a decrease in hybridization efficiency below 100%, do not apply to this system. For a 22-mer DNA strand, the method reported in this paper achieved an LoD of (9.5 ± 1.1) pM with a total analysis time of 10 min, values comparable to similar state-of-the-art systems reported in the literature [16-19]. This LoD is already in the upper limit of the clinical range for circulating miRNAs (fM to pM). The method could distinguish between cDNA and ncDNA targets achieving signal-to-noise ratios between 1.073 ± 0.003 to 4.252 ± 0.591 . Furthermore, the system can be tailored to the target DNA concentrations by using the trade-off between analysis time and LoD.

Overall, the method reported in this paper demonstrates a versatile tool to detect DNA in different assays conditions and has the potential to be used in point-of-need/point-of-care applications in fields as diverse as animal and human health, food safety, environmental analysis, or even biodefense. For miRNA detection, in particular, the LoD could be further improved to reach the lower limit of the clinical range by using, for instance, peptide nucleic acid (PNA) or locked nucleic acid (LNA) oligomers as probes, as they present higher affinity towards complementary RNA.

Chapter 5

Regenerable bead-based microfluidic platform for DNA detection

5. Regenerable Bead-based Microfluidic Device with Integrated Thin-film Photodiodes for Real-time Monitoring of DNA Detection

This chapter reports a regenerable device with the ability to detect DNA. The possibility of regenerating the microfluidic biosensing system allows the implementation of internal control and reusability, resulting in cost reduction. Nanoporous microbead-based microfluidic systems coupled with on-chip signal transduction can enhance sensitivity for biosensing applications. A regenerable bead-based microfluidic device that employs integrated thin-film photodiodes for real-time monitoring of DNA molecular recognition is described in this chapter. The molecular identification of target and complementary DNA is accomplished, followed by the regeneration of the chip using 0.3 M of NaOH and control with a non-complementary target DNA. The best condition for immobilization of probe DNA to allow regeneration of the device was studied, and limits of detection of 1.2 nM and 3.1 nM were obtained for target DNA in buffer and human plasma, respectively, detected by fluorescence assays. Moreover, a chemiluminescence strategy provided the highest sensitivity to detect target DNA with an LoD of 78.5 pM. High-sensitivity assay cycles could be performed without significant loss of probe DNA, demonstrating the potential for the system's reusability, portability, and reproducibility. The contents of this chapter are summarized and reproduced from one original research article entitled "**Regenerable Bead-based Microfluidic Device With Integrated Thin-film Photodiodes for Real-time Monitoring of DNA Detection**" [200] and the conference abstract for an **oral communication presented at the Eurosensors 2018** conference [201]. I fabricated the microfluidic devices. Conceived, designed, performed, and analyzed the experimental results. I was the main writer of the publication.

5.1. Introduction

Detecting specific nucleic acid strands, such as DNA or RNA, is critical for developing nucleic acid biosensors. These sensors can answer the urgent need, especially in a global pandemic, for devices capable of detecting a viral and bacterial presence in a fast, sensitive, and specific fashion [202], [203]. Techniques for sensitive and rapid detection of bacteria and viruses in complex matrices, such as bodily fluids, environmental samples, or even from surfaces, are vital for treating and controlling infectious diseases [204], [205].

Current pathogen detection methods include culture-based methods, which are time-consuming, or molecular-based methods which include PCR-based detection assays performed in centralized labs, requiring specialized technical personnel and equipment. These detection methods can delay identification and treatment, leading to inappropriate therapy or ineffective pathogen suppression. The molecular assays are the most rapid, sensitive, and specific from the standard detection methods. PCR is the gold-standard method used in central labs and has also been increasingly implemented in point-of-care microsystems [74], [206], [207]. Microfluidic devices offer several advantages for detecting bacterial pathogens. These devices allow the reduction of sample volume and reagent consumption, increase the speed of analysis, and simplify the detection process through autonomous systems that will enable bacterial cell isolation, cell lysis, nucleic acid extraction, and amplification and amplicon detection through hybridization of a complementary detection oligo on a single chip [12], [208]. For this reason, several recent efforts have been to design DNA hybridization-based microfluidic biosensors. Many use electrochemical detection techniques that are prone to variability due to changes in the surrounding environment and have complex and time-consuming protocols [209], [210], or magnetic-bead-based detections that usually require a bulky apparatus for the actuation of the beads and the detection of a magnetic signal, increasing the cost of the device [211]. In addition, few studies have focused on the regeneration of the microfluidic device [209], [212]. In Good et al. biosensor regeneration review, there is no description of regeneration studies for DNA optical biosensors. In contrast, other analytes, such as antibodies and proteins, are well described [213]. Regeneration allows more assays on a single chip and enables the measurement of a single control sample under identical experimental conditions, thus providing more precise control of the assay and avoiding false-positive or false-negative results. This aspect is crucial to bringing DNA biosensors to the market. One of the main barriers preventing this type of biosensor from translating from a laboratory prototype to a commercial

product involves safety concerns with the risk of misdiagnosis [214]. The ability to regenerate with effectiveness the device also enables the reuse of the device, leading to a decrease in costs. DNA biosensors are usually designed for single use. Thus, there are few studies of regeneration conditions and optimal immobilization strategies to produce a high-performance DNA biosensor for the assay and the control.

Furthermore, for the majority of regeneration protocols, the capture DNA strand is removed from the sensor surface, and the sensors would then require a new functionalization every time they are reused, increasing the complexity of the regeneration protocol [213] and eliminating the advantage of having a single, consistent control for multiple assays. Several techniques can reconstitute biosensors, such as chemical, thermal, or electrochemical. This work presents a simple chemical regeneration mediated by a basic medium (NaOH). This type of regeneration process is simple to implement on-chip and compatible with our assay since it will not interfere with the sensor output signal and the device's baseline, as would be the case with electrochemical systems or risk denaturation and damage of the capture molecule.

The main goal of this work was to increase the reliability of the assay by having internal quality control. In these systems, having a control in the same microfluidic channel is relevant because inside the microchannel, there is a packed microbead column that can contribute to variability factors such as the degree of column packing and the probe density on the bead surface. The possibility of reusing the device was suggested due to the effectiveness of the regeneration obtained. Increasing the surface-to-volume ratio of the biosensor through the use of microbeads packed inside the microfluidic channel allows more DNA probes to be immobilized on the matrix, promoting higher sensitivities. We have previously demonstrated that using nanoporous microbeads inside a microfluidic network increases biosensors' sensitivity due to the microbeads' high surface-to-volume ratio [165], [171]. Moreover, it is possible to perform regeneration of the microbeads after antibody capture to perform chromatography cycles [215]. However, this methodology has yet to be applied to DNA biosensors. The regeneration of the microfluidic biosensing system results in a further decrease in costs. At the same time, integrating on-chip signal transduction allows for increased sensitivity and flexibility in system design. Recently, Boissinot *et al.* described a bead-based DNA microfluidic device to capture and detect amplicons via DNA hybridization and optical detection [109]. No regeneration of the device was directly attempted. These authors showed a competition between a target strand already immobilized to a probe DNA and a complementary strand flowing

through the device, which results in a release of the target strand from the probe DNA attached to the beads. However, the signal does not return to a baseline value, meaning that not all probes become free to capture a new target DNA. Ariffin *et al.* developed a DNA biosensor using hollow silica spheres as a surface to immobilize the ssDNA probe covalently. This device was regenerated four times using 100 mM of NaOH, with a 4-6% signal decrease after rehybridization with target DNA, and the detection was made via differential pulse voltammetry [212]. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first report of an optical read-out bead-based DNA biosensor with the ability to perform the regeneration of the device without removing or changing the conditions of the capture DNA layer (density, capture efficiency, and sensor baseline). This study can be transposed for short-strand DNA detection via hybridization, and different sequences can be employed.

This paper presents a regenerable bead-based microfluidic device with integrated optical detection via thin-film photodiodes for the real-time monitoring of cDNA and ncDNA molecular recognition to a DNA probe. The ncDNA control assay is performed in the same microfluidic channel as the cDNA assay and thus represents a robust internal control of the assay. The optimal probe DNA immobilization to the beads was achieved by covalent bonding. Covalent bonding immobilization allowed the system's regeneration without significant loss of probe DNA while maintaining the same molecular recognition efficiency. This was confirmed by performing several high-sensitivity assay cycles. This work demonstrates the potential for the system's reusability, portability, and reproducibility.

5.2. Materials and experimental methods

5.2.1. DNA oligonucleotides and beads used for DNA immobilization

Synthetic 23 base-pair single-strand oligonucleotide sequences (Stabvida Genomics Lab, Portugal) were used to perform the immobilization and molecular recognition of 100% cDNA and 100% ncDNA strands (**Table 5.1**) on the surface of the nanoporous agarose beads that were packed inside the microfluidic device (**Figure 5.1 - A**). Three different DNA immobilization strategies were tested (**Figure 5.1 - B**). For QS Fast Flow beads and CA beads (GE Healthcare Life Sciences) (~90 μm average size), the beads were suspended in a solution of biotinylated probe DNA (9.4 μM) : streptavidin (2.35 μM) (Sigma-Aldrich) in a 1:4 M ratio (previously incubated for 10 min), to allow adsorption of the probe DNA : streptavidin complex to the beads through electrostatic interaction (QS) or electrostatic and hydrophobic interaction (CA), as described in

Chapter 4. Aminolink C6-modified probe DNA was covalently immobilized to N-hydroxysuccinimide-Activated Sepharose (NHS-Activated Sepharose 4 Fast Flow beads, GE Healthcare Life Sciences). The coupling of the aminolink C6-modified DNA to the NHS-Activated Sepharose 4 Fast Flow beads was performed as instructed by the supplier and using a 1 : 1 volume ratio of bead suspension and DNA solution [50 μ M]. The coupling had an incubation step of 3 hours at rt with an agitation of 750 rpm/min. All three immobilization strategies were used to verify the optimization of the microcolumn regeneration for DNA detection.

Table 5.1 - Description of the oligonucleotide sequences used in this work and respective modifications.

Oligonucleotide	Sequence	5' Mod	3' Mod
Atto 430LS - probe DNA - biotin	5'-CAGGTCAAAGGGTCCTTAGGGA-3'	Atto 430LS	Biotin
Atto 430LS - probe DNA - aminolink	5'-CAGGTCAAAGGGTCCTTAGGGA-3'	Atto 430LS	Aminolink-C6
probe DNA - aminolink	5'-CAGGTCAAAGGGTCCTTAGGGA-3'	None	Aminolink-C6
probe DNA - biotin	5'-CAGGTCAAAGGGTCCTTAGGGA-3'	None	Biotin
cDNA – Atto 430LS	5'-TCCCTAAGGACCCTTTTGACCTG -3'	None	Atto 430LS
ncDNA – Atto 430LS	5'-CGTGTCGTTACATCTGTCCGT -3'	None	Atto 430LS
cDNA – biotin	5'-TCCCTAAGGACCCTTTTGACCTG -3'	None	Biotin
ncDNA – biotin	5'-CGTGTCGTTACATCTGTCCGT -3'	None	Biotin

5.2.1. Packing of beads and optimization of microcolumn regeneration for DNA detection

For the different types of beads used in this work, the packing was achieved by diluting the bead stock in PBS to obtain a solution with a final concentration of 0.12% bead volume. We used 20 μ L of the PBS diluted bead solution to pack a bead column inside the microfluidic channel by applying negative pressure at the outlet using a syringe pump (NE-1002X, New Era Pump System Inc.) at a flow rate of 7 μ L/min.

Figure 5.1 - Bead-based microfluidic assays. A - Schematics of the microfluidic setup with integrated thin-film p-i-n photodiodes used for optical transduction. The photodiodes were aligned with the channel and positioned underneath the packed beads. B - The three types of nanoporous agarose microbeads evaluated for probe DNA immobilization: Q Sepharose™ (QS) Fast Flow (I-1) and Capto™ Adhere (CA) beads (I-2) provided reversible immobilization of streptavidin – biotinylated probe DNA, while NHS Activated Sepharose™ beads (II-1) were used to immobilize amino-modified probe DNA covalently.

To optimize microcolumn regeneration, we tested two conditions: 3 M and 0.3 M of sodium hydroxide (NaOH), and two types of assays were performed. These concentrations were selected based on similar values reported in the literature [216]. In the first assay, an Atto 430 LS labeled probe DNA was used to determine the effect of the two regeneration conditions on probe density. The following protocol was used when the probe DNA was immobilized via electrostatic or electrostatic and hydrophobic interactions: first, a solution with streptavidin and biotinylated probe DNA Atto 430 LS labeled, was incubated in an [1:4] M ratio for 10 min, as stated before. CA beads or QS beads were added to the previous solution to obtain a final solution with 0.12% bead volume and were incubated for an additional 10 min with orbital agitation at 3000rpm. After this, sodium polyacrylate (PA) 45% (w/w) (8000 average molecular weight) was added to the previous solution, obtaining a final solution with PA 8000 5% volume, which was incubated for 2 min with QS beads or 5 min with CA beads. Using 20 μL of this solution, the beads were packed inside the microchannel. In the case of the beads with covalently immobilized probe DNA - Atto 430 LS, no incubation steps were required, and the bead solution was packed into the microchannel. After a washing step with PBS at 7 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ for 1 min, 0.3 M of NaOH

regeneration solution was pumped through the channel at 7 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ for 3 min, followed by a washing step with PBS at 7 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ for 1 min. Another regeneration condition was tested in the same microcolumn by flowing 3 M of NaOH regeneration solution at 7 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ for 3 min, followed by a washing step with PBS at 7 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ for 1 min. The probe DNA fluorescence was monitored using a Leica DMLM microscope equipped with a DFC300FX CCD camera and a 100 W mercury arc lamp coupled to a blue light excitation filter with a band-pass excitation of 450–490 nm and a long-pass emission filter of 515 nm. Images were captured in 30 seconds intervals with an exposure time of 50 ms, 1 \times gain, and 160 \times magnification. The fluorescence signal was analyzed via measurement of the Green channel in the acquired RGB images using the software ImageJ (National Institutes of Health, Bethesda, MA, USA).

In the second assay, we tested the effect of regeneration on the denaturation of the complementary and non-complementary DNA strands labeled with Atto 430 LS. In this case, the assay flow process was similar to that previously described for the probe DNA immobilization. After packing the beads inside the microchannel, 1 μM of complementary Atto 430 LS labeled DNA was flowed at 7 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ for 5 min, followed by a flow of a regeneration solution of 0.3 or 3 M of NaOH at 7 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ for 3 min concluding with a PBS washing step for 1 min. After that, the non-complementary Atto 430 LS labeled DNA flowed into the same bead-packed microchannel at 7 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ for 5 min, followed by another regeneration step of 0.3 or 3 M of NaOH and PBS washing step. The assay was monitored continuously and analyzed using the same strategy described before.

5.2.2. Calibration curves of one hybridization cycle using a fluorescence microscope

The one hybridization cycle assay consisted of flowing a solution with the strand of complementary Atto 430 LS labeled DNA through a microchannel packed with the beads with a probe DNA covalently immobilized to its surface. Then, a step of regeneration with a 0.3M solution of NaOH followed by a flow of non-complementary Atto 430 LS labeled DNA, followed by another step of regeneration with 0.3M of NaOH, with PBS washing steps in between. The flow rates and times used for each step are the same as in section 2.3, and the target DNA concentrations tested varied from 3 to 1000 nM. Images were acquired using an exposure time of 1 second, 1 \times gain, and 320 \times magnification with a frame rate of 60 seconds.

5.2.3. Chemiluminescence calibration curves of one hybridization cycle

Chemiluminescence detection was also performed to improve the sensitivity of the assay further. Moreover, chemiluminescence detection is simpler to implement in a point-of-care context when compared to fluorescence assays. The simplicity is associated with the setup required (no need for excitation light) and the device itself (the photosensor does not require a filter layer). We used streptavidin horseradish peroxidase conjugate (HRP - streptavidin) as a labeling molecule for the chemiluminescence detection assays, purchased from Invitrogen and diluted from the stock solution to 1 mg/mL in PBS. Luminol SuperSignal[®] West Femto Chemiluminescent Substrate kit (Thermo Scientific) was used as substrate. All the steps were similar to the ones performed in the assay of section 2.4, but, in this case, biotinylated complementary and non-complementary DNA strands were utilized. Then, HRP - streptavidin was diluted to 500 nM in PBS and flowed through the beads at 5 μ L/min for 3 min, followed by a PBS washing step. After that, Luminol was introduced into the channel by applying positive pressure at a flow rate of 20 μ L/min for 2 min. The emitted chemiluminescence light was acquired using thin-film *p-i-n a-Si:H* photodiodes under dark background conditions. The regeneration of the microcolumn was performed using 0.3 M of NaOH after each Luminol step. The target DNA concentrations tested ranged from 10 000 – 30 pM.

5.2.4. Signal transduction using *a-Si:H* photodiodes and for photocurrent acquisition

Here, *p-i-n a-Si:H* photodiodes with (**Figure 5.2 - A I**) and without (**Figure 5.2 - A II**) an amorphous silicon carbide (*a-SiC:H*) absorption filter were used for fluorescence and chemiluminescence assays, respectively.

Figure 5.2 - Integrated optical transduction after target capture in regeneration assays. A - Schematics of the p-i-n a-Si:H photodiode aligned with the bead-packed microchannels. An integrated a-SiC:H excitation light filter is deposited on top of the sensor (I) for fluorescence measurements. An identical sensor was used without the filter (II) for chemiluminescence measurements. B - Schematics of the hybridization assay cycle with regeneration for fluorescence (I) and chemiluminescence (II) detection. For chemiluminescence assays after the biotinylated target DNA, it was necessary to flow the streptavidin-HRP followed by luminal substrate to obtain the optical signal.

To record the photocurrent (measured at 0V), a picoammeter (Model 237; Kiethley Instruments, Inc.) connected to the photodiode PCB via coaxial and triaxial connections was used. The devices, particularly the areas with the packed beads, were manually aligned directly on top of the photodiode. For the fluorescence assays, a 405 nm laser excitation light (photon flux (ϕ) = $1.04 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-2} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$) was used, and the laser beam was run through a 1.5 neutral density filter before being aligned and focused on top of the area with the packed beads. The solutions flowed inside the

microchannel, and the current was continuously measured throughout the assay duration. Moreover, the dark current and the current upon flowing the luminol solution through the channel were also acquired for the chemiluminescence measurements.

5.3. Results and Discussion

5.3.1. Strategies for probe DNA immobilization onto the beads and optimization of microcolumn regeneration conditions

Three probe DNA immobilization strategies for the beads were tested to optimize regeneration: electrostatic interaction, multimodal interaction, and covalent immobilization. The optimized conditions for electrostatic and multimodal immobilization were presented in **Chapter 4**. In the case of covalent immobilization, the highest DNA probe concentration was obtained using a 1 : 1 volume ratio of bead suspension and DNA solution [50 μ M] incubated for 3 hours. This condition was obtained in an optimization assay where 1 : 1, 1 : 0.5, and 1 : 0.25 volume ratios of bead suspension and DNA solution [50 μ M] were tested, as well as different coupling incubation times from 2 – 4 hours. Using an Atto 430 LS labelled probe DNA, we tested three probe DNA immobilization strategies aforementioned, under two regeneration conditions by flowing 0.3 M of NaOH (condition 1) followed by a flow of 3.0 M NaOH (condition 2) (**Figure 5.3 - A**). The goal was to choose a regeneration condition to minimize the removal of probe DNA immobilized on the microbeads. After flowing the regeneration solution, a washing step with PBS is performed. This step is required since the fluorophore's fluorescence can change under different salt conditions. Thus, measuring after the washing step ensures that the fluorescence is not affected by the salt condition of the various regeneration solutions, allowing them to be compared. For condition 1, the covalently immobilized and electrostatically immobilized probe DNA maintained the same initial fluorescence, $97.6\% \pm 3.9\%$ and $99.8\% \pm 5.0\%$, respectively. These results were obtained using the fluorescence values at 4 minutes (**Figure 5.3 - A**). However, for the multimodal immobilization (electrostatic and hydrophobic) using the CA beads, the fluorescence decreased by 10% from the initial fluorescence. Immediately after condition 1 and the washing step, the same channel with the same beads was used to test condition 2. After the PBS washing step, we can observe that the loss of probe DNA is higher than in condition 1. In the case of the electrostatic interaction, there was a loss of $65.6\% \pm 10.3\%$, while for the multimodal interaction, there was a loss of $49.3\% \pm 1.1\%$. As expected, due to the covalent bond between the probe DNA and the NHS-Activated Sepharose 4 Fast Flow beads, the probe DNA loss was minimal (approximately 0%). These results

were obtained using the fluorescence values at 8 minutes (**Figure 5.3 - A**). We can also conclude that using the regeneration condition with 0.3 M NaOH is the best option to avoid probe DNA removal.

However, in this case, we want to ensure that we can de-hybridize and remove the cDNA and the ncDNA from the channel walls and the surface of the beads. To do that, we performed regeneration cycle experiments, in which we evaluated the different probe DNA immobilization strategies through a cycle of hybridization with Atto 430 LS labeled cDNA, followed by 0.3 M NaOH for column regeneration, Atto 430 LS labeled ncDNA and another regeneration step (**Figure 5.3 - B**). This experiment was repeated but used the regeneration condition with 3 M NaOH (**Figure 5.3 - C**). We can conclude that we cannot fully regenerate the bead column using electrostatic and multimodal immobilization for both conditions. Moreover, since the regeneration is not complete after flowing the cDNA and the interaction between the DNA and the beads is due to electrostatic and hydrophobic interactions, the ncDNA can be attached to the beads, giving a final value higher than for cDNA. However, when using the covalent immobilization of probe DNA, even with the lowest concentration of NaOH tested, we can regenerate the bead column after both the cDNA and ncDNA hybridization steps, achieving fluorescence values of the order of the background level after regeneration. Since there was no difference between using 0.3 M or 3 M of NaOH for the covalent immobilization, we selected the lowest concentration as the regeneration condition for the subsequent experiments. This type of regeneration requires only flowing a regeneration solution through the packed beads inside the microfluidic channel, making it compatible with PoC devices.

Furthermore, we can also observe that the system is more stable with covalent immobilization than with the other immobilization strategies used, based on the minor variations between assay repetitions. Selecting the covalent immobilization strategy and the regeneration with 0.3M NaOH allowed to include a ncDNA control assay in the device in the same microfluidic channel as the cDNA assay, leading to robust internal control. This does not always happen when using two different microfluidic channels in parallel to perform in one detection of a target and in another, a control. The robustness of the assay in other channels could be guaranteed only if the assay conditions were exactly the same (probe density, packing of the beads, sample, photosensor output, channel geometry), and fluctuations of these parameters are expected in real assay conditions.

Figure 5.3 - Optimization of microcolumn regeneration conditions. A - Effect of two regeneration conditions on the probe DNA immobilized via electrostatic, multimodal (electrostatic and hydrophobic), or covalent immobilization. The fluorescence is normalized to the maximum fluorescence value, which corresponds to the fluorescence at $t=0$, before flowing any regeneration solution through the channel. B - Measurement of one hybridization assay cycle for the different probe DNA immobilization strategies, using 0.3 M of NaOH for microcolumn regeneration. C - Measurement of one hybridization assay cycle for the different probe DNA immobilization strategies, 3 M of NaOH used for microcolumn regeneration. The error bars correspond to the standard deviation of two individual assays performed in two different microcolumns. DNA hybridization steps were performed using 1000 nM of target DNA, which flowed through the microcolumn for five minutes.

5.3.2. Hybridization cycles: Fluorescence microscope vs thin-film photodiodes measurements

The hybridization/regeneration cycles were performed using the covalent immobilization strategy (NHS-Activated Sepharose 4 Fast Flow beads). The cycle was obtained by first flowing cDNA, followed by 0.3 M NaOH for column regeneration, and then flowing ncDNA while continuously monitoring with fluorescence microscopy (**Figure 5.4 - A**). The column was washed with PBS between each step. A range of target DNA concentrations in buffer (PBS) from 0 - 1000 nM was tested. For all the concentrations tested, complete regeneration of the column was confirmed by measured fluorescence values, comparable to that of the background after regeneration.

The fluorescent values after cDNA and PBS washing for the different concentrations tested are always higher than those measured after the ncDNA and PBS washing step, reflecting the assay's specificity. Calculating the assay's specificity by dividing the fluorescence intensity after flowing the cDNA (6-minute time point in **Figure 5.4 - A**) and after flowing the ncDNA (16-minute time point in **Figure 5.4 - A**), we obtained values that go from 7-fold up to 60-fold for the range of increasing concentrations tested.

The fluorescence acquisition of the regeneration cycle assay was performed using a 200 × 200 μm thin-film *p-i-n* a-Si:H photodiode aligned beneath the area in the microchannel where the microbeads were packed to make this system compatible with a portable setup. The results of the fluorescence microscope were replicated using the photodiodes, as seen in **Figure 5.4 - B**. The results show the photocurrent variation resulting from the photodiode's measurement of fluorescence. A direct comparison between **Figure 5.4 - A** and **Figure 5.4 - B** results shows that the trend is maintained. The results are consistent with fluorescence microscopy's results for the same evaluated DNA target concentrations. This indicates that the device is very promising for point-of-care applications requiring portability. Portability can be achieved by using laser diodes as a light excitation source for fluorescence measurements. Laser diodes are small in size and have low power requirements, which advantages portable devices. We could also integrate a light-emitting diode (LED), a lower-cost option than laser diodes. In the case of the LEDs, we should consider the high divergence and broader emission spectra, which can be overcome by incorporating lenses, waveguides, and filters, as well as source light with the appropriate wavelength to excite the label. Several works have already integrated

laser diodes and LEDs with photodiodes in point-of-care devices [217]–[220]. Regarding current reading post-processing, since microscale thin-film photodiodes designed for integrated detection in microfluidic environments, such as the ones shown here, typically generate nA-level currents, a high-gain transimpedance amplification circuit is required, possibly coupled to a microcontroller board and wireless communication module that allows connection to a personal computing device or a smartphone. Then the data can be acquired and plotted in real-time using a program developed for such purpose. Our group has already developed work in this direction [193], [218].

Furthermore, we repeated the assay with the target DNA spiked in human plasma for a closer approximation of real sample measurements. Since human plasma is a complex matrix with a higher viscosity than the buffer, this can affect the liquid flow through the microbeads, potentially leading to clogging and assay failure. We assessed the device's performance by testing the same DNA target concentrations as before (**Figure 5.4 - C**). Once more, by directly comparing the results from **Figure 5.4 - B** and **Figure 5.4 - C**, we conclude that the system is compatible with the analysis of a real sample due to the excellent correlation between the assay performed in buffer and human plasma. Moreover, we can see that the signal for both assays (buffer and plasma) was almost identical, suggesting that the complex plasma matrix does not affect the assay. It is worth noting that during the bead's regeneration, the device's photoresponse drops almost immediately to the background levels, confirming the regeneration step's efficacy. We consider the background level as the current obtained when the excitation laser is impinging on the device at the beginning of the assay, during the first seconds when no labeled DNA is inside the microchannel. For all target DNA concentrations tested, the signal was always above the dark current of the photodiodes ($I_{\text{Dark}} \approx -1.00 \times 10^{-13}$ A). Furthermore, we tested the possibility of regeneration of the columns to perform several regeneration cycle assays in the same channel, under the same bead packing conditions, and to improve the reproducibility of the assay (**Figure 5.4 - D**). The results show that using the same microcolumn to perform up to four regeneration cycles in buffer and human plasma is possible. Moreover, the results also suggest that the sequential regeneration of the bead microcolumn can be performed without significant loss of probe density and activity. However, we verified that the cycles performed in human plasma displayed more predisposition to clogging, eventually leading to assay failure after the fourth regeneration cycle.

Figure 5.4 - Measurements of the hybridization assay cycles, including detection of specific complementary target DNA, column regeneration, non-complementary target DNA control, and column regeneration. A) Calibration curves of target DNA diluted in PBS buffer from 0 – 1000 nM concentration range. The fluorescence of packed beads was continuously acquired with a fluorescence microscope. B) Calibration curves of target DNA in PBS buffer where the fluorescence signal was acquired with a-Si:H p-i-n photodiodes. C) Calibration curves of target DNA in plasma where the fluorescence signal was acquired with a-Si:H p-i-n photodiodes. D) Measurement of four consecutive hybridization cycles with target DNA (300 nM) diluted in buffer and plasma using the photodiodes to monitor the fluorescence.

5.3.3. Limits of detection of the system with integrated photosensor measurements of fluorescence and chemiluminescence

To obtain the limit of detection of the fluorescence and chemiluminescence assays, we calculated specific signals for both methods.

For the fluorescence assay, the specific signal is obtained by taking the average of the signal during the first 10 seconds of the assay after the laser is turned on and subtracting it from the average of the signal at the end of the PBS washing step, after flowing the target DNA (**Figure 5.5 - A**). By measuring the specific signal for a range of target DNA concentrations, both in PBS buffer and human plasma, we obtained the calibration curve in **Figure 5.5 - B**. Defining the limit of detection as the concentration of target cDNA above the 3.3σ threshold, values of 1.2 nM and 3.1 nM were obtained for target DNA in buffer and human plasma, respectively. One can also observe that

after turning off the laser, the signal rapidly returns to the dark response and remains constant, displaying the photodiode's stability over time.

For the chemiluminescence assay, the specific signal was obtained by subtracting a 10 second average of the dark current signal from a 10 second average around the peak of the current **Figure 5.5 - C**. With these values, we obtained the calibration curve in **Figure 5.5 - D** for the chemiluminescence assay in human plasma resulting in a limit of detection of 78.5 pM. We also compare these results with the values obtained for the fluorescence assay in human plasma. We can see that the chemiluminescence strategy provides an approximately 40-fold higher sensitivity to detect target DNA than the fluorescence assay in the same human plasma matrix. The fluorescence assay limit is also related to the sensor itself and the efficiency of the integrated filter, which decreases the sensitivity. We can also verify that for the chemiluminescence assay, the non-specific signal of the ncDNA is higher than that of the fluorescence assay, which suggests higher selectivity of the latter.

Figure 5.5 - Fluorescence A and B and chemiluminescence C and D monitoring using photosensors. A - Raw data obtained by measuring the current from the p-i-n photodiodes at 0 V bias during the step of the assay cycle when we are detecting complementary 30 nM of target DNA-Atto 430-LS in PBS buffer. B - Specific diode photocurrent values as a function of target DNA concentrations in buffer and spiked in human plasma. The horizontal dashed line represents the 3.3σ threshold. The 3.3σ threshold is calculated as the average of three blank assays, and the error bars represent the standard deviation of three independent measurements. C - Raw data obtained by flowing 3 nM of target DNA HRP spiked in human plasma and acquiring the photosensor signal from chemiluminescence (by flowing Luminol). D - Comparison of specific diode photocurrent values as a function of target DNA concentrations spiked in human plasma for fluorescence and chemiluminescence detection.

5.4. Chapter Conclusions

This chapter demonstrated the regeneration cycling of a microbead-based microfluidic device for detecting target DNA by hybridization to a probe DNA immobilized onto the microbeads. The immobilization of probe DNA by covalent bonding to the beads allowed the system's regeneration without significant loss of probe DNA. Compared with similar methodologies in the literature (**Table 5.2**), our immobilization strategy presents one of the lowest signal losses, close to 0%. When using covalent immobilization of probe DNA, we completely regenerated the bead column after both cDNA and ncDNA hybridization, operating as a regeneration agent 0.3 M of NaOH. It was also demonstrated that the same channel could detect the complementary target DNA and internal control with a non-complementary target DNA. It is useful for a point-of-care device and to guarantee that the assay works correctly. This is also a unique feature usually disregarded in the other works where ssDNA target DNA detection was studied.

Moreover, we demonstrated the reusability of the device up to four regeneration cycles, even when using a complex matrix such as human plasma. When comparing assay duration to detect the target cDNA, we also have the fastest reported assay time of 10 min (including the steps of target DNA capture and sensor regeneration). Regarding LoDs, and comparing with other optical-based sensors [109], we achieved the lowest reported LoD in the range of pM concentrations. In this range of LoD, our system could be used as a standalone device for detecting lung cancer-associated miRNA-21, which can be found in plasma and human serum inside the clinically relevant values at 10 nM to 10 mM reported by Yildiz *et al.* [221]. However, as it is possible to verify in **Table 5.2**, electrochemical biosensors can detect lower concentrations reaching the aM-level, suitable for pathogen detection. One possible solution to decrease the LoD is by integrating a nucleic acid amplification module on-chip before detection, which is the case of the work by Fergusson *et al.*, and it can also justify the low LoD [209].

Furthermore, our assay time is half the time of the assay by Ferguson *et al.* (LoD = < 2×10^{-18} M) and six times faster than Arrifin *et al.* (LoD = 1.74×10^{-18} M). Increasing our assay time could help to decrease the LoD, as well. The nucleic acid detection system described in this work is compatible with fluorescent and chemiluminescent assays. The integration of a thin-film photodetector demonstrates the system's potential as a point-of-use screening tool for biomedical, food, environmental analysis, and biodefense.

Table 5.2 - Critical comparison of similar methodologies in the literature.

Authors	Ref	Biosensor system	Immobilization surface	Probe DNA immobilization	Analyte	Reg conditions	Repeats	Signal loss	Assay time	LoD
This work		Fluorescence tagged ssDNA target optical detection	Agarose porous microbeads (90 µm diameter)	Covalent bond	ssDNA	300 mM of NaOH; probe is maintained	4	non-significant	10 min	7.8×10^{-11} M
Boissinot et al.	[109]	Fluorescence tagged DNA target optical detection	Streptavidin coated polystyrene beads (22.7 µm diameter)	Streptavidin-Biotin	ssDNA amplicons	complementary DNA strand, probe is maintained	1	n.a	5-15 min	$5.6-5.8 \times 10^{-6}$ M*
Ferguson et al.	[209]	Label-free ssDNA electrochemical sensor	Planar gold sensor surface	Thiol-gold	ssDNA amplicons	8 M guanidine hydrochloride	1	2%	20 min	$< 2 \times 10^{-18}$ M
Bronder et al.	[69], [210]	Label-free electrical detection of ssDNA	Planar SiO ₂ sensor surface modified with poly(allylamine hydrochloride) layer	Electrostatic interaction	ssDNA	adsorption of a new poly(allylamine hydrochloride) layer	5	72% to 88% signal loss after 5 repeats	55 min	5×10^{-6} M*
Wang et al.	[211]	ssDNA preparation out of dsDNA amplicons for	Streptavidin-coated magnetic beads (1.05 µm diameter)	Streptavidin-biotin	ssDNA amplicons	100 mM NaOH; probe is maintained	1	n.a	45 min	2.5 ng

Authors	Ref	Biosensor system	Immobilization surface	Probe DNA immobilization	Analyte	Reg conditions	Repeats	Signal loss	Assay time	LoD
		magnetic bead-based microarray analysis with optical detection								
Ariffin et al.	[212]	Label-free electrochemical sensor for ssDNA detection	Hollow silica spheres (HSiSs) (50-200 μm diameter)	Covalent bond	ssDNA	100 mM NaOH; probe is maintained	4	4-6%	60 min	1.74×10^{-18} M
Hong et al.	[117]	Quartz crystal microbalance (QCM) sensor	Avidin modified gold-coated quartz surface	Streptavidin-biotin	ssDNA amplicons	0.8 M Tris-glycine, pH 2.3; probe is maintained	32	30 % signal decrease at cycle 32	50 min	1.6×10^{-9} M
Purse et al.	[222]	Multiplex electrochemical sensor for ssDNA detection	Planar gold sensor surface	Thiol-gold	ssDNA	50mM NaOH; probe is maintained	4	non-significant	20 min	2.50×10^{-13} M

Chapter 6

Bead-based microfluidic device for the capture and detection of DNA amplification products

6. Silica bead-based microfluidic device with integrated photodiodes for the rapid capture and detection of rolling circle amplification products in the femtomolar range

This chapter demonstrated the combination of an isothermal amplification technique, RCA-based nucleic acid amplification off-chip, with on-chip size-selective trapping of amplicons on silica beads (~ 8 nL capture chamber) coupled with a thin-film photodiode (200 × 200 μm area) fluorescence readout. This module can be used as a standalone detection module for labeled products of amplification, acting as a sample concentrator. Parameters such as the flow rate of the amplicon solution and trapping time were optimized, as well as the photodiode measurement settings, providing minimum detection limits below 0.5 fM of targeted nucleic acids and requiring only 5 μL of the pre-amplified sample. Finally, the analytical performance of this approach is evaluated by benchmarking it against a commercial instrument for RCA product (RCP) quantification and further investigated the effect of the number of RCA cycles and elongation times (ranging from 10 to 120 min). Moreover, we demonstrate the application for diagnostic purposes by detecting RNA from influenza and Ebola viruses, thus highlighting its suitability for integrated PoC systems. The contents of this chapter are summarized and reproduced from one original research article entitled “**Silica bead-based microfluidic device with integrated photodiodes for the rapid capture and detection of rolling circle amplification products in the femtomolar range**” [223] co-authored (equal contribution) with Doctor Ruben R. G. Soares (at the time Ph.D. student at INESC-MN), Doctor Felix Neumann and Doctor Narayanan Madaboosi. I was responsible for the development of the experimental microfluidic assays and troubleshooting.

6.1. Introduction

Simple diagnostic devices are currently in high demand to address clinical needs at the PoC, particularly concerning the screening of single-stranded RNA viruses such as Influenza and Ebola, having high mutation rates [224], [225] and the potential to cause devastating pandemics [226]–[228]. Fluorescence-based optical read-outs are the most common transduction method used for bioassays since they are characterized by high sensitivity and specificity [229]. However, fluorescence detection equipment is typically expensive, non-portable, and requires trained personnel, thus being challenging to interface with miniaturized bioassays for field or PoC diagnostic applications [193], [230], [231]. Semiconductor technology allows for true lab-on-a-chip (LoC) applications since optical systems can be miniaturized and integrated with the assay on-chip practically and economically [165]. In these systems, micro-fabricated photodiodes are ideal since they are portable, affordable, reusable, and highly multiplexable for PoC devices [232], [233]. Thin-film hydrogenated amorphous silicon (a-Si:H) photodiodes, as integrated optical signal transducers, have demonstrated promising properties, such as low dark current, fabrication at low temperatures compatible with glass and plastic substrates, high quantum efficiency in the visible spectrum, as well as high sensitivity and a wide dynamic range [234], [235].

Nucleic acid biosensors have revolutionized the field of diagnostics since they simplify traditional testing methods, both in terms of assay time and complexity, offering high specificity and sensitivity. In particular, those based on PCR have shown outstanding performance in the diagnosis of genetic and infectious diseases in healthcare facilities [204]. However, PCR requires specialized instruments for power-intensive thermocycling, thus limiting their use at the PoC [236]. In this context, isothermal amplification methods have been developed to overcome the need for thermocycling [237]. In particular, RCA has proven to be a simple isothermal amplification technique that does not require extensive assay optimization and is typically robust against interferences [238], [239]. Upon combining RCA with PLPs, a powerful molecular detection tool is created, finding numerous applications in the diagnostic field [240]–[242]. RCA products (RCPs) comprise discrete molecules of $\sim 1 \mu\text{m}$ in diameter, which by hybridizing fluorophore-labeled complementary oligonucleotides, display a high local fluorescence intensity that can be imaged using standard low-magnification epifluorescence microscopy, thus making linear RCA-based amplification intrinsically digital, since each molecular recognition event generates one long ssDNA ($\sim 60 \text{ kb}$ at $\sim 1 \text{ kb/min}$ [243]). Different read-outs and biosensing strategies have been reported to

detect RCPs, such as electrical [240], [244], [245], colorimetric [240], or optomagnetic [241]. However, a simple and integrated RCP fluorescent read-out strategy has not been described. It could be highly advantageous to simplify on-chip fluorescence signal transduction using linear RCA-based methods.

In this context, the use of silica microbeads to selectively isolate and concentrate nucleic acids is a practical, cost-effective, and well-known procedure [246] previously integrated into commercial DNA extraction kits [247] and miniaturized devices [248]. The interaction of DNA with silica at neutral pH occurs mainly by hydrophobic and ionic phosphate-silanol interactions [249], largely overcoming the negative charge repulsion between both molecules. These interactions are also known to be significantly promoted in the presence of high concentrations of chaotropic salts such as guanidinium chloride (GdnHCl) [250]. Moreover, the DNA capture efficiency is known to significantly decrease for short fragments, in the range of tens to a few hundred base pairs, even at high salt concentrations, as is the case of the non-specific free detection oligonucleotides [251]. This combination of properties makes silica-based extraction ideal for the selective capture and enrichment of RCPs. In this work, we develop and optimize a silica bead-based microfluidic device integrated with a miniaturized thin-film photodiode for the enrichment and fluorescent detection of RCPs. For this, we characterize the microfluidic trapping of RCPs on silica beads and evaluate the sensitivity of the integrated a-Si:H photodiodes. We further demonstrate the diagnostic capabilities of our biosensor using RNA extracted from infected cell culture isolates of Influenza and Ebola viruses. Thus, this work points towards developing simple bioassay schemes for microfluidic devices with integrated optical-to-electrical signal transduction to address the need for compact and portable biosensing platforms for biomedical applications.

6.2. Materials and experimental methods

6.2.1. Rolling circle amplification (RCA), circle-to-circle amplification (C2CA), and quantification of RCA products (RCPs)

Influenza isolates A/Stockholm/8/2015 grown in MDCK cells was kindly provided by the Karolinska Institute. The RNA was extracted with a MagNA Pure 96 instrument and MagNA Pure 96 DNA and Viral RNA Large Volume Kit (Roche, Sweden). RNA was stored in an elution buffer at -80 °C until further use. The influenza RNA titer was determined by limiting dilution analysis in the Simplexa™ assay and Poisson distribution using the Simplexa™ Flu A/B & RSV Direct Kit (Focus Diagnostics Inc.,

Cypress, USA) according to instructions from the manufacturer. Ebola samples were obtained from the Public Health Agency of Sweden, under BSL-4 biocontainment facilities, as inactivated cell culture isolates. The RNA was extracted using the Direct-zol™ RNA isolation kit (Zymo Research, California, USA) according to instructions from the manufacturer. To perform the reverse transcription, two different optimized protocols were used for either influenza or Ebola samples. For influenza, cDNA synthesis, 100 nM of 5′ biotin-modified primers (Integrated DNA Technologies, Coralville, USA) and 500 μM dNTPs (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, USA) were added to the viral RNA (vRNA). The mixture was preheated at 65 °C for 5 min and snap-cooled on ice. After that, 100 mU/μL RiboLock, an RNase inhibitor, 250 mU/μL Transcript ME reverse transcriptase, and reverse transcription buffer (Blirt S. A., Gdansk, Poland) were added to a total volume of 20 μL. Reverse transcription was performed at 55 °C for 20 min, followed by 5 min heat inactivation at 85 °C. Ebola cDNA synthesis was performed using the SuperScript™ III Reverse Transcriptase kit according to the instructions from the manufacturer (Invitrogen, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, USA). The reverse transcribed influenza and Ebola samples were subjected to C2CA and RCA, respectively, using sets of 8 PLPs each.

The oligonucleotide sequences used are summarized in Table S1. The ligation of PLPs was performed in Φ29 DNA polymerase buffer (33 mM Tris-acetate, pH 7.9, 10 mM Mg-acetate, 66 mM K-acetate, 1 ‰ (v/v) TWEEN® 20 and 1 mM DTT) (Mg-acetate, K-acetate, TWEEN® 20 and DTT were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich, Darmstadt, Germany, while Tris-HCl, PBS, and NaCl were acquired from Karolinska Institute Substrat, Stockholm, Sweden) containing 0.2 μg/μL BSA (Sigma-Aldrich, Darmstadt, Germany), 0.68 mM ATP (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, USA), 500 mU/μL T4 DNA ligase (Blirt S. A., Gdansk, Poland) and 1 nM PLPs at 37 °C for 20 min and inactivated at 65 °C for 2 min. Amplification was performed in Φ29 DNA polymerase buffer containing 125 μM dNTPs, 0.2 μg/μL BSA, and 400 mU/μL Φ29 DNA polymerase (Monserate Biotechnology Group, San Diego, USA) at 37 °C for 10 to 120 min and inactivated at 65 °C for 2 min.

Table 6.1 – Oligonucleotide sequences used. Eight PLPs were designed to target each of the H3N2 influenza subtype genome segments and 7 Ebola genes. Synthetic target DNA and a separate PLP were designed for the time point experiments. Furthermore, 4 detection oligonucleotides were designed for RCP detection. The PLP backbones include the binding site for detecting oligonucleotide and the *Afu* I restriction oligonucleotide (needed for C2CA).

Type of Oligo	Target	Sequence (5' to 3' direction)
RT Primer	H3N2	Biotin-CTCTCTCTCTCTCTCTCTCT AGCGTAGACGCTTTGTC
RT Primer	H3N2	Biotin-CTCTCTCTCTCTCTCTCTCT CACGATGGAAAAGCATG
RT Primer	H3N2	Biotin-CTCTCTCTCTCTCTCTCTCT TCCTCATCGGAGGACTT
RT Primer	H3N2	Biotin-CTCTCTCTCTCTCTCTCTCT GACCAAAGTCTCCCACC
RT Primer	H3N2	Biotin-CTCTCTCTCTCTCTCTCTCT TTTGCGAAAAGCTTGAA
RT Primer	H3N2	Biotin-CTCTCTCTCTCTCTCTCTCT GTAACATGGTGAATAGGAA
RT Primer	H3N2	Biotin-CTCTCTCTCTCTCTCTCTCT TAGGGTTACTTCAAATAACGA
RT Primer	H3N2	Biotin-CTCTCTCTCTCTCTCTCTCT TCCTTTATGACAAAAGAAGAAATAAG
PLP	H3N2	PO ₄ - GGGTGCATCTGATCTCATTAGTGTATGCAGCTCCTCAGTAATAGTGTCT TACATAGCACCGGAATAAGGCCAGACTTGCATTGGCAAT
PLP	H3N2	PO ₄ - TGTTGGCTTGGCGCCAGATTGTGTATGCAGCTCCTCAGTAATAGTGTCT TACATAGCACCGGAATAAGGCCATGTAGCATCTCACCAT
PLP	H3N2	PO ₄ - CATTCCCATTGAGGGCATTGTGTATGCAGCTCCTCAGTAATAGTGTCT TACATAGCACCGGAATAAGGCCCTCCATGTTATTTGGGTCTC
PLP	H3N2	PO ₄ - GCATTTTTATCATCCCCGTGTGTATGCAGCTCCTCAGTAATAGTGTCTT ACATAGCACCGGAATAAGGCCCTGTAATGAAGCTAGCAGTT
PLP	H3N2	PO ₄ - TTCTCAAGGCAGGAGAAGTTGTGTATGCAGCTCCTCAGTAATAGTGTCT TACATAGCACCGGAATAAGGCCCATCCACATAGGCTCTAAAA
PLP	H3N2	PO ₄ - AGAGACTCGAACTGTGTTATGTGTATGCAGCTCCTCAGTAATAGTGTCT TACATAGCACCGGAATAAGGCCCGGAATCTCTGTAGATTTTT
PLP	H3N2	PO ₄ - TTTCATTACCCCCAACCGGAGTGTATGCAGCTCCTCAGTAATAGTGTCT TACATAGCACCGGAATAAGGCCCATTTGCCAGTTTGGCCTTCT

PLP	H3N2	PO ₄ - TAATGGACCGTACTTGTACAGTGTATGCAGCTCCTCAGTAATAGTGTCT TACATAGCACCGGAATAAGGCCCAAGTTTTGTACACTTTTGGG
Synthetic Target	Ebola	Biotin- CTCTCTCTCTCTCTTTTCCTGATACTTTGTGCACATACCGGCACCGGC TCTCTTCTGGCGCTGCTGGTAGACACTCACTCCCGTCA
PLP	Ebola	PO ₄ - CCAGCAGCGCCAGAGTGTATGCAGCTCCTCAGTAATAGTGTCTTACATA TCGAGGATCGTCCGCATACGGGAGTGAGTGTCTA
PLP	Ebola	PO ₄ - CAATTCATTTTCTCGGTAGTGTATGCAGCTCCTCAGTAATAGTGTCTTAC AGTAGCCGTGACTATCGACTAGGATTATTGTCATAAAT
PLP	Ebola	PO ₄ - TTTGTGATTCGTCTTTTGTGTATGCAGCTCCTCAGTAATAGTGTCTTAC AGTAGCCGTGACTATCGACTAAATAATCATTGACTAGT
PLP	Ebola	PO ₄ - CCAGTGTAACAAATCTATGTGTATGCAGCTCCTCAGTAATAGTGTCTTAC AGTAGCCGTGACTATCGACTAATAAAATTGTTGACCAT
PLP	Ebola	PO ₄ - TCTGATCAATTTTGTCTGGTGTATGCAGCTCCTCAGTAATAGTGTCTTAC AGTAGCCGTGACTATCGACTCAACAAAATCATGAATAA
PLP	Ebola	PO ₄ - CGACACCTAGAGGAAGCCAAGTGTATGCAGCTCCTCAGTAATAGTGTCT TACCCTCAATGCTGCTGCTGTACTACGCTGTAGGTCTTTTGATCAG
PLP	Ebola	PO ₄ - TCTTGGAAGATTGGAACCTCTGTGTATGCAGCTCCTCAGTAATAGTGTCT TACCCTCAATGCTGCTGCTGTACTACGGATGACAGGTGGAGCAGCA
DO	RCA product	AF430- or Cy3-TTTTTCCTCAGTAATAGTGTCTTAC
DO	C2CA product	AF430- or Cy3-TTTTTGTAAGACACTATTACTGAGG

After PLP ligation, RCA was performed in Φ 29 DNA polymerase buffer containing 125 μ M dNTPs, 0.2 μ g/ μ L BSA, and 400 mU/ μ L Φ 29 DNA polymerase (Monserate Biotechnology Group, San Diego, USA) at 37 °C for 10–120 min followed by inactivation at 65 °C for 2 min. In the case of C2CA, ligation of PLPs was performed using a mix of 10 nM of each PLP, 0.2 μ g/ μ L of BSA, 500 mU/ μ L Ampligase, and 1 U/ μ L RNase H in Ampligase buffer (Epicentre, Nordic Biolabs AB, Täby, Sweden). 10 μ L of cDNA were added and incubated for 10 min at 37 °C followed by 5 min incubation at 55 °C. Then, the biotinylated cDNA with ligated PLPs was first captured on streptavidin-coated DynabeadsTM MyOneTM T1 (Life Technologies, Oslo,

Norway). The beads were resuspended in 20 μL of amplification mixture (0.2 $\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{L}$ BSA, 125 μM dNTPs, and 200 mU/ μL Φ29 DNA polymerase in Ampligase buffer) and incubated for 20 min at 37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, followed by 2 min enzyme inactivation at 65 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Afterward, the liquid was discarded, and bead-bound RCPs were digested with 120 mU/ μL *Afu* I (New England Biolabs, Bionordika, Stockholm, Sweden), 120 nM restriction oligonucleotide and 0.2 $\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{L}$ BSA in 20 μL Ampligase buffer at 37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 5 min followed by 2 min enzyme inactivation at 65 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The supernatant, containing monomerized RCPs, was transferred to new vials for the second amplification while discarding the magnetic beads. The second amplification mixture contained 0.2 $\mu\text{g}/\mu\text{L}$ BSA, 0.68 mM ATP, 14 mU/ μL T4 DNA ligase, 125 μM dNTPs, and 200 mU/ μL Φ29 DNA polymerase in 10 μL Ampligase buffer. Amplification was performed for 60 min at 37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, and heat-inactivated at 65 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 2 min. Experimental assay steps of C2CA are illustrated in **Figure 6.1 - A**. For quantification, RCPs were labeled by adding 30 μL hybridization buffer (1.4 M NaCl, 0.01% TWEEN® 20, 20 mM of Tris-HCl, pH 8, and EDTA) containing 5 nM of the respective detection oligonucleotide (Table S1) for 2 min at 75 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 20 min at 55 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. RCPs from RCA and C2CA were quantified by amplified single-molecule detection (ASMD) using the dedicated instrument Aquila 400 from Q-linea (Uppsala, Sweden). The measurement average of technical duplicates was obtained, and the standard deviation was calculated.

6.2.1. Packing of silica beads and capture of RCPs in the microfluidic device and fluorescence measurements using fluorescence microscopy

A suspension of mesoporous spherical silica beads (dried flash silica with 40–75 μm diameter and ~ 7 nm pores, purchased from Sigma-Aldrich) was first prepared in a solution of 20% (w/w) polyethylene glycol 8000 in water. After first pre-filling the device with water, the bead suspension was flowed into the 100 μm tall chamber at 10 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ by exerting a negative pressure at one of the outlets. The inlet of the 100 μm tall chamber was then sealed with a 20 ga metallic plug, and the PEG solution was washed with water through the 20 μm tall channel. The RCP solution obtained in **subsection 6.2.1** was then diluted 5-fold in an aqueous solution of 6 M guanidinium hydrochloride ($\geq 99\%$, Sigma-Aldrich) and flowed through the 20 μm tall channel at flow rates ranging from 1.25 to 50 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$.

Figure 6.1 - Schematics of the off-chip target detection and amplification, followed by on-chip RCA product (RCP) capture and fluorescence signal transduction. A - Off-chip padlock probe (PLP)-based detection followed by rolling circle amplification (RCA) or circle-to-circle amplification (C2CA). The labeling of the RCPs is performed by hybridization using an excess concentration of detection oligonucleotides labeled with Alexa 430. B - On-chip RCP capture on silica beads after dilution in a chaotropic salt (guanidinium chloride) solution. The capture of the RCPs is continuously monitored by an a-SiC:H photodiode aligned below the bead microcolumn. An a-SiC:H absorption filter is deposited on top of the photodiode to selectively block the excitation light ($\lambda_{\text{ex}}=405 \text{ nm}$) emitted by a laser diode while being semi-transparent to the emission light ($\lambda_{\text{em}}=540 \text{ nm}$).

The trapping of RCPs was first monitored with fluorescence microscopy using a Leica DMLM microscope equipped with a DFC300FX digital camera and a 100 W mercury short-arc lamp coupled with an I3 filter cube. The illumination was performed discontinuously to periodically acquire images using an exposure time of 1 s. The quantitative analysis of the fluorescence signal was performed via grayscale measurements using the software ImageJ (National Institutes of Health, Bethesda, MA, USA). All solutions were prepared using type I water obtained from a Milli-Q system from Merck.

6.3. Results and Discussion

6.3.1. Design of microfluidic device for RCP capture on silica microbeads

The main goal of this work was to develop a microfluidic device to rapidly quantify RCPs resulting from the bioassay described in the schematics in **Figure 6.1 - A**. The microfluidic device integrating RCP capture, enrichment, and fluorescence signal transduction is schematized in **Figure 6.1 - B**. To perform the analysis, the RCP solution in the hybridization buffer was first diluted 5-fold in 6 M GdnHCl and then flowed through the silica bead-packed chamber. Upon illumination with a 405 nm laser light, the filtered photodiode aligned ~ 100 μm below the chamber allows the continuous and non-contact monitoring of Alexa 430-derived fluorescence emission, which is proportional to the number of captured RCPs on the silica beads. Considering the low bead volumes (a few hundreds of nL) and mass of structural material (~ 1 g) required per PDMS device, these were designed to be disposable after a single measurement, i.e., no regeneration protocol was required to desorb the RCPs from the silica beads. Furthermore, since bare silica beads are used to perform direct RCP capture, the PDMS device containing packed beads can be stored for several years. Upon introduction of GdnHCl to the RCP solution, the hydrophobic and ionic phosphate-silanol interactions are significantly promoted [249], [250]. In addition, the selectivity of silica towards long oligonucleotide molecules is ideal for minimizing the background signal from the free detection oligonucleotides (25 bp).

6.3.2. Fluorescence microscopy imaging and flow-rate optimization

The capture of RCPs on the silica bead chamber was first monitored using fluorescence microscopy (**Figure 6.2 - A**). After flowing an RCP solution at 2.5 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ for 9 min through the chamber, a significant fluorescence signal could be measured. Interestingly, it was observed that the signal was highly heterogeneous and arranged as entangled and elongated filaments rather than individual dots, as previously observed in microfluidic assays where the RCPs are generated on the bead surface [198] or enriched on membranes [252]. These entangled filaments, hypothesized to be stretched RCPs, are dragged along the channel in the direction of the liquid flow, highlighting potential shear stress-derived effects, similar to what has been reported for gold nanowire formation [244], [245]. Therefore, it was critical to subsequently evaluate the effect of flow rate on RCP capture to achieve a balance between (i) RCP

capture efficiency per flowed volume and (ii) RCP capture kinetics, thus maximizing signal output and minimizing assay time and reagent expenditure. On the other hand, flowing hybridization buffer containing free detection oligonucleotides (5 nM) did not provide a measurable increase in fluorescence above the background after 10 min.

The results obtained for the flow-rate optimization are shown in **Figure 6.2 - B**. We observed that the fluorescence intensity and slope (m) measured after flowing a fixed volume of solution are inversely proportional to the flow rate down to 2.5 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$. A decrease in flow-rateflow rate down to 1.25 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ did not provide an increase in capture efficiency, resulting in fluorescence intensity of 32.5 AU after flowing 50 μL of solution at $t = 20$ min, resulting in a two-fold increased detection time compared to using 2.5 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$. When evaluating the capture kinetics, the flow rates of 2.5, 5, and 10 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ provided approximately the same signal intensity after the same time, despite the two- and fourfold higher reagent expenditure using 5 and 10 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$. This trend implies that above 2.5 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$, the capture is already in reaction-limited conditions. On the other hand, the low signals measured above 10 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ indicate that a combination of high shear rates and/or quiet residence times may hinder silica's interaction with the DNA molecules. Overall, a 2.5 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ flow rate provided an optimum balance between assay time and reagent consumption.

Figure 6.2 A - Bright field (top) and fluorescence (bottom) microscopy imaging of the silica bead microcolumn and captured RCPs and B - flow rate optimization. The fluorescence intensity values correspond to the grayscale values measured using an ROI of constant area positioned at the region of RCP concentration. A constant volume of 50 μL and concentration of 41.5 fM target influenza RNA, amplified using C2CA, was used for all experiments.

6.3.3. Monitoring conditions of RCP capture using a-Si:H photodiodes

To perform the continuous monitoring of RCP capture on the silica beads, it was first necessary to optimize the illumination frequency and intensity of the excitation light to minimize photobleaching without a significant compromise in temporal resolution (**Figure 6.3**). By continuously illuminating the chamber with an incident photon flux (φ) of $3.1 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$, corresponding to an ND 1.5 filter (**Figure 6.3 - A**), it was observed that while the capture of RCPs could be effectively monitored above the laser excitation baseline (i.e., residual direct and scattered excitation light leaking through the a-SiC:H absorption filter), a pronounced photobleaching effect could be observed after stopping the liquid flow, having a very significant absolute rate of $\sim 33\%$ relative to the signal increase (i.e., $m_{\text{signal}} = 2.4 \times 10^{-15} \text{ A s}^{-1}$ and $m_{\text{bleach}} = -8.0 \times 10^{-16} \text{ A s}^{-1}$). The excitation was performed discontinuously to minimize photobleaching effects by turning ON the laser every minute for approximately 7.5 s (**Figure 6.3 - B**). This data is then normalized against the excitation baseline (henceforth referred to as specific photocurrent) and plotted over time as shown in **Figure 6.3 - C**. Comparing continuous and discontinuous illumination, the specific current after 10 min was observed to be 37.6% higher using the latter mode. Finally, the intensity of incident light was increased to $\varphi = 1 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (ND 1.0) and $\varphi = 3.1 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (ND 0.5) to optimize the emission output of the fluorophore. The results are shown in **Figure 6.3 - D**. It is possible to conclude that while the ND 1.0 provided a > 2 -fold increase in fluorescence emission, a further rise in excitation photon flux (ND 0.5) did not provide an increased sensitivity, probably due to simultaneous growth in photobleaching effects, which become significant also in the discontinuous mode of excitation. Thus, the ND 1.0 was selected for the subsequent calibration curves at different concentrations of target genetic material.

6.3.1. Detection of Influenza A RNA and benchmarking against a commercial RCP counter

Using the optimized conditions for the read-out microfluidic device, we tested its analytical performance by adapting a C2CA assay to detect Influenza A (Neumann *et al.*, 2018). Serial dilutions of ssRNA from viral isolates were processed by reverse transcription and C2CA (**Figure 6.1 - A**). The resulting RCPs were measured in parallel by our microfluidic read-out device and a commercial RCP counter.

Figure 6.3 - Monitoring RCP capture on the microfluidic device using the integrated photodiode (current values acquired at 1.25 s intervals). The 405 nm laser light used to excite the fluorophores was passed through different neutral density filters ranging from ND 1.5 to ND 0.5, as indicated in each plot, resulting in photon fluxes (ϕ) of $\sim 3.1 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-2} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ up to $3.1 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-2} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$. A constant concentration of 41.5 fM target influenza RNA, amplified using C2CA, was used for all experiments, and flowed at $2.5 \mu\text{L}/\text{min}$. A - Raw current measured for the continuous excitation of the silica microcolumn before and after stopping the flow of the solution. B - Raw current measured for the discontinuous excitation of the bead microcolumn at 60 s intervals for an average pulse duration of 7.5 s. C - Average specific photocurrent measured over time for the data shown in plot B, calculated by subtracting the laser excitation baseline from all data acquired with the laser turned ON. The error bars correspond to $\pm\text{SD}$ of n ranging from 3 to 5 continuous points. D - Optimization of the ND filter used to perform the discontinuous excitation of the bead microcolumn. Error bars correspond to $\pm\text{SD}$ of n ranging from 3 to 5 continuous points. The inset plot shows the average specific photocurrent ($\pm\text{SD}$, $n=2$) measured after 10 min for two independent experiments using each ND filter.

For each resulting RCP solution, the specific photocurrent was monitored for 10 minutes, requiring a total sample volume of $5 \mu\text{L}$ (i.e., $25 \mu\text{L}$ of solution 5-fold diluted in GndHCl). The results are shown in **Figure 6.4 - A**. The RCP capture kinetics between 0 and 10 min could be fit for linear regression. The data shows that the slope significantly increases above the baseline (i.e., sample “zero”, without target genetic material) for increasing initial target concentrations and, despite the non-specific adsorption of free detection oligos being previously undetectable using the fluorescence microscopy setup (**section 6.3.2**), here the sample “zero” also provides a measurable increase of $2.2 \times 10^{-13} \pm 1.9 \times 10^{-14} \text{ A}$ ($t = 10 \text{ min}$) above the laser illumination background. The measured slopes were then plotted against the initial ssRNA concentration (**Figure 6.4 - B**) and the LoD, here defined as the target concentration, which provides a signal equal to 3.29 times the standard deviation of the background (i.e., the concentration of 0.28 fM, which is not significantly different

from the zero), was calculated as 0.46 ± 0.02 fM with a dynamic range of more than 2.7 orders of magnitude.

We obtained a high correlation between our microfluidic device and the commercial RCP counter ($R^2 = 0.995$) (**Figure 6.4 - D**), and by comparing practical features of both systems, the portability and low sample volumes ($5 \mu\text{L}$ against $25 \mu\text{L}$ on the commercial system) intrinsic to our read-out are advantageous. Furthermore, depending on the sensitivity requirements, the analysis time and reagent volumes can be further reduced, considering that significant signals above the laser excitation baseline could be measured in less than 2 min for target concentrations in the tens of femtomolar.

Figure 6.4 - Calibration curve for increasing target RNA concentrations and correlation with a commercial RCP counter (Q-linea Aquila 400). A - Specific photocurrent measured over time for increasing concentrations of influenza RNA. The zero corresponds to a sample without target RNA, establishing the baseline for non-specific amplification and residual capture of free detection oligonucleotides. Error bars correspond to \pm SD of n ranging from 3 to 5 continuous points. B - Average current slope measured between 0 and 10 min at increasing target RNA concentrations. Error bars correspond to \pm SD of two independent measurements for each point. C - RCP counts for each viral RNA concentration measured were using the Q-linea Aquila 400 instrument. D - Correlation between the RCP counts and the average current slope measured using the miniaturized device.

6.3.2. Optimization of amplification time with Ebola RNA extracts

Since the microfluidic-based readout was demonstrated to detect RCPs in a short time at initial target concentrations in the fM-range, we investigated the number of RCA cycles and elongation time required to generate a detectable fluorescence

signal. For this, we first compared the photodiode response when performing RCA and C2CA on Ebola vRNA extracts. **Figure 6.5 - A** shows that both conditions result in a detectable fluorescence signal after only a few minutes of microfluidic trapping, thus demonstrating the suitability of both assays with the developed read-out. However, in this particular assay setup, RCA comes with the advantage of fewer assay steps (3 vs. 7 steps) when compared to C2CA, which facilitates eventual integration with the reported miniaturized device towards PoC applications.

Moreover, to optimize the total assay time, we further investigated the sensor response for increasing times of RCA. **Figure 6.5- B** shows a linear correlation ($R^2 = 0.99$) between elongation time and the measured slope. From the obtained linear regression, the minimum amplification time necessary to provide a significant signal (3.3σ) above the background was calculated as 41.5 min. The linearity of generated signal was maintained throughout all elongation times proving the suitability of our trapping method for a wide range of RCP sizes, estimated to range between 10,000 and 120,000 bp [243], without a simultaneous loss of capture efficiency.

Figure 6.5 - Detection of Ebola vRNA using RCA and the miniaturized read-out device. A - Detection of resulting RCPs after one (RCA) or two (C2CA) cycles of amplification for positive (P) ($14.3 \text{ ng}\cdot\mu\text{L}^{-1}$ of viral RNA) or negative (N) (type I water only) samples. The inset plot shows the slope for technical replicates. B - Detection of RCPs generated using increasing RCA times. The inset plot shows the slope measured in duplicate for the same sample.

6.4. Chapter Conclusions

In conclusion, we have presented a novel and integrated read-out strategy for RCA-based assays in a microfluidic format by combining size-selective trapping on silica beads with miniaturized p-i-n a-Si:H photodiodes. Our device provided a practical, portable, and affordable alternative over commercially available instruments for RCP detection with a wide dynamic range, resorting to sampling volumes below $5 \mu\text{L}$ and achieving total assay sensitivities in the low femtomolar range ($\text{LoD} < 0.5 \text{ fM}$). These figures of merit demonstrate comparable, or superior sensitivities to recently reported

paper-based diagnostic devices using reverse transcription loop-mediated isothermal amplification (RT-LAMP) for viral detection, combined with a dramatic decrease in sample requirements (5–10-fold) and automated signal transduction [253], [254]. On the other hand, while superior sensitivities (~10-fold) were previously reported using fully integrated lab-on-disk devices coupled with RT-PCR amplification [255], significantly higher sample volumes (200 μ L) were required. Immediate future perspectives include the full integration of the RCA assay with the reported read-out, bringing our approach closer to the PoC by avoiding lengthy and laborious off-chip amplification procedures. Furthermore, since the use of PLPs offers high multiplex capability, the assay can be extended to detect several pathogens [252] and implemented in a multiplexed format for a broader selection of targets, including anti-microbial resistance markers.

Chapter 7

Bead-based microfluidic chip for chemical lysis of bacteria and virus-like particles with integrated nucleic acid capture and detection

7. Chemical lysis and nucleic acid capture of Gram-positive, Gram-negative, and virus-like particles using a bead-based microfluidic chip

Point-of-care tests can provide an appropriate medical diagnosis for pathogens, and they should be robust and universal enough to detect Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria and even nonenveloped and enveloped viruses. In this sense, cell lysis and nucleic acid extraction are critical steps with a profound impact on the success of the diagnosis. In this chapter, we describe the development of a simple, continuous, rapid, and universal chemical lysis module featuring an integrated microfluidic bead-based capture chamber for nucleic acid extraction. *Escherichia coli* was used as a model for Gram-negative bacteria, *Staphylococcus aureus* was used as a model for Gram-positive bacteria, and MS2 was used as a model for nonenveloped virus like-particle. Cell lysis and on-chip genomic DNA and RNA detection were performed in under 30 minutes. Using a mass balance approach and quantitative polymerase chain reaction, we could quantify lysis and capture efficiencies on-chip for the different lytic solutions tested. The strategy that provided the best results for Gram-negative and Gram-positive bacteria and nonenveloped virus like-particle was with GenoLyse® + BPER + Proteinase K (50 % \pm 21 %, 58 % \pm 20 %, and 47 % \pm 27 % of capture efficiency, respectively). This work was presented at the 23rd International Conference on Miniaturized Systems for Chemistry and Life Sciences (μ TAS 2019) as a Poster. The contents of this chapter are summarized and reproduced from one original research paper draft submitted for publication. I fabricated the microfluidic devices. Conceived, designed, performed, and analyzed the experimental results. I was the main writer of the publication and creator of the Poster.

7.1. Introduction

Two global health threats of increasing urgency for public health are viral infections and AMR. Viral infections can spread swiftly across the globe and cause a pandemic, as was observed with the COVID-19 pandemic, with significant consequences to human health, the global economy, and social interactions. On the other hand, infections caused by antibiotic-resistant bacteria (ARB) that were disregarded during the pandemic crisis will become more evident again as the world returns to a new normal, becoming a significant threat to global health [256]. AMR is considered a One Health problem that caused more than one million deaths worldwide in 2019, with predictions to reach 10 million deaths annually by 2050 [1]. One proven way to fight these threats is by controlling the source of infection, reducing the spread, and containing the transmission of these pathogens via early detection [257]. In this sense, accurate diagnostic systems are mandatory for successful global health management [258], [259]. Current detection methods rely on culture methods, molecular methods (such as PCR), and enzyme immunoassays, and the test result can often take 2 to 4 days to be obtained [204].

PoC tests can provide an appropriate medical diagnosis for bacterial and viral pathogens. However, PoC tests must be robust and universal enough to detect both Gram-positive bacteria (e.g., MRSA) and Gram-negative bacteria (e.g., CRE) or even enveloped (such as the SARS-CoV-2) and nonenveloped (such as the Norovirus) viruses. PoC devices based on molecular methods would confer the sensitivity required for detection and the specificity to distinguish infections presenting similar symptoms [257], [260]. Although there are already a few commercially available PoC devices to detect infectious diseases, significant improvement is still needed. For instance, sample preparation (including a lysis step) in these devices is usually performed off-chip. A fully integrated device is required, with on-chip sample preparation, that can achieve detection limits of 1-10 CFU or PFU/mL [39], [261]. Expanding the panel of pathogens these devices can detect is also urgent to fight viral infections and antibiotic-resistant bacteria. There is still a need to have a device that will detect specific pathogens, such as viruses or bacteria, starting from the raw biological sample (such as a swab). The first steps in a POC test, which uses a molecular method approach to detect pathogens, are sample preparation and cell lysis. These steps will affect all the downstream processes and impact the success of the diagnosis in terms of sensitivity and specificity. The efficiency of the lysis of bacteria and virus cells may differ due to structural differences, which compromises subsequent analysis steps. Thus, developing a universal lysis and extraction module

that can lyse and capture nucleic acids from Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria and virus-like particles is a challenge that holds the key to successful sample-to-answer PoC tests. This work aims at simplifying both steps in a lysis module that can be used in a fully integrated PoC device. Here we exploit universal chemical cell lysis for bacteria and viruses coupled with SPE (bead-based) of the nucleic acids present in the solution.

Non-mechanical lysis methods can be divided into physical, chemical, and enzymatic processes. In the first case, physical disruption of the membrane is accomplished by non-contact methods that utilize external forces such as heat, pressure, and sound energy. In the case of high temperatures, the proteins in the membrane are denatured, leading to the release of the intracellular components [261]. Thermal lysis was used and considered the gold standard for lysis in this work. To disrupt the membranes, chemical methods use lysis buffers, such as alkali buffers. The main constituents of these buffers are sodium hydroxide and SDS. The OH⁻ ions break the fatty acid glycerol ester bonds, and the SDS solubilizes the membrane leading to cell disruption. One downside of this method is that the process is usually long (6 - 12 h). Detergents such as BPER can also be used to disrupt lipid-lipid, lipid-protein, and protein-protein interactions to affect the membrane. Finally, enzymes such as lysozyme and protease can be used to lyse specific cells. Lysozyme is usually used to lyse Gram-positive bacteria by attacking the peptidoglycan layer and breaking down the glycosidic bond [262].

Commercial lysis kits are also available and can be chosen according to the type of cell to be lysed. Usually, commercial kits use an admixture of standard lysis methods. For instance, GenoLyse® (GL), used to extract DNA from bacteria, uses a combination of alkaline lysis buffer and thermal heating.

The current extraction methods typically use incubation steps with enzymes such as lysozyme and proteinase K (PK) to digest cell wall components and interfering proteins, respectively. They are often user-dependent, complex, time-consuming, or suffer from a low yield of nucleic acid extraction [263]. Recent works of on-chip lysis methods have shown that chemical lysis combined with mechanical lysis has a good DNA recovery [264]–[267]. For instance, in the paper by Sciuto *et al.*, the lysis and extraction required 15 minutes, with an LoD of 8 copies/reaction for the Hepatitis B virus [268].

We used *S. aureus* and *E. coli* as our Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria models, respectively, and bacteriophages M13 and MS2 as nonenveloped virions

models to test and compare different chemical lysis methods. The goal was to optimize lysis efficiency for the various organisms tested. We demonstrate a mass balance approach using a standard molecular method, qPCR, which allows us to calculate the number of nucleic acids extracted and therefore calculate the efficiency of the lysis methods. This method can be generalized to other pathogens and lysis methods to characterize such devices. Moreover, this allowed the quantification of the nucleic acid copies captured on-chip via an SPE method. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first time a continuous on-chip chemical lysis strategy has been applied to virus and bacteria cells. This mass-balance quantification approach can be helpful when selecting a lysis strategy to implement on-chip, especially when high sensitivities are required. Finally, all the tests were performed without amplification on-chip. The next step would be integrating an amplification module with this lysis strategy. The lysis method implemented on-chip will also influence subsequent modules such as amplification. By performing the qPCR outside the chip after the on-chip lysis, we can already indicate if the on-chip amplification would be inhibited due to the on-chip lysis.

7.2. Materials and experimental methods

7.2.1. Bacteria and Bacteriophages

S. aureus (ATCC® 19433) and *E. coli* (ATCC® 13706) were used as Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria models, respectively. *S. aureus* and *E. coli* were grown in tryptic soy agar (TSA, Biokar) and incubated at 36 (±2) °C for 18 (±4) hrs. Following incubation, a cell suspension was prepared in sterile PBS 1×. A solution containing approximately 1.6×10⁸ CFU/mL was obtained for both *S. aureus* and *E. coli* by measuring the optical density (OD) of the solutions in an 1102 UV/vis spectrophotometer (Techcomp, CN) at a wavelength of 600 nm (OD₆₀₀). Bacteria calculations were performed using the following correlation [269]:

$$1 OD_{600} = 8 \times 10^8 \text{ cell per mL culture}$$

Equation 7.1

Adjustments to the solutions were made to reach a final absorbance of 0.200, which corresponds to a concentration of 1.6×10⁸ CFU/mL, according to **Equation 7.1**. Bacteriophage MS2 (ATCC® 15597-B1TM) was quantified using reverse transcription digital PCR (RT-dPCR) carried out on a QuantStudio 3D Digital PCR System (ThermoScientific, US). The stock of MS2 bacteriophage was found to have a concentration of 10¹¹ genome copies (GC)/mL or 10⁹ PFU/mL. The M13

bacteriophage strain used in this study was based on the helper phage M13KO7 (New England Biolabs), engineered in pIII and propagated in *E. coli* 2737 (New England Biolabs). Cultures were grown overnight at 37°C with orbital shaking at 220 rpm in SOB Media supplemented with KCl (2.5 mM), MgCl₂ (10 mM), ampicillin (100 µg/mL), tetracycline (10 µg/mL), and kanamycin (50 µg/mL). For phage recovery, PEG/NaCl was used [270]. M13 phages were obtained from the culture at 10¹¹ PFU/mL in 1 × PBS.

7.2.2. Lysis assays on-chip

The lysis in this work was performed at rt. The on-chip lysis was performed using the chip illustrated in **Figure 7.1**. Inlet 1 contained 60 µL of the microorganisms to be lysed. The concentration inserted was 10⁸ CFU or PFU/mL unless stated otherwise. Inlet 2 was used to insert the mixture of lysis solutions. For the chemical lysis, different combinations were tested. A mixture of 1:1 (v/v) of GL (Hain Lifescience, Nehren, Germany) lysis solution with BPER solution (Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc., Rockford, IL). A mixture of 1:1 (v/v) of GL lysis solution with BPER solution and 0.1 of Proteinase K (Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc., Rockford, IL) and a solution of RNA rapid extraction solution (Invitrogen™, MA, USA). For all cases, the total volume of solution inserted in inlet 2 was 60 µL. Inlet 3 was used to add 60 µL of a neutralization buffer after lysis into the solution. For the mixtures with GL present, the neutralization buffer used was supplied by the GL Kit. PBS 1× was used as a neutralization buffer for the RNA extraction solution. The solutions flowed simultaneously by applying a positive pressure with the conditions given in the bead packing and liquid handling subsection. Thermal lysis was also performed. The solution with the microorganisms was lysed in a microcentrifuge tube and placed at 95 °C (Heating Block QBT1, Grant Instruments, UK) for 10 min. After this, the lysed microorganism was introduced into inlet 1, while inlets 2 and 3 were used to flow PBS 1 ×. After flowing the solutions through the beads, EvaGreen® (EG) dye was flowed through the microfluidic chip to intercalate in the nucleic acids captured by the beads allowing for subsequent on-chip fluorescence detection. A final washing step with PBS was performed prior to the fluorescence measurement. The fluorescence signal was monitored with a Leica DMLM microscope equipped with a DFC300FX CCD camera and a 100 W mercury arc lamp coupled to a blue light excitation filter with a band-pass excitation of 450–490 nm and a long-pass emission filter of 515 nm. The setup used a 10× magnification, and 1× gain to acquire the images. The fluorescence signal was analyzed via measurement of the green channel in the acquired RGB images using the software ImageJ (National Institutes of Health).

Figure 7.1 - Schematics of the microfluidic device for pathogens lysis and genetic material detection. A - Photograph of the actual microfluidic device. B - Detailed image of parallelogram barriers mixer and dimensions of the mixer repeating unit. C - Detailed image of the microfluidic chamber used to pack the beads and respective sizes. The positively charged beads captured the free genomic DNA in the solution after lysis.

7.2.3. Lysis assays of-chip

Several non-mechanical methods were applied: a physical method that uses high temperatures to lyse the organisms (thermal lysis) and three variations of chemical lysis, GL + BPER, GL + BPER + PK, and an RNA extraction kit, performed at rt. The lysis assays off-chip were performed in 1.5 mL microcentrifuge tubes (VWR). All the volumes were maintained the same as those used for on-chip lysis. For the quantification analysis, the outflow was collected in a microcentrifuge tube. Prior to qPCR or reverse transcription qPCR (RT-qPCR), the solution was centrifuged at 9700 g for 10 min.

7.2.4. Nucleic acid purification

The lytic solutions where Proteinase K (PK) was added to the mixture required a purification step before quantification via qPCR. The purification was performed using the QIAamp DNA Blood Mini Kit (Qiagen, MD). The kit allows for lysis and purification of nucleic acids. Still, for the purpose of this work, we skipped the lysis steps in the

protocol supplied by the manufacturer and applied only the steps to purify the solutions using the kit columns, following the manufacturers' instructions.

7.2.5. Real-time quantitative PCR for microfluidic lysis characterization

qPCR, RT-qPCR, and data analysis were performed in a 7300 Real-Time PCR detection system (Applied Biosystems). For the DNA-based pathogens (*E. coli* and *S. aureus*), qPCR was used to quantify the starting DNA quantity in the solutions after the lysis protocol. Amplifications were performed in a 25 μ L reaction mixture containing 12.5 μ L of Maxima Probe/ROX qPCR Master Mix (2 \times) (Thermo Scientific), 0.2 μ L of each primer (800 nM), 0.05 μ L of probe (200 nM), 5 μ L of DNA template. The volume was adjusted to 25 μ L with nuclease-free water. The primers and probes used in this study are presented in **Table 7.1**. Cycling conditions were as follows: 50 $^{\circ}$ C for 2 min; 95 $^{\circ}$ C for 10 min; and 40 cycles of 95 $^{\circ}$ C for 15 s and 60 $^{\circ}$ C for 1 min. To amplify the RNA-based microorganism (MS2), RT-qPCR was performed. In this case, the DNA concentration measured by the RT-qPCR was assumed to correspond directly to the total extracted RNA concentration of the bacteriophage. The quantitative analysis was carried out in 20 μ L of the reaction mixture, where 5 μ L was RNA extract. The complete mix contained 10 μ L of specific one-step RT-qPCR (Luna $^{\circledR}$ Universal One-Step RT-qPCR kit, New England Biolabs Inc.) buffer and 1 μ L of RT-enzyme, 0.16 μ L of forward primer and reverse primer each (800 nM), 0.04 μ L of probe (200 nM), and 3.64 μ L of nuclease-free water (ThermoFisher). Amplification was performed using the following protocol: 10 min at 55 $^{\circ}$ C to allow the reverse transcription to occur, followed by denaturation at 95 $^{\circ}$ C for 10 min, 45 cycles of denaturation at 95 $^{\circ}$ C for 15 s, and annealing at 60 $^{\circ}$ C for 45 s. For all the PCR runs, negative control without target DNA (water was used as a non-template control) was added for each microorganism tested. Positive controls were also added in each reaction and consisted of the genetic material extracted from each pathogen via thermal lysis at 95 $^{\circ}$ C for 10 min. The solutions were centrifuged at 12,000 rpm for 10 min, and dilutions were prepared and analyzed in the same run. Dilutions were performed to avoid false-negative results due to PCR inhibition. Results, such as amplification plots, cycle threshold values (Ct), and initial DNA concentration, were obtained using 7300 Fast System SDS software. All the primers and probes used for amplification are described in **Table 7.1**.

Table 7.1 - Real-time RT-qPCR primers and fluorogenic probes sequences

Name	Sequence (5'-3') ^a	Target Organism	Stock concentration (μM)	Supplier	Ref
836F	TCG AAA TTA AAT GTT GTC GTG TCT TC	<i>S. aureus</i>	100	Frilabo	[271]
836R	TCA TTT TTG ACA TGR AGA GAA ACA TC	<i>S. aureus</i>	100	Frilabo	[271]
836P	6-Fluorescein (FAM)-TCG CGA CAT TCA TTA TGC CCA AAT TTT TAA- Black Hole Quencher™ (BHQ)-1	<i>S. aureus</i>	100	Frilabo	[271]
784F	GTG TGA TAT CTA CCC GCT TCG A	<i>E. coli</i>	100	Metabion international AG	[272]
866R	AGA ACG GTT TGT GGT TAA TCA GGA	<i>E. coli</i>	100	Metabion international AG	[272]
807P	6-carboxy-4',5'-dichloro-2',7'- dimethoxyfluorescein (JOE)-TCG GCA TCC GGT CAG TGG CAG T- BHQ-1	<i>E. coli</i>	100	Metabion international AG	[272]
632F	GTC GCG GTA ATT GGC GC	MS2	100	Eurogentec	[273]
708R	GGC CAC GTG TTT TGA TCG A	MS2	100	Eurogentec	[273]
650P	6-FAM-AGG CGC TCC GCT ACC TTG CCC T-BHQ-1	MS2	100	Eurogentec	[273]
QNIF2	ATG TTC AGR TGG ATG AGR TTC TCW GA	NoVGII	100	Eurogentec	[274]
COG2R	TCG ACG CCA TCT TCA TTC ACA	NoVGII	100	Eurogentec	[275]
QNIFs	AGC ACG TGG GAG GGC GAT CG	NoVGII	100	Eurogentec	[274]

^a Mixed bases in degenerate primers and probe: R, A or G; W, A or T.

Quantification for all targets was performed using standard curves with known concentrations of target. For *S. aureus* (AMPLIRUN® STAPHYLOCOCCUS AUREUS (mecA-) DNA CONTROL, Vircell S.L.) the calibration curve was obtained using concentrations from 1.4×10^4 , 7×10^3 , 1.4×10^3 , 7×10^2 , 1.4×10^2 , 7×10^1 and 1.4×10^1 copies/μL. For *E. coli* and MS2 concentrations, 10^8 to 10 CFU/mL (PFU/mL for the bacteriophage) were used to extract the calibration curves.

7.2.6. Quantification of lysis and genome capture using a mass balance approach

We used a mass balance approach where RT-qPCR was used as a quantification method. We considered that the total mass in the system is equal to the total mass that comes out in the outlet plus the total mass accumulated in the system – more specifically, captured in the microbeads. The quantification was done using RT-qPCR that gives an output of initial DNA copies (or RNA copies for MS2), hence we used these values instead of mass. We can write:

$$Total (DNA/RNA)_{IN} = Total (DNA/RNA)_{SYSTEM} + Total (DNA/RNA)_{OUT}$$

Equation 7.2

The total mass accumulated in the system can be given by:

$$Total (DNA/RNA)_{SYSTEM} = Total (DNA/RNA)_{PDMS} + Total (DNA/RNA)_{BEADS}$$

Equation 7.3

Where $Total (DNA/RNA)_{PDMS}$ is the total mass of DNA/RNA that will get accumulated in the PDMS, couplers and tubing. With this, we can obtain the total DNA or RNA captured by the beads after the lysis:

$$Total (DNA/RNA)_{BEADS} = Total (DNA/RNA)_{IN} - Total (DNA/RNA)_{OUT} - Total (DNA/RNA)_{PDMS}$$

Equation 7.4

The total mass of DNA/RNA that can be accumulated on the walls of the PDMS channels can be obtained by using a microfluidic channel without the packed beads inside and knowing the initial copies of DNA/RNA_{IN} and subtracting to these values the initial copies of DNA/RNA_{OUT} :

$$Total (DNA/RNA)_{PDMS} = Total (DNA/RNA)_{IN,NO BEADS} - Total (DNA/RNA)_{OUT,NO BEADS}$$

Equation 7.5

The expression can be transformed into:

$$\begin{aligned} Total (DNA/RNA)_{BEADS} &= Total (DNA/RNA)_{IN,BEADS} - Total (DNA/RNA)_{OUT,BEADS} \\ &\quad - (Total (DNA/RNA)_{IN,NO BEADS} - Total (DNA/RNA)_{OUT,NO BEADS}) \end{aligned}$$

Equation 7.6

Although the total copies of DNA/RNA_{IN} with BEADS or NO BEADS could be obtained theoretically, knowing the starting concentration of microorganism in solution, we chose to quantify it in the same manner that we quantified the outflow by RT-qPCR. For this, we performed, for each cell lysis strategy, the lysis in a microcentrifuge tube using the same concentrations used on-chip and then quantified as illustrated in **Figure 7.2 - A**. We can assume that:

$$Total (DNA/RNA)_{IN} = Total (DNA/RNA)_{IN,BEADS} = Total (DNA/RNA)_{IN,NO BEADS}$$

Equation 7.7

For the $Total (DNA/RNA)_{OUT,BEADS}$ we collected the outflow solution of a lysis experiment with a chip with packed beads inside the chamber, and this outflow was used to perform a qPCR (**Figure 7.2 - B**). And finally, for $Total (DNA/RNA)_{IN,NO BEADS}$ we collected the outflow solution of a lysis experiment with a chip without beads inside the

chamber, and this outflow was used to perform a qPCR (**Figure 7.2 - C**). Having all the values required, we could obtain the lysis efficiency. The lysis efficiency inside the microfluidic device, for each lysis approach, was calculated as the ratio between the $Total (DNA/RNA)_{IN,NO BEADS}$ and the $Total (DNA/RNA)_{IN}$, that corresponds to perform the lysis outside the chip:

$$Lysis Efficiency (\%) = \frac{Total (DNA/RNA)_{IN,NO BEADS}}{Total (DNA/RNA)_{IN}} \times 100$$

Equation 7.8

The results are presented in **Figure 7.7 - A**. Then, using **Equation 7.6**, we obtained the copies of DNA/RNA captured on the beads for each lysis strategy (**Figure 7.2 - C**) and capture efficiency of the DNA/RNA on the beads calculated as

$$Capture Efficiency (\%) = \frac{Total (DNA/RNA)_{BEADS}}{Total (DNA/RNA)_{IN}} \times 100$$

Equation 7.9

Figure 7.2 - Schematics of the protocol to obtain the total copies of genetic material captured by the beads packed in the microfluidic chamber. A - Schematic of the protocol followed to obtain the total copies of nucleic acid inserted in the microfluidic chip ($Total Copies (DNA/RNA)_{IN}$). B - Schematic of the protocol followed to obtain the total copies of nucleic acid collected at the outlet of the microfluidic chip with the beads packed inside to capture the genetic material in solution ($Total Copies (DNA/RNA)_{OUT_BEADS}$). C - Schematic of the protocol followed to obtain the total copies of nucleic acid collected at the outlet of the microfluidic chip without the beads packed, representing any nonspecific capture of the genetic material in solution ($Total Copies (DNA/RNA)_{OUT_NOBEADS}$).

7.3. Results and discussion

7.3.1. Design of the lysis chip

The microfluidic device was designed considering a chemical lysis strategy. This choice was taken to simplify the microfluidic chip, avoiding active integrated parts (heaters, bead beating chambers, gridding mechanisms, etc.) and to have a gentle lysis method to preserve and avoid cleavage and denaturation of RNA/DNA molecules [276]. Two inlets with a "Y" type design allowed sample and lysis solution insertion into the microfluidic device. Considering a channel cross-sectional area of $100\ \mu\text{m} \times 400\ \mu\text{m}$ and a flow of PBS 1× at a flow rate of $2.5\ \mu\text{L}/\text{min}$, the Reynolds number (Re) is of the order of 0.1, around four orders of magnitude below the transition to turbulent flow. Due to the laminar flow regime in the microfluidic device, mixing only occurs by molecular diffusion. With our channel dimensions, the characteristic diffusion time along the width (T_{DW}) is 16-fold higher than along the height, making mixing along the width of the channel more challenging. Due to this, mixing enhancement of the two solutions is required. Passive mixing strategies were added to the device to accomplish faster mixing of the solutions inside the channel. In the first section, after inlets 1 and 2, parallelogram-shaped barriers were designed using a repeating unit, with a total length of 1.16 cm, as shown in **Figure 7.1 - B**. With a mean velocity of $1.05 \times 10^{-3}\ \text{m}/\text{s}$, it takes 90 ms to pass the length of the barrier mixer (**Figure 7.1 - B**). This type of mixer allows the disruption of the streamlines due to the periodic constraining and expansion of the channel area. It increases the chaotic advection effects, especially in the corners of the barrier [277]. The first barrier mixer, composed of 45 periodically arranged mixing units, increases the convective acceleration, allowing a good mixing of the molecules of the two initial solutions by the end of the mixer. Fang *et al.* reported a microfluidic device with a periodic mixer that required only 24 unit mixing repetitions to accomplish uniform mixing. In our case, since we are using the device to perform lysis, we increased the mixing length for two reasons: (1) to guarantee a good mixing of solutions and (2) to help increase the residence time of the solution for the lysis to occur and to promote the increase of cell lysis efficiency in a continuous flow microfluidic device. A long serpentine channel follows the barrier mixer to allow sufficient time for the lysis. The serpentine structure is a consequence of increasing the channel length in a small footprint, but the serpentine turns contribute to additional solution mixing. It is known that in curvilinear channels, the centrifugal forces created against the walls of the turns will generate pressure and velocity gradients, creating vortex streamlines [278]–[280]. However, it should be noted that for the low Re in this device, the mixing still occurs mainly due

to molecular diffusion and will depend on the residence time of the solutions in the device. Without the barrier mixer and considering a diffusion distance of half of the channel, 200 μm , and a diffusion coefficient of $1.0 \times 10^{-6} \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}$ for BPER [59], which is a best-case scenario since the diffusion coefficients for bacteria and viruses are of the order of 10^{-9} and $10^{-8} \text{ cm}^2/\text{s}$ [281], respectively, the diffusion time is around 200 s. A 2.5 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ flow rate would require at least a 21 cm long channel. This justifies the insertion of the barrier mixer before the serpentine channel, where the lysis solution is in contact with the microorganisms. The length of the channel from the end of the first barrier mixer to the beginning of the second mixer at the end is around 24.5 cm which allows for a contact time between lysis and cell solutions of 4 min. At a flow rate of 2.5 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$, the total residence time of the solution in the serpentine is around 4 min and 20 s. Different contact times to carry out chemical lysis at the macroscale can be found in the literature ranging from a few minutes to several hours. However, a reference optimal contact time for alkaline lysis is around 5 min [282], approximately the contact time achieved in our microfluidic device. If required, an increased contact time can be achieved by decreasing the flow rate at the cost of increasing the processing time. However, in our case, a compromise between the processing time had to be made to align with developing a PoC device. The volumes used were selected to be compatible with the extraction of the sample taken by a swab in which, in some cases, the volumes for lysis can be as low as 100 to 500 μL [103], [283], [284]. Our lysis and microorganism cell suspension has a total volume of 120 μL (excluding the neutralization buffer). The processing time for lysis and nucleic acid extraction is 20 min, allowing us to process 100 μL of the mixture. Another possibility in the design is to increase the channel length. After lysis, a neutralization buffer is inserted in inlet 3, and the second barrier mixer helps to homogenize the solution. Following inlet 3, it is expected that nucleic acids should already be in the solution. A chamber packed with positively charged agarose beads is placed at the end of the channel to perform extraction after cell lysis. The beads capture the nucleic acids in the solution via electrostatic interactions (**Figure 7.1 - C**) [171]. The chamber dimensions were selected considering the average diameter of the QS Fast Flow beads.

7.3.2. Chemical lysis on chip

The lysis in this work was performed at rt. The goal was to develop a lysis module that is as simple as possible and compatible with potential isothermal processing techniques downstream that are performed at rt or near rt. The first commercial lysis kit solution, GL, contains a lysis solution and a neutralization solution. The manufacturers' instructions advise adding and incubating the lysis solution at a high

temperature (5 min at 95°C). The lysis solutions present a pH of 11-12 that should be neutralized at the end of the lysis. In this work, we used the lysis solution without applying a high-temperature step to simplify the protocol and the chip operation requirements. The other commercial lysis solution used was BPER, based on a non-ionic detergent that, by dispersing the membrane lipids, can disrupt the membrane. When testing at the macroscale, using the same volume ratios applied at the microscale and the same incubation assay time, we verified that these lysis solutions used individually did not fully lyse either Gram-positive or Gram-negative bacteria this was confirmed by growth in TSA medium. However, when the two solutions were mixed in a ratio of 1:1 (v/v), no growth was observable for either Gram-positive or Gram-negative bacteria (**Figure 7.3**).

Figure 7.3 - Confirmation of results using TSA plates. (A) and (B) BPER lysis of Gram-positive and negative bacteria. (C) and (D) Combination of GL and BPER solutions to perform chemical lysis. The combination in (C) and (D) showed the best lysis results.

After the cell lysis occurs, a neutralization buffer is inserted in inlet 3, used to equilibrate the pH of the solution and avoid inhibition of the downstream steps. The bacteria cell structure after lysis was also observed with scanning electron microscopy (SEM) (**Figure 7.4**). The control is live bacteria, and thermal lysis was used as the lysis control. We can observe the same defects in the bacteria membranes resulting from the chemical lysis treatment with the lysis solution containing GL and BPER and the thermal lysis treatment. Regarding bacteriophages' lysis, a PK solution was added to the lysis solution. Proteinase K is a serine protease that digests proteins preferentially by cleaving the peptide bonds adjacent to the carboxylic group of aliphatic and aromatic amino acids present in the viral protein capsid that protects the

viral DNA or RNA, helping to release the nucleic acids[285]. The RNA rapid extraction solution was used only for the bacteriophages to test the efficiency of organic extraction for viral DNA/RNA. It uses an organic extraction with SDS.

Figure 7.4 - SEM micrographs. Bacteria were observed in a control condition (live bacteria that was treated to be imaged in SEM), the lysis condition under study (mixture of GL and BPER), and a lysis control (thermal lysis). In the first line, *S. aureus* presents the same cell wall defects when subject to conditions GL and BPER and compared to the lysis control (thermal lysis). The same was observed in the second line for *E. coli*.

7.3.3. Nucleic acid capture and detection on-chip

Lysis occurs along the serpentine channel. After the channel where lysis occurs, a chamber was designed to perform the capture of nucleic acids in the solution. An SPE strategy was used to perform the nucleic acid capture using nanoporous agarose matrix beads functionalized with a quaternary amine that were packed inside the chamber. These positively charged beads interact with the negatively charged nucleic acids in solutions that are captured by electrostatic interactions. After this capture, a solution with a nucleic acid intercalating dye, EG, was inserted into inlet 3 and flowed past the beads with the nucleic acids immobilized on the surface. The EG dye was selected for this work since it can only bind to DNA or RNA of lysed cells as the dye cannot permeate intact cell membranes. According to the manufacturer, the dye has a release on-demand DNA binding mechanism. With no nucleic acids, the dye is in a loop conformation, and in this inactive form, the fluorescence emission should be almost negligible. When DNA is present, the dye molecule opens, and in this new conformation, it can bind to the nucleic acids and emit fluorescence (**Figure 7.5** and **Figure 7.6 - A**).

Figure 7.5 - Fluorescence results of the controls for the EG detection. Fluorescence images were obtained using LEICA DMCM fluorescence microscope and 1× gain, 10× magnification, and 250 milliseconds (*E. coli*), 510 milliseconds. The error bars correspond to the standard deviation of three individual assays.

A preliminary study shown in **Figure 7.5** confirmed that the dye had negligible fluorescence emission with the absence of DNA. When dsDNA was present, EG showed fluorescence with an excitation peak at 500 nm and an emission peak at 530 nm. For dsDNA, the signal increased 70-fold over the signal for zero concentration of DNA. For M13 ssDNA, the signal only increased 21-fold [286]. We also tested the non-specific signal of the dye when diluted in the lysis solution without DNA, with 1 µM of 22-mer dsDNA and 1 µM of 22-mer ssDNA (**Figure 7.5**), verifying that for the same concentration of ssDNA, the fluorescence was slightly lower than for dsDNA, an enhancement of 15-fold and 16-fold, respectively, about a mixture of lysis solution (LS) without ssDNA or dsDNA present in solution. The difference was smaller than that reported in the literature, but this may be explained by the short dimension of the DNA strands since the dye has a lower affinity to short DNA strands and ssDNA than to long dsDNA[286]. Since that, in the capture strategy used, we could also have some cell debris mixed with nucleic acids. We tested the nonspecific binding of the dye to the cell debris. We started by testing BSA 4% as a protein model, and we could see that the signal was very similar to that measured when the negative control (just LS) flowed with no DNA through the beads. Then, we separated the cell debris from the nucleic acids by lysing a solution of *S. aureus* thermally and performing a centrifugation step. The supernatant removed (containing the nucleic acids), and the cell debris were resuspended in a mixture of lysis solution and flowed through the chamber with the packed beads. We could see that both for *S. aureus* and *E. coli*, the signal is 2.6-fold and 3-fold higher than the BSA signal, which implies that some nucleic acids are still attached to the cell debris. However, for the supernatant of *S. aureus* and *E. coli*, we see an enhancement of the signal of 3.4-fold and 4-fold,

respectively, compared to the cell debris. This showed that the fluorescence signal was due to the intercalation of the dye with the available nucleic acids.

Figure 7.6 - Calibration curve of the lysis device for Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria using a chemical lysis strategy (Mixture GL and BPER solutions). (A) Schematics of the nucleic acids captured onto the positively charged beads surface and subsequent detection using a DNA intercalating dye EG. (B) Fluorescence detection of gDNA (10^2 - 10^8 CFU/mL) for *S. aureus* and *E. coli* after cell lysis using $1\times$ gain, $10\times$ magnification, and 510 or 250 milliseconds acquisition time for *S. aureus* and *E. coli*, respectively. The error bars correspond to the standard deviation of three individual assays. Micrograph images of 10^8 CFU/mL of *E. coli* (left) and *S. aureus* (right). (C) Fluorescence signal on the beads after lysing 10^8 CFU/mL of the 4 different pathogens by thermal lysis and different chemical lysis methods: GL+BPER; GL, BPER, and PK (GL+BPER+PK) and RNA Rapid Extraction Solution (RNA Kit). Fluorescence images were obtained using LEICA DMCM fluorescence microscope and $1\times$ gain, $10\times$ magnification, and 250 milliseconds (*E. coli*), 510 milliseconds (*S.aureus*), and 1 second (MS2 and M13) acquisition time. The error bars correspond to the standard deviation of three individual assays.

After the initial tests and controls, we performed a calibration curve using our lysis and detection strategy on-chip (Figure 7.6 - B) for both types of bacteria by measuring the fluorescence in the bead chamber. We used concentrations ranging from 10^8 to 10^2 CFU/mL. The LoD was obtained as the concentration of bacteria above 3.29 times

the standard deviation (σ) of a blank assay for each microorganism[287]. We concluded that within 30 min, we were able to lyse and capture the bacterial genomic material and detect it on the chip with LoDs below 10^6 and 10^4 CFU/mL for *S. aureus* and *E. coli*, respectively (**Figure 7.6 - B**). In this work, cell lysis, and on-chip nucleic acids detection were performed in 30 min (20 min for lysis and 10 min for detection), faster than reported lysis strategies on-chip. The lysis was performed along with the gDNA capture and on-chip detection. Mahalanabis *et al.* reported disposable chips for lysis of Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria via a hybrid chemical/mechanical method [265]. This system detected 10^2 CFU/ml Gram-negative bacteria and 10^3 - 10^4 CFU/ml Gram-positive bacteria. However, while our strategy only required 30 min for the entire process, including lysis, capture, and detection of the nucleic acids, in the work of Mahalanabis, the step of lysis took almost an hour. It is also interesting to note that the lysis solution increased the non-specific signal of the dye when compared to PBS (**Figure 7.5**). The composition of the lysis solution can explain this. The lysis solution of the GL has a yellow color. The molecule that gives this color to the solution is also captured by the QS Fast Flow beads, optically noticeable when observing the chip in the microscope. This observation may also contribute to the non-specific fluorescence background, which explains the signal difference between flowing the dye through the beads when PBS is used or when the lysis solution is used (a 900-fold increase in the fluorescence signal). This can be a limitation when working with low concentrations of extracted DNA. However, this limitation can be overcome if, after the lysis, a nucleic acid amplification is performed, using for instance, an isothermal technique or even PCR that allows not only an increase in the signal as well as a more specific detection, targeting a sequence of interest. Another consideration is that the binding of the dye is based on a release-on-demand interaction. Although higher concentrations of DNA molecules will lead to a higher release of the dye, longer strands will also lead to an increased release of the dye since the binding is not specific to a particular sequence in the strands of the extracted nucleic acids. For instance, we know that the genome size of *S. aureus* can vary from 2.8 to 2.9 Mb, and for *E. coli*, it is almost double (4.5 to 5.5 Mb). The absolute values of fluorescence signals presented in **Figure 7.6 – B** are almost identical for the concentrations tested. However, the exposure time for *S. aureus* is double the exposure time for *E. coli* (510 ms and 250 ms, respectively). Since we cannot truly evaluate if this difference is due to more efficient lysis or a higher release-on-demand interaction between the dye and the *E. coli* genome due to the genome length, we used a different strategy to characterize and compare the chip efficiency for the lysis

and capture of genomic material of bacteria and bacteriophages, that is presented in the next subsection.

To demonstrate the universality of our lysis strategy, we applied the same method to lyse bacteriophages. The virus-like particles used were the M13 bacteriophage, which contains a circular ssDNA, and MS2, an ssRNA bacteriophage, which can be considered a model for nonenveloped viruses [288]. We tested the same lysis solution used for bacteria (GL and BPER) while also adding PK to enhance the denaturation of the proteins that make up the capsid of the bacteriophages. Additionally, and only for the bacteriophages, we also tested a commercial RNA extraction solution. As described before, the tests were performed on-chip, and the nucleic acids extracted were detected via fluorescence microscopy (**Figure 7.6 - C**). In these tests, we could qualitatively detect the presence of 10^8 PFU/mL nucleic acids extracted on-chip without amplification for both bacteriophages (ssDNA and ssRNA). And once more, we saw the limitation of the release-on-demand strategy of the EG dye by having to increase the exposure time (1 sec), relative to the exposure time used for bacteria, to acquire the fluorescence signals of MS2 and M13 (M13 circular ssDNA with ~ 6.4 kb; MS2 ssRNA with ~ 3.5 kb). The fact that both are single-stranded can also contribute to lower fluorescence since the dye has a lower affinity to single-stranded acids. In this sense, we can conclude only between the same taxonomic group. The results show that for all the microorganisms tested. It is possible to have a chemical lysis condition that increases the fluorescence signal compared to thermal lysis. For bacteria, the lysis treatment with GL and BPER is more efficient for releasing the gDNA. For MS2 adding PK to the lysis solution improved the fluorescence signal detected. For M13, the fluorescence signal for all the chemical lysis solutions tested presented a similar fluorescence signal and an improvement in relation to the thermal lysis.

We used thermal lysis as the gold standard for lysis strategies and a term of comparison with the chemical lysis strategies presented here. However, the fluorescence signal was lower when compared with the other strategies and with increased variability. We hypothesize that a non-specific fluorescence signal is responsible for these results. We previously observed that the background, when the lysis solution with the GL component flowed through the beads, had a higher non-specific fluorescence signal (**Figure 7.5**). This is also particularly visible with higher exposure times, such as 1 s, used for the bacteriophages (**Figure 7.6 - C**). In the case of thermal lysis, we only used PBS, which did not contribute to the non-specific fluorescence signal.

All the observations made in this subsection corroborated the need to characterize the efficiency of the miniaturized lysis device quantitatively. However, the strategy used with the lysis and detection on-chip using EG proved to give qualitative results in detecting nucleic acids for bacteria and bacteriophages.

7.3.4. Lysis efficiency

Figure 7.7 summarizes the results obtained using a mass balance approach to quantify and characterize our device. The results are also compiled in **Table 7.2** to facilitate the comparison between values. The lysis efficiency calculated using **Equation 7.8** is presented in **Figure 7.7 - A**. The results showed that except for the RNA kit used to lyse MS2, all the other treatments had a lysis efficiency above 60%. Furthermore, the differences in lysis efficiency for each species using the different methods were not significant. We used thermal lysis as a positive control. Others have also used 95 °C for 10 min as a lysis treatment control of Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria and viruses [185], [289].

Table 7.2 - Summary of the quantitatively results of the different lysis treatments.

		<i>E. coli</i>		<i>S. aureus</i>		MS2	
		Mean	%(CV)	Mean	%(CV)	Mean	%(CV)
DNA starting quantity on beads	Thermal	36700 (copies)	22.7	744000 (copies)	12.3	941000 (copies)	11.3
	GL + BPER	146000 (copies)	21.2	1040000 (copies)	26.4	378000 (copies)	33.1
	GL + BPER + PK	120000 (copies)	27.3	250000 (copies)	19.5	801000 (copies)	26.9
	RNA kit					133000 (copies)	11.5
Lysis Efficiency	Thermal	59.0 (%)	3.6	64.4 (%)	12.3	76.6 (%)	11.3
	GL + BPER	83.7 (%)	19.3	73.8 (%)	26.4	61.7 (%)	22.5
	GL + BPER + PK	87.0 (%)	27.1	62.8 (%)	9.3	76.6 (%)	11.1
	RNA kit					14.9 (%)	5.7
	Thermal	28.1 (%)	22.7	27.4 (%)	12.3	24.8 (%)	11.3

	GL + BPER	48.3 (%)	21.2	57.4 (%)	26.4	46.9 (%)	26.9
Capture Efficiency	GL + BPER + PK	49.7 (%)	21.3	58.4 (%)	19.5	35.5 (%)	33.1
	RNA kit					13.5 (%)	11.5

Regarding bacterial lysis, the results show an increase in efficiency when using chemical lysis treatments over the thermal lysis treatment (**Figure 7.7 - A** – GL+BPER and GL+BPER+PK for *E. coli* and *S. aureus*). The lysis mixture with GL and BPER increased the lysis efficiency for both *E. coli* and *S. aureus*. For *E. coli* we obtained a lysis efficiency of 84% with a 19% coefficient of variation % (CV) and for *S. aureus* was 74% ± 26% (**Figure 7.7 – A** – GL+BPER for *E. coli* and *S. aureus*) (**Table 7.2**). The increased lysis efficiency for bacteria when using the GL and BPER treatment can also be explained by the lytic effect of the mixture in both types of membrane and less degradation of the extracted DNA, compared to the thermal lysis.

GL contains a lysis solution with 1% non-ionic surfactant and less than 0.2% of NaOH, and a dye. It combines the effect of high pH and the impact of non-ionic detergents such as Triton X-100 or Tween 20. These non-ionic detergents have uncharged hydrophilic headgroups that can break protein-lipid and lipid-lipid bonds but not protein-protein. They are considered mild surfactants but effective in membrane solubilization[290]. The NaOH will help break the cell wall, making it more flexible and accessible to the other lysis components by breaking hydrogen bonds in the cell wall or membrane. It will help to denature cellular proteins and chromosomal DNA. We added another non-ionic detergent commonly used to effectively disrupt cell membranes (BPER) [59]. This mixture appears to enhance the lytic effect compared to that of each individual component. Since Gram-positive bacteria have a thicker membrane, as stated before, it can be expected to be more complex to lyse than Gram-negative bacteria, which is what we observe in **Figure 7.7 - A**, where smaller mean values of the lysis efficiency are obtained for *S. aureus* compared to *E. coli* (**Figure 7.7 – A** – GL+BPER and GL+BPER+PK for *E. coli* and *S. aureus*) (**Table 7.2**).

Figure 7.7 - Summary of the lysis results obtained using a mass balance approach for quantification. A - Lysis efficiency of the methods tested in this work after lysing 10^6 CFU/mL of the 3 different pathogens by thermal lysis and different chemical lysis methods: GGL+BPER; GL+BPER+PK and RNA Rapid Extraction Solution (RNA Kit). The error bars correspond to the percentage error of three individual assays. B - DNA Starting Quantity of copies captured by the beads. The values were obtained through a mass balance approximation using qPCR to quantify the DNA starting quantity of copies. C - Capture the efficiency of the genetic material in solution by the beads packed inside the microfluid device.

Regarding the bacteriophages, RNA from MS2 was collected, and reverse transcription was carried out before the amplification step. In this sense, having an extra step may add additional nucleic acid losses to the process. Since MS2 capsid is made mainly of protein-protein interactions, the lysis efficiency is lower than the

bacterial ($62\% \pm 23\%$) (**Figure 7.7 – A – GL+BPER for MS2**) (**Table 7.2**). To increase the lysis efficiency for all microorganisms, PK was added to the lysis mixture. Proteinase K is stable over a wide range of pH (4-12) and is, therefore, not affected by the alkaline condition of the lysis mixture. It also helps to maintain the quality and quantity of nucleic acid extracted by being able to digest proteins that can degrade the sample (nucleases such as DNases and RNases). In this sense, PK should make the lysis of Gram-negative bacteria and the MS2 virion easier. We can see a slight increase in efficiency for *E. coli* ($87\% \pm 27\%$) and MS2 ($80\% \pm 11\%$) (**Figure 7.7 – A – GL +BPER+PK for *E. coli* and MS2**) (**Table 7.2**). Since the peptidoglycan layer is thicker for gram-positive bacteria, the lysis performance is not improved. As stated before, thermal lysis was used as a lysis standard method and not as a method to be applied on-chip. Since thermal lysis was performed off-chip in a microcentrifuge tube and then flowed through the device, and the outflow was collected (**Figure 7.2 - C**), the result could be compared with thermal lysis performed in a microcentrifuge tube that was directly measured by qPCR (Figure 7.2 - A). From this comparison, we conclude that some losses came from the extra handling and flowing of the solution through the microfluidic device. Thus, the lysis efficiency is below 100% for thermal lysis. For the three microorganisms tested, MS2 was the organism that had lower losses with a thermal lysis efficiency of $77\% \pm 11\%$ (**Figure 7.7 – A – Thermal for *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, and MS2**). Furthermore, increased lysis efficiency for both *E. coli* and *S. aureus* when using the GL+BPER treatment can indicate that the thermal had inhibition. The inhibitions may have occurred first in the step of lysis. The high concentration of bacteria could have contributed to a protective agglomerate that allowed not all the bacteria to be heat lysed. A second hypothesis is that the inhibition occurred during the PCR due to the high concentration of starting DNA. The Gram-positive membranes are thicker (30-100 nm) than the membranes of Gram-negative bacteria, with a cell wall made of multi-layered peptidoglycan (higher quantity), with a higher degree of crosslinking which provides more strength and rigidity. The peptidoglycan layer is a covalent multilayer structure composed of glycan chains crosslinked via flexible peptide bridges. In this sense, it is more difficult to disrupt the cell wall of Gram-positive bacteria when compared to Gram-negative bacteria. Although Gram-negative bacteria have a lipid-rich outer membrane, the peptidoglycan single layer is thinner (2-10 nm). Thus, it is easier to have high concentrations of starting DNA for Gram-negative bacteria, which can lead to PCR inhibition, justifying the difference in thermal lysis where the efficiency appears to be lower for *E. coli* than for *S. aureus*, as given by the PCR results. One way to verify this hypothesis would be performing dilution of the starting sample, running the PCR,

and verifying if the results corroborate PCR inhibition due to the high concentration of starting DNA.

One problem we encountered was that for the MS2 samples, a purification step using a solid phase spin column to remove the PK was necessary before the reverse transcription step. In reverse transcription, we use reverse transcriptase to transcribe RNA into complementary DNA (cDNA), and this step is performed at 55 °C for 10 min. When PK is heated from 37 °C to 60 °C, the enzyme activity increases, which leads to the inactivation of the transcriptase in solution, and as such, no amplification will occur. For the bacteria, this did not present a problem since the starting step of the amplification is a denaturation step at 95 °C for 10 min, which is the same protocol that inactivates the PK enzyme. The inactivated PK cannot digest the polymerase, and thus amplification occurs.

7.3.5. Capture efficiency of nucleic acids on-chip

Using **Equation 7.6**, we were able to quantify the number of copies that we could capture onto the surface of the beads using the microfluidic device (**Figure 7.7 - B**). We can also calculate the capture efficiency using **Equation 7.9 (Figure 7.7 - C)**. Overall, more *S. aureus* and MS2 nucleic acid were captured on the beads than that of *E. coli* (**Figure 7.7 - B**). The values with the means and associated error for the copies captured on the beads are also presented in **Table 7.2**. When analyzing capture efficiency (**Figure 7.7 - C**), the results showed an increase in capture efficiency when using the GL+BPER or the GL+BPER+PK lysis treatment for all the species tested compared to thermal lysis. However, the differences between each species using the different methods were not significant. The capture efficiency for thermal lysis was very similar for all the microorganisms. This efficiency was 28 % ± 23 % and 27 % ± 12 % for the Gram-negative and the Gram-positive bacteria, respectively. (**Figure 7.7 - C – Thermal for *E. coli* and *S. aureus* (Table 7.2)**). For the MS2 virion, the capture efficiency was slightly lower, 25 % ± 11 % (**Figure 7.7 – C – Thermal for MS2**). One reason for these low values may be the presence of cell debris in the lysed solutions. It is known that for both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, the membranes are negatively charged. In the case of Gram-positive bacteria, the charge comes mainly from teichoic acid, which has a phosphate group in its structure that confers the negative charge. For Gram-negative bacteria, the charge comes primarily from the outer covering membrane composed of phospholipids and lipopolysaccharides, the latter being strongly negative. The MS2 capsid also behaves as a negatively charged particle over a wide pH range

(isoelectric point ~ 3.5 a 3.9) [291]–[294]. Since the beads are positively charged, the capture of the cell debris can partially block the bead surface, and the capture of nucleic acids would then be hindered. Given the associated CV, there is no statistical difference between the capture efficiencies of the different organisms tested.

For both chemical strategies (GL+BPER or GL+BPER+PK), the capture increased for all the microorganisms compared to the thermal lysis. This may relate to the chemical treatment that allows a good release and neutralization of components in solutions that could block the beads. The best capture for *E. coli* and *S. aureus* was with GL+BPER+PK (50 % ± 25 % and 58 % ± 19 %, respectively), and for MS2 was with GL+BPER (49 % ± 27 %) (**Figure 7.7 - C**) (**Table 7.2**). In contrast, the capture efficiency was only 13 % ± 11 % for the RNA extraction kit (**Figure 7.7 – C – RNA kit** for MS2). This may be explained by the presence of SDS in solution, an anionic detergent. The SDS charge may compete with the RNA charge and thus hinder the capture by the positively charged beads.

Kulinski *et al.* used a silica-impregnated polymer monolith inside a microfluidic channel to perform cell lysis (with chemical assistance) and nucleic acid capture. The process took 40 min and detected *E. coli* to 10¹ CFU/mL after a step of DNA amplification[266]. Although the detection limit is lower than presented in this work, the lysis time is longer. The method was not tested for Gram-positive bacteria that present a thicker cell membrane and can be more challenging to lyse than with virions particles. Strohimer *et al.* used a lab on a disk device (LabDisk) and magnetic particles to perform lysis and extraction within 30 minutes (15 minutes lysis). For the higher bacterial and virion concentrations tested, the most similar ones to the ones used in this work (10⁶ CFU/sample for bacteria and 10⁴ PFU/sample for RNA virus), these authors reached an extraction efficiency of 58.2% (Gram-positive bacteria), 45.3% (Gram-negative bacteria) and 29.5% (RNA virus) [264]. Although the starting quantities are lower than in our work, we have achieved similar or better results with our strategy. Furthermore, the LabDisk requires a processing device to spin the LabDisk, which should be connected to a computer for process control, increasing the complexity of the POC device.

7.4. Chapter Conclusions

Using on-chip chemical cell lysis allowed a simplification in the microfluidic device design compared to mechanical lysis strategies or heat-mediated strategies since no integration of active parts is required. Also, with the microscale dimensions of the device, we decreased the volumes of reagents relative to a typical macroscale

process, leading to potential reduction of cost and reagent usage. We could lyse and extract nucleic acids on-chip within 20 min which could be detected non-specifically using a DNA intercalating dye in 30 min. We successfully lysed and detected gDNA of Gram-positive (*S. aureus*) and Gram-negative bacteria (*E. coli*) without amplification with detection limits below 10^6 CFU/mL and 10^4 CFU/mL, respectively. We extended the research further and tried to see if the chemical lysis strategy also applied to virus-like particles. We conclude that a combined solution of GL and BPER (GL+BPER) was suitable to lyse MS2 and M13, which can be used as models of nonenveloped viruses. Furthermore, adding Proteinase K to the solution enhanced the lysis efficiency for MS2.

Using a mass balance approach, we quantified the copies of target DNA extracted by lysis and captured on the chip. The best lytic mixture tested contained GL, BPER, and PK. One problem detected is that purification should be integrated for different lysis mixtures (when PK was used) to avoid inhibiting downstream processes such as nucleic acid amplification. However, since the on-chip assay is performed in continuous flow conditions, some contaminants may be washed away and not interfere with the downstream processes. Integrating on-chip amplification where the target is immobilized on a solid substrate may be a solution to avoid an extra purification step. Using this device, we can lyse and then capture on-chip, for the best lysis condition, $1.20 \times 10^5 \pm 1.02 \times 10^5$ DNA copies for *S. aureus*, $5.63 \times 10^5 \pm 9.10 \times 10^4$ DNA copies for *E. coli* and $8.01 \times 10^5 \pm 5.08 \times 10^5$ RNA copies for MS2. The lysis efficiency could be increased by increasing the residence time of the lysis and pathogen solution on-chip. This could be achieved by increasing the serpentine length where lysis occurs or decreasing the flow rate. However, and more importantly, the capture efficiency should also be considered. Different types of beads could be tested to determine if capture can be improved. For instance, Capto™ Adhere beads better withstand different salt conditions while maintaining the degree of nucleic acid capture on-chip [171]. Silica beads could also be an option and work as extraction and cleaning step of possible amplification inhibitors. A promising extension of this work is integrating this lysis module with an on-chip amplification strategy to increase sensitivity and selectivity.

Chapter 8

Systematic implementation of padlock probing-based rolling circle amplification in an integrated microfluidic device for quantitative biomolecular analyses

8. Systematic implementation of padlock probing-based rolling circle amplification in an integrated microfluidic device for quantitative biomolecular analyses

The detection of pathogens in primary care settings is increasingly critical, not only for viruses as in the case of the 2019 SARS-CoV-2 pandemic but also for the precise identification of antibiotic-resistant bacteria. Microfluidic devices can be used to develop point-of-care detection systems but are usually insufficiently sensitive for such applications. An on-chip isothermal amplification technique, such as the PLP-RCA technique, could jointly achieve the desired specificity and sensitivity still with the possibility to maintain the complexity of the microfluidic device relatively less. However, on-chip integration of PLP-RCA is challenging and requires good optimization of enzyme concentrations, flow conditions, and target capture to achieve its full potential. In this work, we demonstrate a microfluidic RCA assay performed on porous agarose microbeads that are used as solid-phase capture, packed inside a microfluidic device. Several strategies for effective target capture were systematically compared and quantitatively investigated, starting with single-stranded synthetic DNA oligonucleotides and moving toward genomic *Staphylococcus aureus* bacterial DNA. The microfluidic device is integrated with an amorphous-hydrogenated silicon (a-Si:H) thin film *p-i-n* photodiode and a high-pass interference filter to allow the on-chip acquisition of the fluorescence signal from the amplicons, thus demonstrating the capability of performing a complete PLP-RCA assay on-chip, along with the added

merits of device portability and compatibility with clinical demands. This work was presented at the 2021 IEEE 34th International Conference on Micro Electro Mechanical Systems (MEMS) as a Poster. The contents of this chapter were adapted from a submitted article on the main research presented here and an already published article [295] with a focus on the photosensors used to perform the optical transduction of the signal. Conceived, designed, co-performed, and analyzed the experimental results. I was the main writer of the publication and creator of the Poster.

8.1. Introduction

Fast and decentralized detection of pathogens holds applications not only in viral infections and in the growing burden of antibiotic-resistant bacteria. One proven way to fight these threats is by controlling the source of infection, reducing their spread, and containing the transmission of these pathogens, via early detection[257]. In this context, accurate and robust diagnostic systems have become mandatory for successful global health management [258], [259].

In the domain of molecular diagnostics, PCR is the most common DNA amplification technique used in centralized labs. Although PCR has proven specific and sensitive with advanced PCR variations, it typically requires extensive sample preparation and purification, in addition to a bulky thermocycler to perform the temperature control. The results will often take 1 to 5 days to be obtained or as early as half-a-day for cases with urgency[296]. It has also become a popular method for implementation in microfluidic devices to precisely identify specific DNA sequence characteristics of any given pathogen or disease[72], [74], [207]. Several groups have integrated PCR on-chip in microfluidics as a standalone device or in conjunction with other modules[79]. One can divide the microfluidic devices used for PCR into stationary/reactor type and flow type devices[80], [81]. The amplification occurs in the stationary/reactor type by thermocycling the reagents inside the chamber[70], [82]. For the flow type device, the sample goes through several channel zones with the distinctive temperatures required in the PCR cycle, or the solution can be pumped between reactors at different temperatures [83]. Recently, Huang *et al.* developed a microfluidic chip-based PCR array system to detect 21 pathogens within 1.5 h with an LoD of 103 copies/mL[84]. Hung *et al.* adopted a strategy of performing PCR in a solid phase coupled with a supercritical angle fluorescence microlens array embedded in a microchip for signal detection[85]. They found that the limit of detection of the LOC system was 0.8 fluorophores/ μm^2 , with a sensitivity of the solid phase-PCR as low as 1.6 copies/ μL

for *S. enteritidis* DNA template. In recent years, droplet digital PCR has also been applied to microfluidics, resulting in higher sensitivity[86]. Commercial LoC devices, such as the GeneXpert systems® (Cepheid), have been developed using a PCR-based detection and are already available in the market. These systems have been considered suitable for PoC testing, although they still require a bulky apparatus to perform device control (temperature, fluid movement, signal acquisition, etc.), and in most of them, some of the protocol steps are still performed off-chip by technicians. However, for all PCR-based methods, the requirement of several heating-cooling cycles ranging from around 50 up to 95 °C makes the integration more challenging when compared to isothermal techniques.

To simplify the integration of NAAT on-chip and overcome some of the above limitations displayed by PCR, isothermal nucleic acid amplifications, such as LAMP or RCA, have been developed. The increased interest is particularly towards PoC applications since the issue of a complex temperature profile to perform amplification can be circumvented[75]–[77]. RCA amplifies the nucleic acids at relatively low temperatures ranging from rt to 37°C, and it is based on the rolling circle replication mechanism present in bacteria and viruses. In the specific case of the PLP-RCA, the assay requires a linear DNA PLP template, a short DNA or RNA primer/target, a ligase, and a DNA polymerase with a strong displacement activity, to start the reaction. The amplification generates a long single-stranded molecule containing thousands of repeated copies of the circular template tethered to the original circular DNA. PLPs are linear oligonucleotides composed of two end sequences and a linker sequence. The two end-sequences complement a target DNA, such as the DNA of a pathogen. Upon hybridization with the target, the PLP becomes circularized via a ligase, such as T4 DNA ligase or Tth DNA ligase, which seals the nick between the two linker sequences. Some DNA ligases demand a perfect hybridization to efficiently join the 5'-phosphorylated end of the DNA strand to the 3'-end of another strand, thus providing high molecular specificity. Although this linear amplification process already provides high sensitivity, it can be further enhanced by performing another variation of RCA that allows for exponential amplification, such as hyperbranched RCA, multiprimed RCA, or C2C-RCA [87]. As specific examples of integrating RCA in microfluidic devices, Sato *et al.* reported the integration of PLP and RCA in microfluidics using beads as solid support to capture the target DNA of *S. enterica* to perform the amplification[77]. The amplification on-chip took 3.5 h, and 88 ng of *S. enterica* genomic DNA (30 amol) could be successfully detected. Although there are studies on implementing RCA on-chip, only a few have focused on the direct detection

of double-stranded genomic DNA while not addressing the full integration of the ligation, amplification, and detection events [77], [297].

This work presents a continuous flow RCA module on-chip with a solid-phase capture for specific detection of DNA molecules. The system allowed the visualization of RCPs under the microscope and coupled with miniaturized hydrogenated amorphous silicon a-Si:H *p-i-n* photodiodes to demonstrate the system's portability for PoC use. We also performed a mass balance approach to characterize the capture and amplification efficiencies of the DNA target on-chip. We explore several molecular strategies that would allow the direct use of this module to detect a target sequence directly from a desired DNA sequence of a pathogen. We believe that this study clearly demonstrates the feasibility of using an integrated module with a LoC device, moving from real sample-to-answer analyses, thereby proving compatible with PoC applications.

8.2. Materials and experimental methods

8.2.1. Microfluidic device operation and signal detection

Pierce Streptavidin Agarose (Streptavidin) beads (Thermo Fisher Scientific) with an average size diameter of 80 μm were packed inside the 100 μm height PDMS chamber by adapting a pipette tip with the bead's suspension at the inlet 2 (**Figure 8.1 - A**), closing inlet 1 with a metal plug, and applying negative pressure at the outlet. This negative pressure was created using a syringe pre-filled with PBS 1 \times , connected to the microfluidic structure via capillary tubing and a metal coupler. This syringe is mounted on a syringe pump (NE-1002X, New Era Pump System Inc.) that imposes a packing flow rate of 7 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$. After the chamber was packed, a metal plug was used to seal inlet 2. Mesoporous silica beads (Sigma-Aldrich) with 40–75 μm diameter were also used throughout the work. These beads were first suspended in PBS 1 \times , and then packed in the same way as described above.

Figure 8.1 – A - Schematics of the microfluidic device used for RCA on-chip. The device comprises a chamber to pack microbeads and access channels (A – I). Micrograph of the chamber with packed beads (A-II). (B) Detailed schematics of the model PLP-RCA approach implemented on-chip and used to optimize the amplification conditions. A biotinylated target DNA, complementary to PLP, was immobilized onto streptavidin beads. After PLP hybridization to the target, T4 DNA ligase sealed the nick (B)(I). With the circular PLP, Phi29 DNA polymerase initiated the strand extension through the 3'-end of the target DNA for amplification (B - II). After amplification, oligonucleotides labeled with a fluorophore flowed through the beads to detect the RCA products (RCPs) (B - III). C - Schematics of the RCA strategies tested to detect target single-stranded DNA (ssDNA). D - Schematics of the RCA strategies tested to detect double-stranded target DNA (*S. aureus* genomic DNA, gDNA). The first strategy consisted of a target capture using a biotinylated primer and PLP (D - I). The second strategy consisted of a target capture using a biotinylated anchor (D - II). The third strategy captured the target with a biotinylated primer and used an RCA primer (D - III). The fourth strategy captured the target DNA after being incubated with restriction enzymes, using an

anchor (D - IV). Finally, the last strategy caught a restricted target DNA using a biotinylated anchor, and an RCA primer was also included in this assay design (D - V).

The fluorescence intensity was either measured using a fluorescence microscope or microfabricated a-Si:H *p-i-n* thin-film photodiodes aligned underneath the bead chamber, as reported elsewhere [295]. A Leica DMLM fluorescence microscope coupled to a DFC300FX CCD camera and a 100 W mercury short-arc lamp were used to acquire the fluorescence images. Depending on the fluorophore used, three filter cubes were chosen: an I3 blue excitation filter cube (with a band-pass excitation filter $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 450\text{-}490$ nm; high-pass emission filter $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 515$ nm) for ATTO 430LS fluorophore ($\lambda_{\text{abs}} = 436$ nm; $\lambda_{\text{em, max}} = 545$ nm), a TX2 green excitation filter cube (with a band-pass excitation filter $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 540\text{-}560$ nm; band-pass emission filter $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 645\text{-}675$ nm) for CyTM3 fluorophore ($\lambda_{\text{abs}} = 550$; $\lambda_{\text{em, max}} = 570$ nm) and a D UV/violet filter cube (with a band-pass excitation filter $\lambda_{\text{ex}} 355\text{-}425$ nm; high-pass emission filter $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 470$ nm) for Qdots 605 fluorophore ($\lambda_{\text{em, max}} = 605$ nm). The images were acquired with either 1 s or 510 ms exposure times, and 1x gain, 1x gamma, and 320x magnification. The acquired images were analyzed with ImageJ software by averaging the greyscale intensity of the area inside the chamber (region of interest (ROI) 1, oval shape $600 \times 400 \mu\text{m}^2$) to which the background was subtracted (averaging the greyscale intensity of the area in the connecting channel used to flow the solutions (ROI2), square shape $200 \times 200 \mu\text{m}^2$). For optical to electrical signal transduction, photodiodes with a monolithically integrated high pass-filter (HP570), consisting of a multilayer of SiN_x and SiO₂, were designed to allow the optical signal transduction from Qdots 605 fluorophore ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 405$ nm; $\lambda_{\text{em, max}} = 605$ nm) to an electrical signal for readout. The detailed fabrication of the photodiodes and of the high-pass filter is reported elsewhere [295]. After the RCA protocol was completed, the $200 \times 200 \mu\text{m}$ photodiodes were aligned underneath the bead chamber. A UV excitation light ($\lambda_{\text{ex, laser}} = 405$ nm) irradiated the beads. The current signal was acquired at 0 V bias using a picoammeter (Model 237; Keithley Instruments, Inc.). The current measurements were performed using a GUI programmed in Python and PyQt4.

8.2.2. On-chip rolling circle amplification using single-stranded target DNA

Several strategies for performing RCA on-chip were tested. They all required a DNA oligo to be immobilized on the bead surface via a biotin-streptavidin bond. Three methods with target ssDNA were evaluated. The first one immobilized the target directly onto the beads, where the arms (target-binding regions) of the PLP were complementary to the target sequence (**Figure 8.1 – B** and **Figure 8.1 - C I**). This

strategy is referred to as the model strategy. The target ssDNA was labeled with biotin in the 5'-end. The second strategy used a primer, biotinylated in the 5'-end, complementary to the middle part (backbone) of the PLP and is referred to as strategy A (**Figure 8.1 – C II**). The third strategy used an anchor biotinylated in the 3'-end and is referred to as strategy B. The 5'-end portion of the anchor strand was complementary to the 5'-end of the target ssDNA, and the sequence part of the target complementary to the PLP was left free (**Figure 8.1 – C III**). The sequences used throughout this work can be found in **Table 8.1**.

Table 8.1 - DNA oligonucleotide sequences used throughout this work to perform RCA. The short sequence in blue between the Target DNA and Anchor represents a complementary hybridization area. The short sequences in green between Target DNA and PLP represent a complementary hybridization area. The short sequence in red between PLP and Primer represents a complementary hybridization area. The highlighted yellow sequence in PLP represents one of the detection sequences detected by Detection Oligos 1, 2, and 3. The highlighted green sequence in PLP represents one of the detection sequences detected by Detection Oligo 4.

Function	Sequence (5'-3')	5'- mod.	3'- mod.	Used
Target DNA	TTAAATTAATGTACAAAGGTCAA CCAATGACATTCAGACTATTATT GGTTGATACACCTGAAACAAAG CATCCTAAAAAAGGTGTAGAGA	none	none	Strategy A, Strategy B, Strategy I; Strategy II, Strategy III, Strategy IV, Strategy V
Target DNA - ATTO™ 430LS	TTAAATTAATGTACAAAGGTCAA CCAATGACATTCAGACTATTATT GGTTGATACACCTGAAACAAAG CATCCTAAAAAAGGTGTAGAGA	Atto 430LS carboxy (ATTO™ 430LS)	none	Calibration assays
Target DNA - Biotin	TTAAATTAATGTACAAAGGTCAA CCAATGACATTCAGACTATTATT GGTTGATACACCTGAAACAAAG CATCCTAAAAAAGGTGTAGAGA	Biotin	none	Model strategy
Padlock Probe (PLP)	TGCTTTGTTTCAGGTGTAGTGTA TGCAGCTCCTCAGTAATAGTGT CTTACGGCATCACTGGTTACGT CTGTCTCTACACCTTTTTTAGGA	PO4 - phosphorilati on	none	All the strategies
Primer	TTTTTTTTTTGTAAGACACTATTA CTGAGGA	Biotin	none	Strategy A, Strategy I, Strategy III, Strategy V
Anchor	TCATTGGTTGACCTTTGTACTTT TTTTTTT	none	Biotin	Strategy B, Strategy II, Strategy III, Strategy IV, Strategy V
Detection oligo1 (DO1)	TTTTTCCTCAGTAATAGTGTCTT AC	Sulfo- Cyanine3 (Cy™3)	none	Model strategy
Detection oligo2 (DO2)	TTTTTCCTCAGTAATAGTGTCTT AC	Biotin	none	Model strategy

Detection oligo3 (DO3)	TTTTT CCTCAGTAATAGTGTCTT AC	ATTO™ 430LS	none	Model strategy, Strategy A
Detection oligo4 (DO4)	TTTTT GGCATCACTGGTTACGTC TG	ATTO™ 430LS	none	Strategy A, Strategy B, Strategy I, Strategy II, Strategy III, Strategy IV, Strategy V

The first (model) strategy was exploited to perform optimization of assay conditions in the microfluidic structure using a design of experiment (DoE) approach. Temperature control during the RCA assay was accomplished by placing the PDMS device over a heating Indium Tin Oxide (ITO) glass plate (Okolab) set at 50 °C to control the temperature in order to achieve approximately 37°C inside the channel, as measured with a thermocouple when the setup was defined. Bovine serum albumin (BSA) 4% solution (Sigma-Aldrich) was introduced at 2.5 µL/min for 10 min to block the microchannel surfaces and the beads. A 20 µL solution of biotinylated target DNA (representative of the *nuc* gene of *S. aureus*) (Supplementary Information Table S1), PLPs, T4 DNA ligase (Blirt SA, Poland), 0.2 µg/µL BSA was prepared, and 0.5 mM of ATP in T4 DNA ligase buffer (50 mM Tris-HCl pH 8.3, 75 mM KCl, 3 mM MgCl₂ and 10 mM DTT). The solution flowed through the beads at 0.5 µL/min for 40 min. Amplification was performed in Phi29 DNA polymerase buffer (500 mM Tris-HCl, pH 8.3, 100 mM MgCl₂, 100 mM (NH₄)₂SO₄) (MgCl₂, KCl, TWEEN® 20, and DTT were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich, Darmstadt, Germany, while Tris-HCl, PBS, and NaCl were acquired from Karolinska Institute Substrat, Stockholm, Sweden) containing dNTPs, 0.2 µg/µL BSA and Phi29 DNA polymerase (Monserate Biotechnology Group, San Diego, USA) and 15 µL of this solution flowed through the beads at 0.25 µL/min for 60 min. Finally, a 30 µL solution containing 500 nM of detection oligos (DOs) Cy3 (DO1 in **Table 8.1**) labeled or Atto430 LS (DO3 or DO4 in **Table 8.1**) and prepared in hybridization buffer (1.4 M NaCl, 0.01 % TWEEN® 20, 20 mM of Tris-HCl, pH 8, and EDTA) flowed through the beads at 2.0 µL/min for 15 min. A final washing step with a hybridization buffer was performed at 2.5 µL/min for 2 min. The oligonucleotide sequences used can be found in **Table 8.1**. The concentrations used, the compositions of each solution, flow rates, and times of each step can be found in **Table 8.2**. For strategies A and B, all the steps followed and solutions used are presented in **Table 8.3**.

Table 8.2 - Description of on-chip steps performed in the microfluidic device with the respective flow rates and assay times to detect ssDNA with model strategy. *Target DNA final concentration was tested from 10^{-8} to 10^{-15} M. To maintain always the same volume pipetted (0.2 μ L) into the final ligation solution, the stock concentration used had a concentration 100-fold superior to the final concentration tested.

Solution	Assay	Components	Stock concentration	Final concentration	Volume 1 x (μ L)	Step duration (min)	Temperature ($^{\circ}$ C)	Flow rate (μ L/min)
Ligation	Model Strategy	Target DNA Biotin (μ M)	*	*	0.2	40	37	0.5
		PLP (μ M)	1	0.25	5			
		ATP (mM)	100	0.5	0.10			
		BSA (%)	4	0.04	0.20			
		T4 Buffer	10	1	2			
		T4 (U/ μ L)	5	0.2	0.80			
		Milli-Q			9.9			
Amplification	Model Strategy	Phi29 Buffer	10	1	1.5	60	37	0.25
		BSA (%)	4	0.05	0.20			
		dNTPs (mM)	2.50	0.40	2.40			
		Phi29	10	0.5	0.75			
		Milli-Q			10.15			
Labelling One-step	Organic fluorophores detection (DO1, DO,3 and DO4)	Hybridization Buffer			15	15	37	2.00
		Detection oligos (μ M)	1	0.50	15			
Labelling Two-steps (Step 1)	Quantum dots detection (DO2)	Hybridization Buffer			15	15	37	2.00
		Detection oligos (DO2) (μ M)	1	0.50	15			
Labelling Two-steps (Step 2)	Quantum dots detection (DO2)	Qdot™ 605 Streptavidin Conjugate (μ M)	1	0.01	0.3	15	37	2.00
		PBS Tween® 20	5%	0.5%	14.85			
		Triton™ X-100	10%	1%	14.85			

Table 8.3 - Description of on-chip steps performed in the microfluidic device with the respective flow rates and assay times for the different strategies tested to detect ssDNA.

Solution	Assay	Components	Stock concentration	Final concentration	Volume 1 x (μL)	Step duration (min)	Temperature (°C)	Flow rate (μL/min)
	Strategy A	Primer (μM)	1	0.1	2	40	37	0.5
		PLP (μM)	1	0.25	5			
		PBS			13			
		Target DNA (μM)	1	0.25	5			
		PBS			15			
	Strategy B	Anchor (μM)	1	0.1	2	40		
		Target DNA (μM)	1	0.25	5			
		PBS			13			
		PLP (μM)	1	0.25	2			
		PBS			18			
Ligation	All assays	ATP (mM)	100	0.5	0.10	40		
		BSA (%)	4	0.04	0.20			
		T4 Buffer	10	1	2			
		T4 (U/μL)	5	0.2	0.80			
		Milli-Q			16.9			
Amplification	All assays	Phi29 Buffer	10	1	1.5	60		
		BSA (%)	4	0.05	0.20			
		dNTPs (mM)	2.50	0.40	2.40			
		Phi29	10	0.5	0.75			
		Milli-Q			10.15			
Labelling One-step	Organic fluorophores detection (DO1, DO3 and DO4)	Hybridization Buffer			15	15		
		Detection oligos (μM)	1	0.50	15			
Labelling Two-steps (Step 1)	Quantum dots detection (DO2)	Hybridization Buffer			15	15		
		Detection oligos (DO2) (μM)	1	0.50	15			
Labelling Two-steps (Step 2)	Quantum dots detection (DO2)	Qdot™ 605 Streptavidin Conjugate (μM)	1	0.01	0.3	15		
		PBS Tween® 20	5%	0.5%	14.85			

8.2.3. On-chip rolling circle amplification using double-stranded target DNA

Quantified genomic DNA (gDNA) from *S. aureus* (AMPLIRUN® STAPHYLOCOCCUS AUREUS (mecA-) DNA CONTROL, Vircell S.L.) was used as a target molecule. Three RCA configurations were tested with this gDNA. Two of these configurations exploited the use of restriction enzymes on the gDNA. For the three configurations without restriction enzymes, the first configuration, referred to as strategy I, used a primer biotinylated in the 5'-end, complementary to the PLP backbone. The second configuration (Strategy II) used an anchor biotinylated at the 3'-end. In contrast, the 5'-end of the anchor was complementary to the 5'-end portions of the gDNA that were adjacent to the PLP-binding sequence of the target. The third configuration (Strategy III) used an anchor biotinylated at the 3'-end, while its 5'-end was complementary to the 5'-end of the gDNA, which is in turn adjacent to the PLP-binding sequence of the target, and a primer complementary to the PLP backbone is also used. For strategies II and III, when we tested the use of restriction enzymes on gDNA, they were referred to as Strategy IV and Strategy V, respectively. Restriction enzymes *Avall* and *HPhi* purchased from New England Biolabs were used at a final concentration of 1 U and 2 U, respectively. The steps with restriction enzymes were performed in an Eppendorf with gDNA at a concentration of 4375 copies/ μ L, *Avall*, *HPhi*, CutSmart buffer 1 \times , and Milli-Q water volume of 20 μ L. The solution was incubated for 30 min at 37 °C. Denaturation was also performed off-chip while setting the target DNA with the primer, anchor, and PLP for 10 min at 95 °C. After this, the T4 ligase was added to the previously obtained ligation solution. The assay was then processed as explained in the previous sub-section, starting with a blocking step with BSA 4%. The oligonucleotide sequences used can be found in **Table 8.1**. The concentrations used and the compositions of each solution can be found in **Table 8.4 and 8.5**.

Table 8.4 - Concentration of reagents used in each step of the PLP-RCA assay and flow conditions.

	Molecule	Concentration	Flow rate
gDNA denaturation at 95°C & Hybridization with PLP and primer off-chip	gDNA	4375 copies/ μ L	0.5 μ L/min
	PLP	250 nM	
	Primer	100 nM	
gDNA digestion with restriction enzymes, denaturation at 95°C & Hybridization with PLP and anchor off-chip	gDNA	4375 copies/ μ L	0.5 μ L/min
	Avall	10 Units	
	HpHI	10 Units	
	PLP	250 nM	
	Anchor	100 nM	
PLP Ligation	T4 DNA Ligase Buffer	1X	0.5 μ L/min
	T4 DNA Ligase	0.2 Units/ μ L	
	BSA	0.04%	
	ATP	0.5 mM	
Amplification	Phi29 DNA Polymerase Buffer	1X	0.25 μ L/min
	Phi29 DNA Polymerase	0.5 Units/ μ L	
	dNTPs	0.4 mM	
	BSA	0.05%	
Detection	Detection Oligonucleotides	500 nM	2 μ L/min

Table 8.5 - Description of on-chip steps performed in the microfluidic device with the respective flow rates and assay times for the different strategies tested to detect gDNA. *gDNA was previously incubated off-chip with the restriction enzymes at 37 °C for 30 min and then flowed with the conditions presented in the table. **When a denaturation step was included, after restriction, the solution would also be heated off-chip at 95°C for 10 min and then flowed with the conditions presented in the table. *** Biotin blocking step to block free streptavidin that was still available on the bead surface.

Solution	Components	Stock concentration	Final concentration	Volume 1 x (μ L)	Step duration (min)	Temperature (°C)	Flow rate (μ L/min)
Capture and gDNA mix	Primer (μ M)	1	0.1	2	40	37	0.50
	PLP (μ M)	1	0.25	5			
	gDNA (copies/mL)	14000	4375	6.25			
	PBS 1 x			6.75			
	Anchor (μ M)	1	0.1	2			

	PLP (μM)	1	0.25	5	
Strategy II**	gDNA (copies/mL)	14000	4375	6.25	
	PBS 1 ×			6.75	
	gDNA (copies/mL)	14000	4375	6.25	
	Anchor (μM)	1	0.1	2	40
	PLP (μM)	1	0.25	5	
Strategy III**	PBS 1 ×			6.75	
	Biotin (mg/mL)	1	0.5	10	40***
	PBS			10	
	Primer (μM)	1	0.1	2	40
	PBS 1 ×			18	
	gDNA (copies/mL)	14000	4375	6.25	
	Avall (S. concentration - U/ μL) (Final concentration - U)	10	10	1	
Strategy IV**	HpHI (S. concentration - U/ μL) (Final concentration - U)	5	10	2	80
	CutSmart Buffer (x)	10	1	2	
	Milli-Q			8.75	
	Anchor (μM)	1	0.1	2	
	PLP (μM)	1	0.25	5	
	PBS 1 ×			13	
	gDNA (copies/mL)	14000	4375	6.25	
	Avall (S. concentration - U/ μL) (Final concentration - U)	10	10	1	
Strategy V**	HpHI (S. concentration - U/ μL) (Final concentration - U)	5	10	2	80
	CutSmart Buffer (x)	10	1	2	
	Milli-Q			8.75	
	Anchor (μM)	1	0.1	2	
	PLP (μM)	1	0.25	5	
	Biotin (mg/mL)	1	0.5	10	40***
	PBS			10	
	Primer (μM)	1	0.1	2	40

		PBS 1 ×			18			
Ligation		ATP (mM)	100	0.5	0.10			
		BSA (%)	4	0.04	0.20			
		T4 Buffer	10	1	2	40	37	0.50
		T4 (U/μL)	5	0.2	0.80			
		Milli-Q			16.90			
Amplification	All assays	Phi29 Buffer	10	1	1.5			
		BSA (%)	4	0.05	0.20			
		dNTPs (mM)	2.50	0.40	2.40	60	37	0.25
		Phi29	10	0.5	0.75			
		Milli-Q			10.15			
Labelling		Hybridization Buffer			15			
		Detection oligos (μM)	1	0.50	15	15	37	2.00

8.2.4. Well plate (off-chip) rolling circle amplification using single-stranded target DNA

For the off-chip experiments, the solutions were added to the wells of a PCR multi-well plate, and RCA was done under static conditions. The temperature and incubation times were controlled by a PCR Verity Thermal Cycler (Applied Biosystems). In both assays, the reagents for the ligation solution were added to the well and incubated at 37 °C for 40 min. After that, the amplification solution reagents were added to the well and incubated at 37 °C for 60 min. Lastly, the reagents for the detection solution (hybridization buffer with 500 nM DOs) were added to the well and incubated at 37 °C for 15min. The detection was achieved by flowing the well solution through a microfluidic channel with silica beads packed inside, as explained elsewhere[223]. The RCP solution flowed at 2.5 μL/min through the beads in the microchannel. Using fluorescence microscopy, the signal was acquired with optimal conditions. The concentrations and compositions of each solution can be found in

Table 8.6.

Table 8.6 - Description of on-well RCA for gDNA, solutions prepared for each step, and incubation times on well.*gDNA were previously incubated off-chip with the restriction enzymes at 37 °C for 30 min and then flowed with the conditions presented in the table. **When a denaturation step was included, after restriction, gDNA solution was complemented with all the molecules from the ligation solution (except for T4 (U/μL) ligase enzyme). The solution would also be heated off-chip at 95°C for 10 min, cooled off to rt, and then the T4 ligase enzyme was added, and the ligation proceeded on well.

Solution	Assay	Components	Stock concentration	Final concentration	Volume 1 x (μL)	Step duration (min)	Temperature (°C)	Reaction on
----------	-------	------------	---------------------	---------------------	-----------------	---------------------	------------------	-------------

		gDNA (copies/mL)	14000	4375	6.25			
		Avall (S. concentration - U/ μ L) (Final concentration - U)	10	10	1			
gDNA*		HpHI (S. concentration - U/ μ L) (Final concentration - U)				30	37	Eppendorf
	Well assay with restriction enzymes	CutSmart Buffer (x)	10	1	2			
	(With and without denaturation)	Milli-Q			8.75			
		Primer (μ M)	1	0.1	2			
		PLP (μ M)	1	0.25	5			
		ATP (mM)	100	0.5	0.10			
Ligation**		BSA (%)	4	0.04	0.20	40	37	Well
		T4 Buffer	10	1	2			
		T4 (U/ μ L)	5	0.2	0.80			
		Milli-Q			9.9			
		gDNA (copies/mL)	14000	4375	6.25			
	Well assay without restriction enzymes	Primer (μ M)	1	0.1	2			
		PLP (μ M)	1	0.25	5			
		ATP (mM)	100	0.5	0.10			
gDNA** and ligation	(With and without denaturation)	BSA (%)	4	0.04	0.20	40	37	Well
		T4 Buffer	10	1	2			
		T4 (U/ μ L)	5	0.2	0.80			
		Milli-Q			23.65			
		Phi29 Buffer	10	1	1.5			
		BSA (%)	4	0.05	0.20			
Amplification		dNTPs (mM)	2.50	0.40	2.40	60	37	Well
	All well assays	Phi29	10	0.5	0.75			
		Milli-Q			10.15			
		Hybridization Buffer			15			
Labelling		Detection oligos (DO4) (μ M)	1	0.50	15	15	37	Well

8.3. Results and discussion

8.3.1. On-chip rolling circle amplification using biotin-labeled single-stranded target DNA: Model strategy

RCA on-chip using a solid-phase immobilization strategy was first optimized using a DoE approach and statistical software (Minitab ®), and a screening experiment consisting of a fractional factorial design was developed to identify the main effects of the bead-based RCA on-chip. Seven variables (effects) at two levels (**Table 8.7**) were tested in 8 experiments using a resolution III fractional factorial design. It should be noted that choosing a fractional factorial design instead of a full factorial experiment degrades the resolution of the experimental design. This restricts the ability to distinguish main effects from low-order interactions and can lead to missing signal peaks between the range tested. However, the goal was first to perform a quick screening of the conditions, and for this, the resolution III fractional factorial design was considered the best option. This also allowed us to understand which variables were more relevant for future optimization studies.

Table 8.7 - Fractional factorial design.

Variable	Levels	
	Level -1	Level 1
A: Padlock probe [μM]	0.0001	1
B: T4 DNA ligase [$\text{U}/\mu\text{L}$]	0.05	0.25
C: dNTPs [μM]	125	500
D: Phi29 DNA polymerase [$\text{U}/\mu\text{L}$]	0.125	0.5
E: Detection oligos [μM]	0.5	1
F: Flow rate [$\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$]	0	0.25
G: Amplification time [min]	40	100

The results were imported back to the statistical software and a half-normal plot of the effects was obtained (**Figure 8.2**). It is clear from **Figure 8.2** that there is one factor

that has the largest effect, being the one farther apart from the fitted line (PLP concentration), since the closer, a factor is to the fitted line, the more it is considered a near-zero effect. From the main effects plot obtained from the Minitab ® software, and the linear regression model, it can be concluded that the main factor (PLP concentration) is directly related to higher fluorescence intensity. It is also possible to conclude that higher concentrations of dNTPs and detection oligo lead to a higher response. There is also an indication of an increase in signal when the assays are in-flow compared to a static incubation of the solution in the channel.

Figure 8.2 - Half-normal plot for the various effects and interactions.

Interestingly, it also appears that an excess of T4 enzyme leads to a decrease in the response signal since the signal is above the fitted line. When analyzing the effect of the flow rate on the amplification outcome, we can conclude that when performing an amplification for 100 min with a flow rate of 0.25 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$, there is an increase in the fluorescence output. Higher flow rates, such as 0.5 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ and 1 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ flow rate, were also tested. Although there was an indication that the optimal flow rate for the assay is closer to 0.5 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ than 0.25 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$, due to reagent volume constraints, 0.25 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ flow rate was the one selected for calibration experiments. The final values used for the bead-based RCA assays were: 100 nM PLP, 0.25 U/ μL T4 DNA ligase, 100 μM dNTPs, 0.5 U/ μL Phi29 DNA polymerase, 500 nM DO, with an amplification step of 60 min at 0.25 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$.

After the optimization procedure and considering reagent volume constraints as well, the final values used for the model strategy of on-chip RCA were: 100 nM of PLP, 0.25 U/ μL T4 DNA ligase, 0.4 mM dNTPs, 0.5 U/ μL Phi29 DNA polymerase, 500 nM DOs, with an amplification step of 60 min at 0.25 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$. After this optimization, we

used these conditions and detection based on Qdots 605TM-labeled detection oligos. Intending to characterize the LoD, we performed a dilution series of target DNA from 10^{-15} to 10^{-8} M. The LoD was obtained as the concentration of target DNA above 3.29 times the standard deviation of the control from a blank assay[287]. The results are shown in **Figure 8.3**. **Figure 8.3 – A** shows an LoD of 0.4 fM of target DNA. Using the same strategy, we also performed the detection using our in-house fabricated a-Si:H *p-i-n* photodiodes with a high pass interference filter, which allowed us to reject the excitation light of the laser (405 nm) and let through the emission light of the Qdots 605 (605 nm)[295] (**Figure 8.3 - C**). The photodiode results are shown in **Figure 8.3 - B**, indicating that the photosensor integration is feasible and that the trend is maintained compared with the results obtained with the microscope. In this sense, it is possible to integrate the continuous flow RCA on-chip with photodiode detection in a fit-for-purpose conjugation for PoC devices. Our results compare well with other results in the literature when the RCA is performed off-chip, and the capture of RCPs is done by microfluidic affinity chromatography. Soares *et al.* showed a device capable of detecting as low as 30 fM of ssDNA synthetic target when an RCA of 120 min was performed, followed by a 30 min detection time[298]. Although we only amplified for half of that time for just an hour, along with a detection step of only 15 min, we were still able to increase the assay sensitivity by two orders of magnitude. Sato *et al.* used a similar strategy of on-chip RCA, with primer solid phase immobilization, but using static conditions instead of continuous flow conditions. They could detect as low as 100 fM with a similar assay design [77]. However, the model strategy used above requires the target DNA to be labeled with biotin. Hence, to make this assay compatible with the use of real samples, different appropriate assay designs were studied, as detailed in the following sub-sections.

Figure 8.3 - Calibration curve for detecting biotinylated *S. aureus* target DNA using a solid-phase capture and RCA on-chip. A - Results of intensity measurements obtained using a fluorescence microscope. B - Average values for specific photocurrent are measured with the photodiodes for different target concentrations. The values presented are calculated by subtracting the laser excitation baseline from all data acquired with the laser turned ON. The error bars correspond to \pm SD of three repetitions. C - Schematics of the packed bead chamber and the alignment of the photosensor with an integrated filter HP570 underneath the channel.

8.3.2. On-chip rolling circle amplification using single-stranded target DNA: Strategy A

To optimize the target DNA's capture, we used a 5'-end biotinylated primer complementary to the PLP backbone. The target ssDNA was complementary to the target-binding regions of the PLP. The effect of the flow rate on the capture of the target ssDNA was studied by testing flow rates of 0.25, 0.5, 1.0, and 1.5 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ (**Figure 8.4**). The flow rate selected for capturing target DNA was 0.5 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ since it provided a balance between a high target DNA capture and a fast capture and ligation solution process.

Figure 8.4 - Flow rate optimization for the capture of ssDNA. Average fluorescence values were obtained for the four flow rates tested (0.25, 0.5, 1, and 1.5 μL/min) and the error bars correspond to ±SD of three repetitions.

Having established the flow rate, we used a mass balance approach to quantify the actual number of captured target DNA molecules and, thus, the capture efficiency of the system combining the assay and platform parameters (**Figure 8.5**).

The mass balance approach considers that the total mass of DNA introduced in the system equals the total mass out plus the total mass captured in the system.

$$Total (DNA)_{IN} = Total (DNA)_{CAP} + Total (DNA)_{OUT}$$

Equation 8.1

We used a microfluidic channel as the quantification platform to obtain the values for each term of **Equation 8.1**. Our group has already demonstrated this methodology in previous works[171], [172]. A calibration curve correlating the fluorescence of the target molecules and the number of target molecules was first obtained using a microfluidic channel with functionalized quaternary amine beads. We also verified that the first flow of DNA through a column of positively charged beads, with the assay conditions used, was able to collect the vast majority of DNA in solution, even for the highest concentration of DNA tested (250 nM).

Figure 8.5 - Target single-strand DNA capture studies. The error bars correspond to \pm SD of two repetitions. A - I Schematic of the assay used to quantify the target DNA captured by Q-Sepharose beads. A - II Calibration curves for known concentrations of labeled target DNA, used to determine $Total (DNA)_{OUT,BEADS}$ using a mass balance approach. B - I Schematics of the assay performed to determine $Total (DNA)_{OUT,BEADS}$. The LoD was obtained as the concentration of target DNA above 3.29 times the standard deviation of a blank assay. B - II Fluorescence signal obtained for different target DNA concentrations captured in the streptavidin beads, and fluorescence signal obtained in Q-Sepharose beads after flowing the solution from the outflow of the streptavidin bead channel. The mass balance allowed the capture target DNA efficiency calculation for each concentration of the target DNA tested.

This was confirmed by flowing the outflow of the first column through a second column with unused positively charged beads, using the same assay conditions as the first column. The fluorescence signal in the second column corresponded to less than 1% of the fluorescence signal in the first column (**Figure 8.6**).

The target DNA was labeled with an organic fluorophore. Measuring the fluorescence emitted for different concentrations of target DNA captured in these beads within a linear range allows for a calibration curve (**Figure 8.5 - A I and II**).

Figure 8.6 - Capture capacity for the first column of Q Sepharose beads and a second column.

For this calibration, we assumed that each strand of target DNA is labelled with one fluorophore. As such, a linear correlation can be made between the number of molecules and their fluorescence. We can use this calibration curve to find the mass of DNA coming out of the channel in a standard RCA target DNA capture step (**Figure 8.5 - B I**). The target DNA flows through a channel with streptavidin beads packed inside, with the primer and PLP already immobilized. The outflow is collected and flowed through a second channel with the quaternary amine functionalized beads. Since the results also showed that no DNA is getting accumulated in the PDMS walls of the device, we can assume that the mass of DNA in the system is the mass of DNA collected in the beads. In this case, Error! Reference source not found. can be transformed into:

$$Total (DNA)_{BEADS} = Total (DNA)_{IN} - Total (DNA)_{OUT,BEADS}$$

Equation 8.2

The complete derivation of this equation can be found in Supplementary Information - Quantitative analysis of DNA immobilization and hybridization. The $Total (DNA)_{IN}$ is obtained by knowing the initial concentration of target DNA flowing through the device. The capture efficiency was calculated as

$$Capture Efficiency (\%) = \frac{Total (DNA)_{BEADS}}{Total (DNA)_{IN}} \times 100$$

Equation 8.3

The results in **Figure 8.5 - B II** show that the capture efficiency is lower for higher concentrations of target DNA. We can see that for 250 nM, we obtained a capture efficiency of 27% (which corresponds to capture of $1.3 \times 10^{-12} \pm 5.3 \times 10^{-14}$ mol of

target DNA). This can be explained by a limitation of PLP available to hybridize at higher concentrations of target DNA. Primer and PLP concentrations (0.1 and 0.25 μM , respectively) are of the same order as the target DNA concentration (and not all molecules might have been immobilized on the beads) and the PLPs available for target capture might be insufficient. The increased capture efficiency corroborates this hypothesis as the concentration of target DNA decreases. For 100, 50 and 10 nM of target DNA concentrations, we obtained a capture efficiency of 53% ($1.1 \times 10^{-12} \pm 7.0 \times 10^{-14}$ mol of target DNA), 77% ($7.7 \times 10^{-13} \pm 6.0 \times 10^{-14}$ mol of target DNA) and virtually 100% ($2.0 \times 10^{-13} \pm 0$ mol of target DNA), respectively. For 10 nM, we need to consider into account the LoD of the Q-Sepharose beads. With this technique, we can detect < 0.9 nM of target DNA, and as such, although we cannot detect fluorescence for the outflow of the 10 nM in the QS beads, we can only estimate a maximum capture efficiency of $>91\%$. An associated error in the calculations performed from the calibration curve and limitations inherent to the microscope's sensitivity does not allow us to quantify the capture efficiency for lower concentrations accurately. The fluorescence signal emitted by the remaining 10 nM target DNA solution in Q-Sepharose beads (~ 236 A.U.) is around 12 times higher. In contrast, compared to the value when no target DNA is present on the beads (~ 26 A.U.), which is an indication that there is still a certain amount of DNA that was not captured during the assay, as stated previously. For the applications of POC devices, the fact that for lower concentrations of target DNA, we increase the capture efficiency is an advantage for such devices.

Finally, using the calibration curve obtained in **Figure 8.5 - A II**, we estimated the fluorescence signal that should be obtained for RCA amplification with 100% efficiency. First, we used the calibration curve to extract the value of the estimated fluorescence for a single molecule of Atto 430LS (7.5×10^{-9} A.U.). We know from the literature that Phi29 DNA polymerase can amplify a 100 bp PLP into a complementary concatemer with at least 1000 copies in 1 h [87], [299]. We also considered that only PLPs hybridized with the target DNA are circularized and available for amplification. Assuming 100% capture of 10 nM target DNA, we should have 1.2×10^{11} PLPs available in the channel for amplification. After amplification and using the values available in the literature for the DNA synthesis rate of Phi29 DNA polymerase in a linear RCA assay, we should have about 1.2×10^{14} copies of PLPs available after an hour for detection. We used a concentration of 500 nM of DOs (9×10^{12} molecules). If we assume a 100% hybridization efficiency between the DOs and the

complementary sequence, then we are limited by the number of DOs, and 9×10^{12} fluorescence molecules should correspond to a fluorescence signal of 63,523 A.U.

Using the same rationale, we calculated the expected amplification signal for a 1 nM of starting target DNA. Assuming 100% capture of 1 nM target DNA, we should have 1.204×10^{10} PLPs available for amplification. After amplification and using the values in the literature for DNA synthesis rate of Phi29 DNA polymerase in a linear RCA, we should have 1.2×10^{13} copies of PLPs available after an hour of amplification for detection. We used a concentration of 500 nM of detection oligos (9×10^{12} molecules). Once more, we are limited by the number of DOs, 9×10^{12} molecules, which means that the fluorescence signal should be similar between 1 and 10 nM of target DNA (experimental fluorescence value 1226 A.U., **Figure 8.6**). The experimentally observed signals after amplification for 1 nM and 10 nM of target DNA are 1.9% and 18%, respectively, relative to the theoretical fluorescence signal, considering the limitation imposed by the concentration of DOs used. Sato *et al.* reported a detection efficiency of 8% for a probe concentration of 3 fM[77]. However, when comparing the situation of the capture of the target ssDNA by the PLP in this section to the developed model strategy in the previous section, which also only requires one hybridization event, the obtained experimental signals account for approximately 6% and 69% for 1 nM and 10 nM of target DNA, respectively.

This leads to the conclusion that despite the continuous flow conditions of the assay, we are able to obtain a higher amplification yield when a single hybridization event is required in the model assay. The model assay (and also Sato's) used a target DNA that worked both as a primer and a target, bound to the beads and available to capture the PLP [198]. In the case of the assay in this section, the RCA assay requires two hybridization events prior to ligation. There is a hybridization between the primer and the PLP and a second hybridization event between the PLP and the target DNA (Strategy A). Due to the two hybridization events involved, it is reasonable to assume that our amplification efficiency can be lower because there is a higher probability that one of the two hybridization events does not occur compared to the strategy used by Sato *et al.* However, our method allows us to detect free target DNA in solution. Another difference is that we use a continuous flow assay, while Sato *et al.* uses a steady-state assay. This can also influence the final results. Overall, the results suggest that either we are not 100% efficient in the RCA assay or that we are losing RCPs due to the continuous flow nature of the assay. We developed an alternative capture strategy, strategy B, to investigate this aspect further.

8.3.3. On-chip rolling circle amplification using single-stranded target DNA: Strategy B

A critical point raised at the end of the previous section while investigating the capture optimization of the target DNA was whether a primer with a free 3'-end was leading to the loss of RCPs. This is of particular importance when the target DNA as well as the primer both have a 3'-end free to initiate amplification (**Figure 8.7 - A I**). Since this could lead to loss of RCPs, we compared strategy A to a new capture strategy where a 3'-end biotinylated anchor was used that was complementary to the 5'-end sequence of the target DNA. The PLP can recognize and hybridize with the target DNA sequence (**Figure 8.7 - B I**). The outflow of the RCA amplification was collected and flowed through a column with silica beads for both strategies. In this case, silica beads were used instead of Q-Sepharose beads since some free DOs could be present in the outflow solution, and we only wanted to detect the DOs hybridized to the long RCP products (**Figure 8.7 - A II** and **Figure 8.7 - B II**). This silica bead-based capture of RCPs was already used and demonstrated by our group[223]. Results in **Figure 8.7 - C** show that the fluorescence intensity is slightly higher for strategy A than for B on the streptavidin beads (~ 1.1-fold). However, when comparing the fluorescent intensity of the outflow collected from the streptavidin beads chamber, which is flowed through a chamber packed with silica beads to capture RCPs, the results show a significantly higher fluorescence for strategy A than strategy B (~ 5.0-fold). The signal for strategy B is within the value of the fluorescence obtained for the silica beads control (in this case, not having target DNA in the assays, which should correspond to flowing only the short DOs through the silica beads). The first strategy, strategy A, has a biotinylated primer (with a 3'-OH end free) that binds to PLP, which will capture the ssDNA. In this case, we will have two 3'-OH ends free for the amplification to occur. The second strategy, strategy B, has a biotinylated anchor that captures the free target ssDNA in the sample, which is then used to capture the PLP. Only the 3'-OH end of the target DNA is free for amplification in this strategy. The Phi 29 DNA polymerase presents DNA polymerase activity with a helicase-like activity, called strand displacement activity, as well as 3',5'- exonuclease activity [299]. Regarding the DNA polymerase activity, Phi29 DNA polymerase can perform DNA synthesis while displacing downstream non-template DNA from a template. This strand activity allows isothermal DNA amplification, such as RCA. Due to the strand displacement activity, Phi29 DNA polymerase can catalyze the replication of a linear dsDNA[300]. For this, it is necessary that a 3'-OH end is free to incorporate the nucleotide that is a match for the base on the opposing single-stranded DNA template.

However, in the strategies presented in this section, the strand displacement activity can negatively impact the fluorescence result measured on the beads. In strategy A (**Figure 8.7 - A I**), two primers are present where Phi29 DNA polymerase can perform polymerization, in the blue strand bound to the beads (denominated primer), or in the green strand (denominated the target DNA). If the blue strand is preferred, then the Phi29 DNA polymerase will elongate the primer strand bound to the bead, using the PLP as DNA template. The RCP will stay bound to the bead, and it will be possible to detect it under the microscope. However, if the green strand is preferred, then the Phi29 DNA polymerase will elongate the target DNA strand using the PLP as DNA template. The strand displacement activity of Phi29 DNA polymerase will lead to the dehybridization of the PLP to the primer, and as such, the RCPs will be washed away from the beads. This is possible to be verified by flowing the outflow of the RCA assay through the silica beads (**Figure 8.7 - A II**), where we could measure fluorescence, confirming that this last hypothesis was occurring in strategy A. To avoid the loss of RCPs, we designed strategy B. In this case, only one 3'-OH is free (in the target DNA). The Phi29 DNA polymerase will elongate the target DNA strand using the PLP as a DNA template. The product will stay bound to the beads via the hybridization of the red strand (denominated anchor) to the 5'-end tail of the target DNA. This strategy showed that the loss of RCP was significantly lower when compared to strategy A.

Figure 8.7 - Detection of rolling circle amplification products for strategy A and strategy B. (A)(I) Schematics and micrographs of a chamber after a PLP-RCA assay on streptavidin beads using strategy A. (A)(II) Schematics and micrographs of a chamber of the outflow of the PLP-RCA assay on streptavidin beads using strategy A, after being flowed through silica beads. (B)(I) Schematics and micrographs of a chamber after an PLP-RCA assay on streptavidin beads using strategy B. (B)(II) Schematics and micrographs of a chamber of the outflow of the PLP-RCA assay on streptavidin beads using strategy B after being flowed through silica beads. (C) Average fluorescence values were obtained for the two strategies on the streptavidin bead chamber and silica bead chamber. The error bars correspond to \pm SD of two repetitions.

Phi29 DNA polymerase must be bound to an oligonucleotide primer hybridized to a complementary oligonucleotide template DNA (junction with dsDNA) to initiate polymerization. On the other hand, the 3'→5'- exonuclease activity will work only on ssDNA primers. But in both cases, a free 3'-OH end is required to prime polymerization and exonuclease activity. The exonuclease activity will use that primer

tail, and through the hydrolysis of a phosphodiester bond, Phi29 DNA polymerase will be able to degrade ssDNA oligonucleotide primers[301]. This feature can be helpful when the target DNA is also used as an RCA primer, particularly in practical cases where the target is enclosed in long genome sequences, where the ssDNA tail is removed via exonuclease activity until we have the free 3'-OH close to the dsDNA formed by the target and the PLP [297]. However, in this case, we hypothesize that the exonuclease activity of Phi29 DNA polymerase hindered the fluorescence of strategy B. We expected that the fluorescence in the streptavidin beads would be higher in strategy B than in strategy A due to a decrease in the loss of RCPs. However, as shown in **Figure 8.7 C**, this was not the case. Since in strategy B, only the target DNA is used as the RCA primer, and that is reported in the literature that the 3'→5' exonuclease activity of Phi29 DNA polymerase can degrade RCA primers, thus hampering the amplification yield, we believe that in strategy B this was the reason for the decrease in fluorescence observed. Dean *et al.* modified the primers with thiophosphate linkage in the 3'-end to block the possible primer degradation and increase the amplification yield by 10,000-fold compared with the use of exonuclease sensitive primers (375-fold amplification)[299].

Using the same mass balance analysis as before to calculate the expected fluorescence values after RCA on the chip and to compare them with experimental fluorescence values obtained, we can see that for strategy A, and summing the fluorescence obtained for the RCPs that were washed away and captured in the silica channel, the total fluorescence is approximately 19,300 A.U. which corresponds to approximately 3×10^{12} molecules, and thus to approximately 30% of the fluorescence signal calculated theoretically, considering the limitation imposed by the concentration of the DOs used in the assay. This value is higher than other values (8% detection rate) reported in the literature for microfluidic devices[77]. Although there is an increase in efficiency by considering the lost RCPs, our signal is still below the theoretically expected values. For strategy B, although we don't have lost RCPs, the experimental fluorescence value (10,500 A.U.) corresponds to approximately 16% of the fluorescence value expected, assuming an amplification efficiency of 100%. We hypothesize that, to some degree, the amplification is hindered by the microscale environment of the microfluidic chip, such as a limitation of the diffusion of the molecules on-chip. Towards this end, we next performed both strategies, A and B, in a well plate to test our hypothesis.

8.3.4. Solution-based off-chip rolling circle amplification using single-stranded target DNA

We used the same protocol in the microfluidic chip to perform RCA in a well plate for both strategies A and B. After the RCA was performed, the solution was flowed through a microfluidic chamber with silica beads to capture the RCPs to measure the fluorescence signal. The results are shown in **Figure 8.8**. As we can see in the figure, for both the strategies, there is an increase in the fluorescence signal detected on the well compared with the results obtained in the microfluidic chip. Strategy A presents an enhancement of approximately 4.7-fold, and we have a 4.5-fold fluorescence signal increase for strategy B. These results of RCA in solution for strategy A (54,269 A.U.) and strategy B (58,158 A.U.) are close to the expected fluorescence value (63,523 A.U.). This result sustains the hypothesis that we are hindering the RCA assay in the microfluidic environment. Considering the chamber volume, we can conclude that the chamber accommodates 24 nL of the solution. While flowing through the chamber, each RCA solution is also washing away the molecules present. On the other hand, the in-well RCA will accommodate the solutions of each RCA step in one well throughout the whole experiment. This means that when adding the solution for RCA amplification, we are going from 20 μ L of the initial solution to 35 μ L solution with the reagents of amplification and ligation still present (although diluted 1.5 : 2 (v/v)). Since all the molecules are still present in the solution, there may still be events of ligation occurring while the Phi29 DNA polymerase is performing the amplification. The molecules kept in solution can create more PLP-target DNA complexes that can also be amplified. This means that in the well plate RCA, we expect the RCPs products to have increased variability in RCPs length. It is also important to notice that the on-chip capture of the RCPs, that were amplified off-chip, works as a concentration step for the RCPs helping to increase the detected signal, when compared to amplification on-chip where after the amplification, no concentration of the RCPs is achieved[223]. In the case of the microfluidic chip, we can only amplify the PLP-target DNA complexes created in the ligation step. Afterwards, we don't have in the chamber the required molecules that would allow increasing the PLP-target DNA complexes and, in turn, the RCPs obtained. However, the continuous flow characteristics can also be beneficial for eliminating contaminants and amplification inhibitors. This can be particularly important if a lysis module is coupled with the presented RCA module to allow the direct detection of pathogens in real samples. Another important consideration to move this device closer to a real sample scenario is detecting target DNA embedded in a long-stranded genomic DNA.

We used strategy A and strategy B as starting points to study the capture and amplification of synthetic gDNA.

Figure 8.8 - Comparison of PLP-RCA performed on a well plate and on-chip for both strategies A and B. The error bars correspond to \pm SD of two repetitions.

8.3.5. On-chip rolling circle amplification using double-stranded target DNA

We used purified and quantified gDNA from *S. aureus* to mimic a real sample and employed different assay designs. In **Figure 8.1 - D**, we schematized the assay designs tested. Three configurations were tested using the gDNA directly (**Figure 8.1 - D I, II, and III**), and two configurations exploited the use of restriction enzymes on the gDNA (**Figure 8.1 - D IV and V**).

For the three configurations without restriction enzymes, the first configuration used a primer biotinylated in the 5'-end, complementary to the PLP backbone. This design can translate, for ssDNA as target, into the previous strategy A. The second configuration used an anchor biotinylated at the 3'-end, while the 5'-end of the anchor was complementary to the 5'-end portions of the gDNA, that was next to the target sequence. The PLP ends were complementary to this target sequence. This design can translate, for ssDNA target, into the previous strategy B. The third configuration used the biotinylated anchor at the 3'-end. At the other extremity, the 5'-end of the anchor was complementary to the 5'-end portions of the gDNA and a primer complementary to the PLP backbone.

By comparing strategy II and strategy III, we could understand whether the cleavage of gDNA influenced the final fluorescence signal measured. Results are shown in Figure 6. It was observed that strategy I presented the best results compared to

strategies II and III, with a 2.6 -fold enhancement in fluorescence signal obtained. These results were expected since there is no 3'-OH free end on the target DNA that allows for the catalysis of the Phi29 DNA polymerase in strategy II. In strategy III, although there is a primer no 3'-OH free end bound to the PLP that allows for Phi29 DNA polymerase to elongate the primer strand, the primer is not bound to the beads. As Phi29 DNA polymerase progresses with the amplification, the strand displacement activity will release the amplified product, which will then be washed away by the continuous flow. As such, strategy I appeared to be the more promising, with a good signal-to-noise ratio (SNR). These results encourage us to perform the assay with a smaller fragment of the gDNA. In this work, we used restriction enzyme-mediated cleavage to obtain a DNA fragment with 171 nucleotides, where the target DNA sequence was embedded inside. We initially tested the base strategies II and III, but subsequently added the restriction enzymes on gDNA and obtained the assay configurations for strategies IV and V. The results in **Figure 8.9** show that the use of restriction enzymes increased the fluorescence signal for strategy IV, which compares directly with strategy II. We increased the fluorescence signal 2-fold over strategy II and an SNR of almost two. Strategy V didn't improve the fluorescence signal when compared to strategy III. Once again, this was expected since we have the primer on the PLP ready to initiate the amplification process. Due to the same reason as stated for strategy III, the RCPs are released in solution and washed away from the microfluidic chamber. Of all these strategies, I and IV are the most promising ones in practical applications using clinical samples containing DNA.

Figure 8.9 - Fluorescence signal obtained by microscopy and image analysis for the different strategies used to detect *S. aureus* gDNA. The error bars correspond to \pm SD of two repetitions. The signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) corresponds to the ratio between the RCA of gDNA divided by the control for each strategy. This SNR analysis was done for the most promising strategies (Strategy I and IV).

8.4. Chapter Conclusions

The implementation of RCA on a microfluidic chip in an integrated fashion is herein systematically and quantitatively addressed using multiple experimental conditions and assay configurations. We used a solid phase capture strategy to perform the PLP-RCA experiments in a microfluidic channel. Using a model strategy, that was optimized through a DoE to obtain the best assay conditions, we detected 0.4 fM of target ssDNA, with a total sample-to-result analysis time of 2 hours. We also coupled the complete PLP-RCA microfluidic on-chip fluorescence read-out to a-Si:H p-i-n photodiodes with a high pass interference filter, which is compatible with future PoC applications. To move closer to tests for practical clinical settings, we developed two different strategies for optimal target DNA capture. We concluded that having two 3'-OH ends from a primer or a target DNA coupled to the PLP hindered the fluorescence signal due to loss of RCPs. We observed that the best strategy to detect intact genomic DNA was by having a PLP-RCA primer bound to the bead surface while for restrict-digested genomic DNA, the capture can be made with an anchor. Furthermore, comparison of PLP-RCA performed in the microfluidic chip against the one performed in a well showed that the signal obtained in the well studies is at least 5-fold higher than in the microfluidic chip. We believe that further optimization of the on-chip PLP-RCA pertaining to the reagent concentrations and time of residency, allowing for effective biomolecular interactions, can help to close the gap between the results obtained in the well and on-chip. A calibration curve for target concentration is also required in the future to better understand the LoD for the most promising capture strategies. The on-chip device has also the potential to perform multiplex detection of different pathogens by using diverse PLPs and different DOs labeled with a variety of fluorophores. Thus, the demonstrated on-chip platform can also be integrated with a potential lysis module, allowing to have a truly real sample-to-answer PoC device to address demands in clinically relevant molecular diagnostics.

Chapter 9

Conclusion and Future developments

This chapter provides an overview of the main achievements reached in this Ph.D. project with a focus on improvements related to the state-of-the-art and main novelty, as well as future perspectives to achieve a fully integrated PoC device for pathogen detection using a nucleic acid based-approach.

9. Conclusion and Future developments

9.1. Novelty and main improvements to the state-of-the-art

The work presented in this Ph.D. project focused on developing the individual modules of a PoC device for bacterial detection, although virus-like particles were also explored. The modules developed comprised cell capture/lysis and DNA/RNA extraction, nucleic acid amplification, and detection of the DNA of interest. This corresponded to the full completion of **Task 1**.

The development of a specific optical detection module (**Subtask 1.4**) was addressed in **Chapters 4, 5, and 6**. The main breakthroughs in the detection modules were related to the novel usage of chromatography beads to improve the capture of nucleic acids in solution and the ability to regenerate the beads and performed several cycles of regeneration and capture for the specific capture of a target DNA molecule and also allowing the capability of having accurate internal control for nucleic acid capture. Integrating different photodetection setups to acquire chemiluminescence or fluorescence proved very promising for miniaturization. Although chemiluminescence detection allowed higher sensitivities, the complexity of flowing an enzymatic substrate elongated the time of analysis and only allowed for an endpoint measurement. However, the ability to perform a continuous fluorescence measurement in a miniaturized fashion is highly important to obtain a faster result, a significant goal in a PoC device, instead of detecting an endpoint signal. However, if multiplex detection is required, photodiodes with different integrated filters would be

necessary, increasing the complexity of the device, and an evaluation of the footprint and redimension of detection chambers would be required.

Chapter 7 describes the lysis module. This chapter follows the accomplishment of **Subtasks 1.1 and 1.2**, defined as the development of a lysis module and extraction module, respectively. We developed a device for cell lysis for bacteria and viruses and performed DNA/RNA extraction from the lysate. The main novelty was using a lysis solution capable of lysing bacteria and viruses and integrating nanoporous beads to perform nucleic acid extraction in a single microfluidic device. Most of the lysis microfluidics devices reported in the literature are stand-alone devices, as the module reported in the Ph.D. thesis, but lack the extraction and detection steps. This module could work by itself to detect nucleic acids in a sample, without amplification, by coupling an intercalating DNA dye. By integrating nanoporous beads to capture the nucleic acids, we combined a step of extraction. Since we worked with a chemical lysis method, capturing the bead of the nucleic acids allowed us to remove possible inhibitors for the subsequent steps of nucleic acid amplification.

Then the development of an amplification module (**Subtask 1.3**) was addressed in **Chapter 8**, where we elaborated on different strategies to implement RCA amplification on-chip. The first strategy proved the development of an amplification RCA module on the chip. This allowed us to conclude and reach all the milestones proposed for **Task 1**. Still exploring **Chapter 8**, a further advance using strategies with the appropriate assay architecture to amplify from a real sample was also examined. The main novelty of this module was the detailed study on PLP-RCA configurations to implement on-chip to perform the amplification from a DNA template under continuous flow conditions and maintain the RCPs bound to a solid phase in a limited chamber of the microfluidic device. Integrating the beads to capture the initial DNA and bound the RCPs allowed to complete of **Subtask 2.2** from **Task 2** and the integration of the a-Si:H *p-i-n* photodiodes for the optical detection allowed to complete of **Subtask 2.1**.

9.2. Future developments toward a fully integrated microfluidic system for the detection of pathogens

This section discusses future development to accomplish the tasks and milestones that still need to be completed to achieve a fully integrated microfluidic system for detecting pathogens. During the Ph.D. project, some difficulties were encountered. For instance, although preliminary tests were conducted to incorporate the lysis

module with the extraction and amplification modules, it was found that several optimizations were still required.

To integrate into a device practical for PoC applications and complete **Subtask 2.3** from **Task 2**, the following steps to be tested is the elution of the nucleic acids from the captured nanoporous beads. Elution would allow the DNA to move towards a chamber that can capture the target DNA using the architecture assays explored in **Chapter 8**. Another critical challenge to be solved is the implementation of dsDNA denaturation to allow hybridization to the primers (for PCR) or a PLP probe (for RCA). Most PoC devices use temperature to perform the dsDNA denaturation. However, this strategy is not compatible if the PoC device is to be used at a constant and low temperature. Implementing this step would allow the full integration of the lysis module with the amplification module. One possible line of implementation in the future is the chemical denaturation of dsDNA using, for instance 1 mol/L of NaOH or 60% dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO). The denaturation using the mentioned reagents has been proven to have 100% denaturation efficacy [302]. After denaturation, a stream solution with primers or PLP probes in phosphate buffer can merge with the channel with the denatured target DNA, and after a short contact time, a downstream chamber with beads can be used to capture the target DNA and primers, exploring the configurations study in **Chapter 8**, for instance. A different line of implementation would be exploring isothermal amplification techniques that can also initiate the amplification of dsDNA without a primary denaturation step, such as RPA. However, the sensitivity should be evaluated and compared between the different amplification strategies. Upon appropriate optimization a lysis module coupled with amplification can serve as a disruptive device for PoC devices. This integration would then allow for sensitivity tests with actual clinical samples. Also, optimization regarding the time of analysis should be performed, and assay speed should be improved. Studies, namely on reducing the amplification duration by coupling the three sequential steps into one, should be studied, and the use of quenched probes would allow for continuously monitoring of the fluorescence and use the kinetics of the amplification to determine a positive.

Moreover, the miniaturization of a compact system that would comprise the electronic and software capability to actuate the microfluidic device is also required. The microfluidic device should be discardable, and the reading instrument should house a light source for fluorophore excitation (such as an LED), the photodiodes used as optical detectors and aligned with the detection chamber of the discardable microfluidic device, and the electronic circuits and controllers to allow fluidic and

temperature actuation and control, as well as signal readout. If the result is to be displayed in the instrument, an LCD should be coupled, and a microprocessor to perform data processing should also be installed. A different option is to include wireless signal transmission capabilities to transfer the information for a smartphone, for instance.

Another critical topic to be studied is the sample transfer to the microfluidic chip. Minimal user intervention is required, and steps of sample preparation should be avoided to guarantee that the user of interest readily accepts the device and that it complies with the user's requirements. For instance, for samples collected by swabs (such as in the case of detection of MRSA), we can think about a strategy similar to the strategy employed for the rapid test for SARS-CoV-2, where after collecting the sample, the swab is dipped in a conservation/extraction liquid inside an Eppendorf given to the user. The user can then press the swab against the walls of the Eppendorf tube and use a few drops of the solution to perform the test. Ideally, having this coupled inside the chip, where the swab is inserted directly into a chamber with the extraction liquid, would allow full integration of sample extraction and preparation, achieving a fully functional prototype.

On the long-term developments, something of interest, particularly in the field of antimicrobial resistance, would be to couple bacterial identification to an antibiotic susceptibility test (AST). Pheno-molecular tests to study bacterial drug resistance are done through the measurement of a parameter called minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC), the lowest concentration of a drug that prevents the growth of bacteria [303], [304]. Another exciting root of research is the incorporation of machine learning analysis to recognize patterns in the results and help predict results could be crucial for the AST analysis.

Bibliography

- [1] C. J. Murray *et al.*, 'Global burden of bacterial antimicrobial resistance in 2019: a systematic analysis', *The Lancet*, vol. 399, no. 10325, pp. 629–655, Feb. 2022, doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(21)02724-0/ATTACHMENT/B227DEB3-FF04-497F-82AC-637D8AB7F679/MMC1.PDF.
- [2] World Health Organization, 'WHO strategic priorities on antimicrobial resistance: preserving antimicrobials for today and tomorrow', *World Health Organization*, pp. 1–12, 2021, Accessed: Aug. 12, 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/351719>
- [3] D. E. Bloom and D. Cadarette, 'Infectious disease threats in the twenty-first century: Strengthening the global response', *Front Immunol*, vol. 10, p. 549, 2019, doi: 10.3389/FIMMU.2019.00549/BIBTEX.
- [4] P. A. Greenwood and G. M. Greenway, 'Sample manipulation in micro total analytical systems', *TrAC - Trends in Analytical Chemistry*, vol. 21, no. 11, pp. 726–740, Nov. 2002, doi: 10.1016/S0165-9936(02)01104-4.
- [5] S. C. Terry, J. H. Herman, and J. B. Angell, 'A Gas Chromatographic Air Analyzer Fabricated on a Silicon Wafer', *IEEE Trans Electron Devices*, vol. 26, no. 12, pp. 1880–1886, 1979, doi: 10.1109/T-ED.1979.19791.
- [6] A. Manz, N. Graber, and H. M. Widmer, 'Miniaturized total chemical analysis systems: A novel concept for chemical sensing', *Sens Actuators B Chem*, vol. 1, no. 1–6, pp. 244–248, Jan. 1990, doi: 10.1016/0925-4005(90)80209-I.
- [7] A. Manz, Y. Miyahara, J. Miura, Y. Watanabe, H. Miyagi, and K. Sato, 'Design of an open-tubular column liquid chromatograph using silicon chip technology', *Sens Actuators B Chem*, vol. 1, no. 1–6, pp. 249–255, Jan. 1990, doi: 10.1016/0925-4005(90)80210-Q.
- [8] C. T. Culbertson, T. G. Mickleburgh, S. A. Stewart-James, K. A. Sellens, and M. Pressnall, 'Micro total analysis systems: Fundamental advances and biological applications', *Analytical Chemistry*, vol. 86, no. 1, pp. 95–118, Jan. 07, 2014. doi: 10.1021/ac403688g.
- [9] P. Sengupta, K. Khanra, A. R. Chowdhury, and P. Datta, 'Lab-on-a-chip sensing devices for biomedical applications', in *Bioelectronics and Medical Devices: From Materials to Devices - Fabrication, Applications and Reliability*, Elsevier, 2019, pp. 47–95. doi: 10.1016/B978-0-08-102420-1.00004-2.

- [10] A. J. Tüdos, G. A. J. Besselink, and R. B. M. Schasfoort, 'Trends in miniaturized total analysis systems for point-of-care testing in clinical chemistry', *Lab on a Chip*, vol. 1, no. 2. Royal Society of Chemistry, pp. 83–95, Dec. 01, 2001. doi: 10.1039/b106958f.
- [11] J. G. E. Gardeniers and A. van den Berg, 'Lab-on-a-chip systems for biomedical and environmental monitoring', *Analytical and Bioanalytical Chemistry* 2004 378:7, vol. 378, no. 7, pp. 1700–1703, Jan. 2004, doi: 10.1007/S00216-003-2435-7.
- [12] N. C. Cady, S. Stelick, M. v. Kunnavakkam, and C. A. Batt, 'Real-time PCR detection of *Listeria monocytogenes* using an integrated microfluidics platform', in *Sensors and Actuators, B: Chemical*, Elsevier, May 2005, pp. 332–341. doi: 10.1016/j.snb.2004.10.022.
- [13] E. J. S. Brás, A. M. Fortes, V. Chu, P. Fernandes, and J. P. Conde, 'Microfluidic device for the point of need detection of a pathogen infection biomarker in grapes', *Analyst*, vol. 144, no. 16, pp. 4871–4879, 2019, doi: 10.1039/C9AN01002E.
- [14] J.-Y. Yoon and B. Kim, 'Lab-on-a-Chip Pathogen Sensors for Food Safety', *Sensors*, vol. 12, no. 8, pp. 10713–10741, Aug. 2012, doi: 10.3390/s120810713.
- [15] R. H. Meltzer *et al.*, 'A lab-on-chip for biothreat detection using single-molecule DNA mapping', *Lab Chip*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 863–873, Mar. 2011, doi: 10.1039/c0lc00477d.
- [16] H. Kettler, K. White, and S. Hawkes, 'Mapping the landscape of diagnostics for sexually transmitted infections: key findings and recommendations.', *Mapping the landscape of diagnostics for sexually transmitted infections: key findings and recommendations.*, 2004.
- [17] C. S. Kosack, A. L. Page, and P. R. Klatser, 'A guide to aid the selection of diagnostic tests', *Bull World Health Organ*, vol. 95, no. 9, pp. 639–645, Sep. 2017, doi: 10.2471/BLT.16.187468.
- [18] K. J. Land, D. I. Boeras, X.-S. Chen, A. R. Ramsay, and R. W. Peeling, 'REASSURED diagnostics to inform disease control strategies, strengthen health systems and improve patient outcomes', *Nat Microbiol*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 46–54, 2019, doi: 10.1038/s41564-018-0295-3.

- [19] E. K. Sackmann, A. L. Fulton, and D. J. Beebe, 'The present and future role of microfluidics in biomedical research', *Nature*, vol. 507, no. 7491. Nature Publishing Group, pp. 181–189, Mar. 12, 2014. doi: 10.1038/nature13118.
- [20] D. Chakraborty and S. Chakraborty, 'Microfluidic transport and micro-scale flow physics: An overview', in *Microfluidics and Microfabrication*, Springer US, 2010, pp. 1–85. doi: 10.1007/978-1-4419-1543-6_1.
- [21] N.-T. Nguyen, S. Wereley, and S. A. M. Shaegh, *Fundamentals and applications of microfluidics* | Seyed Ali Mousavi Shaegh; Nam-Trung Nguyen; Steven T. Wereley | download, Third. Artech, 2019. Accessed: Feb. 01, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://b-ok.global/book/5595133/3d88e3>
- [22] G. M. Whitesides, 'The origins and the future of microfluidics', *Nature*, vol. 442, no. 7101. pp. 368–373, Jul. 27, 2006. doi: 10.1038/nature05058.
- [23] K. S. Elvira, X. C. I Solvas, R. C. R. Wootton, and A. J. Demello, 'The past, present and potential for microfluidic reactor technology in chemical synthesis', *Nature Chemistry*, vol. 5, no. 11. pp. 905–915, Nov. 2013. doi: 10.1038/nchem.1753.
- [24] B. Cao, G. A. Stevens, J. Ho, and D. Ma Fat, 'WHO methods and data sources for country-level causes of death 2000-2019 (Global Health Estimates Technical Paper)', Dec. 2000. Accessed: Feb. 03, 2021. [Online]. Available: http://www.who.int/gho/mortality_burden_disease/en/index.html
- [25] Y. R. Saharman, A. Karuniawati, J. A. Severin, and H. A. Verbrugh, 'Infections and antimicrobial resistance in intensive care units in lower-middle income countries: a scoping review', *Antimicrobial Resistance and Infection Control*, vol. 10, no. 1. BioMed Central Ltd, p. 22, Dec. 01, 2021. doi: 10.1186/s13756-020-00871-x.
- [26] K. K. Holmes *et al.*, 'Major Infectious Diseases: Key Messages from Disease Control Priorities, Third Edition', in *Disease Control Priorities, Third Edition (Volume 6): Major Infectious Diseases*, The World Bank, 2017, pp. 1–27. doi: 10.1596/978-1-4648-0524-0_ch1.
- [27] O. Lazcka, F. J. del Campo, and F. X. Muñoz, 'Pathogen detection: A perspective of traditional methods and biosensors', *Biosensors and Bioelectronics*, vol. 22, no. 7. Elsevier, pp. 1205–1217, Feb. 15, 2007. doi: 10.1016/j.bios.2006.06.036.

- [28] X. Zhao, M. Li, and Y. Liu, 'Microfluidic-Based Approaches for Foodborne Pathogen Detection', *Microorganisms*, vol. 7, no. 10, p. 381, Sep. 2019, doi: 10.3390/microorganisms7100381.
- [29] C. H. Su *et al.*, 'Dual aptamer assay for detection of *Acinetobacter baumannii* on an electromagnetically-driven microfluidic platform', *Biosens Bioelectron*, vol. 159, p. 112148, Jul. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.bios.2020.112148.
- [30] X. Hao *et al.*, 'Aptamer surface functionalization of microfluidic devices using dendrimers as multi-handled templates and its application in sensitive detections of foodborne pathogenic bacteria', *Anal Chim Acta*, vol. 1056, pp. 96–107, May 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.aca.2019.01.035.
- [31] A. C. G. Foddai and I. R. Grant, 'Methods for detection of viable foodborne pathogens: current state-of-art and future prospects', *Applied Microbiology and Biotechnology*, vol. 104, no. 10. Springer, pp. 4281–4288, May 01, 2020. doi: 10.1007/s00253-020-10542-x.
- [32] P. Dow, K. Kotz, S. Gruszka, J. Holder, and J. Fiering, 'Acoustic separation in plastic microfluidics for rapid detection of bacteria in blood using engineered bacteriophage', *Lab Chip*, vol. 18, no. 6, pp. 923–932, Mar. 2018, doi: 10.1039/c7lc01180f.
- [33] S. İ. Dönmez, S. H. Needs, H. M. I. Osborn, and A. D. Edwards, 'Label-free smartphone quantitation of bacteria by darkfield imaging of light scattering in fluoropolymer micro capillary film allows portable detection of bacteriophage lysis', *Sens Actuators B Chem*, vol. 323, p. 128645, Nov. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.snb.2020.128645.
- [34] F. Cui, M. Rhee, A. Singh, and A. Tripathi, 'Microfluidic Sample Preparation for Medical Diagnostics', *Annual Review of Biomedical Engineering*, vol. 17. Annual Reviews Inc., pp. 267–286, Dec. 07, 2015. doi: 10.1146/annurev-bioeng-071114-040538.
- [35] C. Schrader, A. Schielke, L. Ellerbroek, and R. Johne, 'PCR inhibitors – occurrence, properties and removal', *J Appl Microbiol*, vol. 113, no. 5, pp. 1014–1026, Nov. 2012, doi: 10.1111/J.1365-2672.2012.05384.X.
- [36] B. Fung *et al.*, 'Direct Comparison of SARS-CoV-2 Analytical Limits of Detection across Seven Molecular Assays', *J Clin Microbiol*, vol. 58, no. 9, pp. e01535-20, Aug. 2020, doi: 10.1128/JCM.01535-20.

- [37] W. Yi-Dong *et al.*, 'Gram Stain-Specific-Probe-Based Real-Time PCR for Diagnosis and Discrimination of Bacterial Neonatal Sepsis', *J Clin Microbiol*, vol. 46, no. 8, pp. 2613–2619, Aug. 2008, doi: 10.1128/JCM.02237-07.
- [38] Md. S. Islam, A. Shahid, K. Kuryllo, Y. Li, M. J. Deen, and P. R. Selvaganapathy, 'Electrophoretic Concentration and Electrical Lysis of Bacteria in a Microfluidic Device Using a Nanoporous Membrane', *Micromachines*, vol. 8, no. 2. 2017. doi: 10.3390/mi8020045.
- [39] D. E. Dietzman, G. W. Fischer, and F. D. Schoenknecht, 'Neonatal escherichia coli septicemia—bacterial counts in blood', *J Pediatr*, vol. 85, no. 1, pp. 128–130, 1974, doi: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-3476\(74\)80308-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-3476(74)80308-2).
- [40] M. Flaender *et al.*, 'Grinding Lysis (GL): A microfluidic device for sample enrichment and mechanical lysis in one', *Sens Actuators B Chem*, vol. 258, pp. 148–155, 2018, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.snb.2017.11.082>.
- [41] C. H. Kim *et al.*, 'On-site extraction and purification of bacterial nucleic acids from blood samples using an unpowered microfluidic device', *Sens Actuators B Chem*, vol. 320, p. 128346, 2020, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.snb.2020.128346>.
- [42] B. Krafft, A. Tycova, R. D. Urban, C. Dusny, and D. Belder, 'Microfluidic device for concentration and SERS-based detection of bacteria in drinking water', *Electrophoresis*, vol. 42, no. 1–2, pp. 86–94, Jan. 2021, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1002/elps.202000048>.
- [43] B. B. Fuchs, S. Eatemadpour, J. M. Martel-Foley, S. Stott, M. Toner, and E. Mylonakis, 'Rapid Isolation and Concentration of Pathogenic Fungi Using Inertial Focusing on a Chip-Based Platform', *Frontiers in Cellular and Infection Microbiology*, vol. 9. 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://www.frontiersin.org/article/10.3389/fcimb.2019.00027>
- [44] M. A. Faridi, H. Ramachandraiah, I. Banerjee, S. Ardabili, S. Zelenin, and A. Russom, 'Elasto-inertial microfluidics for bacteria separation from whole blood for sepsis diagnostics', *J Nanobiotechnology*, vol. 15, no. 1, p. 3, 2017, doi: 10.1186/s12951-016-0235-4.
- [45] X. Lu *et al.*, 'Sheathless and high-throughput elasto-inertial bacterial sorting for enhancing molecular diagnosis of bloodstream infection', *Lab Chip*, vol. 21, no. 11, pp. 2163–2177, 2021, doi: 10.1039/D1LC00085C.

- [46] L. D'Amico, N. J. Ajami, J. A. Adachi, P. R. C. Gascoyne, and J. F. Petrosino, 'Isolation and concentration of bacteria from blood using microfluidic membraneless dialysis and dielectrophoresis', *Lab Chip*, vol. 17, no. 7, pp. 1340–1348, Mar. 2017, doi: 10.1039/c6lc01277a.
- [47] X. F. van Kooten, M. Truman-Rosentsvit, G. v Kaigala, and M. Bercovici, 'Focusing analytes from 50 μ L into 500 pL: On-chip focusing from large sample volumes using isotachopheresis', *Sci Rep*, vol. 7, no. 1, p. 10467, 2017, doi: 10.1038/s41598-017-10579-5.
- [48] S. Azinheiro, K. Kant, M.-A. Shahbazi, A. Garrido-Maestu, M. Prado, and L. Dieguez, 'A smart microfluidic platform for rapid multiplexed detection of foodborne pathogens', *Food Control*, vol. 114, p. 107242, 2020, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2020.107242>.
- [49] A. C. Vinayaka, M. Golabi, T. L. Q. Than, A. Wolff, and D. D. Bang, 'Point-of-care diagnosis of invasive non-typhoidal *Salmonella enterica* in bloodstream infections using immunomagnetic capture and loop-mediated isothermal amplification', *N Biotechnol*, vol. 66, pp. 1–7, 2022, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nbt.2021.08.003>.
- [50] W. Zhou, R. Wu, S. Duraiswamy, W. Wang, L. Zhu, and Z. Wang, 'Development of microfluidic cartridge for culture-free detection of *Staphylococcus aureus* in blood', *Journal of Micromechanics and Microengineering*, vol. 31, no. 5, p. 55012, 2021, doi: 10.1088/1361-6439/abf32f.
- [51] Y.-L. Fang *et al.*, 'An integrated microfluidic system for early detection of sepsis-inducing bacteria', *Lab Chip*, vol. 21, no. 1, pp. 113–121, 2021, doi: 10.1039/D0LC00966K.
- [52] H. Yan *et al.*, 'Multiplex detection of bacteria on an integrated centrifugal disk using bead-beating lysis and loop-mediated amplification', *Sci Rep*, vol. 7, no. 1, p. 1460, 2017, doi: 10.1038/s41598-017-01415-x.
- [53] A. Perebikovskiy *et al.*, 'Rapid sample preparation for detection of antibiotic resistance on a microfluidic disc platform', *Lab Chip*, vol. 21, no. 3, pp. 534–545, 2021, doi: 10.1039/D0LC00838A.

- [54] H. Lu *et al.*, 'Rapid additive-free bacteria lysis using traveling surface acoustic waves in microfluidic channels', *Lab Chip*, vol. 19, no. 24, pp. 4064–4070, 2019, doi: 10.1039/C9LC00656G.
- [55] Y.-J. Lo and U. Lei, 'A Continuous Flow-through Microfluidic Device for Electrical Lysis of Cells', *Micromachines*, vol. 10, no. 4, 2019. doi: 10.3390/mi10040247.
- [56] M. Geissler *et al.*, 'Centrifugal microfluidic lab-on-a-chip system with automated sample lysis, DNA amplification and microarray hybridization for identification of enterohemorrhagic *Escherichia coli* culture isolates', *Analyst*, vol. 145, no. 21, pp. 6831–6845, 2020, doi: 10.1039/D0AN01232G.
- [57] A. Burklund, J. D. Petryk, P. J. Hoopes, and J. X. J. Zhang, 'Microfluidic enrichment of bacteria coupled to contact-free lysis on a magnetic polymer surface for downstream molecular detection', *Biomicrofluidics*, vol. 14, no. 3, p. 34115, May 2020, doi: 10.1063/5.0011908.
- [58] Y. Liu *et al.*, 'The Development of an Effective Bacterial Single-Cell Lysis Method Suitable for Whole Genome Amplification in Microfluidic Platforms', *Micromachines (Basel)*, vol. 9, no. 8, Jul. 2018, doi: 10.3390/M19080367.
- [59] R. Fradique, A. M. Azevedo, V. Chu, J. P. Conde, and M. R. Aires-Barros, 'Microfluidic platform for rapid screening of bacterial cell lysis', *J Chromatogr A*, vol. 1610, p. 460539, Jan. 2020, doi: 10.1016/J.CHROMA.2019.460539.
- [60] A. M. Kaba *et al.*, 'Cavitation-microstreaming-based lysis and DNA extraction using a laser-machined polycarbonate microfluidic chip', *Sens Actuators B Chem*, vol. 346, p. 130511, 2021, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.snb.2021.130511>.
- [61] A. Shamloo and M. Hassani-Gangaraj, 'Investigating the effect of reagent parameters on the efficiency of cell lysis within droplets', *Physics of Fluids*, vol. 32, no. 6, p. 62002, Jun. 2020, doi: 10.1063/5.0009840.
- [62] Y.-D. Ma, Y.-S. Chen, and G.-B. Lee, 'An integrated self-driven microfluidic device for rapid detection of the influenza A (H1N1) virus by reverse transcription loop-mediated isothermal amplification', *Sens Actuators B Chem*, vol. 296, p. 126647, 2019, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.snb.2019.126647>.
- [63] J. Berger *et al.*, 'Portable Pathogen Diagnostics Using Microfluidic Cartridges Made from Continuous Liquid Interface Production Additive Manufacturing',

- Anal Chem*, vol. 93, no. 29, pp. 10048–10055, Jul. 2021, doi: 10.1021/acs.analchem.1c00654.
- [64] R. Zhang, H.-Q. Gong, X. Zeng, C. Lou, and C. Sze, 'A microfluidic liquid phase nucleic acid purification chip to selectively isolate DNA or RNA from low copy/single bacterial cells in minute sample volume followed by direct on-chip quantitative PCR assay', *Anal Chem*, vol. 85, no. 3, pp. 1484–1491, 2013.
- [65] S. R. Jangam, A. K. Agarwal, K. Sur, and D. M. Kelso, 'A point-of-care PCR test for HIV-1 detection in resource-limited settings', *Biosens Bioelectron*, vol. 42, pp. 69–75, 2013, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bios.2012.10.024>.
- [66] J. F. C. Loo *et al.*, 'Sample-to-answer on molecular diagnosis of bacterial infection using integrated lab-on-a-disc', *Biosens Bioelectron*, vol. 93, pp. 212–219, Jul. 2017, doi: 10.1016/J.BIOS.2016.09.001.
- [67] H. Lee, C. Park, W. Na, K. H. Park, and S. Shin, 'Precision cell-free DNA extraction for liquid biopsy by integrated microfluidics', *NPJ Precis Oncol*, vol. 4, no. 1, p. 3, 2020, doi: 10.1038/s41698-019-0107-0.
- [68] N. Li, Y. Lu, J. Cheng, and Y. Xu, 'A self-contained and fully integrated fluidic cassette system for multiplex nucleic acid detection of bacteriuria', *Lab Chip*, vol. 20, no. 2, pp. 384–393, 2020, doi: 10.1039/C9LC00994A.
- [69] Y. Wang, W. Qi, L. Wang, J. Lin, and Y. Liu, 'Magnetic Bead Chain-Based Continuous-Flow DNA Extraction for Microfluidic PCR Detection of Salmonella', *Micromachines (Basel)*, vol. 12, no. 4, p. 384, Apr. 2021, doi: 10.3390/mi12040384.
- [70] L. Magro *et al.*, 'Paper microfluidics for nucleic acid amplification testing (NAAT) of infectious diseases', *Lab Chip*, vol. 17, no. 14, pp. 2347–2371, 2017.
- [71] B. P. Sullivan, A. T. Bender, D. N. Ngyuen, J. Y. Zhang, and J. D. Posner, 'Nucleic acid sample preparation from whole blood in a paper microfluidic device using isotachopheresis', *Journal of Chromatography B*, vol. 1163, p. 122494, 2021, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jchromb.2020.122494>.
- [72] D. L. House, C. H. Chon, C. B. Creech, E. P. Skaar, and D. Li, 'Miniature on-chip detection of unpurified methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) DNA using real-time PCR.', *J Biotechnol*, vol. 146, no. 3, pp. 93–99, 2010, doi: 10.1016/j.jbiotec.2009.12.013.

- [73] C. J. Easley *et al.*, 'A fully integrated microfluidic genetic analysis system with sample-in-answer-out capability', 2006. Accessed: Feb. 05, 2021. [Online]. Available: www.pnas.org/cgi/doi/10.1073/pnas.0604663103
- [74] B. T. Chia, X. Yang, M. Cheng, and Y. Yang, 'A DNA-extraction and polymerase-chain-reaction microchip using magnetic beads and thermo-pneumatic valves', in *2010 IEEE 23rd International Conference on Micro Electro Mechanical Systems (MEMS)*, 2010, pp. 967–970. doi: 10.1109/MEMSYS.2010.5442369.
- [75] X. Fang, Y. Liu, J. Kong, and X. Jiang, 'Loop-mediated isothermal amplification integrated on microfluidic chips for point-of-care quantitative detection of pathogens', *Anal Chem*, vol. 82, no. 7, pp. 3002–3006, Apr. 2010, doi: 10.1021/ac1000652.
- [76] L. Wan *et al.*, 'A digital microfluidic system for loop-mediated isothermal amplification and sequence specific pathogen detection', *Sci Rep*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 1–11, Dec. 2017, doi: 10.1038/s41598-017-14698-x.
- [77] K. Sato *et al.*, 'Microbead-based rolling circle amplification in a microchip for sensitive DNA detection', *Lab Chip*, vol. 10, no. 10, pp. 1262–1266, May 2010, doi: 10.1039/B927460J.
- [78] T. A. Brown, *Gene cloning and DNA analysis: an introduction /*, Seventh edition. 2016. Accessed: Jan. 25, 2022. [Online]. Available: <http://books.google.com/books?id=1AvyrJOYStkC%5Cnpapers2://publication/uuid/C4A4DA17-AEAD-4D7E-B87F-93170B2E7D2F>
- [79] S. Petralia and S. Conoci, 'PCR Technologies for Point of Care Testing: Progress and Perspectives', *ACS Sens*, vol. 2, no. 7, pp. 876–891, Jul. 2017, doi: 10.1021/acssensors.7b00299.
- [80] J. Y. Lee, J. J. Kim, and T. H. Park, 'Miniaturization of polymerase chain reaction', *Biotechnology and Bioprocess Engineering*, vol. 8, no. 4, pp. 213–220, 2003, doi: 10.1007/BF02942268.
- [81] Z. Li, R. Ju, S. Sekine, D. Zhang, S. Zhuang, and Y. Yamaguchi, 'All-in-one microfluidic device for on-site diagnosis of pathogens based on an integrated continuous flow PCR and electrophoresis biochip', *Lab Chip*, vol. 19, no. 16, pp. 2663–2668, 2019.

- [82] R. A. Mendoza-Gallegos, A. Rios, and J. L. Garcia-Cordero, 'An affordable and portable thermocycler for real-time PCR made of 3D-printed parts and off-the-shelf electronics', *Anal Chem*, vol. 90, no. 9, pp. 5563–5568, 2018.
- [83] A. R. Jafek, S. Harbertson, H. Brady, R. Samuel, and B. K. Gale, 'Instrumentation for xPCR Incorporating qPCR and HRMA', *Anal Chem*, vol. 90, no. 12, pp. 7190–7196, 2018.
- [84] E. Huang, Y. Wang, N. Yang, B. Shu, G. Zhang, and D. Liu, 'A fully automated microfluidic PCR-array system for rapid detection of multiple respiratory tract infection pathogens', *Anal Bioanal Chem*, vol. 413, no. 7, pp. 1787–1798, 2021, doi: 10.1007/s00216-021-03171-4.
- [85] T. Q. Hung, W. H. Chin, Y. Sun, A. Wolff, and D. D. Bang, 'A novel lab-on-chip platform with integrated solid phase PCR and Supercritical Angle Fluorescence (SAF) microlens array for highly sensitive and multiplexed pathogen detection', *Biosens Bioelectron*, vol. 90, pp. 217–223, 2017, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bios.2016.11.028>.
- [86] J. Yin *et al.*, 'Integrated microfluidic systems with sample preparation and nucleic acid amplification', *Lab Chip*, vol. 19, no. 17, pp. 2769–2785, 2019.
- [87] R. R. G. Soares, N. Madaboosi, and M. Nilsson, 'Rolling Circle Amplification in Integrated Microsystems: An Uncut Gem toward Massively Multiplexed Pathogen Diagnostics and Genotyping', *Acc Chem Res*, vol. 54, no. 21, pp. 3979–3990, Nov. 2021, doi: 10.1021/acs.accounts.1c00438.
- [88] J. Xu *et al.*, 'An aptasensor for staphylococcus aureus based on nicking enzyme amplification reaction and rolling circle amplification', *Anal Biochem*, vol. 549, pp. 136–142, 2018.
- [89] L. Xu *et al.*, 'Accurate MRSA identification through dual-functional aptamer and CRISPR-Cas12a assisted rolling circle amplification', *J Microbiol Methods*, vol. 173, p. 105917, 2020.
- [90] L. Becherer, N. Borst, M. Bakheit, S. Frischmann, R. Zengerle, and F. von Stetten, 'Loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LAMP)—review and classification of methods for sequence-specific detection', *Analytical Methods*, vol. 12, no. 6, pp. 717–746, 2020.

- [91] Q. Huang, S. Han, Y. Zhang, Y. Kou, X. Zhao, and G. Huang, 'Fast infectious diseases diagnostics based on microfluidic biochip system', *J Innov Opt Health Sci*, vol. 10, no. 02, p. 1650044, 2017.
- [92] M. Azizi, M. Zaferani, S. H. Cheong, and A. Abbaspourrad, 'Pathogenic Bacteria Detection Using RNA-Based Loop-Mediated Isothermal-Amplification-Assisted Nucleic Acid Amplification via Droplet Microfluidics', *ACS Sens*, vol. 4, no. 4, pp. 841–848, Apr. 2019, doi: 10.1021/acssensors.8b01206.
- [93] C. Chen, P. Liu, X. Zhao, W. Du, X. Feng, and B.-F. Liu, 'A self-contained microfluidic in-gel loop-mediated isothermal amplification for multiplexed pathogen detection', *Sens Actuators B Chem*, vol. 239, pp. 1–8, 2017.
- [94] X. Meng *et al.*, 'Rapid Detection of *mecA* and *femA* Genes by Loop-Mediated Isothermal Amplification in a Microfluidic System for Discrimination of Different Staphylococcal Species and Prediction of Methicillin Resistance', *Front Microbiol*, vol. 11, p. 1487, Jul. 2020, doi: 10.3389/fmicb.2020.01487.
- [95] H. Xu *et al.*, 'An ultraportable and versatile point-of-care DNA testing platform', *Sci Adv*, vol. 6, no. 17, p. eaaz7445, 2020.
- [96] Y. Bai *et al.*, 'Recombinase polymerase amplification integrated with microfluidics for nucleic acid testing at point of care', *Talanta*, vol. 240, p. 123209, 2022, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2022.123209>.
- [97] M. Georgoutsou-Spyridonos, M. Filippidou, G. D. Kaprou, D. C. Mastellos, S. Chatzandroulis, and A. Tserepi, 'Isothermal Recombinase Polymerase Amplification (RPA) of *E. coli* gDNA in Commercially Fabricated PCB-Based Microfluidic Platforms', *Micromachines*, vol. 12, no. 11, 2021. doi: 10.3390/mi12111387.
- [98] R. L. D. *et al.*, 'Detection of ESKAPE Bacterial Pathogens at the Point of Care Using Isothermal DNA-Based Assays in a Portable Degas-Actuated Microfluidic Diagnostic Assay Platform', *Appl Environ Microbiol*, vol. 83, no. 4, pp. e02449-16, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.1128/AEM.02449-16.
- [99] A. M. Ichzan *et al.*, 'Solid-phase recombinase polymerase amplification using an extremely low concentration of a solution primer for sensitive electrochemical detection of hepatitis B viral DNA', *Biosens Bioelectron*, vol. 179, p. 113065, 2021.

- [100] J. Chen *et al.*, 'Sensitive and rapid detection of pathogenic bacteria from urine samples using multiplex recombinase polymerase amplification', *Lab Chip*, vol. 18, no. 16, pp. 2441–2452, 2018.
- [101] E.-C. Yeh, C.-C. Fu, L. Hu, R. Thakur, J. Feng, and L. P. Lee, 'Self-powered integrated microfluidic point-of-care low-cost enabling (SIMPLE) chip', *Sci Adv*, vol. 3, no. 3, p. e1501645, 2017.
- [102] J. Yin *et al.*, 'A "sample-in-multiplex-digital-answer-out" chip for fast detection of pathogens', *Lab Chip*, vol. 20, no. 5, pp. 979–986, 2020.
- [103] M. Schulz *et al.*, 'Point-of-care testing system for digital single cell detection of MRSA directly from nasal swabs', *Lab Chip*, vol. 20, no. 14, pp. 2549–2561, 2020.
- [104] J. ZHANG *et al.*, 'Rapid Detection of *Bacillus cereus* Using Cross-Priming Amplification', *J Food Prot*, vol. 82, no. 10, pp. 1744–1750, Sep. 2019, doi: 10.4315/0362-028X.JFP-19-156.
- [105] X. Zhang, X.-J. Du, C. Guan, P. Li, W.-J. Zheng, and S. Wang, 'Detection of *Vibrio cholerae* by isothermal cross-priming amplification combined with nucleic acid detection strip analysis', *Mol Cell Probes*, vol. 29, no. 4, pp. 208–214, 2015.
- [106] T. N. T. Dao, E. Y. Lee, B. Koo, C. E. Jin, T. Y. Lee, and Y. Shin, 'A microfluidic enrichment platform with a recombinase polymerase amplification sensor for pathogen diagnosis', *Anal Biochem*, vol. 544, pp. 87–92, 2018, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ab.2017.12.030>.
- [107] G. Xu *et al.*, 'Cross priming amplification: mechanism and optimization for isothermal DNA amplification', *Sci Rep*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 1–7, 2012.
- [108] F. Shen, E. K. Davydova, W. Du, J. E. Kreutz, O. Piepenburg, and R. F. Ismagilov, 'Digital Isothermal Quantification of Nucleic Acids via Simultaneous Chemical Initiation of Recombinase Polymerase Amplification Reactions on SlipChip', *Anal Chem*, vol. 83, no. 9, pp. 3533–3540, May 2011, doi: 10.1021/ac200247e.
- [109] K. Boissinot *et al.*, 'Real-time monitoring of bead-based DNA hybridization in a microfluidic system: study of amplicon hybridization behavior on solid supports', *Analyst*, vol. 146, no. 13, pp. 4226–4234, Jun. 2021, doi: 10.1039/D1AN00394A.

- [110] A. Ganguli *et al.*, 'Hands-free smartphone-based diagnostics for simultaneous detection of Zika, Chikungunya, and Dengue at point-of-care', *Biomed Microdevices*, vol. 19, no. 4, p. 73, 2017, doi: 10.1007/s10544-017-0209-9.
- [111] A. Sayad, F. Ibrahim, S. Mukim Uddin, J. Cho, M. Madou, and K. L. Thong, 'A microdevice for rapid, monoplex and colorimetric detection of foodborne pathogens using a centrifugal microfluidic platform', *Biosens Bioelectron*, vol. 100, pp. 96–104, 2018, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bios.2017.08.060>.
- [112] B. H. Park *et al.*, 'An integrated rotary microfluidic system with DNA extraction, loop-mediated isothermal amplification, and lateral flow strip based detection for point-of-care pathogen diagnostics', *Biosens Bioelectron*, vol. 91, pp. 334–340, 2017, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bios.2016.11.063>.
- [113] K. Yin *et al.*, 'Multiplexed colorimetric detection of SARS-CoV-2 and other pathogens in wastewater on a 3D printed integrated microfluidic chip', *Sens Actuators B Chem*, vol. 344, p. 130242, 2021, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.snb.2021.130242>.
- [114] M. Safavieh, M. U. Ahmed, E. Sokullu, A. Ng, L. Braescu, and M. Zourob, 'A simple cassette as point-of-care diagnostic device for naked-eye colorimetric bacteria detection', *Analyst*, vol. 139, no. 2, pp. 482–487, 2014.
- [115] P.-X. Yuan, S.-Y. Deng, C.-Y. Zheng, S. Cosnier, and D. Shan, 'In situ formed copper nanoparticles templated by TdT-mediated DNA for enhanced SPR sensor-based DNA assay', *Biosens Bioelectron*, vol. 97, pp. 1–7, 2017, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bios.2017.05.033>.
- [116] B. Nasser, N. Soleimani, N. Rabiee, A. Kalbasi, M. Karimi, and M. R. Hamblin, 'Point-of-care microfluidic devices for pathogen detection', *Biosens Bioelectron*, vol. 117, pp. 112–128, 2018, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bios.2018.05.050>.
- [117] S.-R. Hong, H.-D. Jeong, and S. Hong, 'QCM DNA biosensor for the diagnosis of a fish pathogenic virus VHSV', *Talanta*, vol. 82, no. 3, pp. 899–903, 2010, doi: 10.1016/j.talanta.2010.04.065.
- [118] O. Pashchenko, T. Shelby, T. Banerjee, and S. Santra, 'A Comparison of Optical, Electrochemical, Magnetic, and Colorimetric Point-of-Care Biosensors for Infectious Disease Diagnosis', *ACS Infect Dis*, vol. 4, no. 8, pp. 1162–1178, Aug. 2018, doi: 10.1021/acsinfecdis.8b00023.

- [119] A. S. Rossney, C. M. Herra, G. I. Brennan, P. M. Morgan, and B. O'Connell, 'Evaluation of the Xpert methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) assay using the GeneXpert real-time PCR platform for rapid detection of MRSA from screening specimens', *J Clin Microbiol*, vol. 46, no. 10, pp. 3285–3290, Oct. 2008, doi: 10.1128/JCM.02487-07.
- [120] 'The BioFire® FilmArray® Respiratory Panel 2 plus (RP2plus) - Search'. http://onbase.visole.net/base/FilmArray_Respiratory_Panel_2_plus_Info_Sheet_-2020-01-21-16-50-58.pdf (accessed Jan. 20, 2022).
- [121] 'BioFire® COVID-19 Test Master Table of Contents - Search'. <https://cacmap.fda.gov/media/136353/download> (accessed Jan. 20, 2022).
- [122] M.-J. Jian *et al.*, 'Clinical Comparison of Three Sample-to-Answer Systems for Detecting SARS-CoV-2 in B.1.1.7 Lineage Emergence', *Infect Drug Resist*, vol. 14, pp. 3255–3261, Aug. 2021, doi: 10.2147/IDR.S328327.
- [123] L. Chen, Y. Tian, S. Chen, and O. Liesenfeld, 'Performance of the Cobas(®) Influenza A/B Assay for Rapid Pcr-Based Detection of Influenza Compared to Prodesse ProFlu+ and Viral Culture', *Eur J Microbiol Immunol (Bp)*, vol. 5, no. 4, pp. 236–245, Dec. 2015, doi: 10.1556/1886.2015.00046.
- [124] 'Lucira-HCP-Instructions-For-Use-IFU.pdf (netdna-ssl.com) - Search'. <https://2nyvwd1bf4ct4f787m3leist-wpengine.netdna-ssl.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/11/Lucira-HCP-Instructions-For-Use-IFU.pdf> (accessed Jan. 20, 2022).
- [125] 'US10724079B2 - Colorimetric detection of nucleic acid amplification - Google Patents'. <https://patents.google.com/patent/US10724079B2/en> (accessed Jan. 20, 2022).
- [126] H. Harpaldas, S. Arumugam, C. Campillo Rodriguez, B. A. Kumar, V. Shi, and S. K. Sia, 'Point-of-care diagnostics: recent developments in a pandemic age', *Lab Chip*, vol. 21, no. 23, pp. 4517–4548, 2021, doi: 10.1039/D1LC00627D.
- [127] 'POCT 3.0 英文 (ufileos.com) - Search'. http://cetest01.us-ca.ufileos.com/100001_2006075053/Brochure_EasyNAT_System_20211223.pdf (accessed Jan. 20, 2022).
- [128] L. Cui *et al.*, 'Detection of severe fever with thrombocytopenia syndrome virus by reverse transcription-cross-priming amplification coupled with vertical flow

- visualization', *J Clin Microbiol*, vol. 50, no. 12, pp. 3881–3885, Dec. 2012, doi: 10.1128/JCM.01931-12.
- [129] J. Lu *et al.*, 'Automatic system for high-throughput and high-sensitivity diagnosis of SARS-CoV-2', *Bioprocess Biosyst Eng*, 2022, doi: 10.1007/s00449-021-02674-9.
- [130] D. Liu *et al.*, 'A microfluidic-integrated lateral flow recombinase polymerase amplification (MI-IF-RPA) assay for rapid COVID-19 detection', *Lab Chip*, vol. 21, no. 10, pp. 2019–2026, 2021, doi: 10.1039/D0LC01222J.
- [131] F. Rendong *et al.*, 'Cross-Priming Amplification for Rapid Detection of Mycobacterium tuberculosis in Sputum Specimens ', *J Clin Microbiol*, vol. 47, no. 3, pp. 845–847, Mar. 2009, doi: 10.1128/JCM.01528-08.
- [132] K. Mitsakakis, V. D'Acremont, S. Hin, F. von Stetten, and R. Zengerle, 'Diagnostic tools for tackling febrile illness and enhancing patient management', *Microelectron Eng*, vol. 201, pp. 26–59, Dec. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.mee.2018.10.001.
- [133] J. Hou, H. Wu, X. Zeng, H. Rao, and P. Zhao, 'Clinical evaluation of the loop-mediated isothermal amplification assay for the detection of common lower respiratory pathogens in patients with respiratory symptoms', *Medicine*, vol. 97, no. 51, pp. e13660–e13660, Dec. 2018, doi: 10.1097/MD.00000000000013660.
- [134] 'Biochip molecular biology analyzer - CapitalBio RTisoChip™ - CapitalBio Technology - with microfluidic chips'. <https://www.medicaexpo.com/prod/capitalbio-technology/product-121552-842657.html> (accessed Jan. 20, 2022).
- [135] J. Engberg, L. K. Vejrum, T. V. Madsen, and X. C. Nielsen, 'Verification of analytical bacterial spectrum of QIAstat-Dx® GI V2 and Novodiag® Bacterial GE+ V2-0 diagnostic panels', *Journal of Antimicrobial Chemotherapy*, vol. 76, no. Supplement_3, pp. iii50–iii57, Sep. 2021, doi: 10.1093/jac/dkab242.
- [136] D. Girlich *et al.*, 'Evaluation of the Novodiag CarbaR+, a Novel Integrated Sample to Result Platform for the Multiplex Qualitative Detection of Carbapenem and Colistin Resistance Markers', *Microb Drug Resist*, vol. 27, no. 2, pp. 170–178, Feb. 2021, doi: 10.1089/MDR.2020.0132.
- [137] P. Jokela *et al.*, 'SARS-CoV-2 sample-to-answer nucleic acid testing in a tertiary care emergency department: evaluation and utility', *Journal of Clinical*

- Virology*, vol. 131, p. 104614, 2020, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcv.2020.104614>.
- [138] 'The Idylla™ SARS-CoV-2 Test - Search'. <https://www.biocartis.com/sites/default/files/137531-SARS-Cov2-IVD-Leaflet-A5-pages.pdf> (accessed Jan. 20, 2022).
- [139] C. H. van den Kieboom *et al.*, 'Assessment of a molecular diagnostic platform for integrated isolation and quantification of mRNA in whole blood', *European Journal of Clinical Microbiology & Infectious Diseases*, vol. 34, no. 11, pp. 2209–2212, 2015, doi: 10.1007/s10096-015-2470-2.
- [140] C. de Luca *et al.*, 'Evaluation of a fully closed real time PCR platform for the detection of SARS-CoV-2 in nasopharyngeal swabs: a pilot study', *J Clin Pathol*, p. jclinpath-2021-207516, Apr. 2021, doi: 10.1136/jclinpath-2021-207516.
- [141] 'ePlex Blood Culture Identification Fungal Pathogen (BCID-FP) Panel - Search'. https://www.accessdata.fda.gov/cdrh_docs/reviews/K182690.pdf (accessed Jan. 20, 2022).
- [142] B. B. W. *et al.*, 'Preliminary Evaluation of the Research-Use-Only (RUO) iCubate iC-GPC Assay for Identification of Select Gram-Positive Bacteria and Their Resistance Determinants in Blood Culture Broths', *J Clin Microbiol*, vol. 53, no. 12, pp. 3931–3934, Dec. 2015, doi: 10.1128/JCM.01934-15.
- [143] 'iCubate iC-GPC Assay for use on the iC-System FDA - Search'. https://www.accessdata.fda.gov/cdrh_docs/pdf16/K163390.pdf (accessed Jan. 20, 2022).
- [144] 'BD SARS-CoV-2/Flu for BD MAX™ System FDA - Search'. <https://www.fda.gov/media/145927/download> (accessed Jan. 20, 2022).
- [145] J. E. Mortensen, C. Ventrola, S. Hanna, and A. Walter, 'Comparison of time-motion analysis of conventional stool culture and the BD MAX™ Enteric Bacterial Panel (EBP)', *BMC Clin Pathol*, vol. 15, no. 1, p. 9, 2015, doi: 10.1186/s12907-015-0010-8.
- [146] 'LIAISON MDX ANALYZER - DIASORIN MOLECULAR LLC - Coronavirus Contracts - ProPublica'. <https://projects.propublica.org/coronavirus-contracts/contracts/36C25020P1355> (accessed Jan. 20, 2022).

- [147] 'Patent Application for Devices and methods for molecular diagnostic testing Patent Application'.
<https://pdfpiw.uspto.gov/.piw?PageNum=0&docid=10052629&IDKey=9B96E763FA9D%0D%0A&HomeUrl=http%3A%2F%2Fpatft.uspto.gov%2Fnetathtml%2FFPTO%2Fpatimg.htm> (accessed Jan. 20, 2022).
- [148] 'Molecular Diagnostics Company | Visby Medical'.
<https://www.visbymedical.com/> (accessed Jan. 20, 2022).
- [149] B. M. Katzman, A. M. Wockenfus, B. R. Kelley, B. S. Karon, and L. J. Donato, 'Evaluation of the Visby medical COVID-19 point of care nucleic acid amplification test', *Clin Biochem*, 2021, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clinbiochem.2021.11.007>.
- [150] S. R. Morris *et al.*, 'Performance of a single-use, rapid, point-of-care PCR device for the detection of *Neisseria gonorrhoeae*, *Chlamydia trachomatis*, and *Trichomonas vaginalis*: a cross-sectional study', *Lancet Infect Dis*, vol. 21, no. 5, pp. 668–676, May 2021, doi: [10.1016/S1473-3099\(20\)30734-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1473-3099(20)30734-9).
- [151] E. Tacconelli *et al.*, 'Discovery, research, and development of new antibiotics: the WHO priority list of antibiotic-resistant bacteria and tuberculosis', *Lancet Infect Dis*, vol. 18, no. 3, pp. 318–327, Mar. 2018, doi: [10.1016/S1473-3099\(17\)30753-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1473-3099(17)30753-3).
- [152] J. N. Pendleton, S. P. Gorman, and B. F. Gilmore, 'Clinical relevance of the ESKAPE pathogens', <https://doi.org/10.1586/eri.13.12>, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 297–308, 2014, doi: [10.1586/ERI.13.12](https://doi.org/10.1586/ERI.13.12).
- [153] O. Ayobami, S. Brinkwirth, T. Eckmanns, and R. Markwart, 'Antibiotic resistance in hospital-acquired ESKAPE-E infections in low- and lower-middle-income countries: a systematic review and meta-analysis', *Emerg Microbes Infect*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 443–451, 2022, doi: [10.1080/22221751.2022.2030196](https://doi.org/10.1080/22221751.2022.2030196).
- [154] A. Mai-Prochnow, M. Clauson, J. Hong, and A. B. Murphy, 'Gram positive and Gram negative bacteria differ in their sensitivity to cold plasma', *Scientific Reports 2016 6:1*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 1–11, Dec. 2016, doi: [10.1038/srep38610](https://doi.org/10.1038/srep38610).
- [155] K. D. Young, 'Bacterial Cell Wall', *eLS*, Apr. 2010, doi: [10.1002/9780470015902.A0000297.PUB2](https://doi.org/10.1002/9780470015902.A0000297.PUB2).

- [156] M. Zarei, 'Infectious pathogens meet point-of-care diagnostics', *Biosens Bioelectron*, vol. 106, pp. 193–203, May 2018, doi: 10.1016/J.BIOS.2018.02.007.
- [157] 'Chapter 4 Fluid mechanics', *Membrane Science and Technology*, vol. 10, no. C, pp. 87–109, 2004, doi: 10.1016/S0927-5193(04)80021-4.
- [158] W. E. Svendsen, 'Basic Microfluidics Theory', in *Lab-on-a-Chip Devices and Micro-Total Analysis Systems*, Springer International Publishing, 2015, pp. 17–26. doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-08687-3_2.
- [159] B. Kirby, *Micro- and Nanoscale Fluid Mechanics*. Cambridge University Press, 2010. doi: 10.1017/cbo9780511760723.
- [160] E. Yildiz-Ozturk and O. Yesil-Celiktas, 'Diffusion phenomena of cells and biomolecules in microfluidic devices', *Biomicrofluidics*, vol. 9, no. 5, Sep. 2015, doi: 10.1063/1.4923263.
- [161] A. D. Stroock, S. K. W. Dertinger, A. Ajdari, I. Mezić, H. A. Stone, and G. M. Whitesides, 'Chaotic mixer for microchannels', *Science*, vol. 295, no. 5555, pp. 647–651, Jan. 2002, doi: 10.1126/SCIENCE.1066238.
- [162] B. Adhi Prabowo, P. D. Cabral, P. Freitas, E. Fernandes, and E. The, 'The Challenges of Developing Biosensors for Clinical Assessment: A Review Challenges of Developing Biosensors for Clinical Assessment: A Review', 2021, doi: 10.3390/chemosensors9110299.
- [163] 'Chapter 6 Sensitivity and limit of detection', *Techniques and Instrumentation in Analytical Chemistry*, vol. 1, no. C, pp. 143–156, Jan. 1978, doi: 10.1016/S0167-9244(08)70050-7.
- [164] J. G. Calvert, 'Glossary of atmospheric chemistry terms', *Pure and Applied Chemistry*, vol. 62, no. 11, pp. 2167–2219, Jan. 1990, doi: 10.1351/PAC199062112167/MACHINEREADABLECITATION/RIS.
- [165] I. F. Pinto *et al.*, 'Optical biosensing in microfluidics using nanoporous microbeads and amorphous silicon thin-film photodiodes: quantitative analysis of molecular recognition and signal transduction', *Journal of Micromechanics and Microengineering*, vol. 28, no. 9, p. 94004, 2018, doi: 10.1088/1361-6439/aac66c.
- [166] a. D. Mc Naught and a Wilkinson, 'Compendium of Chemical Terminology-Gold Book', *Iupac*, p. 1670, 2012, doi: 10.1351/goldbook.

- [167] D. A. Armbruster and T. Pry, 'Limit of blank, limit of detection and limit of quantitation', *Clin Biochem Rev*, vol. 29 Suppl 1, no. Suppl 1, pp. S49–S52, Aug. 2008, [Online]. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/18852857>
- [168] 'Q2(R1) Validation of Analytical Procedures: Text and Methodology Guidance for Industry', 2005, Accessed: Aug. 23, 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.fda.gov/vaccines-blood-biologics/guidance-compliance-regulatory-information-biologics/biologics-guidances>
- [169] L. A. Currie, 'Nomenclature in evaluation of analytical methods including detection and quantification capabilities: (IUPAC Recommendations 1995)', *Anal Chim Acta*, vol. 391, no. 2, pp. 105–126, May 1999, doi: 10.1016/S0003-2670(99)00104-X.
- [170] I. F. Pinto *et al.*, 'The application of microbeads to microfluidic systems for enhanced detection and purification of biomolecules', *Methods*, vol. 116, pp. 112–124, 2017, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ymeth.2016.12.005>.
- [171] C. R. F. Caneira *et al.*, 'Development of a rapid bead-based microfluidic platform for DNA hybridization using single- and multi-mode interactions for probe immobilization', *Sens Actuators B Chem*, vol. 286, pp. 328–336, May 2019, doi: 10.1016/J.SNB.2019.01.133.
- [172] I. F. Pinto, D. R. Santos, C. R. F. Caneira, R. R. G. Soares, V. Chu, and J. P. Conde, 'Quantitative analysis of optical transduction in microfluidic biosensing platforms: Nanoporous microbeads coupled with thin-film photodiodes', in *2018 IEEE Micro Electro Mechanical Systems (MEMS)*, 2018, pp. 278–281. doi: 10.1109/MEMSYS.2018.8346539.
- [173] C. Caneira, 'Bead-Based Microfluidic System for DNA and RNA detection', Instituto Superior Técnico, 2015.
- [174] A. A. Saeed, J. L. A. Sánchez, C. K. O'Sullivan, and M. N. Abbas, 'DNA biosensors based on gold nanoparticles-modified graphene oxide for the detection of breast cancer biomarkers for early diagnosis', *Bioelectrochemistry*, vol. 118, pp. 91–99, Dec. 2017, doi: 10.1016/J.BIOELECHEM.2017.07.002.
- [175] X. Fang, Y. Liu, J. Kong, and X. Jiang, 'Loop-mediated isothermal amplification integrated on microfluidic chips for point-of-care quantitative detection of pathogens', *Anal Chem*, vol. 82, no. 7, pp. 3002–3006, Apr. 2010, doi: 10.1021/AC1000652.

- [176] N. v. Zaytseva, V. N. Goral, R. A. Montagna, and A. J. Baeumner, 'Development of a microfluidic biosensor module for pathogen detection', *Lab Chip*, vol. 5, no. 8, pp. 805–811, 2005, doi: 10.1039/B503856A.
- [177] M. Khater, A. de la Escosura-Muñiz, and A. Merkoçi, 'Biosensors for plant pathogen detection', *Biosens Bioelectron*, vol. 93, pp. 72–86, Jul. 2017, doi: 10.1016/J.BIOS.2016.09.091.
- [178] P. Arora, A. Sindhu, N. Dilbaghi, and A. Chaudhury, 'Biosensors as innovative tools for the detection of food borne pathogens', *Biosens Bioelectron*, vol. 28, no. 1, pp. 1–12, Oct. 2011, doi: 10.1016/J.BIOS.2011.06.002.
- [179] M. Khan, A. R. Khan, J. H. Shin, and S. Y. Park, 'A liquid-crystal-based DNA biosensor for pathogen detection', *Scientific Reports 2016 6:1*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 1–12, Mar. 2016, doi: 10.1038/srep22676.
- [180] R. Z. Hao *et al.*, 'DNA probe functionalized QCM biosensor based on gold nanoparticle amplification for *Bacillus anthracis* detection', *Biosens Bioelectron*, vol. 26, no. 8, pp. 3398–3404, Apr. 2011, doi: 10.1016/J.BIOS.2011.01.010.
- [181] U. Bora, U. Bora, A. Sett, and D. Singh, 'Nucleic Acid Based Biosensors for Clinical Applications', *Biosensors Journal*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 1–8, Nov. 2013, doi: 10.4172/2090-4967.1000104.
- [182] K. Kerman, M. Kobayashi, and E. Tamiya, 'Recent trends in electrochemical DNA biosensor technology', *Meas Sci Technol*, vol. 15, no. 2, p. R1, Dec. 2003, doi: 10.1088/0957-0233/15/2/R01.
- [183] A. T. Woolley, 'ABC Spotlight on emerging microRNA analysis methods', *Anal Bioanal Chem*, vol. 407, no. 22, Jun. 2015, doi: 10.1007/S00216-015-8808-X.
- [184] J. Wang, K. Morabito, J. X. Tang, and A. Tripathi, 'Microfluidic platform for isolating nucleic acid targets using sequence specific hybridization', *Biomicrofluidics*, vol. 7, no. 4, Jul. 2013, doi: 10.1063/1.4816943.
- [185] C. H. Wang, K. Y. Lien, J. J. Wu, and G. bin Lee, 'A magnetic bead-based assay for the rapid detection of methicillin -resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* by using a microfluidic system with integrated loop-mediated isothermal amplification', *Lab Chip*, vol. 11, no. 8, pp. 1521–1531, Apr. 2011, doi: 10.1039/C0LC00430H.

- [186] K. Du *et al.*, 'Multiplexed efficient on-chip sample preparation and sensitive amplification-free detection of Ebola virus', *Biosens Bioelectron*, vol. 91, pp. 489–496, May 2017, doi: 10.1016/J.BIOS.2016.12.071.
- [187] J. Kim, J. Heo, and R. M. Crooks, 'Hybridization of DNA to bead-immobilized probes confined within a microfluidic channel', *Langmuir*, vol. 22, no. 24, pp. 10130–10134, Nov. 2006, doi: 10.1021/LA0616956.
- [188] R. D. Sochol, B. P. Casavant, M. E. Dueck, L. P. Lee, and L. Lin, 'A dynamic bead-based microarray for parallel DNA detection', *Journal of Micromechanics and Microengineering*, vol. 21, no. 5, p. 054019, Apr. 2011, doi: 10.1088/0960-1317/21/5/054019.
- [189] W. Na, D. Nam, H. Lee, and S. Shin, 'Rapid molecular diagnosis of infectious viruses in microfluidics using DNA hydrogel formation', *Biosens Bioelectron*, vol. 108, p. 9, Jun. 2018, doi: 10.1016/J.BIOS.2018.02.040.
- [190] D. N. Kim, Y. Lee, and W. G. Koh, 'Fabrication of microfluidic devices incorporating bead-based reaction and microarray-based detection system for enzymatic assay', *Sens Actuators B Chem*, vol. 137, no. 1, pp. 305–312, Mar. 2009, doi: 10.1016/J.SNB.2008.12.042.
- [191] H. Zhang, L. Liu, X. Fu, and Z. Zhu, 'Microfluidic beads-based immunosensor for sensitive detection of cancer biomarker proteins using multienzyme-nanoparticle amplification and quantum dots labels', *Biosens Bioelectron*, vol. 42, no. 1, pp. 23–30, Apr. 2013, doi: 10.1016/J.BIOS.2012.10.076.
- [192] G. Shao *et al.*, 'Design, fabrication and test of a pneumatically controlled, renewable, microfluidic bead trapping device for sequential injection analysis applications', *Analyst*, vol. 141, no. 1, pp. 206–215, Jan. 2016, doi: 10.1039/C5AN01475A.
- [193] R. R. G. Soares *et al.*, 'Multiplexed microfluidic fluorescence immunoassay with photodiode array signal acquisition for sub-minute and point-of-need detection of mycotoxins', *Lab Chip*, vol. 18, no. 11, pp. 1569–1580, May 2018, doi: 10.1039/C8LC00259B.
- [194] J. A. Thompson and H. H. Bau, 'Porous bead-based microfluidic assay: theory and confocal microscope imaging', *Microfluidics and Nanofluidics 2011 12:1*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 625–637, Nov. 2011, doi: 10.1007/S10404-011-0904-4.

- [195] M. S. Shapiro, S. J. Haswell, G. J. Lye, and D. G. Bracewell, 'Design and characterization of a microfluidic packed bed system for protein breakthrough and dynamic binding capacity determination', *Biotechnol Prog*, vol. 25, no. 1, pp. 277–285, Jan. 2009, doi: 10.1002/BTPR.99.
- [196] I. F. Pinto *et al.*, 'A regenerable microfluidic device with integrated valves and thin-film photodiodes for rapid optimization of chromatography conditions', *Sens Actuators B Chem*, vol. 255, pp. 3636–3646, Feb. 2018, doi: 10.1016/J.SNB.2017.09.167.
- [197] B. H. Shadfan *et al.*, 'A multiplexable, microfluidic platform for the rapid quantitation of a biomarker panel for early ovarian cancer detection at the point-of-care', *Cancer Prev Res (Phila)*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 37–48, Jan. 2015, doi: 10.1158/1940-6207.CAPR-14-0248.
- [198] K. Sato *et al.*, 'Microbead-based rolling circle amplification in a microchip for sensitive DNA detection', *Lab Chip*, vol. 10, no. 10, pp. 1262–1266, 2010, doi: 10.1039/B927460J.
- [199] A. W. Peterson, R. J. Heaton, and R. M. Georgiadis, 'The effect of surface probe density on DNA hybridization', *Nucleic Acids Res*, vol. 29, no. 24, p. 5163, Dec. 2001, doi: 10.1093/NAR/29.24.5163.
- [200] C. R. F. Caneira, D. R. Santos, V. Chu, and J. P. Conde, 'Regenerable bead-based microfluidic device with integrated thin-film photodiodes for real-time monitoring of DNA detection', *Sens Actuators B Chem*, vol. 359, p. 131607, 2022, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.snb.2022.131607>.
- [201] C. R. F. Caneira, D. R. Santos, V. Chu, and J. P. Conde, 'Regenerable Bead-Based Microfluidic Device with integrated THIN-Film Photodiodes for Real Time Monitoring of DNA Detection', *Proc West Mark Ed Assoc Conf*, vol. 2, no. 13, 2018, doi: 10.3390/proceedings2130953.
- [202] Z. Fu, Y.-C. Lu, and J. J. Lai, 'Recent Advances in Biosensors for Nucleic Acid and Exosome Detection', *Chonnam Med J*, vol. 55, no. 2, p. 86, 2019, doi: 10.4068/CMJ.2019.55.2.86.
- [203] Y. Saylan, Ö. Erdem, S. Ünal, and A. Denizli, 'An Alternative Medical Diagnosis Method: Biosensors for Virus Detection', *Biosensors (Basel)*, vol. 9, no. 2, Jun. 2019, doi: 10.3390/BIOS9020065.

- [204] T. R. Kozel and A. R. Burnham-Marusich, 'Point-of-Care Testing for Infectious Diseases: Past, Present, and Future', *J Clin Microbiol*, vol. 55, no. 8, pp. 2313–2320, Aug. 2017, doi: 10.1128/JCM.00476-17.
- [205] R. Samson, G. R. Navale, and M. S. Dharne, 'Biosensors: frontiers in rapid detection of COVID-19', *3 Biotech*, vol. 10, no. 9, Sep. 2020, doi: 10.1007/S13205-020-02369-0.
- [206] D. L. House, C. H. Chon, C. B. Creech, E. P. Skaar, and D. Li, 'Miniature on-chip detection of unpurified methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) DNA using real-time PCR', *J Biotechnol*, vol. 146, no. 3, pp. 93–99, 2010, doi: 10.1016/J.JBIOTEC.2009.12.013.
- [207] C. J. Easley *et al.*, 'A fully integrated microfluidic genetic analysis system with sample-in–answer-out capability', *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, vol. 103, no. 51, pp. 19272 LP – 19277, Dec. 2006, doi: 10.1073/pnas.0604663103.
- [208] E. A. Oblath, W. H. Henley, J. P. Alarie, and J. M. Ramsey, 'A microfluidic chip integrating DNA extraction and real-time PCR for the detection of bacteria in saliva', *Lab Chip*, vol. 13, no. 7, pp. 1325–1332, Apr. 2013, doi: 10.1039/C3LC40961A.
- [209] B. S. Ferguson, S. F. Buchsbaum, J. S. Swensen, K. Hsieh, X. Lou, and H. T. Soh, 'Integrated Microfluidic Electrochemical DNA Sensor', *Anal Chem*, vol. 81, no. 15, pp. 6503–6508, Aug. 2009, doi: 10.1021/ac900923e.
- [210] T. S. Bronder, A. Poghossian, M. P. Jessing, M. Keusgen, and M. J. Schöning, 'Surface regeneration and reusability of label-free DNA biosensors based on weak polyelectrolyte-modified capacitive field-effect structures', *Biosens Bioelectron*, vol. 126, pp. 510–517, 2019, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bios.2018.11.019>.
- [211] S. Wang *et al.*, 'An automated microfluidic system for single-stranded DNA preparation and magnetic bead-based microarray analysis', *Biomicrofluidics*, vol. 9, no. 2, Mar. 2015, doi: 10.1063/1.4914024.
- [212] E. Y. Ariffin *et al.*, 'An ultrasensitive hollow-silica-based biosensor for pathogenic *Escherichia coli* DNA detection', *Anal Bioanal Chem*, vol. 410, no. 9, pp. 2363–2375, Mar. 2018, doi: 10.1007/S00216-018-0893-1.

- [213] J. A. Goode, J. V. H. Rushworth, and P. A. Millner, 'Biosensor Regeneration: A Review of Common Techniques and Outcomes', *Langmuir*, vol. 31, no. 23, pp. 6267–6276, Jun. 2015, doi: 10.1021/LA503533G.
- [214] N. v Sergeev, K. E. Herold, and A. Rasooly, 'Regulatory and Validation Issues for Biosensors and Related Bioanalytical Technologies', *Handbook of Biosensors and Biochips*. in Major Reference Works. Oct. 27, 2007. doi: doi:10.1002/9780470061565.hbb132.
- [215] I. F. Pinto *et al.*, 'High-Throughput Nanoliter-Scale Analysis and Optimization of Multimodal Chromatography for the Capture of Monoclonal Antibodies', *Anal Chem*, vol. 88, no. 16, pp. 7959–7967, Aug. 2016, doi: 10.1021/acs.analchem.6b00781.
- [216] X. Wang, H. J. Lim, and A. Son, 'Characterization of denaturation and renaturation of DNA for DNA hybridization', *Environ Health Toxicol*, vol. 29, pp. e2014007–e2014007, Sep. 2014, doi: 10.5620/eh.2014.29.e2014007.
- [217] R. Walczak, 'Fluorescence detection by miniaturized instrumentation based on non-cooled CCD minicamera and dedicated for lab-on-a-chip applications', *Biochip J*, vol. 5, no. 3, p. 271, 2011, doi: 10.1007/s13206-011-5312-z.
- [218] E. J. S. Bras, R. M. R. Pinto, V. Chu, P. Fernandes, and J. P. Conde, 'A Versatile and Fully Integrated Hand-Held Device for Microfluidic-Based Biosensing: A Case Study of Plant Health Biomarkers', *IEEE Sens J*, vol. 20, no. 23, pp. 14007–14015, Dec. 2020, doi: 10.1109/JSEN.2020.3007023.
- [219] D. Liu, Y. Zhu, N. Li, Y. Lu, J. Cheng, and Y. Xu, 'A portable microfluidic analyzer for integrated bacterial detection using visible loop-mediated amplification', *Sens Actuators B Chem*, vol. 310, p. 127834, 2020, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.snb.2020.127834>.
- [220] F. Costantini *et al.*, 'Fluorescent Label-Free Aptasensor Integrated in a Lab-on-Chip System for the Detection of Ochratoxin A in Beer and Wheat', *ACS Appl Bio Mater*, vol. 2, no. 12, pp. 5880–5887, Dec. 2019, doi: 10.1021/acsabm.9b00831.
- [221] U. H. Yildiz, P. Alagappan, and B. Liedberg, 'Naked Eye Detection of Lung Cancer Associated miRNA by Paper Based Biosensing Platform', *Anal Chem*, vol. 85, no. 2, pp. 820–824, Jan. 2013, doi: 10.1021/ac3034008.

- [222] J. P. Pursey, Y. Chen, E. Stulz, M. K. Park, and P. Kongsuphol, 'Microfluidic electrochemical multiplex detection of bladder cancer DNA markers', *Sens Actuators B Chem*, vol. 251, pp. 34–39, Nov. 2017, doi: 10.1016/J.SNB.2017.05.006.
- [223] R. R. G. Soares *et al.*, 'Silica bead-based microfluidic device with integrated photodiodes for the rapid capture and detection of rolling circle amplification products in the femtomolar range', *Biosens Bioelectron*, vol. 128, pp. 68–75, 2019, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bios.2018.12.004>.
- [224] L. Baseler, D. S. Chertow, K. M. Johnson, H. Feldmann, and D. M. Morens, 'The Pathogenesis of Ebola Virus Disease', *Annu Rev Pathol*, vol. 12, pp. 387–418, Jan. 2017, doi: 10.1146/ANNUREV-PATHOL-052016-100506.
- [225] J. K. Taubenberger and D. M. Morens, 'The pathology of influenza virus infections', *Annu Rev Pathol*, vol. 3, pp. 499–522, 2008, doi: 10.1146/ANNUREV.PATHMECHDIS.3.121806.154316.
- [226] R. Sanjuán, M. R. Nebot, N. Chirico, L. M. Mansky, and R. Belshaw, 'Viral mutation rates', *J Virol*, vol. 84, no. 19, pp. 9733–9748, Oct. 2010, doi: 10.1128/JVI.00694-10.
- [227] World Health Organization, 'Ebola virus disease', 2021. <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/ebola-virus-disease> (accessed Oct. 15, 2022).
- [228] World Health Organization, 'Influenza (Seasonal)', 2018. [https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/influenza-\(seasonal\)](https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/influenza-(seasonal)) (accessed Oct. 15, 2022).
- [229] S. M. Yoo and S. Y. Lee, 'Optical Biosensors for the Detection of Pathogenic Microorganisms', *Trends Biotechnol*, vol. 34, no. 1, pp. 7–25, Jan. 2016, doi: 10.1016/J.TIBTECH.2015.09.012.
- [230] M. L. Sin, K. E. Mach, P. K. Wong, and J. C. Liao, 'Advances and challenges in biosensor-based diagnosis of infectious diseases', *Expert Rev Mol Diagn*, vol. 14, no. 2, pp. 225–244, Mar. 2014, doi: 10.1586/14737159.2014.888313.
- [231] J. R. Wojciechowski *et al.*, 'Organic photodiodes for biosensor miniaturization', *Anal Chem*, vol. 81, no. 9, pp. 3455–3461, May 2009, doi: 10.1021/AC8027323.

- [232] U. Obahiagbon *et al.*, 'A compact, low-cost, quantitative and multiplexed fluorescence detection platform for point-of-care applications', *Biosens Bioelectron*, vol. 117, pp. 153–160, Oct. 2018, doi: 10.1016/J.BIOS.2018.04.002.
- [233] R. R. G. Soares *et al.*, 'Multiplexed microfluidic fluorescence immunoassay with photodiode array signal acquisition for sub-minute and point-of-need detection of mycotoxins', *Lab Chip*, vol. 18, no. 11, pp. 1569–1580, May 2018, doi: 10.1039/C8LC00259B.
- [234] A. C. Pimentel, D. M. F. Prazeres, V. Chu, and J. P. Conde, 'Fluorescence detection of DNA using an amorphous silicon p-i-n photodiode', *J Appl Phys*, vol. 104, no. 5, p. 054913, Sep. 2008, doi: 10.1063/1.2976343.
- [235] I. F. Pinto *et al.*, 'A regenerable microfluidic device with integrated valves and thin-film photodiodes for rapid optimization of chromatography conditions', *Sens Actuators B Chem*, vol. 255, pp. 3636–3646, Feb. 2018, doi: 10.1016/J.SNB.2017.09.167.
- [236] S. S. Modak, C. A. Barber, E. Geva, W. R. Abrams, D. Malamud, and Y. S. Y. Ongagna, 'Rapid Point-of-Care Isothermal Amplification Assay for the Detection of Malaria without Nucleic Acid Purification', *Infect Dis*, vol. 9, p. IDRT.S32162, Jan. 2016, doi: 10.4137/IDRT.S32162.
- [237] P. Craw and W. Balachandran, 'Isothermal nucleic acid amplification technologies for point-of-care diagnostics: a critical review', *Lab Chip*, vol. 12, no. 14, pp. 2469–2486, Jul. 2012, doi: 10.1039/C2LC40100B.
- [238] T. Conze *et al.*, 'Analysis of genes, transcripts, and proteins via DNA ligation', *Annu Rev Anal Chem (Palo Alto Calif)*, vol. 2, pp. 215–239, 2009, doi: 10.1146/ANNUREV-ANCHEM-060908-155239.
- [239] M. Fakruddin *et al.*, 'Nucleic acid amplification: Alternative methods of polymerase chain reaction', *J Pharm Bioallied Sci*, vol. 5, no. 4, p. 245, Oct. 2013, doi: 10.4103/0975-7406.120066.
- [240] A. R. Pavankumar, A. Engström, J. Liu, D. Herthnek, and M. Nilsson, 'Proficient Detection of Multi-Drug-Resistant Mycobacterium tuberculosis by Padlock Probes and Lateral Flow Nucleic Acid Biosensors', *Anal Chem*, vol. 88, no. 8, pp. 4277–4284, May 2016, doi: 10.1021/ACS.ANALCHEM.5B04312.

- [241] A. Mezger, C. Öhrmalm, D. Herthnek, J. Blomberg, and M. Nilsson, 'Detection of rotavirus using padlock probes and rolling circle amplification', *PLoS One*, vol. 9, no. 11, Nov. 2014, doi: 10.1371/JOURNAL.PONE.0111874.
- [242] M. Nilsson, H. Malmgren, M. Samiotaki, M. Kwiatkowski, B. P. Chowdhary, and U. Landegren, 'Padlock probes: circularizing oligonucleotides for localized DNA detection', *Science*, vol. 265, no. 5181, pp. 2085–2088, 1994, doi: 10.1126/SCIENCE.7522346.
- [243] F. Dahl, J. Banér, M. Gullberg, M. Mendel-Hartvig, U. Landegren, and M. Nilsson, 'Circle-to-circle amplification for precise and sensitive DNA analysis', *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*, vol. 101, no. 13, p. 4548, Mar. 2004, doi: 10.1073/PNAS.0400834101.
- [244] M. Guo, I. Hernández-Neuta, N. Madaboosi, M. Nilsson, and W. van der Wijngaart, 'Efficient DNA-assisted synthesis of trans-membrane gold nanowires', *Microsystems & Nanoengineering 2018 4:1*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 1–8, Feb. 2018, doi: 10.1038/micronano.2017.84.
- [245] C. Russell *et al.*, 'Gold nanowire based electrical DNA detection using rolling circle amplification', *ACS Nano*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 1147–1153, Feb. 2014, doi: 10.1021/NN4058825.
- [246] M. S. Elphinstone, G. N. Hinten, M. J. Anderson, and C. J. Nock, 'An inexpensive and high-throughput procedure to extract and purify total genomic DNA for population studies', *Mol Ecol Notes*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 317–320, Jun. 2003, doi: 10.1046/J.1471-8286.2003.00397.X.
- [247] N. v. Ivanova, J. R. Dewaard, and P. D. N. Hebert, 'An inexpensive, automation-friendly protocol for recovering high-quality DNA', *Mol Ecol Notes*, vol. 6, no. 4, pp. 998–1002, Dec. 2006, doi: 10.1111/J.1471-8286.2006.01428.X.
- [248] C. W. Price, D. C. Leslie, and J. P. Landers, 'Nucleic acid extraction techniques and application to the microchip', *Lab Chip*, vol. 9, no. 17, pp. 2484–2494, 2009, doi: 10.1039/B907652M.
- [249] B. Shi, Y. K. Shin, A. A. Hassanali, and S. J. Singer, 'DNA Binding to the Silica Surface', *J Phys Chem B*, vol. 119, no. 34, pp. 11030–11040, Aug. 2015, doi: 10.1021/ACS.JPCB.5B01983.

- [250] T. Poeckh, S. Lopez, A. O. Fuller, M. J. Solomon, and R. G. Larson, 'Adsorption and elution characteristics of nucleic acids on silica surfaces and their use in designing a miniaturized purification unit', *Anal Biochem*, vol. 373, no. 2, pp. 253–262, Feb. 2008, doi: 10.1016/J.AB.2007.10.026.
- [251] L. Liu, Z. Guo, Z. Huang, J. Zhuang, and W. Yang, 'Size-selective separation of DNA fragments by using lysine-functionalized silica particles', *Sci Rep*, vol. 6, Feb. 2016, doi: 10.1038/SREP22029.
- [252] M. Kühnemund, I. Hernández-Neuta, M. I. Sharif, M. Cornaglia, M. A. M. Gijs, and M. Nilsson, 'Sensitive and inexpensive digital DNA analysis by microfluidic enrichment of rolling circle amplified single-molecules', *Nucleic Acids Res*, vol. 45, no. 8, 2017, doi: 10.1093/NAR/GKW1324.
- [253] K. Kaarj, P. Akarapipad, and J. Y. Yoon, 'Simpler, Faster, and Sensitive Zika Virus Assay Using Smartphone Detection of Loop-mediated Isothermal Amplification on Paper Microfluidic Chips', *Scientific Reports 2018 8:1*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 1–11, Aug. 2018, doi: 10.1038/s41598-018-30797-9.
- [254] N. M. Rodriguez, J. C. Linnes, A. Fan, C. K. Ellenson, N. R. Pollock, and C. M. Klapperich, 'Paper-Based RNA Extraction, in Situ Isothermal Amplification, and Lateral Flow Detection for Low-Cost, Rapid Diagnosis of Influenza A (H1N1) from Clinical Specimens.', *Anal Chem*, vol. 87, no. 15, pp. 7872–7879, Jul. 2015, doi: 10.1021/ACS.ANALCHEM.5B01594.
- [255] F. Stumpf *et al.*, 'LabDisk with complete reagent prestorage for sample-to-answer nucleic acid based detection of respiratory pathogens verified with influenza A H3N2 virus', *Lab Chip*, vol. 16, no. 1, pp. 199–207, 2016, doi: 10.1039/C5LC00871A.
- [256] S. Ghosh, C. Bornman, and M. M. Zafer, 'Antimicrobial Resistance Threats in the emerging COVID-19 pandemic: Where do we stand?', *J Infect Public Health*, vol. 14, no. 5, pp. 555–560, May 2021, doi: 10.1016/J.JIPH.2021.02.011.
- [257] C. Wang, M. Liu, Z. Wang, S. Li, Y. Deng, and N. He, 'Point-of-care diagnostics for infectious diseases: From methods to devices', *Nano Today*, vol. 37, p. 101092, Apr. 2021, doi: 10.1016/J.NANTOD.2021.101092.

- [258] T. M. Oeschger *et al.*, 'Early Warning Diagnostics for Emerging Infectious Diseases in Developing into Late-Stage Pandemics', *Acc Chem Res*, vol. 54, no. 19, pp. 3656–3666, Oct. 2021, doi: 10.1021/ACS.ACCOUNTS.1C00383.
- [259] J. Piret and G. Boivin, 'Pandemics Throughout History', *Front Microbiol*, vol. 11, Jan. 2021, doi: 10.3389/FMICB.2020.631736/FMICB_11_631736_PDF.PDF.
- [260] J. Bell *et al.*, 'Multicenter clinical evaluation of the novel Alere™ i Influenza A&B isothermal nucleic acid amplification test', *J Clin Virol*, vol. 61, no. 1, pp. 81–86, 2014, doi: 10.1016/J.JCV.2014.06.001.
- [261] M. S. Islam, A. Aryasomayajula, and P. R. Selvaganapathy, 'A Review on Macroscale and Microscale Cell Lysis Methods', *Micromachines 2017, Vol. 8, Page 83*, vol. 8, no. 3, p. 83, Mar. 2017, doi: 10.3390/MI8030083.
- [262] R. Sharma, B. D. Dill, K. Chourey, M. Shah, N. C. Verberkmoes, and R. L. Hettich, 'Coupling a detergent lysis/cleanup methodology with intact protein fractionation for enhanced proteome characterization', *J Proteome Res*, vol. 11, no. 12, pp. 6008–6018, Dec. 2012, doi: 10.1021/PR300709K.
- [263] R. Martzy *et al.*, 'Simple lysis of bacterial cells for DNA-based diagnostics using hydrophilic ionic liquids', *Scientific Reports 2019 9:1*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 1–10, Sep. 2019, doi: 10.1038/s41598-019-50246-5.
- [264] O. Strohmeier *et al.*, 'Automated nucleic acid extraction from whole blood, *B. subtilis*, *E. coli*, and Rift Valley fever virus on a centrifugal microfluidic LabDisk', *RSC Adv*, vol. 5, no. 41, pp. 32144–32150, Apr. 2015, doi: 10.1039/C5RA03399C.
- [265] M. Mahalanabis, H. Al-Muayad, M. D. Kulinski, D. Altman, and C. M. Klapperich, 'Cell lysis and DNA extraction of gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria from whole blood in a disposable microfluidic chip', *Lab Chip*, vol. 9, no. 19, pp. 2811–2817, 2009, doi: 10.1039/B905065P.
- [266] M. D. Kulinski, M. Mahalanabis, S. Gillers, J. Y. Zhang, S. Singh, and C. M. Klapperich, 'Sample preparation module for bacterial lysis and isolation of DNA from human urine', *Biomed Microdevices*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 671–678, 2009, doi: 10.1007/S10544-008-9277-1.
- [267] G. Czilwik *et al.*, 'Rapid and fully automated bacterial pathogen detection on a centrifugal-microfluidic LabDisk using highly sensitive nested PCR with

- integrated sample preparation', *Lab Chip*, vol. 15, no. 18, pp. 3749–3759, Aug. 2015, doi: 10.1039/C5LC00591D.
- [268] E. L. Sciuto, S. Petralia, G. Calabrese, and S. Conoci, 'An integrated biosensor platform for extraction and detection of nucleic acids', *Biotechnol Bioeng*, vol. 117, no. 5, pp. 1554–1561, May 2020, doi: 10.1002/BIT.27290.
- [269] D. G. Fraenkel and F. Neidhardt, 'Escherichia coli and Salmonella: cellular and molecular biology', in *Escherichia coli and Salmonella. Cellular and molecular biology*, 2nd ed. Washington, D.C.: American Society for Microbiology, 1996, pp. 189–198.
- [270] F. Fouladvand, P. Bemani, M. Mohammadi, R. Amini, and F. A. Jalilian, 'A review of the methods for concentrating M13 phage', *Journal of Applied Biotechnology Reports*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 7–15, 2020, doi: 10.30491/JABR.2020.105916.
- [271] Y. Masago, T. Shibata, and J. B. Rose, 'Bacteriophage P22 and Staphylococcus aureus attenuation on nonporous fomites as determined by plate assay and quantitative PCR', *Appl Environ Microbiol*, vol. 74, no. 18, pp. 5838–5840, Sep. 2008, doi: 10.1128/AEM.00352-08.
- [272] E. Frahm and U. Obst, 'Application of the fluorogenic probe technique (TaqMan PCR) to the detection of Enterococcus spp. and Escherichia coli in water samples', *J Microbiol Methods*, vol. 52, no. 1, pp. 123–131, Jan. 2003, doi: 10.1016/S0167-7012(02)00150-1.
- [273] K. P. O'Connell *et al.*, 'Real-time fluorogenic reverse transcription-PCR assays for detection of bacteriophage MS2', *Appl Environ Microbiol*, vol. 72, no. 1, pp. 478–483, Jan. 2006, doi: 10.1128/AEM.72.1.478-483.2006/ASSET/278A7522-FA98-4B91-8BCD-66775E6A8F11/ASSETS/GRAPHIC/ZAM0010663720003.JPEG.
- [274] F. Loisy, R. L. Atmar, P. Guillon, P. Le Cann, M. Pommepuy, and F. S. Le Guyader, 'Real-time RT-PCR for norovirus screening in shellfish', *J Virol Methods*, vol. 123, no. 1, pp. 1–7, Jan. 2005, doi: 10.1016/J.JVIROMET.2004.08.023.
- [275] T. Kageyama *et al.*, 'Broadly reactive and highly sensitive assay for Norwalk-like viruses based on real-time quantitative reverse transcription-PCR', *J Clin Microbiol*, vol. 41, no. 4, pp. 1548–1557, Apr. 2003, doi:

10.1128/JCM.41.4.1548-1557.2003/ASSET/4FDDC41B-9B21-49BE-BCE2-8E1BABC76200/ASSETS/GRAPHIC/JM0430526003.JPEG.

- [276] M. E. Bahamonde, 'Bacterial Cell Breakage or Lysis', in *Practical Handbook of Microbiology, Third Edition*, Routledge Handbooks Online, 2015, pp. 265–274. doi: 10.1201/B17871-18.
- [277] Y. Fang *et al.*, 'Mixing enhancement by simple periodic geometric features in microchannels', *Chemical Engineering Journal*, vol. 187, pp. 306–310, Apr. 2012, doi: 10.1016/J.CEJ.2012.01.130.
- [278] M. U. Javaid, T. A. Cheema, and C. W. Park, 'Analysis of Passive Mixing in a Serpentine Microchannel with Sinusoidal Side Walls', *Micromachines (Basel)*, vol. 9, no. 1, p. 8, Dec. 2017, doi: 10.3390/mi9010008.
- [279] S. Hossain, M. A. Ansari, and K. Y. Kim, 'Evaluation of the mixing performance of three passive micromixers', *Chemical Engineering Journal*, vol. 150, no. 2–3, pp. 492–501, Aug. 2009, doi: 10.1016/J.CEJ.2009.02.033.
- [280] S. Akgönül, A. Özbey, M. Karimzadehkhoei, D. Gozuacik, and A. Koşar, 'The effect of asymmetry on micromixing in curvilinear microchannels', *Microfluidics and Nanofluidics 2017 21:7*, vol. 21, no. 7, pp. 1–15, Jun. 2017, doi: 10.1007/S10404-017-1952-1.
- [281] D. Bray, *Cell Movements : From Molecules to Motility*, 2nd Edition. New York: Garland Science, 2000. doi: 10.4324/9780203833582.
- [282] M. Clemson and W. J. Kelly, 'Optimizing alkaline lysis for DNA plasmid recovery', *Biotechnol Appl Biochem*, vol. 37, no. 3, pp. 235–244, Jun. 2003, doi: 10.1042/BA20030002.
- [283] N. Panpradist *et al.*, 'Swab sample transfer for point-of-care diagnostics: characterization of swab types and manual agitation methods', *PLoS One*, vol. 9, no. 9, 2014, doi: 10.1371/JOURNAL.PONE.0105786.
- [284] R. C. Wood *et al.*, 'Characterization of oral swab samples for diagnosis of pulmonary tuberculosis', *PLoS One*, vol. 16, no. 5, May 2021, doi: 10.1371/JOURNAL.PONE.0251422.
- [285] W. Saenger, 'Proteinase K', in *Handbook of Proteolytic Enzymes*, Academic Press, 2013, pp. 3240–3242. doi: 10.1016/B978-0-12-382219-2.00714-6.

- [286] F. Mao, W. Y. Leung, and X. Xin, 'Characterization of EvaGreen and the implication of its physicochemical properties for qPCR applications', *BMC Biotechnol*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 1–16, Nov. 2007, doi: 10.1186/1472-6750-7-76/TABLES/1.
- [287] L. A. Currie, 'Limits for Qualitative Detection and Quantitative Determination: Application to Radiochemistry', *Anal Chem*, vol. 40, no. 3, pp. 586–593, Mar. 1968, doi: 10.1021/AC60259A007/ASSET/AC60259A007.FP.PNG_V03.
- [288] C. E. Anderson and A. B. Boehm, 'Transfer Rate of Enveloped and Nonenveloped Viruses between Fingerpads and Surfaces', *Appl Environ Microbiol*, vol. 87, no. 22, Oct. 2021, doi: 10.1128/AEM.01215-21.
- [289] T. H. Kim, J. Park, C. J. Kim, and Y. K. Cho, 'Fully integrated lab-on-a-disc for nucleic acid analysis of food-borne pathogens', *Anal Chem*, vol. 86, no. 8, pp. 3841–3848, Apr. 2014, doi: 10.1021/AC403971H/SUPPL_FILE/AC403971H_SI_002.AVI.
- [290] M. Johnson, 'Detergents: Triton X-100, Tween-20, and More', *Materials and Methods*, vol. 3, Jan. 2013, doi: 10.13070/MM.EN.3.163.
- [291] M. Varghese and M. Balachandran, 'Antibacterial efficiency of carbon dots against Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria: A review', *J Environ Chem Eng*, vol. 9, no. 6, p. 106821, Dec. 2021, doi: 10.1016/J.JECE.2021.106821.
- [292] T. J. Silhavy, D. Kahne, and S. Walker, 'The Bacterial Cell Envelope', *Cold Spring Harb Perspect Biol*, vol. 2, no. 5, 2010, doi: 10.1101/CSHPERSPECT.A000414.
- [293] V. S. Farafonov and D. Nerukh, 'MS2 bacteriophage capsid studied using all-atom molecular dynamics.', *Interface Focus*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 20180081–20180081, Apr. 2019, doi: 10.1098/RSFS.2018.0081.
- [294] B. Michen and T. Graule, 'Isoelectric points of viruses', *J Appl Microbiol*, vol. 109, no. 2, pp. 388–397, Aug. 2010, doi: 10.1111/J.1365-2672.2010.04663.X.
- [295] K. Nikolaidou *et al.*, 'Monolithically integrated optical interference and absorption filters on thin film amorphous silicon photosensors for biological detection', *Sens Actuators B Chem*, vol. 356, p. 131330, 2022, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.snb.2021.131330>.

- [296] N. Younes *et al.*, 'Challenges in Laboratory Diagnosis of the Novel Coronavirus SARS-CoV-2', *Viruses* 2020, Vol. 12, Page 582, vol. 12, no. 6, p. 582, May 2020, doi: 10.3390/V12060582.
- [297] X. Y. Li, Y. C. Du, Y. P. Zhang, and D. M. Kong, 'Dual functional Phi29 DNA polymerase-triggered exponential rolling circle amplification for sequence-specific detection of target DNA embedded in long-stranded genomic DNA', *Scientific Reports* 2017 7:1, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 1–10, Jul. 2017, doi: 10.1038/s41598-017-06594-1.
- [298] R. R. G. Soares *et al.*, 'Sub-attomole detection of HIV-1 using padlock probes and rolling circle amplification combined with microfluidic affinity chromatography', *Biosens Bioelectron*, vol. 166, p. 112442, Oct. 2020, doi: 10.1016/J.BIOS.2020.112442.
- [299] F. B. Dean, J. R. Nelson, T. L. Giesler, and R. S. Lasken, 'Rapid Amplification of Plasmid and Phage DNA Using Phi29 DNA Polymerase and Multiply-Primed Rolling Circle Amplification', *Genome Res*, vol. 11, no. 6, p. 1095, 2001, doi: 10.1101/GR.180501.
- [300] L. Blanco, A. Bernads, J. M. Lharo, G. Martins, C. Garmendia, and M. Salasn, 'Highly Efficient DNA Synthesis by the Phage ϕ 29 DNA Polymerase: Symmetrical Mode of DNA Replication', *Journal of Biological Chemistry*, vol. 264, no. 15, pp. 8935–8940, May 1989, doi: 10.1016/S0021-9258(18)81883-X.
- [301] W. Yang, J. Y. Lee, and M. Nowotny, 'Making and Breaking Nucleic Acids: Two-Mg²⁺-Ion Catalysis and Substrate Specificity', *Mol Cell*, vol. 22, no. 1, pp. 5–13, Apr. 2006, doi: 10.1016/J.MOLCEL.2006.03.013.
- [302] X. Wang, H. J. Lim, and A. Son, 'Characterization of denaturation and renaturation of DNA for DNA hybridization', *Environ Health Toxicol*, vol. 29, p. e2014007, Sep. 2014, doi: 10.5620/EHT.2014.29.E2014007.
- [303] Witold Postek, Natalia Pacocha, and Piotr Garstecki, 'Microfluidics for antibiotic susceptibility testing', *Lab Chip*, vol. 22, no. 19, pp. 3637–3662, Sep. 2022, doi: 10.1039/D2LC00394E.
- [304] G. D. Kaprou, I. Bergšpica, E. A. Alexa, A. Alvarez-Ordóñez, and M. Prieto, 'Rapid Methods for Antimicrobial Resistance Diagnostics', *Antibiotics* 2021,

Vol. 10, Page 209, vol. 10, no. 2, p. 209, Feb. 2021, doi:
10.3390/ANTIBIOTICS10020209.